

**SUBSPACE METHODS FOR
LINEAR, NONLINEAR, AND
EIGEN PROBLEMS**

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SUBSPACE METHODS FOR LINEAR, NONLINEAR, AND EIGEN PROBLEMS

Deelruimte methoden voor lineaire,
niet-lineaire, en eigen problemen

(met een samenvatting in het Nederlands)

Proefschrift

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*a small step for man
a BiCGstab for mankind*

PREFACE

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CONTENTS

Preface	v
List of Algorithms	xi
Introduction	1
1 Nested Krylov methods and preserving the orthogonality	23
1.1 Introduction	24
1.2 Consequences of inner orthogonalization	28
1.3 Implementation	32
1.3.1 GCR and GMRESR	32
1.3.2 GCRO with GMRES as inner iteration	32
1.4 Truncation	33
1.4.1 A strategy for truncation	33
1.4.2 Dropping a vector	35
1.4.3 Assembly of two vectors	36
1.5 Numerical experiments	37
1.5.1 Problem 1	37
1.5.2 Problem 2	39
1.5.3 Problem 3	42
1.6 Conclusions	43
2 BiCGstab(ℓ) for linear equations	47
2.1 Introduction	47
2.2 Theoretical justification of BiCGstab(ℓ)	51
2.3 The BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm	54
2.3.1 The computation of the Bi-CG iteration coefficients	54
2.3.2 The construction of the BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm	55

2.3.3	The Bi-CG part	58
2.3.4	The MR part	59
2.3.5	The computational cost and memory requirements	61
2.3.6	Remarks on the implementation of the algorithm	63
2.3.7	Variants	65
2.3.8	The stability	66
2.4	The preconditioned BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm	67
2.5	Numerical examples	68
2.5.1	Example 1	68
2.5.2	Example 2	69
2.5.3	Example 3	72
2.5.4	Example 4	72
2.6	Conclusions	75
3	Enhanced implementation of BiCGstab(ℓ)	77
3.1	Introduction	77
3.2	Maintaining the convergence	81
3.3	Reliable updates	83
3.4	Description of FORTRAN code	85
3.5	Numerical experiments	95
3.5.1	Example 1	95
3.5.2	Example 2	95
3.6	Conclusions	97
4	Generalized conjugate gradient squared	99
4.1	Introduction	99
4.2	Bi-CG and CGS	102
4.3	Disadvantages of squaring the iteration polynomial	105
4.4	Generalized CGS: methods of CGS type	106
4.5	Well known methods of CGS type	108
4.5.1	CGS: using the Bi-CG polynomials	108
4.5.2	Bi-CGSTAB: using products of optimal first degree factors	108
4.6	New methods of CGS type	109
4.6.1	CGS2: using related Bi-CG polynomials	110
4.6.2	Shifted CGS: using delayed Bi-CG polynomials	112
4.7	Numerical examples	113
4.7.1	Characteristics of CGS2	114
4.7.2	Characteristics of Shifted CGS	115
4.7.3	CGS2 as linear solver in a Newton scheme	118

4.7.4	Shifted CGS as linear solver in a Newton scheme	120
4.8	Conclusions	122
5	Accelerated Inexact Newton schemes	125
5.1	Introduction	125
5.2	Inexact Newton methods	127
5.3	Accelerating Inexact Newton methods	128
5.3.1	Acceleration in the linear case	129
5.3.2	Acceleration in the nonlinear case	130
5.4	Computational considerations	132
5.4.1	Restart	132
5.4.2	Update	134
5.4.3	The projected problem	135
5.4.4	Expanding the search subspace	135
5.5	How linear solvers fit in the AIN framework	135
5.5.1	GCR	135
5.5.2	FOM and GMRES	135
5.5.3	GMRESR	136
5.6	AIN schemes for mildly nonlinear problems	136
5.6.1	Arnoldi's method	137
5.6.2	Davidson's method	138
5.6.3	Jacobi-Davidson	138
5.7	AIN schemes for general nonlinear problems	139
5.8	Numerical experiments	140
5.8.1	A 1D Burgers' equation	141
5.8.2	The Bratu problem	143
5.8.3	The driven cavity problem	143
5.9	Conclusions	146
6	Jacobi-Davidson style QR and QZ algorithms	149
6.1	Introduction	149
6.2	The standard eigenproblem	152
6.2.1	Jacobi-Davidson	153
6.2.2	Practical selection and implicit restart	153
6.2.3	JDQR	156
6.2.4	Preconditioning	159
6.2.5	The selection of Ritz pairs	162
6.2.6	Notes on the speed of convergence	166
6.2.7	The quality of the deflated preconditioner	167

6.3	The generalized eigenproblem	168
6.3.1	Jacobi-Davidson	168
6.3.2	Practical selection and implicit restart	174
6.3.3	JDQZ	174
6.3.4	Preconditioning	176
6.3.5	The selection of Petrov pairs	177
6.4	Numerical experiments	181
6.4.1	The influence of the correction equation	183
6.4.2	The effect of preconditioning	184
6.4.3	Multiple eigenvalues	185
6.4.4	Harmonic Ritz values	187
6.4.5	Tracking	189
6.4.6	The influence of \mathbf{Q}_k and \mathbf{Z}_k in the correction equation	190
6.4.7	More multiple eigenvalues	192
6.4.8	Harmonic Ritz values for generalized problems	195
6.5	Conclusions	197
.1	Modified Gram-Schmidt	199
.2	Sorting the Schur form	200
.3	Sorting the generalized Schur form	201
	Summary	205
	Samenvatting	207
	A Python implementation of BISTBL	211

LIST OF ALGORITHMS

1.1	GCR	25
1.2	GMRESR(m)	25
1.3	Generic GCRO	27
1.4	Efficient GCRO(m) with GMRES	34
2.1	Bi-CG	51
2.2	BiCGstab(ℓ)	62
3.1	Preconditioned BiCGstab(ℓ)	80
3.2	Convex combination	82
3.3	Enhanced preconditioned BiCGstab(ℓ)	84
4.1	Bi-CG	104
4.2	CGS	104
4.3	GCGS	109
4.4	Bi-CGSTAB	110
4.5	CGS2	112
5.1	Inexact Newton	128
5.2	Jacobi Iteration	129
5.3	Accelerated Inexact Newton	133
6.1	JD with restart	155
6.2	Preconditioned JDQR, part 1	163
6.3	Preconditioned JDQR, part 2	164
6.4	Preconditioned JDQZ, part 1	178
6.5	Preconditioned JDQZ, part 2	179

INTRODUCTION

This thesis concerns iterative subspace methods for linear-, nonlinear-, and eigenproblems, which appear frequently in many different areas of science, including chemistry, economics, engineering, and physics. In these disciplines, studying the behavior of some kind of phenomenon generally involves a set of (non)linear partial differential equations that has to be solved.

Subspace methods are suitable for solving these, sometimes large, problems efficiently and are particularly useful when direct solution methods are not feasible, due to memory limitations, excessive use of CPU-time, or when just no explicit solution formula exists. They may also be an alternative for direct methods when only an approximate solution is wanted. In that case subspace methods may be more efficient.

In this introduction we will briefly sketch the ideas behind subspace methods. We will discuss some well-known existing subspace methods for particular classes of problems and point out some of their weaknesses. Identifying these weaknesses is one step in the direction towards methods with improved properties. We will also discuss contemporary developments that relate to the chapters in this thesis. Each of the chapters consists of a paper and can be read separately.

The general idea. Subspace methods compute iteratively an approximate solution for a given problem. They generate a basis for a subspace of increasing dimension and determine the best solution in this subspace. This leads to a much smaller problem that resembles the original large problem. To increase the dimension of the subspace often a suitable nearby system is solved. With the solution of this nearby system (preconditioner, or correction equation) the subspace is expanded and the process is repeated until convergence.

In this setting, keystones to an efficient and fast converging method for a particular problem involve the following aspects:

- the computation of a suitable basis for the subspace,
- the choice of preconditioner, or the correction equation.

The identification of an approximate solution in the subspace is often a minor problem, but we will also consider this aspect.

In the following, we will comment on these aspects for the different classes of problems, addressed in this thesis.

Subspace methods for linear problems. In Chapter 1–4 we present subspace methods for linear problems

$$Ax = b,$$

in which A is a, usually large and sparse, nonsingular ($n \times n$)-matrix and b a given n -vector. Starting from an initial guess x_0 , the objective is to compute an approximate solution x_k for which the *residual* $r_k = b - Ax_k$ is small in some sense.

Many iterative methods belong to the class of so-called Krylov subspace methods. The methods in this class have in common that they compute approximate solutions x_k for which $x_k - x_0$ belongs to the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}^k(A; r_0)$ of order k spanned by $\{r_0, Ar_0, \dots, A^{k-1}r_0\}$.

One of the simplest schemes in this class, is the following standard Richardson type of method:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Set } k = -1 \text{ and choose an initial approximation } x_0. \\ &\text{Set } r_0 = b - Ax_0 \text{ and repeat until } r_k \text{ is small enough:} \\ &\quad k = k + 1 \\ &\quad x_{k+1} = x_k + r_k \\ &\quad r_{k+1} = r_k - Ar_k \end{aligned}$$

This iterative scheme converges linearly with a rate proportional to the spectral radius of $(I - A)$, provided it is smaller than 1. Unfortunately, for most linear systems, this value is either very close to 1, or larger. The convergence properties are poor and the main reason for this is that the solution is *statically* updated.

More sophisticated Krylov methods with better convergence properties update the solution *dynamically*. With a suitable linear combination of all the basis vectors, they exploit the whole Krylov subspace. We can subdivide the class of these methods as follows:

- *The Galerkin methods:* Construct x_k for which the residual r_k is orthogonal to $\mathcal{K}^k(A; r_0)$;
- *The minimal residual methods:* Construct x_k for which the residual $\|r_k\|_2$ is minimal;
- *The Petrov-Galerkin methods:* Construct x_k for which the residual r_k is orthogonal to some other suitable k -dimensional subspace.

An example of a Galerkin method is Lanczos' method [57] for symmetric matrices. Starting with $v_1 = r_0/\|r_0\|_2$, the method constructs a sequence of orthogonal basis vectors v_2, v_3, \dots for the Krylov subspace using a three-term recurrence. Denoting $V_k = [v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k]$ we can formulate the relations in terms of matrices as:

$$AV_k = V_k T_k + t_{k+1,k} v_{k+1} e_k^T,$$

where $T_k = (t_{i,j})$ is a symmetric tridiagonal $(k \times k)$ -matrix. The approximate solution is $x_k = x_0 + V_k y_k$, where y_k follows from the Galerkin condition

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= V_k^T (b - Ax_k) = V_k^T (r_0 - AV_k y_k) \\ &= V_k^T (r_0 - V_k T_k y_k) \\ &= \|r_0\|_2 e_1 - T_k y_k. \end{aligned}$$

The latter equation can be solved easily with standard techniques for tridiagonal matrices, see, e.g., LAPACK [1].

When the matrix A is in addition positive definite, we can use the Cholesky decomposition of T_k to split the three-term recurrence into a coupled two-term recurrence for the solution of the tridiagonal system and update the solution on the fly! This elegant procedure is the famous Conjugate Gradients method (CG) [51]. It has very nice properties: it is remarkably stable, it minimizes the A -norm of the error, and the memory requirements and the computational costs are constant per iteration.

For general unsymmetric problems the Generalized Minimal Residual (GMRES) [82] is probably the most famous. It follows the minimal residual approach, as the name already suggests. The method is based on Arnoldi's method [2] for the construction of an orthogonal basis $\{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k\}$ for the Krylov subspace of order k :

```

v1 = r0/||r0||2
for j = 1, 2, ..., k
  ṽ = Avj
  for i = 1, 2, ..., j
    hi,j = (ṽ, vj)
    ṽ = ṽ - hi,jvj
  end
  hi+1,j = ||ṽ||2
  vj+1 = ṽ/hi+1,j
end

```

In terms of matrices this can be expressed as

$$AV_k = V_k H_k + h_{k+1,k} v_{k+1} e_k^T,$$

where H_k is an $(k \times k)$ upper Hessenberg matrix, or as

$$AV_k = V_{k+1} \bar{H}_k,$$

where

$$\bar{H}_k = \begin{bmatrix} H_k & \\ & h_{k+1,k} e_k^T \end{bmatrix}.$$

Using this relation, the minimal residual solution $x_k = V_k y_k$ now follows from minimizing

$$\begin{aligned} \|b - Ax_k\|_2 &= \|r_0 - AV_k y_k\|_2 \\ &= \|r_0 - V_{k+1} \bar{H}_k y_k\|_2 \\ &= \|V_{k+1}^T (r_0 - V_{k+1} \bar{H}_k y_k)\|_2 \\ &= \|\|r_0\|_2 e_1 - \bar{H}_k y_k\|_2. \end{aligned}$$

Using Givens rotations the last minimization problem can be solved easily. The method has also nice properties: it converges monotonically and cannot break down before the solution is found. However, GMRES has to use long recursions and needs all basis vectors throughout the process [35]. This leads to increasing memory needs and to increasing computational overhead per iteration step. A simple solution to overcome this problem is to restart GMRES with the most recent approximation as an initial guess after, say, m iteration steps. Unfortunately, by doing this GMRES loses its optimality, see, e.g., [104].

The bi-Lanczos method [57] is another approach for unsymmetric linear problems and belongs to the Petrov-Galerkin class. It avoids long recursions by constructing *bi-orthogonal* bases for $\mathcal{K}^k(A; r_0)$ and $\mathcal{K}^k(A^T; \tilde{r}_0)$, where \tilde{r}_0 is an arbitrary, but fixed, vector. More specifically, bi-Lanczos constructs bi-orthogonal bases V_k and W_k for $\mathcal{K}^k(A; r_0)$ and $\mathcal{K}^k(A^T; \tilde{r}_0)$, respectively, using three-term recursions such that

$$\begin{aligned} AV_k &= V_k T_k + t_{k+1,k} v_k e_k^T, \\ A^T W_k &= W_k T_k + t_{k+1,k} w_k e_k^T, \text{ and} \\ W_k^T V_k &= D_k, \end{aligned}$$

where T_k is a tridiagonal $(k \times k)$ -matrix and D_k a diagonal $(k \times k)$ -matrix. The approximate solution is $x_k = x_0 + V_k y_k$, where y_k follows from the Petrov-Galerkin condition with respect to $\mathcal{K}^k(A^T; \tilde{r}_0)$

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= W_k^T (b - Ax_k) = W_k^T (r_0 - AV_k y_k) \\ &= W_k^T (r_0 - V_k T_k y_k) \\ &= W_k^T V_k (\|r_0\|_2 e_1 - T_k y_k) \\ &= D_k (\|r_0\|_2 e_1 - T_k y_k). \end{aligned}$$

We have assumed that this procedure can be carried out, but this is not always the case: the three-term recursion breaks down when a diagonal element d_i of D_k becomes zero. In the literature this event is referred to as the ‘‘Lanczos’’ breakdown. In finite precision arithmetic an exact breakdown is unlikely, but a near breakdown, i.e., $d_i \approx 0$, may lead to numerical instabilities. These instabilities can be repaired to a large extent by using so-called look-ahead techniques [72, 41, 48]. The idea is to construct block bi-orthogonal bases.

With the help of an LU decomposition of T_k without pivoting, the bi-Lanczos procedure can be implemented, similar to CG, very efficiently with short recursions and the use of only the last 2 basis vectors of both subspaces. The resulting method is known as Bi-Conjugate Gradient (Bi-CG) [36]. A problem here is that the LU decomposition not always exists in which case we have another breakdown: the ‘‘pivot’’ breakdown.

Apart from the possible (near) breakdowns, Bi-CG has another few drawbacks:

- two matrix multiplications are necessary for each iteration step, since two Krylov subspaces are involved;

- A^T is needed which may not be readily available;
- the method may involve large intermediate residual vectors that may spoil the accuracy of the approximate solution [91].

In summary, the unsymmetric case gives rise to different problems. For GMRES the dimension of the subspace must be limited to restrict computational overhead; for Bi-CG, the non-orthogonality may lead to stability problems.

Further information on Krylov subspace methods for linear problems can be found in, e.g., [11, 44, 86].

In the past decade, much research has been done in order to improve on GMRES and Bi-CG, with respect to the above mentioned problems, and many new variants have been proposed.

In the following we highlight some of the most important developments. We will distinguish between methods that are based on the minimal residual approach (GMRES), and methods that are based on the Petrov-Galerkin approach (Bi-CG). We will use this exposé to frame our new contributions.

The minimal residual approach. In [5, 81] and [105] several minimal residual methods were proposed in which the idea of building a pure Krylov subspace is abandoned. Instead, a subspace is built with (possibly) different “preconditioners” per iteration step.

The methods consist of an inner and an outer iteration scheme. First, a suitable linear system is (approximately) solved to find an expansion vector (the inner iteration). Then, the subspace is expanded and the minimal residual solution is determined with respect to this new subspace (the outer iteration). For the inner iteration one can use, for example, the same method as in the outer iteration (nesting), some appropriate approximate inverse, or even some other (preconditioned) iterative method. The only restriction is that the inner iteration should produce an expansion vector with which in the outer iteration the residual is reduced; otherwise the methods break down.

Because the subspace (hopefully) contains better components of the solution (with respect to the pure Krylov subspace), the size of the subspace necessary to find an acceptable solution can be kept smaller, and consequently the memory requirements and the computational overhead are more favorable.

The variants presented in [5] are based on the Generalized Conjugate Gradient solver (GENCG), see also [3]. The method in [81] is very similar to GMRES and is called Flexible GMRES (FGMRES). The method in [105] (GMRESR) is based on GCR [34] and constructs (in exact arithmetic) the same iterates as

one of the methods presented in [5] provided the same preconditioner is used in each iteration.

However, compared with GMRESR, the methods in [5] are more expensive per iteration in terms of inner products, vector updates, and/or matrix multiplications. For example, one algorithm needs two matrix multiplications per step, the other about twice as many inner products and 50% more vector updates. Moreover, the algorithm in [5] uses standard Gram-Schmidt, which potentially may lead to numerical instabilities, in contrast to GMRESR, which uses Modified Gram-Schmidt.

FGMRES builds a subspace that is different from the one in GMRESR or GENCG. The difference is that in FGMRES the linear system in the inner iteration involves the last basis vector of the (outer) subspace, whereas in GMRESR or GENCG the linear system involves the most recent residual. Working with the last residual offers better opportunities to control the breakdown possibility, see [105].

Moreover, FGMRES is not as flexible as GMRESR or GENCG if one wants to reduce the size of the subspace for efficiency reasons (truncation). The reason for this is that FGMRES relies on the Arnoldi recursion relations for determining the approximate solution, and these are destroyed if the basis for the subspace is changed.

For many linear systems the methods work quite well and are more efficient than restarted (variants) of GMRES. However, there are cases where the speed of convergence is still unsatisfactory. One of the reasons for this is that the inner iterations “know” nothing about the outer subspace and so it might happen that the inner iteration produces a poor expansion vector, i.e., a vector that does not help to reduce the residual very much. If one is not careful, this phenomenon might repeat itself in the next iterations and thus the speed of convergence deteriorates. In such a situation one may consider to change the preconditioner, but this is not always feasible.

In Chapter 1 we propose a strategy to transfer information from the outer iteration to the inner iteration. This may help to overcome the deterioration of the convergence speed.

Even though the mentioned methods are designed to keep the dimension of the subspace limited, it may happen that the size still exceeds available computer resources. We will also present a truncation strategy that helps to discard parts of the subspace and that appears to affect the speed of convergence not too much.

We have chosen to apply our ideas to GMRESR, since this is the most flexible one of the methods mentioned before.

Below we give the abstract of Chapter 1.

CHAPTER 1

Nested Krylov methods and preserving the orthogonality

Abstract. The GMRESR [105] inner-outer iteration scheme for the solution of linear systems of equations was proposed by Van der Vorst and Vuik. Similar methods have been proposed by Axelsson and Vassilevski [5], and Saad (FGMRES) [81]. The outer iteration is GCR, which minimizes the residual over a given subspace. The inner iteration is GMRES, which at each step computes an expansion for the subspace by approximately solving a correction equation. However, the optimality of the approximation over the outer subspace is ignored in the inner iteration. This leads to suboptimal corrections to the solution in the outer iteration, as parts of the outer subspace may reenter in the inner iteration process. Therefore we propose to preserve the orthogonality relations of GCR also in the inner iteration. This gives optimal corrections, however, it involves working with a singular, nonsymmetric operator. We will discuss some important properties and we will show by experiments, that in terms of matrix vector products this modification (almost) always leads to better convergence. However, because we do more orthogonalizations, it does not always give an improved performance in CPU-time. Furthermore, we will discuss an efficient implementation as well as truncation possibilities of the outer GCR process. Of course, we can also use other iteration schemes than GMRES as the inner method. Methods with short recurrences like Bi-CGSTAB seem especially interesting. The experimental results indicate that, especially for such methods, it is advantageous to preserve the orthogonality in the inner iteration.

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The Petrov-Galerkin approach. The research concerning variants of Bi-CG has focused mainly on the (possibly inefficient) multiplication with A^T , the breakdown possibilities, and on the irregular convergence.

Below we discuss important contributions from the same period with respect to these problems.

The quasi minimal residual approach. The Quasi Minimal Residual method (QMR) [41] attacks the last two problems and has been designed to cure the two (near) breakdown possibilities of Bi-CG and to smooth down the irregular convergence. QMR is based on the look-ahead version of the bi-Lanczos algorithm [72], combined with a “quasi” minimal residual approach. The method works as follows.

Suppose, for simplicity, that no look-ahead is necessary. Recall that the bi-Lanczos algorithm produces bi-orthogonal bases V_k and W_k such that:

$$\begin{aligned} AV_k &= V_k T_k + t_{k+1,k} v_k e_k^T, \\ A^T W_k &= W_k T_k + t_{k+1,k} w_k e_k^T, \text{ and} \\ W_k^T V_k &= D_k. \end{aligned}$$

Denoting

$$\bar{T}_k = \begin{bmatrix} T_k \\ t_{k+1,k} e_k^T \end{bmatrix},$$

we have that

$$AV_k = V_{k+1} \bar{T}_k.$$

It follows that for the norm of the residual r_k we have the following expression:

$$\begin{aligned} \|b - Ax_k\|_2 &= \|r_0 - AV_k y_k\|_2 \\ &= \|r_0 - V_{k+1} \bar{T}_k y_k\|_2. \\ &= \|V_{k+1} (\|r_0\|_2 e_1 - \bar{T}_k y_k)\|_2. \end{aligned}$$

Ideally, we would like to choose y_k such that $\|r_k\|_2$ is minimal. However, this would require much effort because in general V_{k+1} is not orthogonal. The QMR iterates now follow from minimizing the *quasi residual*

$$\|z_k\|_2 = \|\|r_0\|_2 e_1 - \bar{T}_k y_k\|_2,$$

ignoring the fact that V_{k+1} is not orthogonal. This does not truly minimize the residual, which explains the prefix “quasi”. In fact one can show that [41]

$$\sigma_{\min}(V_{k+1}) \|z_k\|_2 \leq \|r_k^{\text{QMR}}\|_2 \leq \sqrt{k+1} \|z_k\|_2.$$

The Bi-CG iterates can be recovered from the QMR process and the method exhibits smooth convergence, but essentially the convergence speed is the same as for Bi-CG [24]. It can be proven that:

$$\|r_k^{\text{Bi-CG}}\| = \frac{\|z_k^{\text{QMR}}\|_2}{\sqrt{1 - (\|z_k^{\text{QMR}}\|_2 / \|z_{k-1}^{\text{QMR}}\|_2)^2}},$$

and thus whenever QMR has a local significant reduction for the quasi residuals, then the corresponding residual norm for Bi-CG is comparable.

Attempts to eliminate the necessity of multiplications with A^T in the QMR approach can be found in, for instance, [39, 18, 42]. However, no look-ahead strategies to overcome the possible Lanczos breakdowns are incorporated, which may be a disadvantage with respect to QMR.

The composite step approach. In [10, 9] a different approach is followed. A fairly simple modification to Bi-CG is proposed to cure the (near) pivot breakdown. This is done by incorporating a so-called “composite step”. The idea is to skip over one step of the Bi-CG method explicitly when the corresponding iterate is not well-defined.

The polynomial approach. In [15, 16] and also [47] the breakdown problem is tackled from the point of view of polynomials. Since $x_k - x_0$ belongs to the Krylov subspace spanned by $\{r_0, Ar_0, \dots, A^{k-1}r_0\}$ it follows that

$$x_k - x_0 = -\alpha_1 r_0 - \dots - \alpha_k A^{k-1} r_0,$$

which means that

$$\begin{aligned} r_k &= r_0 + \alpha_1 Ar_0 + \dots + \alpha_k A^k r_0 \\ &= \phi_k(A)r_0 \end{aligned}$$

for the polynomial

$$\phi_k(t) = 1 + \alpha_1 t + \dots + \alpha_k t^k.$$

And thus, the Bi-CG algorithm can be linked with the theory of formal orthogonal polynomials with respect to a particular linear functional. Breakdowns in the Bi-CG algorithm naturally translate to breakdowns in the generation of such polynomials and visa versa. The rich theory of formal orthogonal polynomials then provides means to construct breakdown-free algorithms, e.g., MRZ, the method of recursive zoom [15].

The hybrid approach. In [93] the polynomial point of view was also taken and it led to the Conjugate Gradient Squared method (CGS). CGS uses (implicitly) the square of the Bi-CG polynomial ϕ_k and constructs, with short recursions, approximate solutions \mathbf{x}_k with corresponding residual

$$\mathbf{r}_k = \phi_k(A)^2 r_0.$$

A remarkable fact is that CGS does not need multiplications with A^T , in contrast to Bi-CG. Moreover, for many problems CGS is about twice as efficient as Bi-CG and therefore the method has become quite popular. However, the method is also notorious for its irregular convergence behavior with large intermediate residuals, which may spoil the accuracy of the solution and may deteriorate the speed of convergence. Moreover, since it is based on the Bi-CG polynomial it may suffer from the same breakdowns.

In [102] another approach was taken in an attempt to smooth the convergence of CGS. Instead of using the square of the Bi-CG polynomial ϕ_k , a product of polynomials of the form $\psi_k \phi_k$ was taken. More precisely, ψ_k was chosen as

$$\psi_k(t) = (1 - \omega_1 t)(1 - \omega_2 t) \cdots (1 - \omega_k t),$$

with coefficient ω_i such that $\|\mathbf{r}_i\|_2$ is minimal with respect to ω_i . The resulting method is known as Bi-CGSTAB and it exhibits smooth and fast convergence behavior for many problems. However, in addition to the Bi-CG breakdowns, it may suffer from another (near) breakdown possibility, namely when ω_i is (almost) equal to zero.

CGS and Bi-CGSTAB belong to the so-called class of Hybrid Bi-CG methods. They are called hybrid because their residuals \mathbf{r}_k can be formally written as

$$\mathbf{r}_k = \psi_k(A) \phi_k(A) r_0,$$

in which $\psi_k \in \mathcal{P}_k^1$, the space of all polynomials p of degree $\leq k$ with $p(0) = 1$, and ϕ_k is the Bi-CG polynomial. In CGS the polynomial ψ_k is chosen as the Bi-CG polynomial ϕ_k . In Bi-CGSTAB it is chosen as a product of locally minimizing polynomials of degree 1.

CGS and Bi-CGSTAB are certainly improvements over Bi-CG for many problems, and they can compete with GMRES and its variants. Unfortunately they also introduce new weaknesses: CGS may converge even more irregularly; and Bi-CGSTAB may suffer from one additional breakdown possibility.

In Chapter 2–4 we explore the possibilities for selecting other polynomials ψ_k to improve on Bi-CG and on the above mentioned problems.

Below we give the abstracts of the Chapters 2–4.

CHAPTER 2

BiCGstab(ℓ) for linear equations involving unsymmetric matrices with complex spectrum

Abstract. For the solution of classes of linear systems of equations arising from realistic problems, the Bi-CGSTAB algorithm [102] is attractive. Unfortunately, for some relevant problems, where, for instance, Bi-CG performs well, the convergence of Bi-CGSTAB stagnates. This was observed specifically in the case of discretized advection dominated PDE's. The stagnation is due to the fact that for this type of equations the matrix has almost pure imaginary eigenvalues. With his BiCGStab2 algorithm Gutknecht [49] attempted to avoid this stagnation. Here, we generalize the Bi-CGSTAB algorithm further, and overcome some shortcomings of BiCGStab2. The new algorithm combines GMRES(ℓ) and Bi-CG.

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CHAPTER 3

Enhanced implementation of BiCGstab(ℓ) for solving linear systems of equations

Abstract. In this paper, we present a FORTRAN implementation of the BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm [85]. The implementation is based on the power basis variant of BiCGstab(ℓ). This variant is enhanced with a more stable way of determination of the iteration coefficients and with a more reliable update strategy for the residuals [91, 88]. These enhancements improve the accuracy and rate of convergence at almost no additional computational costs.

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CHAPTER 4

Generalized conjugate gradient squared

Abstract. The Conjugate Gradient Squared (CGS) is an iterative method for solving nonsymmetric linear systems of equations. However, during the iteration large residual norms may appear, which may lead to inaccurate approximate solutions or may even deteriorate the convergence rate. Instead of squaring the Bi-CG polynomial as in CGS, we propose to consider products of two nearby Bi-CG polynomials which leads to generalized CGS methods, of which CGS is just a particular case. This approach allows the construction of methods that converge less irregularly than CGS and that improve on other convergence properties as well. Here, we are interested in a property that got less attention in literature: we concentrate on retaining the excellent approximation qualities of CGS with respect to components of the solution in the direction of eigenvectors associated with extreme eigenvalues. This property seems to be important in connection with Newton's scheme for nonlinear equations: our numerical experiments show that the number of Newton steps may decrease significantly when using a generalized CGS method as linear solver for the Newton correction equations.

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Subspace methods for nonlinear problems. In Chapter 5 we discuss a class of methods for general nonlinear problems. The methods in this class are suitable for computing approximate solutions of the general nonlinear problem

$$F(x) = 0.$$

A widely used approach for nonlinear problems is the Inexact Newton method [31, 69]. This method updates its current estimate by solving, approximately, a linear problem that involves the Jacobian. More specifically, for a given approximate solution x_k , an approximation p_k for the error $\Delta x = x - x_k$ is obtained through the linear approximation

$$F(x_k) + J_k \Delta x \approx F(x_k + \Delta x) = F(x) = 0,$$

where $J_k = F'(x_k)$, the Jacobian of F in x_k . That is, the *correction equation*

$$J_k \Delta x = -F(x_k)$$

is solved approximately with approximate solution p_k and the new approximate solution is updated as

$$x_{k+1} = x_k + p_k.$$

The described procedure is then repeated until convergence.

For a sufficiently good initial guess, the speed of convergence is asymptotically quadratical when the correction equation is solved exactly. When using only an approximation, the speed of convergence depends on how good the correction equation is solved. It can be controlled through *forcing terms* η_k [30]: for some sequence (η_k) let p_k be such that

$$\frac{\|F(x_k) + J_k p_k\|_2}{\|F(x_k)\|_2} \leq \eta_k.$$

If $\eta_k \rightarrow 0$, then the speed of convergence is typically superlinear, and if $\eta_k \leq c\|F(x_k)\|_2$, then it is typically quadratic. However, in practice it may be difficult to fulfill one of these requirements, in which case the speed of convergence is typically linear at most.

The observation that Inexact Newton is a 1-dimensional subspace method, leads to the idea of using subspaces of higher dimension. By using larger subspaces one may hope that the speed of convergence increases.

For example, in [4] nonlinear versions of the Generalized Conjugate Gradient are described that construct the update as a linear combination of the current correction p_k and all previously computed corrections p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{k-1} , such that

$$\|F(x_{k+1})\|_2 = \|F(x_k + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i p_i)\|_2$$

is minimal.

In [17] another so-called model trust region approach is proposed. The update is taken from the Krylov subspace V_k , generated by k steps of GMRES, as $p_k = V_k y$, where y is the point on the dogleg curve for which $\|y\|_2 = \tau$, the trust region size: y is an approximation for

$$\min_y \|F(x_k + V_k y)\|_2.$$

Many choices are possible and in Chapter 5 we describe a framework that, amongst others, contains the above described methods. The framework helps to identify new, possibly more efficient, methods for solving general nonlinear problems.

Below we give the abstract of Chapter 5.

CHAPTER 5

Accelerated Inexact Newton schemes for large systems of nonlinear equations

Abstract.

Classical iteration methods for linear systems, such as Jacobi Iteration, can be accelerated considerably by Krylov subspace methods like GMRES. In this paper, we describe how Inexact Newton methods for nonlinear problems can be accelerated in a similar way and how this leads to a general framework that includes many well known techniques for solving linear and nonlinear systems, as well as new ones. Inexact Newton methods are frequently used in practice to avoid the expensive exact solution of the large linear system arising in the (possibly also inexact) linearization step of Newton's process. Our framework includes acceleration techniques for the "linear steps" as well as for the "nonlinear steps" in Newton's process. The described class of methods, the **AIN** (Accelerated Inexact Newton) methods, contains methods like GMRES and GMRESR for linear systems, Arnoldi and Jacobi-Davidson for linear eigenproblems, and many variants of Newton's method, like Damped Newton, for general nonlinear problems. As numerical experiments suggest, the **AIN** approach may be useful for the construction of efficient schemes for solving nonlinear problems.

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Subspace methods for eigenproblems. In Chapter 6 we present two algorithms, one for computing a few solutions of the standard eigenproblem

$$Ax = \lambda x,$$

and one for the generalized eigenproblem

$$\beta Ax = \alpha Bx.$$

A very simple method for computing the dominant eigenvalue λ_{\max} of a symmetric matrix is the Power method. By dominant we mean that $|\lambda_{\max}| \gg |\lambda_i|$, where λ_i are all the other eigenvalues.

Starting with some vector v_1 , the method iterates with powers of A applied to v_1 . The ratio of the norm of the last two iterates converges to the absolute value of the dominant eigenvalue:

$$\frac{\|A^k v_1\|_2}{\|A^{k-1} v_1\|_2} \rightarrow |\lambda_{\max}|$$

For convergence it is necessary that v_1 has a component in the direction of the dominant eigenvector. This seems like a restriction, but in practice, using finite precision arithmetic, rounding errors provide such a component sooner or later. The speed of convergence depends on how well $|\lambda_{\max}|$ is separated from the absolute value of the other eigenvalues.

A more sophisticated method for the standard eigenproblem is the method of Arnoldi [2]. It uses a Krylov subspace as we have seen before in GMRES, and it suffers from the same restriction on the size of the subspace. Restarting may be a solution, but one should realize that by restarting valuable information is lost and that convergence may be set back. Moreover, identifying a suitable restart vector is not a trivial task [80, 83].

The method of Arnoldi constructs an orthogonal basis V_k such that

$$AV_k = V_k H_k + v_{k+1} h_{k+1,k} e_k^T,$$

where H_k is a $(k \times k)$ upper Hessenberg matrix. The matrix H_k can be seen as the projection of A onto $\mathcal{K}^k(A; v_1)$, i.e.,

$$V_k^T AV_k = H_k.$$

The dimension of the matrix H_k is in general much smaller than that of A . Hence, the eigenpairs of H_k can be computed easily using standard techniques available from, for instance, LAPACK [1].

If (θ, y) is an eigenpair of H_k , then the *Ritz pair* (θ, s) , with $s = V_k y$, is taken as an approximation to an eigenpair of A . θ is called a *Ritz value* with respect to V_k , and s is the corresponding *Ritz vector*.

It is well known that the speed of convergence of Ritz values is usually faster to exterior eigenvalues than to interior ones [98, 99]. The approximation of interior eigenvalues may be a problem, but this can be overcome by using so-called Shift-and-Invert [80] variants of Arnoldi's method. In these kind of methods the basis is built with the operator $(A - \sigma I)^{-1}$, which favors eigenvalues in the neighborhood of σ .

For the generalized eigenproblem there exists no method that is similar to the Arnoldi method for the standard eigenproblem. However, a variant of Shift-and-Invert Arnoldi does exist and the method constructs a basis using $(A - \sigma B)^{-1}B$ [80].

Another, more general, method for the generalized eigenproblem is the Rational Krylov Subspace method (RKS) [77, 78], which works with operators of the form

$$(\delta_k A - \gamma_k B)^{-1}(\sigma_k A - \rho_k B).$$

This operator may vary from iteration to iteration, in contrast to Shift-and-Invert Arnoldi, and the coefficients may be chosen such that convergence is improved for eigenvalues in specific regions of the complex plane.

However, a problem associated with these kind of methods is that they need the inversion of a matrix, which may be costly or even infeasible for large matrices.

Papers like [94, 58, 83] renewed interest in Arnoldi based algorithms. In these papers it is tried to overcome Arnoldi's main problem, i.e., convergence problems due to the limited size of the subspace, by incorporating sophisticated restart strategies.

The method in [83] applies Chebychev polynomials to the restarting vector in an attempt to damp unwanted components. This approach is helpful when computing a few exterior eigenvalues.

The Implicit Restarted Arnoldi (IRA) method, proposed in [94] and refined in [58], follows another approach and uses an *implicit shifted* QR [38, 95] mechanism to eliminate unwanted Ritz values from the Arnoldi subspace. It does so without the need for explicitly restarting the Arnoldi process, and thus avoids expensive matrix multiplications. The method is based on the following observations.

Suppose we have a k -dimensional basis for the Krylov subspace with Arnoldi's orthogonalization method, i.e., we have a $(n \times k)$ -matrix V_k and a $(k + 1) \times k$ Hessenberg matrix \bar{H}_k such that

$$AV_k = V_{k+1}\bar{H}_k.$$

One step of the shifted QR method with shift μ on \bar{H}_k yields

$$\bar{H}_k - \mu I = \bar{Q}_k R_k, \quad \bar{H}_{k-1}^+ := R_k \bar{Q}_{k-1} + \mu I,$$

where \bar{Q}_{k-1} is the $k \times (k-1)$ upper block of the $(k+1) \times k$ orthogonal Hessenberg matrix \bar{Q}_k and R_k is $k \times k$ upper triangular. Then \bar{H}_{k-1}^+ is also a $k \times (k-1)$ Hessenberg matrix and

$$\bar{Q}_k \bar{H}_{k-1}^+ = \bar{H}_k \bar{Q}_{k-1}.$$

With $V_{k-1}^+ = V_k \bar{Q}_{k-1}$ we see that

$$AV_{k-1}^+ = AV_k \bar{Q}_{k-1} = V_{k+1} \bar{H}_k \bar{Q}_{k-1} = V_{k+1} \bar{Q}_k \bar{H}_{k-1}^+ = V_k^+ \bar{H}_{k-1}^+,$$

which is an Arnoldi factorization of order $k-1$. Further

$$(A - \mu I)V_k = V_{k+1}(\bar{H}_k - \mu I) = V_{k+1} \bar{Q}_k R_k = V_k^+ R_k.$$

Since R_k is upper triangular, this shows that

$$(A - \mu I)v_1 = \gamma v_1^+,$$

which means that the columns of V_{k-1}^+ form an orthonormal basis of a new Krylov subspace of order $k-1$ generated by $(A - \mu I)v_1$. This approach can be repeated: if $\psi(\lambda) = (\lambda - \mu_1) \cdots (\lambda - \mu_p)$ then applying the shifted QR steps with shifts $\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_p$ yields an Arnoldi factorization $AV_{k-p}^{++} = V_{k-p+1} \bar{H}_{k-p}^{++}$ with orthogonal matrix V_{k-p}^{++} containing the orthogonal basis vectors of a Krylov subspace of order $k-p$ generated by $\psi(A)v_1$. Observe that the new Arnoldi factorization can be formed without additional matrix vector multiplications (by A) or inner products. The number of vector updates can be limited by forming the $(k \times (k-p))$ orthogonal transformation matrix first, before transforming V_k into V_{k-p}^{++} .

In [94] it is then suggested to apply the above sketched procedure p times to a $(k+p)$ -dimensional basis, using different unwanted Ritz values of H_k as shifts, thereby reducing it to a k -dimensional basis and filtering out the p unwanted Ritz values. The procedure is used iteratively through a repeated expansion and reduction of the subspace until convergence.

Numerical experiments in [59] show that this method is effective. The paper compares state-of-the-art software based on Arnoldi and “subspace iterations” methods, see, e.g., [97, 8, 33], which are generalizations of the power method and often suitable for computing dominant eigenvalues.

Another method for the standard eigenproblem is the method of Lanczos [56]. The method reduces the matrix A to a tridiagonal matrix T_k similar to the bi-Lanczos method for linear problems. Consequently, it shares the same kind of problems, but there is more. For one thing, there exists no efficient and reliable algorithm for computing eigenvalues of large unsymmetric tridiagonal matrices, in contrast to the symmetric case. This restricts the size of the subspaces. Also problematic is the appearance of so-called ghost eigenvalues during the computations. This undesirable phenomenon is caused by the loss of bi-orthogonality among the subspaces, which goes hand in hand with the convergence of Ritz values, when three-term recursions are used.

In [25, 23] it is tried to overcome this problem by heuristics to identify the ghost eigenvalues. The idea is that components of the starting vector play an essential role in the computation of desired eigenvalue approximations. It is suggested to compare Ritz values of the tridiagonal $(k \times k)$ -matrix T_k with Ritz values of its lower $(k - 1) \times (k - 1)$ part. The latter matrix can be seen as the projection of A onto the subspace from which the starting vector has been removed. Since information is missing in this projection, the ghost eigenvalues can now be identified: they appear as Ritz values of both matrices.

In [7] a different approach is followed. There, selective reorthogonalization of the subspaces is used to avoid the ghost eigenvalues [27]. The methods are quite useful if one wants to compute large (exterior) parts of the spectrum.

Just as for the Arnoldi and subspace iteration methods, there exist generalizations of Lanczos type methods for the generalized eigenproblem. However, they need the inversion of a matrix too, which may make them expensive for large problems.

For more details, we refer to the cited papers and the classical references for eigenvalue problems [109, 71]. Books that discuss state-of-the-art algorithms of the time are, e.g., [80, 20].

A new method for solving eigenproblems, introduced at the time of writing, is the Jacobi-Davidson method presented in [90]. The proposed method no longer uses a Krylov subspace. Instead, a subspace is generated by considering an optimal correction equation. The method works as follows.

Suppose we have an orthogonal subspace V_k and a Ritz pair (θ, s) , with residual

$$r = As - \theta s.$$

A correction for s is computed by solving

$$(I - ss^*)(A - \theta I)(I - ss^*)\Delta s = -r,$$

for $\Delta s \perp s$. This equation is motivated by the fact that, if θ is replaced by the exact eigenvalue λ , then $s + \Delta s$ is the corresponding eigenvector. This correction is used for expansion of the subspace and the procedure is repeated until convergence.

Solving exactly this correction equation yields asymptotically quadratical convergence for unsymmetric problems and cubical convergence for symmetric matrices. In practice however, it may be more efficient, to solve it approximately by, for example, an iterative method.

Extensions to the generalized eigenproblem and to higher order polynomial eigenproblems have been suggested in [84].

In Chapter 6 we extend the Jacobi-Davidson approach both for the standard eigenproblem as well as for the generalized eigenproblem with a restart strategy to make it more suitable for the computation of several eigenvalues. The extension is based on the reduction of the subspace to a partial Schur form.

The abstract of Chapter 6 is given below.

CHAPTER 6

Jacobi-Davidson style QR and QZ algorithms for the partial reduction of matrix pencils

Abstract.

The Jacobi-Davidson subspace iteration method offers possibilities for solving a variety of eigenproblems. In practice one has to apply restarts because of memory limitations, in order to restrict computational overhead, and also if one wants to compute several eigenvalues. In general, restarting has negative effects on the convergence of subspace methods. We will show how effective restarts can be incorporated in the Jacobi-Davidson subspace methods, very similar to the implicit restart procedure for the Arnoldi process. We will present two algorithms, JDQR for the standard eigenproblem, and JDQZ for the generalized eigenproblem, that are based on the iterative construction of the (generalized) partial Schur form with the Jacobi-Davidson subspace approach. The algorithms are suitable for the efficient computation of several (even multiple) eigenvalues, and the corresponding eigenvectors, near a user-specified target value in the complex plane.

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CHAPTER 1

NESTED KRYLOV METHODS AND PRESERVING THE ORTHOGONALITY

E. DE STURLER AND D. R. FOKKEMA

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Abstract. The GMRESR [105] inner-outer iteration scheme for the solution of linear systems of equations was proposed by Van der Vorst and Vuik. Similar methods have been proposed by Axelsson and Vassilevski [5], and Saad (FGMRES) [81]. The outer iteration is GCR, which minimizes the residual over a given subspace. The inner iteration is GMRES, which at each step computes an expansion for the subspace by approximately solving a correction equation. However, the optimality of the approximation over the outer subspace is ignored in the inner iteration. This leads to suboptimal corrections to the solution in the outer iteration, as parts of the outer subspace may reenter in the inner iteration process. Therefore we propose to preserve the orthogonality relations of GCR also in the inner iteration. This gives optimal corrections, however, it involves working with a singular, nonsymmetric operator. We will discuss some important properties and we will show by experiments, that in terms of matrix vector products this modification (almost) always leads to better convergence. However, because we do more orthogonalizations, it does not always give an improved performance in CPU-time. Furthermore, we will discuss an efficient implementation as well as truncation possibilities of the outer GCR process. Of course, we can also use other iteration schemes than GMRES as the inner method. Methods with short recurrences like Bi-CGSTAB seem especially interesting. The experimental results indicate that, especially for such methods, it is advantageous to preserve the orthogonality in the inner iteration.

Key words. Nonsymmetric linear systems, Iterative solvers, Krylov subspace, GMRES, GMRESR, Bi-CGSTAB, Truncation

AMS subject classification. 65F10

1.1. Introduction. For the solution of systems of linear equations the so-called Krylov subspace methods are very popular. However, for general matrices no Krylov method can satisfy a global optimality requirement and have short recurrences [35]. Therefore, either restarted or truncated versions of optimal methods, such as GMRES(m) [82], may be used. Alternatively, one may use methods with short recurrences, which do not satisfy a global optimality requirement, such as Bi-CG [36], Bi-CGSTAB [102], BiCGstab(ℓ) [85], CGS [93] or QMR [41]. Van der Vorst and Vuik introduced a new type of method, GMRESR [105], see ALG. 1.2, which is a nested GMRES method.

The GMRESR algorithm is based upon GCR [34], see ALG. 1.1. For a given initial guess x_0 , both GCR and GMRESR compute approximate solutions x_k , such that $x_k - x_0 \in \text{span}\{\hat{u}_1, \hat{u}_2, \dots, \hat{u}_k\}$ and $\|r_k\|_2 = \|b - Ax_k\|_2$ is minimal. The difference lies in the choice of the direction vectors \hat{u}_k . GCR sets \hat{u}_k simply to the residual r_{k-1} , while GMRESR sets \hat{u}_k to the approximate solution as produced by m steps of GMRES, when solving the correction equation $Ae_{k-1} = r_{k-1}$ (represented by $\mathcal{P}_{m,k}(A)r_{k-1}$ in ALG. 1.2). For efficiency and stability reasons, the basis $U_k = [u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k]$ for the direction vectors is used, and constructed such that $C_k = [Au_1, Au_2, \dots, Au_k]$ is orthogonal. In more detail, the algorithms can be explained as follows.

Assume we are given the system of equations $Ax = b$, where A is a real, nonsingular, linear ($n \times n$)-matrix and b is a n -vector. Let U_k and C_k be two ($n \times k$)-matrices for which

$$(1.1) \quad C_k = AU_k, \quad C_k^T C_k = I_k,$$

and let x_0 be an initial guess. For $x_k - x_0 \in \text{span}\{U_k\}$ the minimization problem

$$(1.2) \quad \|b - Ax_k\|_2 = \min_{x \in \text{span}\{U_k\}} \|r_0 - Ax\|_2.$$

is solved by

$$x_k = x_0 + U_k C_k^T r_0$$

and $r_k = b - Ax_k$ satisfies

$$(1.3) \quad r_k = r_0 - C_k C_k^T r_0, \quad r_k \perp \text{span}\{C_k\}.$$

In fact we have constructed the inverse of the restriction of A to $\text{span}\{U_k\}$ onto $\text{span}\{C_k\}$. This inverse is given by

$$A^{-1} C_k C_k^T = U_k C_k^T.$$

```

Choose  $x_0$  and  $tol$ 
 $r_0 = b - Ax_0$ 
 $k = 0$ 
while  $\|r_k\|_2 > tol$  do
   $k = k + 1$ 
   $\hat{u}_k = r_{k-1}$ 
   $\hat{c}_k = A\hat{u}_k$ 
  for  $i = 1, \dots, k - 1$  do
     $\alpha_{i,k} = c_i^T \hat{c}_k$ 
     $\hat{c}_k = \hat{c}_k - \alpha_{i,k} c_i$ 
     $\hat{u}_k = \hat{u}_k - \alpha_{i,k} u_i$ 
  enddo
   $\alpha_{k,k} = \|\hat{c}_k\|_2$ 
   $u_k = \hat{u}_k / \alpha_{k,k}$ 
   $c_k = \hat{c}_k / \alpha_{k,k}$ 
   $\gamma_k = c_k^T r_{k-1}$ 
   $x_k = x_{k-1} + \gamma_k u_k$ 
   $r_k = r_{k-1} - \gamma_k c_k$ 
endwhile

```

ALGORITHM 1.1. GCR

```

Choose  $x_0$ ,  $m$ , and  $tol$ 
 $r_0 = b - Ax_0$ 
 $k = 0$ 
while  $\|r_k\|_2 > tol$  do
   $k = k + 1$ 
   $\hat{u}_k = \mathcal{P}_{m,k}(A)r_{k-1}$ 
   $\hat{c}_k = A\hat{u}_k$ 
  for  $i = 1, \dots, k - 1$  do
     $\alpha_{i,k} = c_i^T \hat{c}_k$ 
     $\hat{c}_k = \hat{c}_k - \alpha_{i,k} c_i$ 
     $\hat{u}_k = \hat{u}_k - \alpha_{i,k} u_i$ 
  enddo
   $\alpha_{k,k} = \|\hat{c}_k\|_2$ 
   $u_k = \hat{u}_k / \alpha_{k,k}$ 
   $c_k = \hat{c}_k / \alpha_{k,k}$ 
   $\gamma_k = c_k^T r_{k-1}$ 
   $x_k = x_{k-1} + \gamma_k u_k$ 
   $r_k = r_{k-1} - \gamma_k c_k$ 
endwhile

```

$\mathcal{P}_{m,k}(A)$ indicates the GMRES polynomial, that is implicitly constructed in m steps of GMRES, when solving the correction equation $Ae_{k-1} = r_{k-1}$.

ALGORITHM 1.2. GMRESR(m)

This principle underlies the GCR method. In GCR the matrices U_k and C_k are constructed such that $\text{span}\{U_k\}$ is equal to the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}^k(A; r_0) = \text{span}\{r_0, Ar_0, \dots, A^{k-1}r_0\}$. Provided GCR does not break down, i.e., if $c_k \not\perp r_{k-1}$, it is a finite method and at step k it solves the minimization problem (1.2).

But obviously, we may construct other matrices U_k and C_k : replacing r_{k-1} in the step $\hat{u}_k = r_{k-1}$ (in GCR) by any other vector, results in an algorithm that still solves (1.2). The $\text{span}\{U_k\}$ will be different from $\mathcal{K}^k(A; r_0)$, of course. The optimal, but infeasible, choice would be $\hat{u}_k = e_{k-1}$, where e_{k-1} is the error

$x - x_{k-1}$. Fortunately, we can find approximations to e_{k-1} , by using the relation

$$(1.4) \quad Ae_{k-1} = r_{k-1}.$$

Any method which gives an approximate solution to this correction equation can be used to find acceptable choices for \hat{u}_k . In the GMRESR algorithm m steps of GMRES are chosen to find such an approximation.

However, since we already have an optimal x_{k-1} , such that r_{k-1} is orthogonal to $\text{span}\{C_{k-1}\}$, we need also an approximation \hat{u}_k (to e_{k-1}), such that $A\hat{u}_k$ is orthogonal to $\text{span}\{C_{k-1}\}$. Such an approximation is computed explicitly by the orthogonalization loop in the outer GCR iteration. Because in GMRESR this is not taken into account in the inner GMRES iteration, a less than optimal minimization problem is solved, leading to suboptimal corrections to the residual.

Another disadvantage of GMRESR is that the inner iteration is essentially a restarted GMRES. It therefore also displays some of the problems of restarted GMRES. Most notably it can have the tendency to stagnate (see also our numerical experiments in Section 1.5).

From this we infer, that it might be more favorable to preserve the orthogonality of the correction to the residual also in the inner GMRES iteration.

Combining (1.3) and (1.4) leads to the following observation

$$\begin{aligned} Ae_{k-1} &= (I - C_{k-1}C_{k-1}^T)Ae_{k-1} \\ &= A(I - U_{k-1}C_{k-1}^T A)e_{k-1} \\ &= (I - C_{k-1}C_{k-1}^T)A(I - U_{k-1}C_{k-1}^T A)e_{k-1} \\ &= r_{k-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Denoting $P_k = C_k C_k^T$ and $Q_k = U_k C_k^T A$, we can formulate the *projected* correction equation: solve $e_{k-1} \perp A^T C_{k-1}$ such that

$$(1.5) \quad \begin{cases} e_{k-1} = (I - Q_{k-1})e_{k-1}, & \text{and} \\ (I - P_{k-1})A(I - Q_{k-1})e_{k-1} = r_{k-1}. \end{cases}$$

If \hat{u}_k is an approximate solution orthogonal to $A^T C_{k-1}$ then $(I - Q_{k-1})\hat{u}_k = \hat{u}_k$ and $A\hat{u}_k$ is a proper correction to the residual.

The resulting variant GCRO of the GMRESR iteration scheme, which has an improved performance for many problems (see also our numerical experiments in Section 1.5), is given in ALG. 1.3. Note that the outer orthogonalizations are not necessary anymore.

```

Choose  $x_0$  and  $tol$ 
 $r_0 = b - Ax_0$ 
 $U_0 = []$ ;  $C_0 = []$ ;
 $k = 0$ 
while  $\|r_k\|_2 > tol$  do
   $k = k + 1$ 
  Solve  $\hat{u}_k$  (approximately) from:
    
$$\begin{cases} \hat{u}_k = (I - U_{k-1}C_{k-1}^T A)\hat{u}_k & \text{and} \\ (I - C_{k-1}C_{k-1}^T)A(I - U_{k-1}C_{k-1}^T A)\hat{u}_k = r_{k-1} \end{cases}$$

   $\hat{c}_k = A\hat{u}_k$ 
   $\alpha_{k,k} = \|\hat{c}_k\|_2$ 
   $u_k = \hat{u}_k/\alpha_{k,k}$ ,  $U_k = [U_{k-1}, u_k]$ ;
   $c_k = \hat{c}_k/\alpha_{k,k}$ ,  $C_k = [C_{k-1}, c_k]$ ;
   $\gamma_k = c_k^T r_{k-1}$ 
   $x_k = x_{k-1} + \gamma_k u_k$ 
   $r_k = r_{k-1} - \gamma_k c_k$ 
endwhile

```

ALGORITHM 1.3. Generic GCRO

In the next section we will discuss the implications of the projections, when using GMRES as the inner method. We will see that this leads to an optimal approximation over the space spanned by both the outer and the inner iteration vectors. It also introduces a potential problem: the possibility of breakdown in the generation of the Krylov space in the inner iteration, since we iterate with a singular operator. It will turn out, however, that such a breakdown not only can never happen before a specific (generally large) number of iterations, but is also easily repaired.

In Section 1.3 we will present an efficient implementation of GCRO with GMRES as an inner method. In Section 1.4 we will propose a truncation strategy for the outer GCR iteration and discuss its implementation. In Section 1.5 we will discuss results of some numerical experiments. Some concluding remarks are in Section 1.6.

1.2. Consequences of inner orthogonalization. This section involves a theoretical discussion of optimality, the possibility of breakdown, and the continuation after breakdown. For the theorems, we will only give a short indication of the proofs or omit them completely. The proofs can be found in [28]. Throughout the rest of this article we will use the following notations:

- By A_k we denote the operator defined as $A_k \equiv (I - P_k)A(I - Q_k)$
- By $V_m = [v_1, \dots, v_m]$ we denote the orthonormal matrix generated by m steps of Arnoldi with A_k and such that $v_1 = r_k / \|r_k\|_2$.

Observe that, since $AQ_k = P_kA$, the following relations hold

$$A_k = (I - P_k)A(I - Q_k) = (I - P_k)A = A(I - Q_k).$$

By construction, the inner GMRES process delivers the optimal correction to the approximate solution x_{k+1} over the “global” space $\text{span}\{U_{k+1}, V_m\}$. This is formulated in the next theorem.

THEOREM 1.1. *The Arnoldi process in the inner GMRES iteration defines the relation $A_k V_m = V_{m+1} \bar{H}_m$, with \bar{H}_m an $((m+1) \times m)$ -Hessenberg matrix. Let y be defined by*

$$(1.6) \quad y : \min_{\tilde{y} \in \mathbb{R}^m} \|r_k - A_k V_m \tilde{y}\|_2 = \min_{\tilde{y} \in \mathbb{R}^m} \|r_k - V_{m+1} \bar{H}_m \tilde{y}\|_2.$$

Then the minimal residual solution of the inner GMRES iteration, $((I - Q_k)V_m y)$, gives the outer approximation

$$(1.7) \quad x_{k+1} = x_k + (I - Q_k)V_m y,$$

which is also the solution to the “global” minimization problem

$$(1.8) \quad x_{k+1} : \min_{\tilde{x} \in \text{span}\{U_k, V_m\}} \|b - A\tilde{x}\|_2.$$

REMARK 1.1. From this theorem it follows, that the residual computed in the inner GMRES iteration equals the residual of the outer GCR iteration: $r_{k+1} = r_k - A_k V_m y$. Apparently, $\hat{u}_{k+1} = ((I - Q_k)V_m y)$ and $\hat{c}_{k+1} = A_k V_m y$. Observe, that $A_k V_m y$ is easily computed from the relation $A_k V_m y = V_{m+1} \bar{H}_m y$. Additionally, as a result of using GMRES in the inner iteration, the norm of the residual r_{k+1} as well as the norm of \hat{c}_k ($\alpha_{k,k}$) are already known at no extra computational costs (cf. [82]). It even follows that $\gamma_k = c_k^T r_k = \alpha_{k,k}$. Consequently, the outer GCR iteration becomes very simple.

We will now consider the possibility of breakdown, when generating a Krylov space with a singular, nonsymmetric operator. Although GMRES is still optimal in the sense that at each iteration it delivers the minimum residual solution over the generated Krylov subspace, the generation of the Krylov subspace itself, from a singular operator, may terminate too early. The following simple example shows that this may happen before the solution is found, even when the solution and the right hand side are both in the range of the given (singular) operator and in the orthogonal complement of its null-space.

Define the matrix $A = (e_2 \ e_3 \ e_4 \ 0)$, where e_i denotes the i -th Cartesian basis vector. Note that $A = (I - e_1 e_1^T)(e_2 \ e_3 \ e_4 \ e_1)$, which is the same type of operator as A_k , an orthogonal projection times a nonsingular operator. Now consider the system of equations $Ax = e_3$. Then GMRES (or any other Krylov method) will search for a solution in the space

$$\text{span}\{e_3, Ae_3, A^2e_3, \dots\} = \text{span}\{e_3, e_4, 0, 0, \dots\}.$$

So we have a breakdown of the Krylov space and the solution is not contained in it.

In the remainder of this section we will show that a breakdown in the inner GMRES method cannot occur, before the total number of iterations exceeds the dimension of the Krylov space $\mathcal{K}(A; r_0)$. This means that, in practice, a breakdown will be rare. Furthermore, we will show how such a breakdown can be overcome.

We will now define breakdown of the Krylov space for the inner GMRES iteration more formally.

DEFINITION 1.1. We say to have a breakdown of the Krylov subspace in the inner GMRES iteration if $A_k v_m \in \text{span}\{V_m\}$, since this implies we can no longer expand the Krylov subspace. We call it a *lucky breakdown* if $v_1 \in \text{span}\{A_k V_m\}$, because we then have found the solution (the inverse of A is known over the space $\text{span}\{A_k V_m\}$). We call it a *true breakdown* if $v_1 \notin \text{span}\{A_k V_m\}$, because then the solution is not contained in the Krylov subspace.

The following theorem relates true breakdown to the invariance of the sequence of subspaces in the inner method for the operator A_k . Part four indicates, that it is always known, whether a breakdown is true or lucky.

THEOREM 1.2. *The following statements are equivalent:*

1. *A true breakdown occurs in the inner GMRES iteration at step m*

2. $\text{span}\{A_k V_{m-1}\}$ is an invariant subspace of A_k
3. $A_k v_m \in \text{span}\{A_k V_{m-1}\}$
4. $A_k V_m = V_m \bar{H}_m$, and \bar{H}_m is a singular ($m \times m$) matrix.

From THEOREM 1.1, one can already conclude that a true breakdown occurs if and only if A_k is singular over $\mathcal{K}^m(A_k; r_k)$. From the definition of A_k we know $\text{null}\{A_k\} = \text{span}\{U_k\}$. We will make this more explicit in the following theorem, which relates true breakdown to the intersection of the inner search space and the outer search space.

THEOREM 1.3. *A true breakdown occurs if and only if*

$$\text{span}\{V_m\} \cap \text{span}\{U_k\} \neq \{0\}.$$

The following theorem indicates, that no true breakdown in the inner GMRES iteration can occur, before the total number of iterations exceeds the dimension of the Krylov space $\mathcal{K}(A; r_0)$.

THEOREM 1.4. *Let $m = \dim(\mathcal{K}(A; r_0))$ and let l be such that $r_k = \mathcal{P}_l(A)r_0$ for some polynomial \mathcal{P}_l of degree l . Then*

$$\dim(\mathcal{K}^{j+1}(A_k; r_0)) = j + 1 \quad \text{for } j + l < m$$

and therefore no true breakdown occurs in the first j steps of the inner GMRES iteration.

We will now show how a true breakdown can be overcome. There are basically two ways to continue:

- *In the inner iteration:* by finding a suitable vector to expand the Krylov space
- *In the outer iteration:* by computing the solution of the inner iteration just before the true breakdown and then by making one LSQR-step (see below) in the outer iteration.

We will consider the continuation in the inner GMRES iteration first. The following theorem indicates how one can continue the generation of the Krylov space $\mathcal{K}(A; r_k)$ if in the inner GMRES iteration a true breakdown occurs.

THEOREM 1.5. *If a true breakdown occurs in the inner GMRES iteration then*

$$\exists c \in \text{span}\{C_k\} : A_k c \notin \text{span}\{A_k V_{m-1}\}.$$

This implies that one can try the vectors c_i until one of them works. However, one should realize that the minimization problem (1.6) is slightly more complicated.

Another way to continue after a true breakdown in the inner GMRES iteration is to compute the inner iteration solution just before the breakdown and then apply a LSQR-switch (see below) in the outer GCR iteration. The following theorem states the reason why one has to apply a LSQR-switch.

THEOREM 1.6. *Suppose one computes the solution of the inner GMRES iteration just before a true breakdown. Then stagnation will occur in the next inner iteration, that is $r_{k+1} \perp \mathcal{K}(A_{k+1}; r_{k+1})$. This will lead to a breakdown of the outer GCR iteration.*

The reason for this stagnation in the inner GMRES iteration is that the new residual r_{k+1} remains in the same Krylov space $\mathcal{K}(A_k; r_k)$, which contains a $u \in \text{span}\{U_k\}$. So we have to “leave” this Krylov space. We can do this using the so-called LSQR-switch, which was introduced in [105], to remedy stagnation in the inner GMRES iteration. Just as in the GMRESR method, stagnation in the inner GMRES iteration will result in a breakdown in the outer GCR iteration, because the residual cannot be updated. The following theorem states that this LSQR-switch actually works.

THEOREM 1.7. *If stagnation occurs in the inner GMRES iteration, that is if*

$$\min_{\tilde{y} \in \mathbb{R}^m} \|r_{k+1} - A_k V_m \tilde{y}\|_2 = \|r_{k+1}\|_2,$$

then one can continue by setting (LSQR-switch)

$$\begin{aligned} u_{k+2} &= \gamma(I - Q_{k+1})A^T r_{k+1}, \quad \text{and} \\ c_{k+2} &= \gamma A_{k+1} A^T r_{k+1}, \end{aligned}$$

where γ is a normalization constant. This leads to

$$\begin{aligned} x_{k+2} &= x_{k+1} - (r_{k+1}^T c_{k+2})u_{k+2}, \quad \text{and} \\ r_{k+2} &= r_{k+1} - (r_{k+1}^T c_{k+2})c_{k+2}, \end{aligned}$$

which always gives an improved approximation. Therefore, these vectors can be used as the start vectors for a new inner GMRES iteration.

1.3. Implementation. In this section we will describe how to implement GCRO with GMRES as the inner method efficiently. We begin by showing that GCR and GMRESR can be implemented more efficiently by incorporating an implicit representation of U_k . We then show how to incorporate a similar representation of U_k in GCRO in combination with GMRES. The implementation of GCRO with a method like Bi-CGSTAB in the inner iteration will then be obvious (see also [28]).

1.3.1. GCR and GMRESR. GCR and GMRESR can be implemented more efficiently as follows. Observe that with (cf. ALG. 1.1 and ALG. 1.2)

$$\widehat{U}_k = [\widehat{u}_1, \widehat{u}_2, \dots, \widehat{u}_k], \quad Z_k = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{1,1} & \alpha_{1,2} & \cdots & \alpha_{1,k} \\ 0 & \alpha_{2,2} & & \alpha_{2,k} \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & \alpha_{k,k} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{and} \quad d_k = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_1 \\ \gamma_2 \\ \vdots \\ \gamma_k \end{bmatrix},$$

it follows that

$$(1.9) \quad A\widehat{U}_k = C_k Z_k,$$

and that the approximate solution x_k , corresponding to r_k , can be written implicitly as

$$(1.10) \quad x_k = x_0 + \widehat{U}_k Z_k^{-1} d_k.$$

Using this relation, x_k can be computed at the end of the complete iteration. The implicit representation of $U_k = \widehat{U}_k Z_k^{-1}$ saves all the intermediate updates of previous u_i to a new u_{k+1} , which is approximately 30% of the computational costs in the outer iteration of both GCR and GMRESR.

1.3.2. GCRO with GMRES as inner iteration. We can save computational work in GCRO with GMRES as inner iteration in a similar way. In the inner GMRES iteration we construct the orthogonal matrix V_m such that

$$(1.11) \quad AV_m = C_k B_m + V_{m+1} \bar{H}_m, \quad \text{for} \quad B_m \equiv C_k^T AV_m.$$

This can be done with the usual GMRES algorithm [82], in which the vectors Av_i are first orthogonalized on C_k . From (1.11) it is obvious that $AV_m - C_k B_m = A_k V_m = V_{m+1} \bar{H}_m$ (cf. THEOREM 1.1). Now observe that (cf. ALG. 1.3), with y according to (1.6),

$$\alpha_{k,k} u_k = (I - Q_k) V_m y = V_m y - U_k B_m y.$$

Setting

$$\widehat{u}_k = V_m y \quad \text{and} \quad Z_{1\dots k,k} = \begin{bmatrix} B_m y \\ \alpha_{k,k} \end{bmatrix}$$

again leads to a relation of the form $U_k = \widehat{U}_k Z_k^{-1}$. An implementation based on this relation is given in ALG. 1.4. It also incorporates the observations made in REMARK 1.1.

1.4. Truncation. In practice, since memory space may be limited and since the method becomes increasingly expensive for large k (the number of outer search vectors), we want to truncate the set of outer iteration vectors (\widehat{u}_i) and (c_i) at $k = k_{\max}$, where k_{\max} is some positive integer. Basically, there are two ways to do this: one can discard one or more iteration vector(s) (dropping) or one can assemble two or more iteration vectors into one single iteration vector (assembly). We will first discuss the strategy for truncation and then its implementation.

1.4.1. A strategy for truncation. In each outer iteration step the matrices \widehat{U}_k and C_k are augmented with one extra column. To keep the memory requirement constant, at step $k = k_{\max}$, it is therefore sufficient to diminish the matrices $\widehat{U}_{k_{\max}}$ and $C_{k_{\max}}$ by one column. From (1.10) we have $x_k = x_0 + \widehat{U}_k Z_k^{-1} d_k$. Denote $\xi_k = Z_k^{-1} d_k$. Consider the sequence of vectors (ξ_k) . The components $\xi_k^{(i)}$ of these vectors ξ_k are the coefficients for the updates \widehat{u}_i of the approximate solution x_k . These coefficients $\xi_k^{(i)}$ converge to the limits $\xi^{(i)}$ as k increases. Moreover, $(\xi_k^{(1)})$ converges faster than $(\xi_k^{(2)})$, and $(\xi_k^{(2)})$ converges faster than $(\xi_k^{(3)})$ etc.. Suppose that the sequence $(\xi_k^{(1)})$ has converged to $\xi^{(1)}$ within machine precision. From then on it makes no difference for the computation of x_k when we perform the update $x_0 + \xi^{(1)} \widehat{u}_1$. In terms of direction vectors this means that the outer direction vector \widehat{u}_1 will not reenter as component in the inner iteration process. Therefore one might hope that discarding the vector c_1 will not spoil the convergence. This leads to the idea of dropping the vector $c_1 (= A \widehat{u}_1)$ or of assembling c_1 with c_2 into \tilde{c} (say) when

$$(1.12) \quad \delta(k) = \left| \frac{\xi_k^{(1)} - \xi_{k-1}^{(1)}}{\xi_k^{(1)}} \right| < \epsilon,$$

where $\epsilon > 0$ is a small constant. The optimal ϵ , which may depend on k , can be determined from experiments. When $\delta(k) > \epsilon$ we drop $c_{k_{\max}-1}$ or we assemble $c_{k_{\max}-1}$ and $c_{k_{\max}}$ (of course other choices are feasible as well, but we will not consider them in this article). With this strategy we hope to avoid stagnation by

```

Choose  $x_0$ ,  $m$ , and  $tol$ 
 $r_0 = b - Ax_0$ 
 $\beta = \|r_0\|_2$ 
 $l = 0$ 
while  $\beta > tol$  do
   $l = l + 1$ 
   $v_1 = r_{l-1}/\beta$ 
   $t = \beta e_1$ 
   $k = 0$ 
  while  $\beta > tol$  and  $k < m$  do
     $k = k + 1$ 
     $\tilde{v} = Av_k$ 
    for  $j = 1, 2, \dots, l - 1$  do
       $B_{j,k} = (c_j, \tilde{v}), \quad \tilde{v} = \tilde{v} - B_{j,k}c_j$ 
    enddo
    for  $j = 1, 2, \dots, k$  do
       $\bar{H}_{j,k} = (v_j, \tilde{v}), \quad \tilde{v} = \tilde{v} - \bar{H}_{j,k}v_j$ 
    enddo
     $\bar{H}_{k+1,k} = \|\tilde{v}\|_2, \quad v_{k+1} = \tilde{v}/\bar{H}_{k+1,k}$ 
     $S_{1\dots k+1,k} = G_{k-1} \cdots G_1 \bar{H}_{1\dots k+1,k}$ 
    Construct and apply the Givens rotation
     $G_k$  to  $S_{1\dots k+1,k}$  such that its last element be-
    comes zero.
     $t = G_k t$ 
     $\beta = |t_{k+1}|$ 
  endwhile
   $\hat{t} = (t_1 \dots t_k)^T$ 
   $y = S^{-1} \hat{t}$ 
   $(z_{1,l} \dots z_{l-1,l})^T = By$ 
   $\gamma_l = \alpha_{l,l} = \|\hat{t}\|_2$ 
   $d_l = \gamma_l, \quad z_{l,l} = \alpha_{l,l}$ 
   $\hat{u}_l = V_k y$ 
   $\hat{c}_l = V_{k+1} \bar{H} y$ 
   $r_l = r_{l-1} - \hat{c}_l$ 
   $c_l = \hat{c}_l / \gamma_l$ 
endwhile
 $x = x_0 + \hat{U}_l Z^{-1} d_l$ 

```

ALGORITHM 1.4. Efficient GCRO(m) with GMRES as the inner iteration method.

keeping the most relevant part of the subspace $\text{span}\{C_k\}$ in store as a subspace of dimension $k - 1$. In the next subsections we describe how to implement this strategy and its consequences for the matrices C_k and \widehat{U}_k .

1.4.2. Dropping a vector. Let $1 \leq j \leq k = k_{\max}$. Dropping the column c_j is easy. We can discard it without consequences. So let C'_{k-1} be the matrix C_k without the column c_j . Dropping a column from \widehat{U}_k needs more work, since x_k is computed as $x_k = x_0 + \widehat{U}_k Z_k^{-1} d_k$. Moreover, in order to be able to apply the same dropping strategy in the next outer iteration we have to be able to compute x_{k+1} in a similar way. For that purpose, assume that x_k can be computed as

$$(1.13) \quad x_k = x'_{k-1} = x'_0 + \widehat{U}'_{k-1} (Z'_{k-1})^{-1} d'_{k-1},$$

where \widehat{U}'_{k-1} and Z'_{k-1} are matrices such that $A\widehat{U}'_{k-1} = C'_{k-1}Z'_{k-1}$ (see (1.9)). These matrices \widehat{U}'_{k-1} and Z'_{k-1} are easily computed by using the j -th row of (1.9) to eliminate the j -th column of C_k in (1.9). In order to determine x'_0 and d'_{k-1} we use that $U_k = \widehat{U}_k Z_k^{-1}$, which allows us to write

$$x_k = (x_0 + d_k^{(j)} u_j) + \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq j}}^k d_k^{(i)} u_i \quad \text{and} \quad u_j = (\widehat{u}_j - \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} z_{ij} u_i) / z_{jj}.$$

Substituting the equation for u_j into the equation for x_k we can compute x_k from

$$x_k = (x_0 + \frac{d_k^{(j)}}{z_{jj}} \widehat{u}_j) + \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} (d_k^{(i)} - d_k^{(j)} \frac{z_{ij}}{z_{jj}}) u_i + \sum_{i=j+1}^k d_k^{(i)} u_i.$$

Notice that this equation precisely defines x'_0 and d'_{k-1} :

$$\begin{aligned} x'_0 &= x_0 + (d_k^{(j)} / z_{jj}) \widehat{u}_j, \\ d_{k-1}^{(i)'} &= d_k^{(i)} - d_k^{(j)} (z_{ij} / z_{jj}), \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, j-1 \text{ and} \\ d_{k-1}^{(i)'} &= d_k^{(i+1)}, \quad \text{for } i = j, \dots, k-1. \end{aligned}$$

Now we have deallocated two vectors and we compute x_k as in (1.13). We can continue the algorithm.

1.4.3. Assembly of two vectors. Let $1 \leq j < l \leq k = k_{\max}$. Again assembling c_j and c_l is easy. Let $\tilde{c} = (d_k^{(j)}c_j + d_k^{(l)}c_l)$ overwrite the l -th column of C_k . Then, let C'_{k-1} be this new matrix C_k without the j -th column. Analogous to the above, we wish to compute x_k as (1.13). For the purpose of determining the matrices \widehat{U}'_{k-1} and Z'_{k-1} , let $\tilde{u} = (d_k^{(j)}u_j + d_k^{(l)}u_l)$ and compute $t_1^{(m)}$ and $t_2^{(m)}$ such that

$$z_{jm}u_j + z_{lm}u_l + t_1^{(m)}u_j = t_2^{(m)}\tilde{u},$$

which gives $t_1^{(m)} = z_{lm}(d_k^{(j)}/d_k^{(l)}) - z_{jm}$ and $t_2^{(m)} = z_{lm}/d_k^{(l)}$. This enables us to write

$$(1.14) \quad \widehat{u}_m = \sum_{i=1}^m z_{im}u_i, \quad \text{for } m = 1, \dots, j-1$$

$$(1.15) \quad \widehat{u}_m = \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq j, l}}^m z_{im}u_i + t_2^{(m)}\tilde{u} - t_1^{(m)}u_j, \quad \text{for } m = j, \dots, k.$$

Substituting $u_j = (\widehat{u}_j - \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} z_{ij}u_i)/z_{jj}$, to eliminate u_j from (1.15) we get

$$\widehat{u}_m = \sum_{i=1}^m z_{im}u_i, \quad \text{for } m = 1, \dots, j-1$$

$$\widehat{u}_m + \frac{t_1^{(m)}}{z_{jj}}\widehat{u}_j = \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq j, l}}^m (z_{im} + t_1^{(m)}\frac{z_{ij}}{z_{jj}})u_i + t_2^{(m)}\tilde{u}, \quad \text{for } m = j+1, \dots, k.$$

This equation determines the matrices \widehat{U}'_{k-1} and Z'_{k-1} . In order to determine x'_0 and d'_{k-1} , note that x_k can be computed as

$$x_k = x_0 + \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq j, l}}^k d_k^{(i)}u_i + \tilde{u}.$$

Therefore x'_0 is just x_0 and d'_{k-1} equals the vector d_k without the j -th element and the l -th element overwritten by 1. Similarly as before, we have deallocated two vectors from memory. The assembled vectors \tilde{u} and \tilde{c} overwrite \widehat{u}_l and \widehat{c}_l . The locations of \widehat{u}_j and \widehat{c}_j can therefore be used in the next step.

Finally, we remark that these computations can be done with rank one updates.

1.5. Numerical experiments. We will discuss the results of some numerical experiments, which concern the solution of two dimensional convection diffusion problems on regular grids, discretized using a finite volume technique, resulting in a pentadiagonal matrix. The system is preconditioned with ILU applied to the scaled system, see [32, 62]. The first two problems are used to illustrate and compare the following solvers:

- (full) GMRES
- Bi-CGSTAB
- GMRESR(m), where m indicates the number of inner GMRES iterations between the outer iterations
- GCRO(m), which is GCR with m adapted GMRES iterations as inner method, using A_k (cf. ALG. 1.4)
- GMRESRSTAB, which is GMRESR with Bi-CGSTAB as the inner method
- GCROSTAB, which is GCRO with the adapted Bi-CGSTAB algorithm as inner method, using A_k .

We will compare the convergence of these methods both with respect to the number of matrix vector products and with respect to CPU-time on one processor of the Convex 3840. This means, e.g., that each step of Bi-CGSTAB (and variants) is counted for two matrix vector products. We give both these convergence rates because the main trade off between (full) GMRES, the GCRO variants and the GMRESR variants is less iterations against more dot products and vector updates per iteration. Any gain in CPU-time, then depends on the relative cost of the matrix vector multiplication and preconditioning versus the orthogonalization cost on the one hand and on the difference in iterations on the other hand. We will use our third problem to show the effects of truncation and compare two strategies.

1.5.1. Problem 1. This problem comes from the discretization of

$$-(u_{xx} + u_{yy}) + bu_x + cu_y = 0$$

on $[0, 1] \times [0, 4]$, where

$$b(x, y) = \begin{cases} 100 & \text{for } 0 \leq y < 1 \quad \text{and} \quad 2 \leq y < 3 \\ -100 & \text{for } 1 \leq y < 2 \quad \text{and} \quad 3 \leq y \leq 4 \end{cases}$$

and $c = 100$. The boundary conditions are $u = 1$ on $y = 0$, $u = 0$ on $y = 4$, $u' = 0$ on $x = 0$ and $u' = 0$ on $x = 1$, where u' denotes the (outward) normal derivative. The stepsize in x -direction is $1/100$ and in y -direction is $1/50$.

FIGURE 1.1. Convergence history for problem 1.

In this example we compare the performances of GMRES, GCRO(m) and GMRESR(m), for $m = 5$ and $m = 10$. The convergence history of problem 1 is given in FIG. 1.1 and FIG. 1.2. FIG. 1.1 shows that GMRES converges fastest (in matrix vector products), which is of course to be expected, followed by GCRO(5), GMRESR(5), GCRO(10) and GMRESR(10). From FIG. 1.1 we also see that GCRO(m) converges smoother and faster than GMRESR(m). Note that GCRO(5) has practically the same convergence behavior as GMRES. The vertical “steps” of GMRESR(m) are caused by the optimization in the outer GCR iteration, which does not involve a matrix vector multiplication.

We also observe that the GMRESR(m) variants tend to lose their super-linear convergence behavior, at least during certain stages of the convergence history. This seems to be caused by stagnation or slow convergence in the inner GMRES iteration, which (of course) essentially behaves like a restarted GMRES. For GCRO(m), however, we see a much smoother and faster convergence behavior and the superlinearity of (full) GMRES is preserved. This is explained by the

FIGURE 1.2. Convergence in time for problem 1.

“global” optimization over both the inner and the outer search vectors (the latter form a sample of the entire, previously searched Krylov subspace). So we may view this as a semi-full GMRES. FIG. 1.2 gives the convergence with respect to CPU-time. In this example GCRO(5) is the fastest, which is not surprising in view of the fact, that it converges almost as fast as GMRES, but against much lower costs. Also, we see that GCRO(10), while slower than GMRESR(5) is still faster than GMRESR(10). In this case the extra orthogonalization costs in GCRO are outweighed by the improved convergence behavior.

1.5.2. Problem 2. This problem is taken from [102]. The linear system comes from the discretization of

$$-(au_x)_x - (au_y)_y + bu_x = f$$

on the unit square, with $b = 2 \exp 2(x^2 + y^2)$. Along the boundaries we have Dirichlet conditions: $u = 1$ for $y = 0, x = 0$ and $x = 1$, and $u = 0$ for $y = 1$. The functions a and f are defined as shown in FIG. 1.6; $f = 0$ everywhere, except for the small subsquare in the center where $f = 100$. The stepsize in x -direction and in y -direction is $1/128$.

FIGURE 1.3. Convergence history for problem 2.

FIGURE 1.4. Convergence history for Bi-CGSTAB variants for problem 2.

In FIG. 1.3 a convergence plot is given for (full) GMRES, GCRO(m) and GMRESR(m). We used $m = 10$ and $m = 50$ to illustrate the difference in convergence behavior in the inner GMRES iteration of GMRESR(m) and GCRO(m). GMRESR(50) stagnates in the inner GMRES iteration whereas GCRO(50) more or less displays the same convergence behavior as GCRO(10) and full GMRES. For the number of matrix vector products, it seems that for GMRESR(m) small m are the best choice.

FIGURE 1.5. Convergence in time for problem 2. FIGURE 1.6. Coefficients for problem 2.

In FIG. 1.4 a convergence plot is given for (full) GMRES, Bi-CGSTAB, and the Bi-CGSTAB variants, GMRESRSTAB and GCROSTAB. To our experience the following strategy gave the best results for the Bi-CGSTAB variants:

- For GMRESRSTAB we ended an inner iteration after either 20 steps or a relative improvement of the residual of 0.01
- For GCROSTAB we ended an inner iteration after either after 25 steps or a relative improvement of the residual of 0.01.

The convergence of GMRESRSTAB for this example is somewhat typical for GMRESRSTAB in general (albeit very bad in this case). This might be explained from the fact that the convergence of Bi-CGSTAB depends on a “shadow” Krylov subspace, which it implicitly generates. Now, if one restarts, then Bi-CGSTAB also starts to build a new, possibly different, “shadow” Krylov subspace. This may lead to erratically convergence behavior in the first few steps. Therefore, it may happen that, if in the inner iteration Bi-CGSTAB does not

converge (to the relative precision), the “solution” of the inner iteration is not very good and therefore the outer iteration may not give much improvement either. At the start the same more or less holds for GCROSTAB, however, after a few outer GCR iterations the “improved” operator (A_k) somehow yields a better convergence than Bi-CGSTAB by itself. This was also observed for more tests, although it also may happen that GCROSTAB converges worse than Bi-CGSTAB.

In FIG. 1.5 a convergence plot versus the CPU-time is given for GMRESR(10), GCRO(10), Bi-CGSTAB, and GCROSTAB. The fastest convergence in CPU-time is achieved by GCROSTAB, which is $\approx 20\%$ faster than Bi-CGSTAB notwithstanding the extra work in orthogonalizations. We also see, that although GCRO(10) takes less iterations than GMRESR(10), in CPU-time the latter is faster. So in this case the decrease in iterations does not outweigh the extra work in orthogonalizations. For completeness we mention that GMRESRSTAB took almost 15 seconds to converge, whereas GMRES took almost 20 seconds.

1.5.3. Problem 3. The third problem is taken from [81]. The linear system stems from the discretization of the partial differential equation

$$-u_{xx} - u_{yy} + 1000(xu_x + yu_y) + 10u = f$$

on the unit square with zero Dirichlet boundary conditions. The stepsize in both x -direction and y -direction is $1/65$. The right-hand side is selected once the matrix is constructed so that the solution is known to be $x = (1, 1, \dots, 1)^T$. The zero vector was used as an initial guess.

In FIG. 1.7 we see a plot of the convergence history of full GMRES, GMRESR(5), GCRO(5), and GCRO(10,5) for two different truncation strategies, where the first parameter gives the dimension of the outer search space and the second the dimension of the inner search space. The number of vectors in the outer GCR iteration is twice the dimension of the search space. For the truncated version:

- “da” means that we took $\epsilon = 10^{-3}$ and dropped the vectors \hat{u}_1 and c_1 when $\delta(k) < \epsilon$ and assembled the vectors \hat{u}_9 and \hat{u}_{10} as well as the vectors c_9 and c_{10} when $\delta(k) > \epsilon$
- “tr” means that we dropped the vectors \hat{u}_9 and c_9 each step ($\epsilon = 0$, see also [108]).

Notice that GCRO(5) displays almost the same convergence behavior as full GMRES. GMRESR(5) converges eventually, but only after a long period of

FIGURE 1.7. Convergence history for problem 3.

stagnation. The truncated versions of GCRO(5) also display stagnation, but for a much shorter period. After that the “da” version seems to converge superlinear, whereas the “tr” version still displays periods of stagnation, most notably at the end. This indicates that the “da” version is more capable of keeping most of the “convergence history” than the “tr” version. This kind of behavior was seen in more tests: “assembled” truncation strategies seem to work better than just discarding one or more iteration vectors.

In TAB. 1.1 we give the number of matrix vector products, the number of memory vectors and the CPU-time on a Sun Workstation. From this table we see that GCRO(5) is by far the fastest method and uses about half the amount of memory vectors full GMRES and GMRESR(5) use. More interesting is that GCRO(10,5) “da” converges in the same time as GMRESR(5), but uses only one third of the memory space.

1.6. Conclusions. We have derived from the GMRESR inner-outer iteration schemes a modified set of schemes, which preserve the optimality of the outer iteration. This optimality is lost in GMRESR since it essentially uses

Method	MVs	Memory Vectors	CPU-time
GMRES	77	77	21.3
GMRESR(5)	188	81	18.5
GCRO(5)	83	39	9.4
GCRO(10,5) “da”	150	25	18.3
GCRO(10,5) “tr”	244	25	30.3

TABLE 1.1. Number of matrix vector products, number of memory vectors and CPU-time in seconds for problem 3.

“restarted” inner GMRES iterations, which do not take advantage of the outer “convergence history”. Therefore, GMRESR may lose superlinear convergence behavior, due to stagnation or slow convergence of the inner GMRES iterations.

In contrast, the GCRO variants exploit the “convergence history” to generate a search space, that has no components in any of the outer directions in which we have already minimized the error. For GCRO(m) this means we minimize the error over both the inner search space and a sample of the entire previously searched Krylov subspace (the outer search space), resulting in a semi-full GMRES. This probably leads to the smooth convergence (much like GMRES) and the absence of stagnation, which may occur in the inner GMRES iteration of GMRESR. Apparently the small subset of Krylov subspace vectors, that is kept, approximates the entire Krylov subspace that is generated, sufficiently well. For both GMRESR(m) and GCRO(m) it seems that a small number of inner iterations works well.

We may also say, that the GCRO variants construct a new (improved) operator (of decreasing rank) after each outer GCR iteration. Although there is the possibility of breakdown in the inner method for GCRO, this seems to occur rarely as is indicated by THEOREM 1.4 (it has never happened in any of our experiments).

With respect to performance of the discussed methods we have seen that GCRO(m) (almost) always converges in less iterations than GMRESR(m). Because GCRO(m) is in average more expensive per iteration, this does not always lead to faster convergence in CPU-time. This depends on the relative costs of the matrix vector product and preconditioner with respect to the cost of the

orthogonalizations and the reduction in iterations for GCRO(m) relative to GMRESR(m). Our experiments, with a cheap matrix vector product and preconditioner (in terms of the number of floating point operations), show that already in this case the GCRO variants are very competitive with other solvers. However, especially when the matrix vector product and preconditioner are expensive or when not enough memory is available for (full) GMRES, GCRO(m) is very attractive. GCRO with Bi-CGSTAB also seems to be a useful method especially when a large number of iterations is necessary or when the available memory space is small relative to the problem size. GMRESR with Bi-CGSTAB does not seem to work so well, probably because, to our observation, restarting Bi-CGSTAB does not work so well.

We have derived sophisticated truncation strategies and shown by numerical example that superlinear convergence behavior can be maintained. From our experience, the “assembled” version seems to have most promises.

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CHAPTER 2

BICGSTAB(ℓ) FOR LINEAR EQUATIONS INVOLVING UNSYMMETRIC MATRICES WITH COMPLEX SPECTRUM

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Abstract. For the solution of classes of linear systems of equations arising from realistic problems, the Bi-CGSTAB algorithm [102] is attractive. Unfortunately, for some relevant problems, where, for instance, Bi-CG performs well, the convergence of Bi-CGSTAB stagnates. This was observed specifically in the case of discretized advection dominated PDE's. The stagnation is due to the fact that for this type of equations the matrix has almost pure imaginary eigenvalues. With his BiCGStab2 algorithm Gutknecht [49] attempted to avoid this stagnation. Here, we generalize the Bi-CGSTAB algorithm further, and overcome some shortcomings of BiCGStab2. The new algorithm combines GMRES(ℓ) and Bi-CG.

Key words. Nonsymmetric linear systems, Iterative solvers, Krylov subspace, Bi-Conjugate gradients, CGS, Bi-CGSTAB, GMRES

AMS subject classification. 65F10

2.1. Introduction. The bi-conjugate gradient method (Bi-CG) [36, 57] solves iteratively equations

$$(2.1) \quad Ax = b$$

in which A is some given non-singular unsymmetric $n \times n$ matrix and b some given n -vector. Typically n is large and A is sparse. We will assume A and b

to be real, but our methods are easily generalized to the complex case. In each iteration step, the approximation x_k is corrected by some search correction that depends on the true residual r_k ($r_k = b - Ax_k$) and some “shadow residual” \tilde{r}_k . The residuals r_k are “forced to converge” by making r_k orthogonal to the shadow residuals \tilde{r}_j for $j < k$. Any iteration step requires a multiplication by A to produce the next true residual and a multiplication by A^T (the real transpose of A) to produce the next shadow residual. This strategy involves short recursions and hence an iteration step is cheap with respect to the computational cost (except for the matrix multiplications) and memory requirement. In addition to the MVs (i.e., matrix-vector multiplications), a few DOTs (inner products) and AXPYs (vector updates) are required, and apart from the x_k , four other vectors have to be stored.

Bi-CG seems like an ideal algorithm but in practice it has a few disadvantages:

- (i) The transpose (either complex or real) of A is often not (easy) available.
- (ii) Although the computational cost is low in terms of AXPYs and DOTs, each step requires two matrix multiplications, which is double the cost of CG.
- (iii) Bi-CG may suffer from breakdown. This can be repaired by look-ahead strategies [10, 40]. We will not consider the breakdown situation for Bi-CG in this paper.
- (iv) Bi-CG often converges irregularly. In finite precision arithmetic, this irregular behavior may slow down the speed of convergence.

In [93] Sonneveld observed that the computational effort to produce the shadow residuals could as well be used to obtain an additional reduction of the Bi-CG residuals r_k . His CGS algorithm computes approximations \mathbf{x}_k with a residual of the form $\mathbf{r}_k = q_k(A)r_k$, where q_k is some appropriate polynomial of degree k . The \mathbf{r}_k are computed explicitly, while the polynomials q_k and the Bi-CG residuals r_k play only a theoretical role. One step of the CGS algorithm requires two multiplications by A and no multiplication at all by the transpose of A . The computational complexity and the amount of memory is comparable to that of Bi-CG. In case $q_k(A)$ gives an additional reduction, CGS is an attractive method [93]. Unfortunately, in many situations, the CGS choice for q_k leads to amplifications of r_k instead of reduction. This causes irregular convergence or even divergence and makes the method more sensitive to evaluation errors [102, 101].

Van der Vorst [102] proposes to take for q_k a product of appropriate 1-step MR-polynomials (Minimal Residual polynomials), i.e., degree one polynomials of the form $1 - \omega_k t$ for some optimal ω_k . To a large extent, this choice fulfills the promises: for many problems, his Bi-CGSTAB algorithm converges rather smoothly and also often faster than Bi-CG and CGS. In such cases $q_k(A)$ reduces the residual significantly, while the Bi-CGSTAB iteration steps only slightly more expensive than the CGS steps.

However, ω_k may be close to zero, and this may cause stagnation or even breakdown. As numerical experiments confirm, this is likely to happen if A is real and has nonreal eigenvalues with an imaginary part that is large relative to the real part. One may expect that second degree MR-polynomials can better handle this situation. In [49] Gutknecht introduces a BiCGStab2 algorithm that employs such second degree polynomials. Although this algorithm is certainly an improvement in many cases, it may still suffer from problems in cases where Bi-CGSTAB stagnates or breaks down. At every second step, Gutknecht corrects the first degree MR-polynomial from the previous step to a second degree MR-polynomial. However, in the odd steps, the problem of a nearly degenerate MR-polynomial of degree one may already have occurred (this is comparable to the situation where GCR breaks down while GMRES (or Orthodir) proceeds nicely (cf. [82])). In BiCGStab2 (as well as in the other methods CGS, Bi-CGSTAB and the more general method BiCGstab(ℓ), to be introduced below), the Bi-CG iteration coefficients play a crucial role in the computation. If, in an odd step, the MR polynomial almost degenerates, the next second degree polynomial as well as the Bi-CG iteration coefficients may be polluted by large errors and this may affect the process severely.

In this paper, we introduce the BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm. For $\ell = 1$, this algorithm coincides with Bi-CGSTAB. In BiCGstab(ℓ), the polynomial q_k is chosen as the product of ℓ -step MR-polynomials: for $k = m\ell + \ell$ we take

$$(2.2) \quad \begin{aligned} q_k &= q_{m\ell+\ell} = p_m p_{m-1} \cdots p_0, \text{ where the } p_i \text{'s are of degree } \ell, \\ p_i(0) &= 1, \text{ and } p_m \text{ minimizes } \|p_m(A)q_{k-\ell}(A)r_k\|_2. \end{aligned}$$

We form an ℓ -degree MR-polynomial p_m after each ℓ -th step. In the intermediate steps $k = m\ell + i$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, \ell - 1$, we employ simple factors t^i and the p_m are reconstructed from these powers. In this way, we can avoid certain near-breakdowns in these steps. Near-breakdown may still occur in our approach if the leading coefficient of p_m is almost 0. However, second degree or more general even degree polynomials seem to be well suited for complex eigenpairs and near-breakdown is hardly a problem in practice (although it may occur if,

for instance, A is a cyclic matrix: $Ae_i = e_{i-1}$ for $i = 2, 3, \dots$). On the other hand, $\text{BiCGstab}(\ell)$ still incorporates the breakdown dangers of Bi-CG.

- (i) In exact arithmetic, if BiCGStab2 does not break down, it produces the same result as our $\text{BiCGstab}(2)$. In actual computation the results can be quite different. Our version proceeds nicely as should be expected from $\text{BiCGstab}(2)$ also in cases where BiCGStab2 stagnates due to the MR-choice in the odd steps. In cases where Gutknecht version does well, our version seems to converge slightly faster. In some cases in finite precision arithmetic, the approximations \mathbf{x}_k and the residuals \mathbf{r}_k drift apart (i.e., $b - A\mathbf{x}_k \not\approx \mathbf{r}_k$), due to irregular convergence behavior of the underlying Bi-CG process. Gutknecht's algorithm seems to be significantly more sensitive to this effect than ours.
- (ii) In addition the steps of our version are cheaper with respect to both computational cost as well as memory requirement: except for the number of MVs, which is the same for both versions, our version is about 33% less expensive and it needs about 10% less memory space.
- (iii) Gutknecht's approach can also be used to construct a $\text{BiCGstab}(\ell)$ version. However, if ℓ increases, the formulas and the resulting algorithm will become increasingly more complicated, while we have virtually the same algorithm for every ℓ . We can easily increase ℓ if stagnation threatens.
- (iv) In some situations it may be profitable to take $\ell > 2$. Although the steps of $\text{BiCGstab}(\ell)$ are more expensive for larger ℓ , numerical experiments indicate that, in certain situations, due to a faster convergence, for instance, $\text{BiCGstab}(4)$ performs better than $\text{BiCGstab}(2)$. Our $\text{BiCGstab}(\ell)$ algorithm combines the advantages of both Bi-CG and GMRES(ℓ) and seems to converge faster than any of those.

In the next section, we give theoretical details on the above observations. Section 2.3 contains a detailed description of the $\text{BiCGstab}(\ell)$ algorithm and its derivation. In addition, it contains comments on the implementation, the computational costs and the memory requirement. We conclude Section 2.3 with a number of possible variants for $\text{BiCGstab}(\ell)$. In Section 2.4 we give some remarks on preconditioning. In the last section, we present some numerical experiments.

choose x_0 and some \tilde{r}_0
 $k = -1$
 $r_0 = b - Ax_0$
 $u_{-1} = \tilde{u}_{-1} = 0, \rho_{-1} = 1$
repeat until $\|r_{k+1}\|$ is small enough:
 $k = k + 1$
 $\rho_k = (r_k, \tilde{r}_k), \quad \beta_k = -\rho_k / \rho_{k-1}$
 $u_k = r_k - \beta_k u_{k-1}, \quad c_k = Au_k$
 $\tilde{u}_k = \tilde{r}_k - \beta_k \tilde{u}_{k-1}$
 $\gamma_k = (c_k, \tilde{r}_k), \quad \alpha_k = \rho_k / \gamma_k$
 $x_{k+1} = x_k + \alpha_k u_k$
 $r_{k+1} = r_k - \alpha_k c_k$
 $\tilde{r}_{k+1} = \tilde{r}_k - \alpha_k A^T \tilde{u}_k$

ALGORITHM 2.1. The Bi-CG algorithm

2.2. Theoretical justification of BiCGstab(ℓ). The Bi-CG algorithm [36, 57] in ALG. 2.1 solves iteratively the linear equation (2.1).

One has to select some initial approximation x_0 for x and some “shadow” residual \tilde{r}_0 . Then the Bi-CG algorithm produces iteratively sequences of approximations x_k , residuals r_k and search directions u_k by

$$(2.3) \quad u_k = r_k - \beta_k u_{k-1}, \quad x_{k+1} = x_k + \alpha_k u_k, \quad r_{k+1} = r_k - \alpha_k Au_k$$

(where $u_{-1} = 0$, and r_0 is computed by $r_0 = b - Ax_0$). The scalars α_k and β_k are computed such that both Au_k and r_k are orthogonal to the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_k(A^T; \tilde{r}_0)$ of order k , spanned by the vectors $\tilde{r}_0, A^T \tilde{r}_0, \dots, (A^T)^{k-1} \tilde{r}_0$.

By induction it follows that both u_k and r_k belong to the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_{k+1}(A; r_0)$. Moreover, $r_k = \phi_k(A)r_0$, for some ϕ_k in the space \mathcal{P}_k^1 of all polynomials p of degree k for which $p(0) = 1$. Since, in the generic case, by increasing k the “shadow” Krylov subspaces $\mathcal{K}_k(A^T; \tilde{r}_0)$ “fill” the complete space, the sequence of $\|r_k\|$ may be expected to decrease. The vector r_k is the unique element of the form $p(A)r_0$, with $p \in \mathcal{P}_k^1$ that is orthogonal to $\mathcal{K}_k(A^T; \tilde{r}_0)$: in some weak sense, p is the best polynomial in \mathcal{P}_k^1 .

Consider some sequence of polynomials q_k of exact degree k . The vectors Au_k

and r_k are orthogonal to $\mathcal{K}_k(A^T; \tilde{r}_0)$ if and only if these vectors are orthogonal to $\tilde{s}_j = q_j(A^T)\tilde{r}_0$ for all $j = 0, 1, \dots, k-1$. Now, as we will see in 2.3.1,

$$(2.4) \quad \beta_k = \theta_k \frac{(r_k, \tilde{s}_k)}{(r_{k-1}, \tilde{s}_{k-1})} \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha_k = \frac{(r_k, \tilde{s}_k)}{(Au_k, \tilde{s}_k)}$$

in which θ_k is a scalar that depends on the leading coefficients of the polynomials ϕ_j and q_j for $j = k, k-1$. The Bi-CG algorithm takes $q_k = \phi_k$ (and $\theta_k = 1$), so that the \tilde{s}_j are computed by the same recursions as for the r_j (see ALG. 2.1, where for the choice $q_k = \phi_k$, we use the notation \tilde{r}_k instead of \tilde{s}_k). However, in exact arithmetic, for any choice of q_k the same approximations x_k , residuals r_k and search directions u_k can be constructed.

Algorithms as CGS, Bi-CGSTAB and BiCGstab(ℓ) are based on the observation that

$$(2.5) \quad \begin{aligned} (r_k, \tilde{s}_k) &= (r_k, q_k(A^T)\tilde{r}_0) = (q_k(A)r_k, \tilde{r}_0) \quad \text{and} \\ (Au_k, \tilde{s}_k) &= (Aq_k(A)u_k, \tilde{r}_0). \end{aligned}$$

In the ideal case the operator $\phi_k(A)$ reduces r_0 . One may try to select q_k such that $Q_k = q_k(A)$ additionally reduces r_k as much as possible. In such a case it would be an advantage to avoid the computation of r_k and u_k , and one might try to compute immediately $\mathbf{r}_k = Q_k r_k$, $\mathbf{u}_k = Q_k u_k$, and the associated approximation \mathbf{x}_k by appropriate recursions. As (2.4) and (2.5) show, one can use these vectors to compute the Bi-CG iteration coefficients β_k and α_k (for more details, see 2.3.1). If the polynomials q_k are related by simple recursions, these recursions can be used to compute efficiently the iterates \mathbf{r}_k , \mathbf{u}_k and \mathbf{x}_k without computing r_k and u_k explicitly. Therefore, the computational effort of the Bi-CG algorithm to build the shadow Krylov subspace can also be used to obtain an additional reduction (by Q_k) for the Bi-CG residual r_k . Since r_{2k} would have been constructed from the “weakly best” polynomial in \mathcal{P}_{2k}^1 , we may not expect that $\|\mathbf{r}_k\| \ll \|r_{2k}\|$: which says that a method based on Q_k can only converge twice as fast (in terms of costs). Since a Bi-CG step involves two MVs it only makes sense to compute \mathbf{r}_k instead of r_k if we can obtain \mathbf{r}_k from \mathbf{r}_{k-1} by 4 MVs at most and a few vector updates and if we can update simultaneously the corresponding approximation \mathbf{x}_k , where $\mathbf{r}_k = b - A\mathbf{x}_k$. This has been realized in CGS and Bi-CGSTAB (these algorithms require 2 MVs per step):

(i) The choice

$$(2.6) \quad q_k = \phi_k$$

leads to the CGS (Conjugate Gradient-squared) algorithm of Sonneveld [93]. Since $\phi_k(A)$ is constructed to reduce r_0 as much as possible, one may not expect that $\phi_k(A)$ reduces r_k as well. Actually, for a large class of problems $\phi_k(A)$ often transforms the r_k to a sequence of residuals \mathbf{r}_k that converges very irregularly or even diverges [101].

- (ii) In [102], Van der Vorst attempted to repair this irregular convergence behavior of CGS by choosing

$$q_k(t) = (1 - \omega_k t)q_{k-1}(t) \text{ with } \omega_k \text{ such that } \|(I - \omega_k A)q_{k-1}(A)r_k\|_2$$

is minimal with respect to the scalar ω for $\omega = \omega_k$.

In fact this is a special case of our algorithm, namely $\ell = 1$.

Unfortunately, for matrix-vector equations with real coefficients, ω_k is real as well. This may lead to a poor reduction of $\hat{r} = q_{k-1}(A)r_k$, i.e., $\|\mathbf{r}_k\| \approx \|\hat{r}\|$, where $\mathbf{r}_k = (I - \omega_k A)\hat{r}$. The convergence of Bi-CGSTAB may even stagnate (and actually does, cf. experiments in [61]). The Bi-CG iteration coefficients α_k and β_k cannot be computed from \mathbf{r}_k (see (2.5)) if the polynomial q_k is not of exact degree k . This happens if $\omega_k = 0$. Likewise, $\omega_k \approx 0$ may be expected to lead to inaccurate Bi-CG iteration coefficients. Consequently, stagnation in the Minimal Residual stage ($\omega_k \approx 0$) may cause breakdown or poor convergence of Bi-CGSTAB. One may come across an almost zero ω_k if the matrix has non-real eigenvalues λ with relatively large imaginary parts. If the components of \hat{r} in the direction of the associated eigenvectors are relatively large then the best reduction by $I - \omega_k A$ is obtained for $\omega_k \approx 0$. This fatal behavior of Bi-CGSTAB may be “cured” as follows.

Select some $\ell \geq 2$. For $k = m\ell + \ell$, take

$$(2.7) \quad \begin{aligned} q_k &= p_m q_{k-\ell}, \text{ where } p_m \text{ is a polynomial of degree } \ell, \\ p_m(0) &= 1 \text{ such that } \|p(A)q_{k-\ell}(A)r_k\|_2 \text{ is minimal} \\ &\text{with respect to } p \in \mathcal{P}_\ell^1 \text{ for } p = p_m \end{aligned}$$

and where $q_{k-\ell}$ is the product of MR-polynomials in \mathcal{P}_ℓ^1 constructed in previous steps. In the intermediate steps, $k = m\ell + i$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, \ell - 1$, we take $q_k = q_{m\ell}$ to compute the residual $\mathbf{r}_k = \mathbf{r}_{m\ell+i} = q_{m\ell}(A)r_k$ and search direction $\mathbf{u}_k = q_{m\ell}(A)u_k$. We use $t^i q_{m\ell}$ to compute the Bi-CG iteration coefficients through $(A^i \mathbf{r}_k, \tilde{r}_0)$ and $(A^{i+1} \mathbf{u}_k, \tilde{r}_0)$ (cf. (2.5) and (2.4)). This choice leads to the BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm in Section 2.3.2. A pseudo code for the algorithm is given in ALG. 2.2.

So, only for $k = m\ell$, do the polynomials q_k that we use belong to \mathcal{P}_k^1 . In the intermediate steps we employ two types of polynomials, polynomials of exact degree k (the $t^i q_{m\ell}$) and polynomials that are 1 in 0 (the $q_{m\ell}$).

The vectors \mathbf{r}_k , \mathbf{u}_k , $A^i \mathbf{r}_k$ and $A^{i+1} \mathbf{u}_k$ can be computed efficiently. However, we are interested in approximations \mathbf{x}_k and not primarily in the residual \mathbf{r}_k . These approximations can easily be computed as a side-product: if $\mathbf{r}_{k+1} = \mathbf{r}_k - A w$ then $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{x}_k + w$. Whenever we update \mathbf{r}_k by some vector u we have its original under $A^{-1}u$ as well. The polynomials used in the algorithm ensure that this is possible.

The residuals \mathbf{r}_k in the intermediate steps $k = m\ell + i$ will not be optimal in $\mathcal{K}_{k+k}(A; r_0)$. They cannot, because they belong to $\mathcal{K}_{k+m\ell}(A; r_0)$. Although the BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm produces approximations and residuals also in the intermediate steps, the approximations and residuals of interest are only computed every ℓ -th step.

In the BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm we have that $\mathbf{r}_k = q_k(A)\phi_k(A)r_0$. For $k = m\ell$ the reduction operator $q_k(A)\phi_k(A)$ that acts on r_0 is the product of the Bi-CG reduction operator and a GMRES(ℓ)-like reduction operator: $q_k(A)$ is the product of a sequence of GMRES reduction operators of degree ℓ (or, equivalently, of ℓ -step Minimal Residual operators; see [82]). Note that $q_k(A)$ is not the operator that would be obtained by applying k steps of GMRES(ℓ) to the residual $\phi_k(A)r_0$ of k steps Bi-CG. After each ℓ steps of Bi-CG we apply an ℓ -step Minimal Residual step and accumulate the effect. Nevertheless BiCGstab(ℓ) seems to combine the nice properties of both methods. If GMRES stagnates in the first ℓ steps then typically GMRES(ℓ) does not make any progress later. By restarting, the process builds approximately the same Krylov subspace as before the restart, thus encountering the same point of stagnation. This is avoided in the BiCGstab(ℓ) process where the convergence may keep on going by the incorporated Bi-CG process. The residual $\hat{\mathbf{r}} = q_{k-\ell}(A)r_k$ may differ significantly from the residual $q_{k-\ell}(A)r_{k-\ell}$. Therefore, each “Minimal Residual phase” in BiCGstab(ℓ) in general has a complete “new” starting residual, while, in case of stagnation, at each new start, GMRES(ℓ) employs about the same starting residual, keeping stagnating for a long while.

2.3. The BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm. Let u_k , c_k , r_k be the vectors as produced by Bi-CG and let α_k , β_k be the Bi-CG iteration coefficients, $c_k = Au_k$ (see ALG. 2.1).

2.3.1. The computation of the Bi-CG iteration coefficients. Consider the Bi-CG method in ALG. 2.1. We are not really interested in the shadow residuals \tilde{r}_k nor in the shadow search directions \tilde{u}_k . Actually, as observed in

Section 2.2, we only need \tilde{r}_k to compute β_k and α_k through the scalars (r_k, \tilde{r}_k) and (c_k, \tilde{r}_k) . We can compute these scalars by means of any vector \tilde{s}_k of the form $\tilde{s}_k = q_k(A^T)\tilde{r}_0$ where q_k is some polynomial in \mathcal{P}_k of which the leading coefficient is non-trivial and known.

To prove this, suppose $q_k \in \mathcal{P}_k$ has non-trivial leading coefficient σ_k , that is $q_k(t) - \sigma_k t^k$ is a polynomial in \mathcal{P}_{k-1} . Note that $\tilde{r}_k = \phi_k(A^T)\tilde{r}_0$ for the Bi-CG polynomial $\phi_k \in \mathcal{P}_k^1$ and that $\phi_k(t) - \tau_k t^k$ belongs to \mathcal{P}_{k-1} for $\tau_k = (-\alpha_{k-1})(-\alpha_{k-2}) \cdots (-\alpha_0)$. Hence, both the vectors $\tilde{r}_k - \tau_k(A^T)^k\tilde{r}_0$ and $\tilde{s}_k - \sigma_k(A^T)^k\tilde{r}_0$ belong to $\mathcal{K}_k(A^T; \tilde{r}_0)$. Since both the vectors r_k and c_k are orthogonal to this space (see [36]), we have that

$$(2.8) \quad (r_k, \tilde{r}_k) = \frac{\tau_k}{\sigma_k}(r_k, \tilde{s}_k) \quad \text{and} \quad (c_k, \tilde{r}_k) = \frac{\tau_k}{\sigma_k}(c_k, \tilde{s}_k).$$

Hence,

$$(2.9) \quad \beta_k = -\frac{(r_k, \tilde{r}_k)}{(r_{k-1}, \tilde{r}_{k-1})} = -\frac{\tau_k \sigma_{k-1}}{\sigma_k \tau_{k-1}} \frac{(r_k, \tilde{s}_k)}{(r_{k-1}, \tilde{s}_{k-1})} = \alpha_{k-1} \frac{\sigma_{k-1}}{\sigma_k} \frac{(r_k, \tilde{s}_k)}{(r_{k-1}, \tilde{s}_{k-1})}$$

and

$$(2.10) \quad \alpha_k = \frac{(r_k, \tilde{r}_k)}{(c_k, \tilde{r}_k)} = \frac{(r_k, \tilde{s}_k)}{(c_k, \tilde{s}_k)}.$$

Using (2.5) it even follows that we do not need \tilde{s}_k . With $\mathbf{r}_k = q_k(A)r_k$ and $\mathbf{c}_k = q_k(A)c_k$, we have that

$$(2.11) \quad (r_k, \tilde{s}_k) = (\mathbf{r}_k, \tilde{r}_0) \quad \text{and} \quad (c_k, \tilde{s}_k) = (\mathbf{c}_k, \tilde{r}_0).$$

Therefore, we can compute the Bi-CG iteration coefficients α_k and β_k by means of \mathbf{r}_k and \mathbf{c}_k . We do not need the \tilde{r}_k , \tilde{u}_k , nor \tilde{s}_k .

2.3.2. The construction of the BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm. The Bi-CG vectors u_k , c_k , r_k are only computed implicitly — they only play a role in the derivation of the algorithm — while the Bi-CG iteration coefficients α_k , β_k are computed explicitly — they are explicitly needed in the computation.¹ Instead of the Bi-CG vectors, for certain indices $k = \ell m$, we compute explicitly vectors

¹Moreover, even if they were not needed in the computation, it could be worthwhile to compute them: from these coefficients one can easily compute the representation of the matrix of A with respect to the basis of the Bi-CG vectors c_i . This matrix is tri-diagonal and enables us to compute cheaply approximations (Ritz values) of the eigenvalues of A .

\mathbf{u}_{k-1} , \mathbf{r}_k and \mathbf{x}_k : \mathbf{x}_k is the approximate solution with residual \mathbf{r}_k and \mathbf{u}_{k-1} is a search direction.

The BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm (ALG. 2.2) iteratively computes \mathbf{u}_{k-1} , \mathbf{x}_k and \mathbf{r}_k for $k = \ell, 2\ell, 3\ell, \dots$. These steps are called outer iteration steps. One single outer step, in which we proceed from $k = m\ell$ to $k = m\ell + \ell$, consists of an inner iteration process. In the first half of this inner iteration process (*the Bi-CG part*) we implicitly compute new Bi-CG vectors. In the second half (*the MR part*) we construct by a Minimal Residual approach a locally minimal residual.

We describe the BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm by specifying one inner loop.

Suppose, for $k = m\ell$ and for some polynomial $q_k \in \mathcal{P}_k$ with $q_k(0) = 1$ we have computed \mathbf{u}_{k-1} , \mathbf{r}_k and \mathbf{x}_k such that

$$(2.12) \quad \mathbf{u}_{k-1} = Q_k \mathbf{u}_{k-1}, \quad \mathbf{r}_k = Q_k \mathbf{r}_k \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{x}_k, \quad \text{where} \quad Q_k = q_k(A).$$

The steps of the inner loop may be represented by a triangular scheme as in SCHEME 2.1, where the steps for the computation of residuals and search directions are indicated for $\ell = 2$ (and $k = m \cdot 2$). The computation proceeds from row to row, replacing vectors from the previous row by vectors on the next row. In SCHEME 2.1 vector updates derived from the Bi-CG relations (2.3) are indicated by arrows. For instance, in the transition from the first row to the second one, we use $Q_k \mathbf{u}_k = Q_k(\mathbf{r}_k - \beta_k \mathbf{u}_{k-1}) = Q_k \mathbf{r}_k - \beta_k Q_k \mathbf{u}_{k-1}$ and to get from the second row to the third, we use $Q_k \mathbf{r}_{k+1} = Q_k(\mathbf{r}_k - \alpha_k A \mathbf{u}_k) = Q_k \mathbf{r}_k - \alpha_k A Q_k \mathbf{u}_k$. The computation involves other vector updates as well (in the MR part); these are not represented. Vectors that are obtained by multiplication by the matrix A are framed. The column at the left edge represents iteration coefficients computed according to (2.9)–(2.11) before replacing the old row by the new one. Recall that $\mathbf{c}_k = A Q_k \mathbf{u}_k$. The scheme does not show how the approximations for x are updated from row to row. However, their computation is analogous to the update of the residuals $Q_k \mathbf{r}_{k+j}$: when a residual is updated by adding a vector of the form $-Aw$, the approximation for x is updated by adding the vector w .

In the Bi-CG part, we construct the next row from the previous rows by means of the Bi-CG recursions (2.3) and matrix multiplication. The fifth row, for instance, is computed as follows: since $r_{k+2} = r_{k+1} - \alpha_{k+1} A u_{k+1}$ we have that

$$\begin{aligned} Q_k r_{k+2} &= Q_k r_{k+1} - \alpha_{k+1} A Q_k u_{k+1} \quad \text{and} \\ A Q_k r_{k+2} &= A Q_k r_{k+1} - \alpha_{k+1} A^2 Q_k u_{k+1}. \end{aligned}$$

SCHEME 2.1. The computational schema for BiCGstab(2).

By multiplying $AQ_k r_{k+2}$ by A we compute the vector $A^2 Q_k r_{k+2}$ on the diagonal of the scheme. After 2ℓ rows we have the vectors $A^i Q_k r_{k+\ell}$ and $A^i Q_k u_{k+\ell-1}$ ($i = 0, 2, \dots, \ell$).

In the MR part, we combine these vectors $A^i Q_k r_{k+\ell}$ to find the *minimal residual* $\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell}$. This vector is the residual in the best approximation of $Q_k r_{k+\ell}$ in the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_{\ell-1}(A; AQ_k r_{k+\ell})$. The computation of the scalars γ_i needed for this linear combination is done by the modified Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization process. The γ_i and $A^i Q_k u_{k+\ell-1}$ lead to $\mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1}$:

$$\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell} = Q_k r_{k+\ell} - \sum_{i=1}^{\ell} \gamma_i A^i Q_k r_{k+\ell} \quad \text{and}$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1} = Q_k u_{k+\ell-1} - \sum_{i=1}^{\ell} \gamma_i A^i Q_k u_{k+\ell-1}.$$

In this part we determine from a theoretical point of view the polynomial $p_m(t) = 1 - \gamma_1 t - \dots - \gamma_\ell t^\ell$. Implicitly we update q_k to find $q_{k+\ell}$. We emphasize that we do not use complicated polynomials until we arrive at the last row of the scheme where we form implicitly p_m .

The vectors in the second column of vectors, the $Q_k r_{k+j}$ (\widehat{r}_0 in the algorithm and in the detailed explanation below) are also residuals (corresponding to \widehat{x}_0 in the algorithm). The vectors $A^j Q_k u_{k+j-1}$ and $A^j Q_k r_{k+j}$ along the diagonal are

used in the computation of the Bi-CG iteration coefficients α_{k+j} and β_{k+j+1} . The computation of all these “diagonal vectors” require also 2ℓ multiplications by A (MVs). Note that ℓ steps of the Bi-CG algorithm require also 2ℓ multiplications by some matrix: ℓ multiplications by A and another ℓ by A^T . As indicated above, the other vectors $A^i Q_k r_{k+j}$ and $A^i Q_k u_{k+j-1}$ ($i = 0, 1, \dots, j-1$) in the triangular schemes can cheaply be constructed from vector updates: we obtain the vectors $Q_k r_{k+\ell}, A Q_k r_{k+\ell}, \dots, A^{\ell-1} Q_k r_{k+\ell}$ as a by-product. Consequently, the last step in the inner loop can easily be executed. The vector $\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell}$ is the minimal residual of the form $p(A) Q_k r_{k+\ell}$, where $p \in \mathcal{P}_\ell^1$. In exact arithmetic, ℓ steps of GMRES starting with the residual $\widehat{\mathbf{r}}_0 = Q_k r_{k+\ell}$ would yield the same residual $\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell}$ (see [82]). However, GMRES would require ℓ MVs to compute this projection. For stability reasons, GMRES avoids the explicit computation of vectors of the form $A^i \widehat{\mathbf{r}}_0$. Since we keep the value for ℓ low (less than 8), our approach does not seem to give additional stability problems besides the ones already encountered in the Bi-CG process. We trade a possible instability for efficiency (see also Section 2.3.8).

We now give details on the Bi-CG part, justify the computation of the Bi-CG iteration coefficients and discuss the MR part. In the MR part, we compute $\mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1}$, $\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell}$ and $\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell}$.

2.3.3. The Bi-CG part. In this section, in ℓ steps, we compute iteratively $A^i Q_k u_{k+\ell-1}$, $A^i Q_k r_{k+\ell}$ ($i = 0, 1, \dots, \ell$), the approximation \widehat{x}_0 for which $b - A\widehat{x}_0 = Q_k r_{k+\ell}$, the Bi-CG iteration coefficients α_{k+j} , β_{k+j} ($j = 0, 1, \dots, \ell-1$) and an additional scalar ρ_0 . We start our computation with the vectors $\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_0 = \mathbf{u}_{k-1} = Q_k u_{k-1}$, $\widehat{\mathbf{r}}_0 = \mathbf{r}_k = Q_k r_k$ and $\widehat{x}_0 = \mathbf{x}_k$, the scalar α_{k-1} and some scalars ρ_0 and ω from the previous step; $-\omega$ is the leading coefficient of p_{m-1} .

Suppose after j -steps, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_i &= A^i Q_k u_{k+j-1}, \quad \widehat{\mathbf{r}}_i = A^i Q_k r_{k+j} \quad (i = 0, 1, \dots, j), \\ \widehat{x}_0 &\text{ such that } \widehat{\mathbf{r}}_0 = b - A\widehat{x}_0, \\ \alpha &= \alpha_{k+j-1} \quad \text{and} \quad \rho_0 = (\widehat{\mathbf{r}}_{j-1}, \widetilde{\mathbf{r}}_0). \end{aligned}$$

Note that

$$\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_i = A^{i-1} Q_k A u_{k+j-1} = A^{i-1} Q_k c_{k+j-1}.$$

Then the $(j+1)$ -th step proceeds as follows (the “old” vectors “ $\widehat{\mathbf{u}}$ ”, “ $\widehat{\mathbf{r}}$ ” and \widehat{x}_0 may be replaced by the new ones. For clarity of explanation we label the new

vectors with a $'$). Below, we comment on the computation of α_{k+j} and β_{k+j} .

$$\rho_1 = (\widehat{r}_j, \widetilde{r}_0) = (A^j Q_k r_{k+j}, \widetilde{r}_0), \quad \beta = \beta_{k+j} = \alpha \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_0}, \quad \rho_0 = \rho_1,$$

$$\widehat{u}'_i = A^i Q_k u_{k+j} = A^i Q_k (r_{k+j} - \beta_{k+j} u_{k+j-1}) = \widehat{r}_i - \beta \widehat{u}_i \quad (i = 0, 1, \dots, j),$$

$$\widehat{u}'_{j+1} = A \widehat{u}'_j \quad (\text{multiplication by } A),$$

$$\gamma = (\widehat{u}'_{j+1}, \widetilde{r}_0) = (A^j Q_k c_{k+j}, \widetilde{r}_0), \quad \alpha = \alpha_{k+j} = \frac{\rho_0}{\gamma},$$

$$\widehat{r}'_i = A^i Q_k r_{k+j+1} = A^i Q_k (r_{k+j} - \alpha_{k+j} c_{k+j}) = \widehat{r}_i - \alpha \widehat{u}'_{i+1} \quad (i = 0, 1, \dots, j),$$

$$\widehat{r}'_{j+1} = A \widehat{r}'_j \quad (\text{multiplication by } A),$$

$$\widehat{x}'_0 = \widehat{x}_0 + \alpha \widehat{u}'_0 \quad (b - A \widehat{x}'_0 = \widehat{r}_0 - \alpha A \widehat{u}'_0 = \widehat{r}_0 - \alpha \widehat{u}'_1 = \widehat{r}'_0).$$

Now, drop the $'$ and repeat this step for $j = 0, 1, \dots, \ell - 1$.

The computation of the Bi-CG iteration coefficients. Consider some $j \in \{0, 1, \dots, \ell - 1\}$ and let $\gamma = (A^j Q_k c_{k+j}, \widetilde{r}_0)$ and $\rho_1 = (A^j Q_k r_{k+j}, \widetilde{r}_0)$.

For $j = 0$, let $\rho_0 = (A^{\ell-1} Q_k r_{k-\ell}, \widetilde{r}_0)$. The leading coefficient of $q_k(t)$ is equal to the leading coefficient of $t^{\ell-1} q_{k-\ell}(t)$ times $-\omega_{m-1}$, where $-\omega_{m-1}$ is the leading coefficient of the ‘‘MR polynomial’’ p_{m-1} for which $q_k = p_{m-1} q_{k-\ell}$. Hence, by (2.9), (2.10) and (2.11), we have that

$$\beta_k = -\frac{\alpha_{k-1}}{\omega_{m-1}} \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_0} \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha_k = \frac{\rho_1}{\gamma}.$$

In case $j > 0$, let $\rho_0 = (A^{j-1} Q_k r_{k+j-1}, \widetilde{r}_0)$. Now, the polynomials $t^j q_k(t)$ and $t^{j-1} q_k(t)$ have the same leading coefficient. Therefore, again by (2.9), (2.10) and (2.11), we have that

$$\beta_{k+j} = \alpha_{k+j-1} \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_0} \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha_{k+j} = \frac{\rho_1}{\gamma}.$$

2.3.4. The MR part. Suppose $\widehat{x}_0, \widehat{r}_j, \widehat{u}_j$ are known for $j = 0, 1, \dots, \ell$ such that

$$\widehat{r}_0 = b - A \widehat{x}_0 \quad \text{and} \quad \widehat{r}_j = A \widehat{r}_{j-1}, \quad \widehat{u}_j = A \widehat{u}_{j-1} \quad (j = 1, 2, \dots, \ell)$$

(as after the ℓ steps of the Bi-CG part).

Let $\sum_{j=1}^{\ell} \gamma_j \widehat{r}_j$ the orthogonal projection of \widehat{r}_0 onto $\text{span}\{\widehat{r}_1, \widehat{r}_2, \dots, \widehat{r}_\ell\}$. With $p_m(t) = 1 - \gamma_1 t - \dots - \gamma_\ell t^\ell$ ($t \in \mathbf{R}$) we have that

$$\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell} = \widehat{r}_0 - \sum_{j=1}^{\ell} \gamma_j \widehat{r}_j = p_m(A) \widehat{r}_0 = p_m(A) Q_k r_{k+\ell} = Q_{k+\ell} r_{k+\ell}.$$

Further,

$$\mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1} = \widehat{u}_0 - \sum_{j=1}^{\ell} \gamma_j \widehat{u}_j = p_m(A) \widehat{u}_0 = Q_{k+\ell} u_{k+\ell-1}$$

and

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell} = \widehat{x}_0 + \sum_{j=1}^{\ell} \gamma_j \widehat{r}_{j-1}.$$

We wish to compute these quantities as efficiently as possible.

The orthogonal vectors q_1, q_2, \dots, q_ℓ are computed by modified Gram-Schmidt from $\widehat{r}_1, \widehat{r}_2, \dots, \widehat{r}_\ell$; the arrays for $\widehat{r}_1, 2, \dots, \widehat{r}_\ell$ may be used to store q_1, q_2, \dots, q_ℓ . For ease of discussion, we consider the $n \times \ell$ matrices R, Q and U for which

$$R e_j = \widehat{r}_j, \quad Q e_j = q_j, \quad U e_j = \widehat{u}_j \quad \text{for } j = 1, 2, \dots, \ell.$$

Moreover, we consider the $\ell \times \ell$ matrices T, D, S , where T is the upper triangular matrix for which $R = QT$, D is the diagonal matrix given by $Q^T Q = D$, and S is given by $S e_1 = 0$ and $S e_j = e_{j-1}$ ($j = 2, 3, \dots, \ell$). If $\vec{\gamma} \in \mathbf{R}^\ell$ minimizes

$$\|\widehat{r}_0 - R\vec{\gamma}\|_2 = \|\widehat{r}_0 - QT\vec{\gamma}\|_2,$$

or equivalently, $\vec{\gamma}$ is the least square solution of $QT\vec{\gamma} = \widehat{r}_0$, then

$$\vec{\gamma} = T^{-1} D^{-1} Q^T \widehat{r}_0$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r}_{k+\ell} &= \widehat{r}_0 - R\vec{\gamma} = \widehat{r}_0 - QD^{-1}Q^T \widehat{r}_0, \\ \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1} &= \widehat{u}_0 - U\vec{\gamma}, \\ \mathbf{x}_{k+\ell} &= \widehat{x}_0 + \gamma_1 \widehat{r}_0 + RS\vec{\gamma} = \widehat{x}_0 + \gamma_1 \widehat{r}_0 + QTS\vec{\gamma}. \end{aligned}$$

or, with

$$\vec{\gamma}' = D^{-1} Q^T \widehat{r}_0, \quad \vec{\gamma} = T^{-1} \vec{\gamma}' \quad \text{and} \quad \vec{\gamma}'' = TS\vec{\gamma},$$

we have

$$\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell} = \widehat{r}_0 - Q\vec{\gamma}', \quad \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1} = \widehat{u}_0 - U\vec{\gamma}, \quad \mathbf{x}_{k+\ell} = \widehat{x}_0 + \gamma_1\widehat{r}_0 + Q\vec{\gamma}''.$$

Since $-\gamma_l$ is the leading coefficient of the polynomial p_m we have $\omega_m = \gamma_l$ (ω in the algorithm).

In the algorithm we use the same arrays for \widehat{r}_j and q_j . Therefore, q_j is written as \widehat{r}_j in the algorithm.

REMARK 2.1. In Bi-CG as well as in several other iterative methods the vector Au_k is a scalar multiple of $r_{k+1} - r_k$. Unfortunately, $A\mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1}$ is not a multiple of $\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell} - \mathbf{r}_k$ nor of $\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell} - Q_k r_{k+\ell}$ which would facilitate the computation of $A\mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1}$. For similar reasons one cannot save on the costs of the computation of $\mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1}$, unless one is willing to rearrange the Bi-CG part (see [92] or our discussion in Section 2.3.7).

2.3.5. The computational cost and memory requirements.

BiCGstab(ℓ) as well as for instance GMRES(ℓ) and CGS are Krylov subspace methods. These methods compute iteratively a sequence (x_k) (or $(x_{m\ell})$) of approximations of x for which, for every k , x_k belongs to the k -dimensional Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_k(A; r_0)$ (or $x_{m\ell} \in \mathcal{K}_{m\ell}(A; r_0)$ for every m ; actually, the approximation $x_k - x_0$ of $x - x_0$ belongs to this Krylov subspace. Without loss of generality we assume $x_0 = 0$). The success of such a method depends on

- its capability to find a good (best) approximation in the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_k(A, r_0)$ (also in the presence of evaluation errors)
- the efficiency to compute the next approximation x_{k+1} from the ones of the previous step(s)
- the memory space that is required to store the vectors that are needed for the computation.

For none of the methods, are all the conditions optimally fulfilled (unless the linear problem to be solved is symmetric, or otherwise nice). For instance, in some sense GMRES finds the best approximation in the Krylov subspace (it finds the approximation with the smallest residual), but the steps are increasingly expensive in computational cost as well as in memory requirement. Bi-CG proceeds efficiently from step to step, but it does not find the best approximation. This makes it hard to compare the methods of this type analytically.

```

Choose  $x_0$  and some  $\tilde{r}_0$ 
 $k = -\ell$ 
   $\mathbf{r}_0 = b - Ax_0$ 
   $\mathbf{u}_{-1} = 0, \mathbf{x}_0 = x_0, \rho_0 = 1, \alpha = 0, \omega = 1$ 
  repeat until  $\|\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell}\|$  is small enough:
     $k = k + \ell$ 
     $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_0 = \mathbf{u}_{k-1}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}_0 = \mathbf{r}_k, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 = \mathbf{x}_k$ 
     $\rho_0 = -\omega\rho_0$ 
    for  $j = 0, 1, \dots, \ell - 1$  do
       $\rho_1 = (\hat{\mathbf{r}}_j, \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0), \beta = \beta_{k+j} = \alpha \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_0}, \rho_0 = \rho_1$ 
      for  $i = 0, 1, \dots, j$  do
         $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_i = \hat{\mathbf{r}}_i - \beta\hat{\mathbf{u}}_i$ 
      enddo
       $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{j+1} = A\hat{\mathbf{u}}_j$ 
       $\gamma = (\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{j+1}, \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0), \alpha = \alpha_{k+j} = \frac{\rho_0}{\gamma}$ 
      for  $i = 0, 1, \dots, j$  do
         $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_i = \hat{\mathbf{r}}_i - \alpha\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{i+1}$ 
      enddo
       $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{j+1} = A\hat{\mathbf{r}}_j, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 + \alpha\hat{\mathbf{u}}_0$ 
    enddo
    for  $j = 1, 2, \dots, \ell$  do
      for  $i = 1, 2, \dots, j - 1$  do
         $\tau_{ij} = \frac{1}{\sigma_i}(\hat{\mathbf{r}}_j, \hat{\mathbf{r}}_i)$ 
         $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_j = \hat{\mathbf{r}}_j - \tau_{ij}\hat{\mathbf{r}}_i$ 
      enddo
       $\sigma_j = (\hat{\mathbf{r}}_j, \hat{\mathbf{r}}_j), \gamma'_j = \frac{1}{\sigma_j}(\hat{\mathbf{r}}_0, \hat{\mathbf{r}}_j)$ 
    enddo
     $\gamma_\ell = \gamma'_\ell, \omega = \gamma_\ell$ 
    for  $j = \ell - 1, \ell - 2, \dots, 1$  do
       $\gamma_j = \gamma'_j - \sum_{i=j+1}^{\ell} \tau_{ji}\gamma_i$ 
    enddo
    for  $j = 1, 2, \dots, \ell - 1$  do
       $\gamma''_j = \gamma_{j+1} + \sum_{i=j+1}^{\ell-1} \tau_{ji}\gamma_{i+1}$ 
    enddo
     $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_0 = \hat{\mathbf{u}}_0 - \gamma_\ell\hat{\mathbf{u}}_\ell, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 + \gamma_1\hat{\mathbf{r}}_0, \hat{\mathbf{r}}_0 = \hat{\mathbf{r}}_0 - \gamma'_\ell\hat{\mathbf{r}}_\ell$ 
    for  $j = 1, 2, \dots, \ell - 1$  do
       $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_0 = \hat{\mathbf{u}}_0 - \gamma_j\hat{\mathbf{u}}_j$ 
       $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 + \gamma''_j\hat{\mathbf{r}}_j$ 
       $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_0 = \hat{\mathbf{r}}_0 - \gamma'_j\hat{\mathbf{r}}_j$ 
    enddo
     $\mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1} = \hat{\mathbf{u}}_0, \mathbf{x}_{k+\ell} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0, \mathbf{r}_{k+\ell} = \hat{\mathbf{r}}_0$ 

```

BI-CG PART

(mod. GS) MR PART

ALGORITHM 2.2. The BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm

It is hard to get access to the convergence behavior, to its capability to find good approximations of x . Nevertheless one can easily investigate the computational cost per iteration step, which we will do now. Note that some methods do not aim to find a good approximation in Krylov subspaces of all dimensions; CGS and Bi-CGSTAB head for even dimensions, while the BiCGstab(ℓ) approximation \mathbf{x}_k is only computed for $k = m\ell$, for $\mathbf{x}_{m\ell} \in \mathcal{K}_{2m\ell}(A; r_0)$. In addition the computational cost may vary from step to step, as is the case for GMRES(ℓ) and BiCGstab(ℓ). For these reasons we give the average costs to increase the dimension of the approximating Krylov subspace by one. If, for a certain linear system, the methods we wish to compare are all able to find an equally good approximation in the Krylov subspace of interest, then this average cost represents the overall efficiency of the methods well. If some less efficient method finds better approximations, then it depends on the number of iteration steps which one is the best. We assume that the problem size n is large and therefore that the costs of small vector operations (involving vectors of dimension ℓ) are negligible.

In TABLE 2.1 we list the computational cost and the memory requirements for a number of Krylov subspace methods. GMRESR(ℓ, m) was introduced in [105] (see also [81]); in this modification of GMRES(ℓ) (or, more appropriate, of GCR(ℓ)), GMRES(m) is used as a preconditioner. GMRES(ℓ) as well as GMRESR(ℓ, m) avoid excessive use of memory by restarting after a certain number of steps.

The column “computational costs” contains the average amount of large vector operations that is needed to increase the dimension of the relevant Krylov subspace by one.

Furthermore, the table shows the maximum number of n -vectors that have to be stored during the computation; we do not count the locations needed to store the matrix (but our count includes b , \tilde{r}_0 , \mathbf{x}_k , and \mathbf{r}_k).

2.3.6. Remarks on the implementation of the algorithm.

- (i) Actually we only introduced the vectors \mathbf{u}_{k-1} , \mathbf{x}_k and \mathbf{r}_k for ease of presentation. Neither of them have to be stored: they can overwrite \hat{u}_0 , \hat{x}_0 and \hat{r}_0 .
- (ii) The computation of \hat{u}_0 in the MR part of ALG. 2.2 involves a number of vector updates. In order to restrict memory traffic, it is worth postponing the updates to the end and to combine them in the next Bi-CG part (when $j, i = 0$) where \hat{u}_0 has to be updated again. A similar remark applies to the final update of \hat{x}_0 in the Bi-CG part and the first update of

METHOD	COMPUTATIONAL COSTS			MEMORY
	MVS	AXPY	DOT	REQUIREMENTS
Bi-CG	2	6.5	2	7
CGS	1	3.25	1	7
Bi-CGSTAB	1	3	2	7
BiCGstab2	1	5.5	2.75	10
BiCGstab(2)	1	3.75	2.25	9
BiCGstab(ℓ)	1	$0.75(\ell + 3)$	$0.25(\ell + 7)$	$2\ell + 5$
GMRES(ℓ)	1	$\approx 0.5(\ell + 3)$	$\approx 0.5(\ell + 1)$	$\ell + 3$
GMRESR(ℓ, m)	1	$\approx g_{\ell, m} + 1$	$\approx g_{m, \ell}$	$m + 2\ell + 4$

$$\text{where } g_{\ell, m} = 0.5(m + 3) + (\ell + 2)/(2m)$$

The algorithm BiCGstab2 [49], may be improved slightly. For instance, it computes certain vectors in each step while it suffices to compute them in the even steps only. Our list above is based on the improved algorithm.

TABLE 2.1. The average cost per Krylov dimension.

\hat{x}_0 in the MR part. One can also gain computational speed by computing inner products together with the appropriate vector updates or matrix multiplications. For instance ρ_1 in the Bi-CG part can be computed in combination with the last vector update for \hat{r}_0 in the MR part.

- (iii) The final updates in the MR part should be implemented using the BLAS2 subroutine `_GEMV` (or `_GEMM` from BLAS3) instead of the BLAS1 subroutine `_AXPY`. Depending on the computer architecture this will improve efficiency.
- (iv) Another change in the algorithm that would reduce significantly the amount of work involves the modified Gram-Schmidt process. One can use the generalized inverse of R in order to compute the necessary coefficients γ_i for the MR-polynomial (see “The MR part” in Section 2.3.2). More precisely one can compute these coefficients from the normal equations as $\vec{\gamma} = (R^T R)^{-1} R^T \hat{r}_0$. Now we do not have to compute an orthogonal basis for $\text{range}(R)$ and we have saved $(\ell - 1)/4$ vector updates per Krylov dimension.

This approach not only reduces the total amount of work, but it also makes the algorithm more suitable for *parallel* implementation. However, when ℓ is large this approach may be more unstable than the one based on modified Gram-Schmidt. Consequently one might not expect to obtain the best possible reduction for \widehat{r}_0 . We discuss this variant and we analyze its stability in [92].

2.3.7. Variants. Many variants of the above process are feasible. We will mention only a few. For a detailed discussion, numerical experiments and conclusions, we refer to [92].

Dynamic choice of ℓ For a number of problems the BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm (with $\ell > 1$) converges about as fast as the BiCGstab(1) algorithm, i.e., the average reduction per step of the residuals in one algorithm is comparable to the reduction in the other. In such a case it is more efficient to work with $\ell = 1$, since for larger ℓ the average cost per step is higher. However, particularly if BiCGstab(1) stagnates (if $\omega \approx 0$), one should take an ℓ larger than 1. It may be advantageous not to fix ℓ at the start of the process, but to choose ℓ for each new inner loop depending on information from the previous inner loop.

If for larger ℓ a significant reduction can be obtained locally, it is also worth switching to larger ℓ .

It is not obvious how the switch can be realized and what the correct switching criterion would be. We further discuss this issue in [92]. The switch that we will discuss there is based on a BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm in which, in the inner loop, the MR part and the Bi-CG part are reversed. This costs slightly more memory and vector updates, but it facilitates the selection of an appropriate ℓ before any stagnation or breakdown occurs.

Bi-CG combined with some polynomial iteration The MR part does not require any additional MVs but it needs quite a number of AXPYs and DOTs due to the orthogonalization process. If one knows the coefficients γ_i of the polynomial $p_m(t) = 1 - \sum_{j=1}^{\ell} \gamma_j t^j$, then one can skip the orthogonalization. Unfortunately, the optimal γ_j will not be known a priori, but one might hope that the γ_j from previous steps work as well (at least for a number of consecutive steps). Further, since the Bi-CG iteration coefficients provide information on the spectrum of A , one might use this information to construct a shifted Chebychev polynomial of degree ℓ and take this for p_m . Of course, one may up-

date the polynomial in each step. Note that the construction of the Chebychev polynomial does not involve extra operations with n -vectors.

Bi-CG combined with standard GMRES or Bi-CG Instead of computing $\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell}$ by correcting $\widehat{\mathbf{r}}_0$ with some explicit linear combination of vectors $A^j \widehat{\mathbf{r}}_0$ as we do, one can apply ℓ steps of standard GMRES with starting residual $\widehat{\mathbf{r}}_0$. This approach would require ℓ MVs to obtain $\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell}$. One has to compute the γ_j from the GMRES results in order to construct $\mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1}$ (see also the remark on the MR part in Section 2.3.2). If one decides to pursue this last approach, one can save ℓ MVs and a number of AXPYs and DOTs in the Bi-CG part as follows. The Bi-CG iteration coefficients α_{k+j} and β_{k+j} can also be computed from the vectors $AQ_k u_{k+j}$, $Q_k r_{k+j-1}$, $Q_k r_{k+j}$ (the \widehat{u}_1 , $\widehat{\mathbf{r}}_0$ in the algorithm) and the shadow residuals \widetilde{r}_{j-1} , \widetilde{r}_j . Instead of building a triangular scheme of residuals and search directions (see SCHEME 2.1) one can stick to a scheme of three columns of $Q_k u_{k+j}$, $Q_k r_{k+j}$, $AQ_k u_{k+j}$. The shadow residuals $\widetilde{r}_1, \widetilde{r}_2, \dots, \widetilde{r}_{\ell-1}$ need only be computed and stored once.

If these shadow residuals are available, it is tempting to apply ℓ steps of Bi-CG to compute $\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell}$ starting with $Q_k r_{k+\ell}$. This saves a number of AXPYs and DOTs in the ‘‘MR part’’. The search direction $\mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1}$ has also to be computed. This can be done without additional MVs: from the Bi-CG relations (2.3) it follows that the $A^j \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1}$ are linear combination of $A^i Q_k r_{k+\ell}$ and $AQ_k u_{k+\ell-i}$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, j$). The scalars in the linear combination can be expressed in terms of the Bi-CG iteration coefficients β_{k+j} , α_{k+j} . Hence, $\mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1}$ can be computed by updating $Q_k u_{k+\ell-1}$ using the previously computed vectors $AQ_k u_{k+\ell-j}$ and $A^j Q_k r_{k+\ell}$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, \ell$).

2.3.8. The stability. We obtain $\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell}$ by subtracting some explicit linear combination of vectors $A^j \widehat{\mathbf{r}}_0$ from $\widehat{\mathbf{r}}_0$. One may object that this approach might be unstable especially if ℓ is not small. However, we restrict ourselves to small ℓ ($\ell \leq 8$). Our strategy resembles somewhat the look ahead strategy in the Lanczos algorithms in [40, 48, 50]. In our numerical experiments the convergence did not seem to suffer from such instabilities. On the contrary, the residual reduction of BiCGstab(ℓ) proceeds more smoothly than those of Bi-CG or CGS. Bi-CG and ℓ -step MR seem to improve their mutual stability. The following two observations may help to understand why the γ_i may be affected by non-small errors without spoiling the convergence.

- (i) The polynomial p_m must be non-degenerate (i.e., the contribution $\gamma_\ell A^\ell \widehat{\mathbf{r}}_0$ should be significant also in finite precision arithmetic) and the same

scalars should be used to update the residual, the search direction and the approximation. The *Bi-CG part* does not impose other restrictions on the γ_i used in the actual computation.

(ii) In the *MR part*, any reduction is welcome even it is not the optimal one.

As an alternative to our approach, one may gain stability by computing $\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell}$ by ℓ steps of GMRES with starting residual \widehat{r}_0 (see the “GMRES variant” in Section 2.3.7). One also has to keep track of the search directions. Since this GMRES stability “cure” is directed towards the residuals it is not clear whether this approach would improve the stability of the computation of the search directions. We return to these stability questions in [92].

In [49], for $\ell = 2$, Gutknecht “avoids” the instability caused by working with the “naive” basis for the Krylov subspace. He computes $\mathbf{r}_{k+\ell}$ from \widehat{r}_0 by a GCR-type method (in his algorithm the GCR part and the Bi-CG part are intertwined), thus incorporating the breakdown dangers of GCR.

2.4. The preconditioned BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm. Let K be a preconditioning matrix. Instead of solving $Ax = b$, one may as well solve

$$(2.13) \quad K^{-1}A = K^{-1}b$$

or

$$(2.14) \quad AK^{-1}y = b \quad \text{with} \quad x = K^{-1}y$$

Therefore, by replacing A by $K^{-1}A$ and $\mathbf{r}_0 = b - Ax_0$ by $\mathbf{r}_0 = K^{-1}(b - Ax_0)$, we have an algorithm that solves (2.13) iteratively. In this case the computed residuals \mathbf{r}_k are not the real residuals (even not in exact arithmetic) but $\mathbf{r}_k = K(b - A\mathbf{x}_k)$.

By replacing A by AK^{-1} and $\mathbf{x}_0 = x_0$ by $\mathbf{x}_0 = Kx_0$, we have an algorithm that solves iteratively (2.14). The computed residuals are the real ones, that is, $\mathbf{r}_k = b - AK^{-1}\mathbf{x}_k$, but now \mathbf{x}_k is not the approximation we are interested in: we would like to have $K^{-1}\mathbf{x}_k$ instead. If we do not want to monitor the approximations of the exact solution x , it suffices to compute $K^{-1}\mathbf{x}_k$ only after termination.

In both variants, the BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm may converge faster, due to the preconditioning. However, in order to get either the real residual (in (2.13)) or the real approximate (in (2.14)), some additional work is required. In contrast to algorithms as Bi-CG and GCR, there is no variant of preconditioned BiCGstab(ℓ) that generates the real residual and the approximations of interest without additional computational work or additional storage requirement.

2.5. Numerical examples. In this section we will discuss some numerical experiments. These experiments are intended to show the characteristic behavior of BiCGstab(ℓ) for certain linear systems. We do not pretend that the problems are solved in the best possible way. For instance, in some experiments we used a preconditioner, whereas in others we did not. With a suitable preconditioner all methods can be made to converge efficiently, but this is not the point we would like to make. The experiments are used to show that BiCGstab(ℓ) may be a good alternative for certain problems. The algorithm was implemented as in ALG. 2.2.

All partial differential equations were discretized with finite volumes discretization. When a preconditioner was used then the explicitly left preconditioned system was solved (see (2.13)). In all cases $x_0 = 0$ was taken as an initial guess. The experiments were done on a CRAY Y-MP 4/464, in a multi-user environment. The iterations were stopped when $\|\mathbf{r}_k\|_2/\|\mathbf{r}_0\|_2 < 10^{-9}$ (except in example 2 where the iterations were stopped when $\|\mathbf{r}_k\|_2/\|\mathbf{r}_0\|_2 < 10^{-12}$), or when the number of matrix multiplications exceeded 1000.

The figures show the convergence behavior of the iterative methods. For BiCGstab(ℓ) we have plotted the norms of the residuals $\mathbf{r}_{m\ell}$ that are computed by ALG. 2.2, i.e., only every ℓ -th step (see our discussion at the end of Section 2.2). Horizontally the number of matrix multiplications is counted. In exact arithmetic this number represents the dimension of the relevant Krylov subspace, except for Bi-CG, where it should be divided by two.

At the end of this section we give in TABLE 2.2 an overview of the required CPU-time for the *true* residual norm of several iterative methods. The numbers between brackets () are the log of the ℓ_2 -norm of the final *true* residuals: $\log_{10}(\|b - A\mathbf{x}_k\|_2)$. The log of the norm of the computed updated residuals can be seen from the figures. A ‘*’ in TABLE 2.2 indicates that the method did not meet the required tolerance before 1000 multiplications of the matrix A . We did our experiments for Bi-CG, CGS and several popular or successful GMRES variants. We selected algorithms that have about the same memory requirements as the BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithms that we tested. If one can store 13, say, n -vectors then one may choose for instance between BiCGstab(4), GMRES(10) and GMRESR(3,4) [105]. In our experiments BiCGstab(4) then seems to be the better choice.

2.5.1. Example 1. First we consider an advection dominated 2-nd order partial differential equation, with Dirichlet boundary conditions, on the unit cube (this equation was taken from [61]):

$$u_{xx} + u_{yy} + u_{zz} + 1000u_x = F.$$

FIGURE 2.1. Convergence plot of example 1.

The function F is defined by the solution

$$u(x, y, z) = \exp(xyz) \sin(\pi x) \sin(\pi y) \sin(\pi z).$$

This equation was discretized using $(52 \times 52 \times 52)$ volumes, resulting in a seven-diagonal linear system of order 125000. No preconditioning was used.

In FIG. 2.1 we see a plot of the convergence history. Bi-CGSTAB stagnates as might be anticipated from the fact that this linear system has large complex eigenpairs. Surprisingly, Bi-CGSTAB does even worse than Bi-CG. For this type of matrices this behavior of Bi-CGSTAB is not uncommon and might be explained by the poor first degree minimal residual reductions. In that case the Bi-CG iteration coefficients α_k and β_k are not accurately computed. BiCGstab(2) converges quite nicely and almost twice as fast as Bi-CG (see our discussion in Section 2.2).

2.5.2. Example 2. Next, we give an example where BiCGStab2 [49] suffers from the underlying Bi-CGSTAB algorithm (see our discussion in the introduction).

FIGURE 2.2. Convergence plot for example 2.

The symmetric positive definite linear system stems from a (200×200) discretization of

$$-(Du_x)_x - (Du_y)_y = 1,$$

over the unit square, with Dirichlet boundary conditions along $y = 0$ and Neumann conditions along the other parts of the boundary. The function D is defined as

$$D = 1000 \text{ for } 0.1 \leq x, y \leq 0.9 \text{ and } D = 1 \text{ elsewhere.}$$

This example was taken from [102] and we used a Modified Incomplete Cholesky decomposition [46] as a preconditioner. A convergence plot is given in FIG. 2.2.

Here the underlying Bi-CG algorithm loses bi-orthogonality among the residuals in a very early phase and consequently superlinear convergence takes place for none of the methods (in contrast to what might be expected; see, for instance, [98] and [103]), but apparently the BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm for $\ell = 2, 4$, has less problems. Gutknecht's BiCGStab2 follows the convergence

FIGURE 2.3. Convergence plot for example 3.

history of Bi-CGSTAB almost perfectly. This kind of behavior was also observed by Gutknecht. Apparently the polynomials of degree one in the odd steps spoil the overall convergence behavior of BiCGStab2.

In exact arithmetic we have that $\mathbf{r}_k = b - A\mathbf{x}_k$. In finite precision arithmetic the true residual $b - A\mathbf{x}_k$ and the recursively computed \mathbf{r}_k may differ. The difference will be more significant if the convergence history of the residuals shows large peaks. In our algorithm the updates for the approximations follow very closely the updates for the residuals: in each step we have $\hat{x}_0 = \hat{x}_0 + w$ where $\hat{r}_0 = \hat{r}_0 - Aw$. In Gutknecht's version the formulas that describe the update of the approximations are quite different from the ones for the residuals. Therefore, if the true residuals and the computed ones drift apart this is much more apparent in Gutknecht's version. In this experiment the final computed preconditioned residual norms were of order 10^{-8} , whereas the *true* preconditioned residual norms were of order 10^{-4} for BiCGstab(ℓ), $\ell = 1, 2, 4$, but only of order 10^{-1} for BiCGStab2 (see TABLE 2.2).

Although BiCGstab(ℓ) becomes more expensive with respect to the number

of inner products and vector updates as ℓ increases, the convergence may be faster, and therefore, the total CPU-time needed to find an accurate approximation may *decrease*. In this example the BiCGstab(4) algorithm (for instance) is faster than the BiCGstab(2) algorithm (see TABLE 2.2). So it is sometimes more profitable to use an $\ell > 2$ (see also our next example).

2.5.3. Example 3. Our third example shows more clearly that taking $\ell > 2$ may be beneficial. Here BiCGstab(2) converges very slowly, whereas BiCGstab(4) does not seem to have any problem: it converges quite nicely, although linearly. This example was taken from [75].

The nonsymmetric linear system comes from a (201×201) finite volume discretization of

$$-\epsilon(u_{xx} + u_{yy}) + a(x, y)u_x + b(x, y)u_y = 0,$$

on the unit square, where

$$a(x, y) = 4x(x - 1)(1 - 2y), \quad b(x, y) = 4y(1 - y)(1 - 2x),$$

with Dirichlet boundary conditions $u(x, y) = \sin(\pi x) + \sin(13\pi x) + \sin(\pi y) + \sin(13\pi y)$. We took $\epsilon = 10^{-1}$ and did not use any preconditioning. A convergence plot is shown in FIG. 2.3.

2.5.4. Example 4. Our last example shows that even if Bi-CGSTAB converges well, BiCGstab(ℓ), $\ell = 2, 4, \dots$, may be good competitors. Moreover, when the problem is discretized on a finer grid BiCGstab(2) seems to be a better choice for solving this problem. The problem was taken from [102].

The two nonsymmetric linear systems come from a (129×129) and a (201×201) finite volume discretization of the partial differential equation

$$-(Au_x)_x - (Au_y)_y + B(x, y)u_x = F$$

over the unit square, with $B(x, y) = 2 \exp(2(x^2 + y^2))$. Along the boundaries we have Dirichlet conditions: $u = 1$ for $y = 0$, $x = 0$ and $x = 1$, and $u = 0$ for $y = 1$. The function A is defined as shown in figure 2.6; $F = 0$ everywhere, except for the small subsquare in the center where $F = 100$. Incomplete LU factorization was used as a preconditioner.

From FIG. 2.4 we observe that Bi-CGSTAB and BiCGstab(2) behave similarly for the coarser grid with BiCGstab(2) slightly faster, but on the finer grid (FIG. 2.5) BiCGstab(2) performs much better than Bi-CGSTAB. BiCGstab(4) and BiCGstab(8) have a similar convergence history as BiCGstab(2). Compare also TABLE 2.2.

FIGURE 2.4. Convergence plot for example 4 (129×129).

METHOD	Ex. 1	Ex. 2	Ex. 3	Ex. 4 (129)	Ex. 4 (201)
Bi-CG	4.96(10.5)	6.35(4.2)	2.71(2.4)*	1.60(7.0)	4.58(7.0)
CGS	divergence	4.54(4.4)	breakdown	divergence	divergence
Bi-CGSTAB	stagnation	4.67(4.3)	3.22(3.4)*	1.10(7.0)	7.87(6.2)
BiCGstab2	4.42(10.7)	5.63(1.9)	4.26(2.6)*	1.31(6.8)	3.77(6.7)
BiCGstab(2)	3.88(10.4)	4.45(4.5)	4.00(3.6)*	1.01(6.8)	3.68(6.7)
BiCGstab(4)	4.17(10.9)	4.00(4.5)	4.35(7.5)	1.11(6.8)	3.68(6.8)
BiCGstab(8)	5.03(11.1)	4.36(3.5)	5.54(6.9)	1.27(7.5)	4.06(6.9)
GMRES(6)	5.27(10.3)	stagnation	4.69(2.7)*	stagnation	stagnation
GMRES(10)	6.30(10.3)	stagnation	5.16(3.5)*	stagnation	stagnation
GMRESR(2,2)	8.85(10.3)	stagnation	5.71(2.5)*	stagnation	stagnation
GMRESR(3,4)	6.25(10.3)	stagnation	5.16(2.6)*	stagnation	stagnation

TABLE 2.2. CPU-time and $-\log_{10}$ of the *true* residual norm (see the introduction of Section 2.5).

FIGURE 2.6. The coefficients for example 4.

2.6. Conclusions. From our numerical experiments we have learned that the BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm may be an attractive method for solving linear systems of equations. The algorithm is a generalization of Van der Vorst's BiCGSTAB [102]. For $\ell = 1$ BiCGstab(ℓ) computes exactly the same approximation \mathbf{x}_k as Bi-CGSTAB does.

For $\ell > 1$ it seems that BiCGstab(ℓ) is less affected by relatively large complex eigenpairs (as one encounters in advection dominated partial differential equations). Its computational work and memory requirement is modest.

BiCGstab(2) is, in exact arithmetic, equivalent with BiCGStab2 [49]. However we have given arguments and experimental evidence for the superiority of our version.

Therefore, we conclude that BiCGstab(ℓ) may be considered as a competitive algorithm to solve nonsymmetric linear systems of equations.

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CHAPTER 3

ENHANCED IMPLEMENTATION OF BiCGSTAB(ℓ) FOR SOLVING LINEAR SYSTEMS OF EQUATIONS

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Abstract. In this paper, we present a FORTRAN implementation of the BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm. The implementation is based on the power basis variant of BiCGstab(ℓ). This variant is enhanced with a more stable way of determination of the iteration coefficients and with a more reliable update strategy for the residuals. These enhancements improve the accuracy and rate of convergence at almost no additional computational costs.

Key words. Nonsymmetric linear systems, Iterative solvers, BiCGstab(ℓ), Krylov subspace

AMS subject classification. 65F10

3.1. Introduction. The BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm [85] is an iterative solution method for linear problems

$$(3.1) \quad Ax = b,$$

where A is some given nonsingular ($n \times n$)-matrix and b some given right hand side. Typically n is large and A is sparse. The algorithm belongs to the class of hybrid BiCG methods. The methods in this class iteratively compute, for a given

initial guess \mathbf{x}_0 , approximate solutions \mathbf{x}_k for which the residual $\mathbf{r}_k = b - A\mathbf{x}_k$ can be written formally as

$$(3.2) \quad \mathbf{r}_k = q_k(A)r_k,$$

in which q_k is a polynomial of degree k with $q(0) = 1$, and r_k is the k th BiCG [36, 57] residual. In BiCGstab(ℓ) the polynomial q_k is chosen as a product of locally minimizing polynomials of degree ℓ . More precisely, for $k = m\ell$, with \mathcal{P}_ℓ^1 the space of polynomials p of degree $\leq \ell$ with $p(0) = 1$,

$$(3.3) \quad q_k = p_{m,\ell}^{\text{MR}} q_{k-\ell}, \text{ with } p_{m,\ell}^{\text{MR}} \in \mathcal{P}_\ell^1 \text{ such that } \|p(A)q_{k-\ell}(A)r_k\|_2 \\ \text{is minimal with respect to } p \in \mathcal{P}_\ell^1 \text{ for } p = p_{m,\ell}^{\text{MR}}.$$

There are numerous ways to implement this procedure, see, for instance, [102, 85, 92, 49], but basically the iteration steps of a BiCGstab method can be divided into two parts, namely,

- (i) *the BiCG part*, in which the BiCG residual is implicitly updated using the short recursions of BiCG
- (ii) *the polynomial part*, in which the minimal residual polynomial is constructed and used to update the new residual and corresponding approximate solution.

REMARK 3.1. In the following, our notation reflects the notation used in the algorithms ALG. 3.1–3.3: the index k of the iteration vectors is suppressed. For instance, after the BiCG part in ALG. 3.1, we have that $\mathbf{r}_0 = q_k(A)r_{k+\ell}$, and after the polynomial part, $\mathbf{r}_0 = q_{k+\ell}(A)r_{k+\ell}$.

Furthermore, in the algorithms, we use the MATLAB index notation.

In ALG. 3.1 we have pictured an efficient variant of BiCGstab(ℓ) that is suggested in [85, 92]. After the BiCG part (starting with $\mathbf{r}_0 = q_k(A)r_k$) a power basis

$$\mathbf{R} = [\mathbf{r}_0, A\mathbf{r}_0, \dots, A^\ell \mathbf{r}_0]$$

is available, such that $\mathbf{r}_0 = q_k(A)r_{k+\ell}$. In the polynomial part, this basis \mathbf{R} is then used to minimize the residual with the help of the normal equations, i.e., with $\widehat{\mathbf{R}} = [A\mathbf{r}_0, A^2\mathbf{r}_0, \dots, A^\ell \mathbf{r}_0]$

$$\mathbf{r}_0 \leftarrow \mathbf{r}_0 - \widehat{\mathbf{R}}(\widehat{\mathbf{R}}^*\widehat{\mathbf{R}})^{-1}\widehat{\mathbf{R}}^*\mathbf{r}_0.$$

The associated approximate solution \mathbf{x} ($= \mathbf{x}_{k+\ell}$), and the search direction \mathbf{u}_0 , needed in the BiCG part, are updated correspondingly.

However, whereas the minimal residual polynomials are optimal for reducing the residual, they are not optimal for an accurate determination of the BiCG iteration coefficients (α and β in ALG. 3.1) [88, 89]. Inaccurate coefficients are undesirable, because they may disturb the underlying BiCG process, and this may affect the speed of convergence.

In [88, 89] it is argued that, for accurate coefficients (at least locally) one should take a different polynomial, namely, the orthogonal polynomial $p_{m,\ell}^{\text{OR}}$ that is characterized by

$$(3.4) \quad p_{m,\ell}^{\text{OR}} \in \mathcal{P}_\ell^1 \quad \text{for which} \quad p_{m,\ell}^{\text{OR}}(A)\mathbf{r}_0 \perp [\mathbf{r}_0, A\mathbf{r}_0, \dots, A^{\ell-1}\mathbf{r}_0]$$

Unfortunately, these kinds of polynomials may amplify the residual, and this also may affect the speed of convergence.

The suggestion is then to take a suitable convex combination of $p_{m,\ell}^{\text{MR}}$ and $p_{m,\ell}^{\text{OR}}$ as a compromise. This choice may still amplify the residual, but whereas the amplification by $p_{m,\ell}^{\text{OR}}$ can be unbounded, the amplification by the convex combination is at most $\sqrt{2}$ (for $\Omega = \sqrt{2}/2 \approx 0.7$, see Section 3.2 below) and usually much less. If this leads to divergence, then increasing the value of ℓ may help. The implementation of this procedure is the subject of Section 3.2.

REMARK 3.2. In fact, taking a convex combination may be viewed as a cure for a breakdown possibility in the polynomial part. We do not address the breakdown possibilities in the BiCG recursions.

Of course, speed of convergence is one thing, but accuracy¹ of the solution is desired as well: because the approximate solution and the residual are updated with recursions, rounding errors may cause significant differences in the *recursively computed* residual \mathbf{r}_0 and the *true* residual $b - A\mathbf{x}$. As an inspection of the algorithm shows, possible rounding errors in the approximation are not corrected in the update for the residual (see also [91, 45]).

Since the residual is usually involved in some kind of stopping criterion, this may cause a premature termination of the algorithm: the true residual $b - A\mathbf{x}$ and therefore the approximate solution \mathbf{x} does not satisfy the stopping criterion.

A naive strategy to overcome this problem would be to replace the computed residual by the true residual. Not only is this expensive because an extra matrix multiplication is needed in each iteration, but these true residuals do not satisfy the given BiCG recursions and this may even destroy the convergence eventually.

¹We say that an algorithm is *accurate* for a certain problem if the recursively computed residuals \mathbf{r}_0 and the true residual $b - A\mathbf{x}$ are of comparable size, i.e., $\|b - A\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{r}_0\|_2$ should be small.

```

Choose an initial guess  $\mathbf{x}_0$  and some  $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0$ 
 $\mathbf{r}_0 = K^{-1}(b - A\mathbf{x}_0)$ ,  $\zeta_0 = \|\mathbf{r}_0\|_2$ 
 $\mathbf{u}_0 = 0$ ,  $\alpha = \rho_0 = \omega = 1$ ,  $\zeta = \zeta_0$ 
while  $\zeta > \epsilon\zeta_0$  do
  — The BiCG part —
   $\rho_0 = -\omega\rho_0$ 
  for  $j = 0, 1, \dots, \ell - 1$  do
     $\rho_1 = (\mathbf{r}_j, \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0)$ ,  $\beta = \alpha(\rho_1/\rho_0)$ 
     $\rho_0 = \rho_1$ 
    for  $i = 0, 1, \dots, j$  do
       $\mathbf{u}_i = \mathbf{r}_i - \beta\mathbf{u}_i$ 
    enddo
     $\mathbf{u}_{j+1} = K^{-1}A\mathbf{u}_j$ 
     $\sigma = (\mathbf{u}_{j+1}, \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0)$ ,  $\alpha = \rho_1/\sigma$ 
     $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x} + \alpha\mathbf{u}_0$ 
    for  $i = 0, 1, \dots, j$  do
       $\mathbf{r}_i = \mathbf{r}_i - \alpha\mathbf{u}_{i+1}$ 
    enddo
     $\mathbf{r}_{j+1} = K^{-1}A\mathbf{r}_j$ 
  enddo
  — The polynomial part —
  for  $i = 1, 2, \dots, \ell$  do
    for  $j = 1, 2, \dots, i$  do
       $Z(i, j) = \overline{Z(j, i)} = (\mathbf{r}_j, \mathbf{r}_i)$ 
    enddo
     $y(i) = (\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}_i)$ 
  enddo
   $y = Z^{-1}y$ ,  $\omega = y(\ell)$ 
  for  $i = 1, 2, \dots, \ell$  do
     $\mathbf{u}_0 = \mathbf{u}_0 - y(i)\mathbf{u}_i$ 
     $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x} + y(i)\mathbf{r}_{i-1}$ 
     $\mathbf{r}_0 = \mathbf{r}_0 - y(i)\mathbf{r}_i$ 
  enddo
   $\zeta = \|\mathbf{r}_0\|_2$ 
endwhile

```

ALGORITHM 3.1. Left preconditioned BiCGstab(ℓ) with power basis and normal equations. The matrix K is a preconditioner for A .

In [91], it is shown that an occasional replacement of the recursively computed residual by the true residual at strategic points during the iterations may lead to more accurate solutions, while maintaining the speed of convergence. However, if these replacements are performed for residuals much smaller than the initial residual, then also the update of the approximate solution requires a special treatment. This is done by accumulating groups of updates for updating the approximation. The implementation of such a strategy is the subject of Section 3.3.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 3.4 we present a FORTRAN implementation that incorporates these enhancements. In Section 3.5 we present some numerical examples. Section 3.6 contains our conclusions.

3.2. Maintaining the convergence. In [88, 89] the following convex combination for a more stable determination of the BiCG coefficients is proposed: in the polynomial part, take $\mathbf{r}_0 \leftarrow p(A)\mathbf{r}_0$ with

$$(3.5) \quad p = \frac{1 - \hat{\omega}\gamma}{1 - \hat{\omega}^2} p_{m,\ell}^{\text{MR}} + \frac{\hat{\omega}\gamma - \hat{\omega}^2}{1 - \hat{\omega}^2} p_{m,\ell}^{\text{OR}}$$

where

$$(3.6) \quad \hat{\omega} := \frac{\|p_{m,\ell}^{\text{MR}}(A)\mathbf{r}_0\|_2}{\|p_{m,\ell}^{\text{OR}}(A)\mathbf{r}_0\|_2} \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma := \max(\hat{\omega}, 0.7).$$

An equivalent formulation (cf. [88]), more suitable for implementation, is the following. With

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{R}} &= [A\mathbf{r}_0, A^2\mathbf{r}_0, \dots, A^{\ell-1}\mathbf{r}_0], \\ \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0 &= \mathbf{r}_0 - \hat{\mathbf{R}}(\hat{\mathbf{R}}^*\hat{\mathbf{R}})^{-1}\hat{\mathbf{R}}^*\mathbf{r}_0, \\ \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_\ell &= A^\ell\mathbf{r}_0 - \hat{\mathbf{R}}(\hat{\mathbf{R}}^*\hat{\mathbf{R}})^{-1}\hat{\mathbf{R}}^*A^\ell\mathbf{r}_0, \end{aligned}$$

take

$$(3.7) \quad \mathbf{r}_0 \leftarrow \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0 - \hat{\gamma} \frac{\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0\|_2}{\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_\ell\|_2} \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_\ell,$$

where

$$(3.8) \quad \hat{\gamma} := (\varrho/|\varrho|) \max(|\varrho|, 0.7), \quad \text{and} \quad \varrho := \frac{(\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0, \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_\ell)}{\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0\|_2 \|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_\ell\|_2}.$$

```

—  $Z = \mathbf{R}^* \mathbf{R}$  —
for  $i = 0, 1, \dots, \ell$  do
  for  $j = 0, 1, \dots, i$  do
     $Z(i+1, j+1) = \overline{Z(j+1, i+1)} = (\mathbf{r}_j, \mathbf{r}_i)$ 
  enddo
enddo
—  $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0$  and  $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_\ell$  —
 $y_0 = (-1, (Z(2:\ell, 2:\ell)^{-1} Z(2:\ell, 1))^*, 0)^*$ 
 $y_\ell = (0, (Z(2:\ell, 2:\ell)^{-1} Z(2:\ell, \ell+1))^*, -1)^*$ 
— Convex combination —
 $\kappa_0 = \sqrt{y_0^* Z y_0}$ ,  $\kappa_\ell = \sqrt{y_\ell^* Z y_\ell}$ ,  $\varrho = \frac{y_\ell^* Z y_0}{\kappa_0 \kappa_\ell}$ 
 $\hat{\gamma} = (\varrho/|\varrho|) \max(|\varrho|, 0.7)$ ,
 $y_0 = y_0 - \hat{\gamma} \frac{\kappa_0}{\kappa_\ell} y_\ell$ 
— Update —
 $\omega = y_0(\ell+1)$ 
for  $i = 1, 2, \dots, \ell$  do
   $\mathbf{u}_0 = \mathbf{u}_0 - y_0(i+1) \mathbf{u}_i$ 
   $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x} + y_0(i+1) \mathbf{r}_{i-1}$ 
   $\mathbf{r}_0 = \mathbf{r}_0 - y_0(i+1) \mathbf{r}_i$ 
enddo
 $\zeta = \sqrt{y_0^* Z y_0}$ 

```

ALGORITHM 3.2. Convex combination of $p_{m,\ell}^{\text{MR}}(A)\mathbf{r}_0$ and $p_{m,\ell}^{\text{OR}}(A)\mathbf{r}_0$.

This strategy can be incorporated by replacing the polynomial part in algorithm ALG. 3.1 by the algorithm in ALG. 3.2.

The implementation follows from the observation that with

$$\mathbf{R} = [\mathbf{r}_0, A\mathbf{r}_0, \dots, A^\ell \mathbf{r}_0] \quad \text{and} \quad Z = \mathbf{R}^* \mathbf{R},$$

$\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0$ is given by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0 = \mathbf{R}y_0, \quad \text{for } y_0 = (1, -(Z(2:\ell, 2:\ell))^{-1}Z(2:\ell, 1))^*, 0)^*$$

and, similarly, $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_\ell$ is given by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_\ell = \mathbf{R}y_\ell, \quad \text{for } y_\ell = (0, -(Z(2:\ell, 2:\ell))^{-1}Z(2:\ell, \ell+1))^*, 1)^*.$$

The inner product $(\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0, \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_\ell)$ and the norms $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0\|_2$ and $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_\ell\|_2$ follow from observing that:

$$\begin{aligned} (\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0, \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_\ell) &= y_\ell^* \mathbf{R}^* \mathbf{R} y_0 = y_\ell^* Z y_0, \\ \|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0\|_2 &= \sqrt{y_0^* \mathbf{R}^* \mathbf{R} y_0} = \sqrt{y_0^* Z y_0}, \\ \|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_\ell\|_2 &= \sqrt{y_\ell^* \mathbf{R}^* \mathbf{R} y_\ell} = \sqrt{y_\ell^* Z y_\ell}. \end{aligned}$$

This implies hardly any additional costs (see also TAB. 3.1).

3.3. Reliable updates. In [91] the accuracy of computed residuals is addressed. Efficient and easy to implement strategies are proposed that improve the accuracy significantly, while maintaining the speed of convergence.

Such a strategy can be incorporated as displayed in ALG. 3.3. For performing a group wise update of the approximate solution, we have chosen the following conditions (cf. [91]):

$$(3.9) \quad \text{if } (\|\mathbf{r}_0\|_2 < \delta \zeta_0 \ \& \ \zeta_0 \leq M(x)) \text{ then 'update_app' = 'true'},$$

where ζ_0 is the norm of the initial residual, $\delta = 10^{-2}$, and $M(x)$ is the maximum of the norm of the residuals since the last group wise update of the approximation. For replacing the recursively computed residual by the true residual, we have chosen the following conditions (cf. [91]):

$$(3.10) \quad \text{if } \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\|\mathbf{r}_0\|_2 < \delta M(r) \ \& \ \zeta_0 \leq M(r)) \\ \text{or 'update_app' = 'true'} \end{array} \right\} \text{ then 'compute_res' = 'true'},$$

where ζ_0 is the norm of the initial residual, $\delta = 10^{-2}$, and $M(r)$ is the maximum of the norm of the residuals since the last computation of the true residual. This combination of conditions for updating the solution and the replacement of the recursively computed residual by the true residual gives a compromise between costs and accuracy (cf. [91]).

```

Choose an initial guess  $\mathbf{x}_0$  and some  $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0$ 
 $\mathbf{r}_0 = K^{-1}(b - A\mathbf{x}_0)$ ,  $\zeta_0 = \|\mathbf{r}_0\|_2$ 
 $\mathbf{u}_0 = 0$ ,  $\alpha = \rho_0 = \omega = 1$ ,  $\zeta = \zeta_0$ 
 $\mathbf{x}' = \mathbf{x}_0$ ,  $\mathbf{x} = 0$ ,  $b' = \mathbf{r}_0$ 
 $k = -\ell$ 
while  $\zeta > \epsilon \zeta_0$  do
  — The BiCG part —
   $\rho_0 = -\omega\rho_0$ 
  for  $j = 0, 1, \dots, \ell - 1$  do
     $\rho_1 = (\mathbf{r}_j, \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0)$ ,  $\beta = \alpha(\rho_1/\rho_0)$ 
     $\rho_0 = \rho_1$ 
    for  $i = 0, 1, \dots, j$  do
       $\mathbf{u}_i = \mathbf{r}_i - \beta\mathbf{u}_i$ 
    enddo
     $\mathbf{u}_{j+1} = K^{-1}A\mathbf{u}_j$ 
     $\sigma = (\mathbf{u}_{j+1}, \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0)$ ,  $\alpha = \rho_1/\sigma$ 
     $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x} + \alpha\mathbf{u}_0$ 
    for  $i = 0, 1, \dots, j$  do
       $\mathbf{r}_i = \mathbf{r}_i - \alpha\mathbf{u}_{i+1}$ 
    enddo
     $\mathbf{r}_{j+1} = K^{-1}A\mathbf{r}_j$ 
  enddo
  — The polynomial part —
  Compute convex combination as in ALG. 3.2
  — The reliable update part —
  set 'update_app' (cf. (3.9)) and 'compute_res' (cf. (3.10))
  if 'compute_res' = 'true'
     $\mathbf{r}_0 = b' - A\mathbf{x}$ 
    if 'update_app' = 'true'
       $\mathbf{x}' = \mathbf{x}' + \mathbf{x}$ ,  $\mathbf{x} = 0$ ,  $b' = \mathbf{r}_0$ 
    endif
  endif
  'compute_res' = 'update_app' = 'false'
endwhile
 $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}' + \mathbf{x}$ 

```

ALGORITHM 3.3. Enhanced left preconditioned BiCGstab(ℓ).
The matrix K is a preconditioner for A .

METHOD	COMPUTATIONAL COSTS			MEMORY
	MVS	AXPYS	DOTS	REQUIREMENTS
BiCGstab(ℓ)	2ℓ	$\ell^2 + 5\ell$	$\ell^2/2 + 7/2\ell + 1$	$2\ell + 3$
Enhanced BiCGstab(ℓ)	2ℓ (*)	$\ell^2 + 5\ell$	$\ell^2/2 + 9/2\ell + 1$ (*)	$2\ell + 5$

The ‘(*)’ indicates that additional costs are involved when a reliable update is done: 1 axpy + 1 MV, when the residual is replaced; 1 axpy + 2 copies, when the solution is updated.

TABLE 3.1. Computational costs per iteration.

3.4. Description of FORTRAN code. Here we present a FORTRAN code for the enhanced version of BiCGstab(ℓ). In TAB. 3.1 an overview of the computational costs per iteration for the unmodified and for the enhanced version is given. As we see, the additional costs are low: 2 extra vectors for keeping track of the groups of updates for the approximate solution (\mathbf{x}' and b'); ℓ dots for determining $M(x)$ and $M(r)$; and some costs for when a reliable update is performed.

The calling sequence and the parameters are explained below. The FORTRAN code itself uses subroutines and functions from LAPACK [1].

BISTBL BISTBL — Left Preconditioned BiCGstab(ℓ) for the iterative solution of linear systems $Ax = b$.

Declaration subroutine **bistbl** (ℓ , n, x, b, mv, solve, tol, mxmv,
work, ldw, rwork, ldrw, iwork,
info)

Parameters integer ℓ
On entry, ℓ specifies the degree of the polynomial ($\ell > 1$).
Suggested values are $\ell = 1, 2, 4, 8$. Unchanged on exit.

integer **n**
On entry, n specifies the dimension of the matrix A ($n > 1$).
Unchanged on exit.

x

double precision array of size n . On entry, the array x has the value of the initial guess to the solution, e.g., $x = 0$. On exit, if $info = 0$, x is overwritten by the approximate solution.

b

double precision array of size n . On entry, the array b has the value of the right hand side of the linear problem $Ax = b$. Unchanged on exit.

external **mv**

external subroutine `mv(n, x, y)`. Must be supplied by the user and should return the vector $y = Ax$ of size n .

external **solve**

external subroutine `solve(n, x)`. Must be supplied by the user and should return $x \leftarrow K^{-1}x$, where K is a preconditioner for A .

double precision **tol**

On entry, $tol > 0$ specifies the stopping tolerance. On exit, if $info = 0$, tol has the value of the relative norm of the true residual.

integer **mxmv**

On entry, $mxmv$ specifies the maximum number of matrix multiplications. On exit, if $info = 0$, $mxmv$ has the value of the number of matrix multiplications actually performed.

work

double precision array of size ldw . Workspace for $(3 + 2(\ell + 1))$ vectors of size n .

integer **ldw**

On entry, ldw specifies the length of $work$. $ldw \geq (3 + 2(\ell + 1))n$. Unchanged on exit.

rwork

double precision array of size $ldrw$. Workspace for three vectors of size $\ell + 1$ and two matrices of size $(\ell + 1) \times (\ell + 1)$.

integer **ldrw**

On entry, $ldrw$ specifies the length of $rwork$. $ldrw \geq (3 + 2(\ell + 1))(\ell + 1)$. Unchanged on exit.

iwork

integer array of size $\ell + 1$. Workspace for one pivot array of size $\ell + 1$

integer **info**

On exit, $info$ defines the exit code.

<i>info</i>	Description
< 0	If $info = -i$, the i th argument had an illegal value.
0	The method was successful.
1	The method did not meet the specified tolerance within the specified number of matrix multiplications.
2	Breakdown; a division by zero occurred.

Note The implementation does not handle Lanczos and pivot breakdowns.

The FORTRAN code

```

1      subroutine bistbl (l, n, x, b, mv, solve, tol,
2          $          mxmv, work, ldw, rwork, ldrw, iwork, info)
3      c
4      c  subroutine bistbl v1.0 1995
5      c
6      c  Copyright (c) 1995 by D.R. Fokkema.
7      c  Permission to copy all or part of this work is granted
8      c  provided that the copies are not made or distributed

```

```

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13 c PROVIDES NO WARRANTY WHATSOEVER, EITHER EXPRESSED OR
    IMPLIED,
14 c REGARDING THE WORK, INCLUDING WARRANTIES WITH RESPECT
    TO ITS
15 c MERCHANTABILITY OR FITNESS FOR ANY PARTICULAR PURPOSE.
16 c
17     implicit none
18 c
19 c     .. Parameters ..
20 c
21     integer l, n, mxmv, ldw, ldrw, iwork(1+1), info
22     double precision x(n), b(n), tol
23     double precision work(n,3+2*(1+1)), rwork(1
        +1,3+2*(1+1))
24 c
25 c     .. Matrix ..
26 c
27     external mv
28     external solve
29 c
30 c     .. Local ..
31 c
32     logical rcmp, xpd
33     integer i, j, k, nmv
34     double precision alpha, beta, omega, rho0, rho1,
        sigma
35     double precision varrho, hatgamma
36     double precision rnr0, rnr
37     double precision mxnrmx, mxnr, kappa0, kappal
38 c
39 c     .. Work Aliases ..
40 c
41     integer z, zz, y0, y1, y
42     integer rr, r, u, xp, bp
43 c
44 c     .. Constants ..
45 c
46     double precision zero, one, delta

```

```
47     parameter (zero = 0d0, one = 1d0, delta = 1d-2)
48     c
49     c     .. BLAS and LAPACK ..
50     c
51     c     subroutine daxpy
52     c     subroutine dcopy
53     c     subroutine dgemv
54     c     subroutine dgetrf
55     c     subroutine dgetrs
56     c     subroutine dlacpy
57     c     subroutine dlaset
58     c     subroutine dsymv
59     c     function ddot
60     c     function dnorm2
61     c
62     double precision dnorm2, ddot
63     c
64     c     .. Intrinsic ..
65     c
66     intrinsic abs, max, sqrt
67     c
68     c     =====
69     c     .. Executable Statements ..
70     c     =====
71     c
72     info = 0
73
74     if (l.lt.1) info = -1
75     if (n.lt.1) info = -2
76     if (tol.le.zero) info = -7
77     if (mxmv.lt.0) info = -8
78
79     rr = 1
80     r = rr+1
81     u = r+(l+1)
82     xp = u+(l+1)
83     bp = xp+1
84     if (bp*n.gt.ldw) info = -10
85
86     z = 1
87     zz = z+(l+1)
88     y0 = zz+(l+1)
```

```

89      y1 = y0+1
90      y = y1+1
91      if (y*(1+1).gt.ldrw) info = -12
92
93      if (info.ne.0) return
94  C
95  C      --- Initialize first residual
96  C
97      call mv (n, x, work(1,r))
98      do i=1,n
99          work(i,r) = b(i) - work(i,r)
100     enddo
101     call solve (n, work(1,r))
102  C
103  C      --- Initialize iteration loop
104  C
105     nmv = 0
106
107     call dcopy (n, work(1,r), 1, work(1,rr), 1)
108     call dcopy (n, work(1,r), 1, work(1,bp), 1)
109     call dcopy (n, x, 1, work(1,xp), 1)
110     call dlaset ('n', n, 1, zero, zero, x, 1)
111     rnrn0 = dnrn2 (n, work(1,r), 1)
112     rnrn = rnrn0
113
114     mxnrnx = rnrn0
115     mxnrnr = rnrn0
116     rcmp = .false.
117     xpdt = .false.
118
119     alpha = zero
120     omega = one
121     sigma = one
122     rho0 = one
123  C
124  C      --- Iterate
125  C
126     do while (rnrn.gt.tol*rnrn0 .and. nmv.lt.mxmv)
127  C
128  C      =====
129  C      --- The BiCG part ---
130  C      =====

```

```

131 c
132      rho0 = -omega*rho0
133      do k=1,l
134          rho1 = ddot (n, work(1,rr), 1, work(1,r+k-1)
135                    , 1)
135          if (rho0.eq.zero) then
136              info = 2
137              return
138          endif
139          beta = alpha*(rho1/rho0)
140          rho0 = rho1
141          do j=0,k-1
142              do i=1,n
143                  work(i,u+j) = work(i,r+j) - beta*work(
144                    i,u+j)
144              enddo
145          enddo
146          call mv (n, work(1,u+k-1), work(1,u+k))
147          call solve (n, work(1,u+k))
148          nmv = nmv+1
149          sigma = ddot (n, work(1,rr), 1, work(1,u+k),
150                    1)
151          if (sigma.eq.zero) then
152              info = 2
153              return
154          endif
155          alpha = rho1/sigma
156          call daxpy (n, alpha, work(1,u), 1, x, 1)
157          do j=0,k-1
158              call daxpy (n, (-alpha), work(1,u+j+1),
159                    1,
160                    work(1,r+j), 1)
158          enddo
159          call mv (n, work(1,r+k-1), work(1,r+k))
160          call solve (n, work(1,r+k))
161          nmv = nmv+1
162          rnorm = dnorm2 (n, work(1,r), 1)
163          mxnrmx = max (mxnrmx, rnorm)
164          mxnrmr = max (mxnrmr, rnorm)
165          enddo
166
167 c
168 c      =====

```

```

169 c      --- The convex polynomial part ---
170 c      =====
171 c
172 c      ---  $Z = R'R$ 
173 c
174 c      do i=1,l+1
175 c          call dgemv ('t', n, l+1-(i-1), one, work(1,r
176 c              +i-1),
177 c              $          n, work(1,r+i-1), 1, zero, rwork(i,z+i
178 c              -1), 1)
179 c          call dcopy (l-(i-1), rwork(i+1,z+i-1), 1,
180 c              $          rwork(i,z+i), l+1)
181 c      enddo
182 c      call dlacpy ('a', l+1, l+1, rwork(1,z), l+1,
183 c              $          rwork(1,zz), l+1)
184 c      call dgetrf (l-1, l-1, rwork(2,zz+1), l+1,
185 c              $          iwork, info)
186 c
187 c      --- tilde r0 and tilde r1 (small vectors)
188 c
189 c      rwork(1,y0) = -one
190 c      call dcopy (l-1, rwork(2,z), 1, rwork(2,y0), 1)
191 c      call dgetrs ('n', l-1, 1, rwork(2,zz+1), l+1,
192 c              $          iwork,
193 c              $          rwork(2,y0), l+1, info)
194 c      rwork(l+1,y0) = zero
195 c
196 c      rwork(1,y1) = zero
197 c      call dcopy (l-1, rwork(2,z+1), 1, rwork(2,y1),
198 c              $          1)
199 c      call dgetrs ('n', l-1, 1, rwork(2,zz+1), l+1,
200 c              $          iwork,
201 c              $          rwork(2,y1), l+1, info)
202 c      rwork(l+1,y1) = -one
203 c
204 c      --- Convex combination
205 c
206 c      call dsymv ('u', l+1, one, rwork(1,z), l+1,
207 c              $          rwork(1,y0), 1, zero, rwork(1,y), 1)
208 c      kappa0 = sqrt(ddot (l+1, rwork(1,y0), 1,
209 c              $          rwork(1,y), 1))

```

```

206      call dsymv ('u', l+1, one, rwork(1,z), l+1,
207      $          rwork(1,y1), 1, zero, rwork(1,y), 1)
208      kappal = sqrt(ddot (l+1, rwork(1,y1), 1,
209      $          rwork(1,y), 1))
210
211      call dsymv ('u', l+1, one, rwork(1,z), l+1,
212      $          rwork(1,y0), 1, zero, rwork(1,y), 1)
213      varrho =
214      $          ddot (l+1, rwork(1,y1), 1, rwork(1,y), 1)
215      $          / (kappa0*kappal)
216
217      hatgamma =
218      $          varrho/abs(varrho)*max(abs(varrho),7d-1)
219      $          * (kappa0/kappal)
220
221      call daxpy (l+1, (-hatgamma), rwork(1,y1), 1,
222      $          rwork(1,y0), 1)
223  C
224  C      --- Update
225  C
226      omega = rwork(l+1,y0)
227
228      call dgemv ('n', n, l, (-one), work(1,u+1), n,
229      $          rwork(2,y0), 1, one, work(1,u), 1)
230      call dgemv ('n', n, l, one, work(1,r), n,
231      $          rwork(2,y0), 1, one, x, 1)
232      call dgemv ('n', n, l, (-one), work(1,r+1), n,
233      $          rwork(2,y0), 1, one, work(1,r), 1)
234
235      call dsymv ('u', l+1, one, rwork(1,z), l+1,
236      $          rwork(1,y0), 1, zero, rwork(1,y), 1)
237      rnrms = sqrt (ddot (l+1, rwork(1,y0), 1,
238      $          rwork(1,y), 1))
239  C
240  C      =====
241  C      --- The reliable update part ---
242  C      =====
243  C
244      mxnrms = max (mxnrms, rnrms)
245      mxnrmr = max (mxnrmr, rnrms)
246      xpdt = (rnrms.lt.delta*rnrms0.and.rnrms0.lt.mxnrms
              )

```

```

247         rcmp = ((rnrmlt.delta*mxnrmlr.and.rnrml0.lt.
                mxnrmlr)
248     $         .or.xpdt)
249     if (rcmp) then
250         call mv (n, x, work(1,r))
251         call solve (n, work(1,r))
252         do i=1,n
253             work(i,r) = work(i,bp) - work(i,r)
254         enddo
255         mxnrmlr = rnrml
256         if (xpdt) then
257             call daxpy (n, one, x, 1, work(1,xp), 1)
258             call dlaset ('n', n, 1, zero, zero, x, 1)
259             call dcopy (n, work(1,r), 1, work(1,bp),
                1)
260             mxnrmlx = rnrml
261         endif
262     endif
263 enddo
264 C
265 C     =====
266 C     --- End of iterations ---
267 C     =====
268 C
269     call daxpy (n, one, work(1,xp), 1, x, 1)
270 C
271 C     --- Check stopping criterion
272 C
273     call mv (n, x, work(1,r))
274     do i=1,n
275         work(i,r) = b(i) - work(i,r)
276     enddo
277     call solve (n, work(1,r))
278     rnrml = dnrml2 (n, work(1,r), 1)
279     if (rnrml.gt.tol*rnrml0) info = 1
280 C
281 C     --- Return
282 C
283     tol = rnrml/rnrml0
284     mxmv = nmv
285
286     return

```

287

end

3.5. Numerical experiments. In this section we compare the performance of the unmodified BiCGstab(ℓ) version (ALG. 3.1) and the enhanced version (ALG. 3.3). We consider two of the linear problems that are also used in [91, 88]. In both cases no preconditioning is used. The computations were done in double precision (≈ 15 digits) on a Sun workstation.

3.5.1. Example 1. With this example we show that taking a convex combination of the MR polynomial and the OR polynomial may indeed cure stagnation.

The linear system stems from a 65×65 finite volume discretization on the unit square of the partial differential equation

$$-\Delta u + 100(xu_x + yu_y) - 200u = f,$$

where f is such that $u(x, y) \equiv 1$ is the solution.

In FIG. 3.1 and 3.2 we have plotted the number of matrix multiplications versus the \log_{10} of the *true* residual norm for the unmodified and for the enhanced version of BiCGstab(ℓ) for $\ell = 1, 2, 4, 8$, respectively. FIG. 3.3 and 3.4 display plots for the number of flops versus the true residual norm. The maximum number of matrix multiplications was set to 300.

From these figures we see that the unmodified version of BiCGstab(1) stagnates, whereas the enhanced version does converge. Apparently, taking the convex combination of the MR polynomial and the OR polynomial of degree 1 cures the stagnation. For larger values of ℓ the unmodified version converges increasingly better, but still they converge not as fast as their enhanced counterparts.

In number of matrix multiplications, the enhanced version converges comparable for all considered values of ℓ . Looking at the number of flops we see that the enhanced BiCGstab(1) algorithm is the most efficient.

3.5.2. Example 2. With this example we show that taking the convex combination does not always cure stagnation. In this case increasing the value of ℓ helps. Moreover, the reliable update strategy in the enhanced version results in a more accurate solution.

The linear system stems from a 65×65 finite volume discretization on the unit square of the partial differential equation

$$-\Delta u + 1000(xu_x + yu_y) + 10u = f,$$

FIGURE 3.1. Number of MVs versus \log_{10} of the true residual norm for $\text{BiCGstab}(\ell)$ for example 1.

FIGURE 3.2. Number of MVs versus \log_{10} of the true residual norm for Enhanced $\text{BiCGstab}(\ell)$ for example 1.

FIGURE 3.3. Number of flops versus \log_{10} of the true residual norm for Enhanced $\text{BiCGstab}(\ell)$ for example 1.

FIGURE 3.4. Number of flops versus \log_{10} of the true residual norm for Enhanced $\text{BiCGstab}(\ell)$ for example 1.

FIGURE 3.5. Number of MVs versus \log_{10} of the true residual norm for BiCGstab(ℓ) for example 2.

FIGURE 3.6. Number of MVs versus \log_{10} of the true residual norm for Enhanced BiCGstab(ℓ) for example 2.

where f is such that $u(x, y) \equiv 1$ is the solution.

In FIG. 3.5 and 3.6 we have plotted the number of matrix multiplications versus the \log_{10} of the *true* residual norm for the unmodified and for the enhanced version of BiCGstab(ℓ) for $\ell = 1, 2, 4, 8$, respectively. FIG. 3.7 and 3.8 display plots for the number of flops versus the \log_{10} of the true residual norm. The maximum number of matrix multiplications was set to 1000.

From these figures we see that taking the convex combination of the MR polynomial and the OR polynomial of degree 1 does not cure the stagnation and leads to divergence. Increasing ℓ however, results in increasingly better convergence (in terms of MVs) for the unmodified version. The convergence for the enhanced version is for $\ell = 2, 4, 8$ comparable. Apparently, the BiCG iteration coefficients of the enhanced version are already accurate for $\ell = 2$ and increasing ℓ does not lead to better convergence. Notice that with the reliable update strategy we obtain almost full precision.

3.6. Conclusions. We have presented an enhanced FORTRAN implementation of the BiCGstab(ℓ) algorithm. The enhancements consist of two parts: (1) the accuracy of the BiCG iteration coefficients (and thereby the convergence

FIGURE 3.7. Number of flops versus \log_{10} of the true residual norm for Enhanced $\text{BiCGstab}(\ell)$ for example 2.

FIGURE 3.8. Number of flops versus \log_{10} of the true residual norm for Enhanced $\text{BiCGstab}(\ell)$ for example 2.

behavior) is improved by taking a suitable combination of minimal residual (MR-) and orthogonal (OR-) polynomials in the polynomial part of the $\text{BiCGstab}(\ell)$ algorithm, and (2) the accuracy of the approximate solution is improved by incorporating a “reliable update” strategy. The additional computational costs involved are small and easily compensated for by the much better overall performance.

Taking a suitable convex combination of MR- and OR-polynomials may cure stagnation (as is sometimes observed for $\text{BiCGstab}(1)$, for instance). It may also lead to divergence, but then increasing the value of ℓ usually helps.

The reliable update strategy occasionally replaces the recursively computed residual by the true residual at strategically chosen points, thereby improving the accuracy of the approximate solution without affecting the speed of convergence. A stopping criterion that involves the residual is therefore much more reliable.

CHAPTER 4

GENERALIZED CONJUGATE GRADIENT SQUARED

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Abstract. The Conjugate Gradient Squared (CGS) is an iterative method for solving nonsymmetric linear systems of equations. However, during the iteration large residual norms may appear, which may lead to inaccurate approximate solutions or may even deteriorate the convergence rate. Instead of squaring the Bi-CG polynomial as in CGS, we propose to consider products of two nearby Bi-CG polynomials which leads to generalized CGS methods, of which CGS is just a particular case. This approach allows the construction of methods that converge less irregularly than CGS and that improve on other convergence properties as well. Here, we are interested in a property that got less attention in literature: we concentrate on retaining the excellent approximation qualities of CGS with respect to components of the solution in the direction of eigenvectors associated with extreme eigenvalues. This property seems to be important in connection with Newton's scheme for nonlinear equations: our numerical experiments show that the number of Newton steps may decrease significantly when using a generalized CGS method as linear solver for the Newton correction equations.

Key words. Nonsymmetric linear systems, Krylov subspace, Iterative solvers, Bi-CG, CGS, BiCGstab(ℓ), Nonlinear systems, Newton's method

AMS subject classification. 65F10

4.1. Introduction. There is no best iterative method for solving linear systems of equations [67]. However, in many applications a particular method is preferred. CGS [93] is a frequently used method, but the popularity of CGS has diminished over time, because of its irregular convergence behavior. Nev-

ertheless, in some situations, for instance, when in combination with Newton's method for nonlinear equations in the context of device simulations, CGS is often still the method of choice¹.

The observation is that a Newton scheme in combination with CGS usually solves the nonlinear problem in less Newton steps than a Newton scheme in combination with other iterative methods. And although other methods, e.g., Bi-CGSTAB [102], sometimes need less iteration steps to solve the linear equations involved, Newton in combination with CGS turns out to be more efficient (see also our examples in Section 4.7).

For other situations where CGS or CGS-type of methods, such as TFQMR [39], are more suitable, refer to [60, pp. 128–133] and [14].

However, the large intermediate residuals produced by CGS badly affect its speed of convergence and limit its attainable accuracy [92], and this in turn has a (very) negative effect on the convergence of the overall Newton process.

In this paper we discuss variants of CGS that have improved convergence properties, while still having the important “quadratic reduction” property discussed below.

We will now try to explain why CGS may be so successful as a linear solver in a Newton scheme. In our heuristic arguments the eigensystem, the eigenvalues λ_j , and the eigenvectors v_j , of the local Jacobian matrices (the matrices of partial derivatives of the nonlinear problem, evaluated at the approximation) play a role. We consider the components of the approximate solutions and residuals in the direction of these eigenvectors, distinguishing between components associated with exterior eigenvalues (“exterior components”) and components associated with interior eigenvalues (“interior components”). By “exterior” and “interior” we refer to the position of the eigenvalue in the convex hull of the spectrum of the Jacobian matrix.

CGS (cf. Section 4.2) is based on Bi-CG [36, 57]. This linear solver tends to approximate the exterior components of the solution better and faster than the interior components [53, 77]. Any residual of a linear solver that we consider can be represented by a polynomial in the matrix representing the linear system (for instance, the Bi-CG residual can be written as $r_k^{\text{Bi-CG}} = \phi_k(A)r_0$, where ϕ_k is a polynomial of degree k) and the size of the eigenvector components of the residual is proportional to the (absolute) value of the polynomial in the associated eigenvalue (for instance for Bi-CG $r_k^{\text{Bi-CG}} = \sum_{j=1}^n \phi_k(\lambda_j)v_j$).

¹Personal communication by W. Schilders and M. Driessen, Philips Research Laboratories. They have also observed that for their semiconductor device modeling, where the system is often expressed in terms of voltages, the conservation of currents is better maintained when working with CGS.

The absolute value of Bi-CG polynomials tends to be smaller in the exterior eigenvalues than in the interior ones. A small component $\phi_k(\lambda_j)v_j$ of the residual r_k means that the corresponding component of the solution x_k is well approximated. CGS polynomials are the squares of Bi-CG polynomials: the residual of CGS can be written as $r_k^{\text{CGS}} = \phi_k^2(A)r_0$. Therefore, CGS approximations tend to have very accurate exterior components. A polynomial associated with, for instance, the BiCGstab methods is the product of a Bi-CG polynomial and another polynomial of the same degree ($r_k^{\text{BiCGstab}} = \tilde{\phi}_k(A)\phi_k(A)r_0$). This other polynomial (a product of locally minimizing degree 1 polynomials for Bi-CGSTAB ($\tilde{\phi}_k(t) = \prod_{i=1}^k (1 - \omega_i t)$) and a product of such polynomials of degree ℓ for BiCGstab(ℓ) [85]) does not have this strong tendency of reducing in exterior eigenvalues better than in the interior ones. Therefore, comparing approximations with residuals of comparable size (2-norm), we may expect that approximate solutions as produced by a BiCGstab method have exterior components that are less accurate than those of the CGS approximations, since the error components are larger. Of course, with respect to interior components, the situation will be in favor of the BiCGstab methods.

Now, we come to the implication for Newton's method. The nonlinearity of the problem seems often stronger in the (linear combination of) exterior components than in the (linear combination of) interior ones. This observation explains the nice convergence properties in the outer iteration when CGS is used in the inner iteration of Newton's process. CGS tends to deliver approximate solutions of which the exterior components are very accurate. With respect to these components, the Newton process, in which the linear systems are solved approximately by CGS, compares to a Newton process in which the linear systems are solved exactly, while this may not be true for the Newton process in combination with the BiCGstab methods (or others).

In summary, we wish to retain in our modifications the attractive property of CGS that it converges faster with respect to exterior components within a Newton method, without losing its efficiency, the fact that it is transpose free, and its fast convergence. However, we wish to avoid irregular convergence and large intermediate residuals, since they may badly affect the speed of convergence of the inner iteration.

Techniques as proposed in, e.g., [111, 68, 91] smooth down the convergence by operating a posteriori on approximates and residuals. Although they may lead to more accurate approximates (see the "additional note" in Section 4.7 or [91]), they do not change the speed of convergence. For a detailed discussion, see [91].

The polynomial associated with our new methods is the product of the Bi-CG polynomial with another “nearby” polynomial of the same degree (cf. Section 4.4). We refer to these methods as *generalized CGS* methods. They are about as efficient as CGS per iteration step (cf. Section 4.4). We pay special attention to the case where this second polynomial is a Bi-CG polynomial (cf. Section 4.6.1) of another (nearby) Bi-CG process, or a polynomial closely related to such a Bi-CG polynomial (cf. Section 4.6.2). The difference between the square of a Bi-CG polynomial and the product of two “nearby” Bi-CG polynomials of the same degree may seem insignificant, but, as we will see in our numerical examples in Section 4.7, this approach may lead to faster convergence in norm as well as to more accurate results. Moreover, this approach seems to improve the convergence of (exterior components in) nonlinear schemes. A discussion on the disadvantages of squaring the Bi-CG polynomial can be found in Section 4.3. Since we are working with products of Bi-CG polynomials, the new methods reduce exterior components comparable fast as CGS (cf. Section 4.6.1). It is obvious that Bi-CG and the ideas behind CGS are essential in deriving the new methods and therefore Bi-CG and CGS are discussed in Section 4.2. In that section we also introduce most of our notation.

4.2. Bi-CG and CGS. The Bi-CG method [36, 57] is an iterative solution scheme for linear systems

$$Ax = b,$$

in which A is some given nonsingular $n \times n$ matrix and b some given n -vector. Typically n is large and A is sparse. For ease of presentation, we assume A and b to be real.

Starting with an initial guess x_0 , each iteration of Bi-CG computes an approximation x_k to the solution. It is well known that the Bi-CG residual $r_k = b - Ax_k$ can be written as $\phi_k(A)r_0$ where ϕ_k is a certain polynomial in the space \mathcal{P}_k^1 of all polynomials ψ of degree k for which $\psi(0) = 1$. The Bi-CG polynomial ϕ_k is implicitly defined by the Bi-CG algorithm through a coupled two-term recurrence:

$$\begin{aligned} u_k &= r_k - \beta_k u_{k-1}, \\ r_{k+1} &= r_k - \alpha_k A u_k. \end{aligned}$$

The iteration coefficients α_k and β_k follow from the requirement that r_k and Au_k are orthogonal to the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_k(A^T; \tilde{r}_0)$ of order k , generated by A^T and an arbitrary, but fixed \tilde{r}_0 .

If $(\tilde{\phi}_k)$ is some sequence of polynomials of degree k with a nontrivial leading coefficient θ_k then (see [93] or [85]):

$$(4.1) \quad \beta_k = \frac{\theta_{k-1}}{\theta_k} \frac{\rho_k}{\sigma_{k-1}} \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha_k = \frac{\rho_k}{\sigma_k},$$

where

$$(4.2) \quad \rho_k = (r_k, \tilde{\phi}_k(A^T)\tilde{r}_0) \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_k = (Au_k, \tilde{\phi}_k(A^T)\tilde{r}_0).$$

In standard Bi-CG the polynomial $\tilde{\phi}_k$ is taken to be the same as the Bi-CG polynomial: $\tilde{\phi}_k = \phi_k$, where ϕ_k is such that $r_k = \phi_k(A)r_0$. This leads to another coupled two-term recurrence in the Bi-CG algorithm:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{u}_k &= \tilde{r}_k - \beta_k \tilde{u}_{k-1}, \\ \tilde{r}_{k+1} &= \tilde{r}_k - \alpha_k A^T \tilde{u}_k. \end{aligned}$$

Since A and b are assumed to be real, this means that \tilde{r}_k and $A^T \tilde{u}_k$ are orthogonal to the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_k(A; r_0)$, in particular the sequences (r_k) and (\tilde{r}_k) are bi-orthogonal. Of course, other choices for $\tilde{\phi}_k$ are possible. For instance, when A and b are complex and if we still want to have bi-orthogonality, then we should choose $\tilde{\phi}_k = \bar{\phi}_k$.

The leading coefficient of ϕ_k is $(-\alpha_{k-1})(-\alpha_{k-2}) \cdots (-\alpha_0)$ and therefore we have that

$$\frac{\theta_{k-1}}{\theta_k} = \frac{-1}{\alpha_{k-1}}$$

and thus

$$\beta_k = \frac{-1}{\alpha_{k-1}} \frac{\rho_k}{\sigma_{k-1}} \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha_k = \frac{\rho_k}{\sigma_k}.$$

A pseudo-code for the standard Bi-CG algorithm is given in ALG. 4.1.

It was Sonneveld [93] who suggested to rewrite the inner products so as to avoid the operations with A^T , e.g.,

$$(4.3) \quad \rho_k = (r_k, \tilde{\phi}_k(A^T)\tilde{r}_0) = (\tilde{\phi}_k(A)r_k, \tilde{r}_0),$$

and to take advantage of both ϕ_k and $\tilde{\phi}_k$ for the reduction of the residual by generating recurrences for the vectors $\mathbf{r}_k = \tilde{\phi}_k(A)r_k$. In fact, he suggested to take $\tilde{\phi}_k = \phi_k$, which led to the CGS method: $\mathbf{r}_k = \phi_k^2(A)r_0$. The corresponding search directions \mathbf{u}_k for the corresponding approximation \mathbf{x}_k can be easily

```

Choose an initial guess  $x_0$  and
some  $\tilde{r}_0$ 
 $r_0 = b - Ax_0$ 
 $u_{-1} = \tilde{u}_{-1} = 0, \alpha_{-1} = \sigma_{-1} = 1$ 
for  $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$  do
   $\rho_k = (r_k, \tilde{r}_k)$ 
   $\beta_k = (-1/\alpha_{k-1})(\rho_k/\sigma_{k-1})$ 
   $u_k = r_k - \beta_k u_{k-1}$ 
   $\tilde{u}_k = \tilde{r}_k - \beta_k \tilde{u}_{k-1}$ 
   $c = Au_k$ 
   $\sigma_k = (c, \tilde{r}_k)$ 
   $\alpha_k = \rho_k/\sigma_k$ 
   $x_{k+1} = x_k + \alpha_k u_k$ 
  if  $x_{k+1}$  is accurate enough,
    then quit
   $r_{k+1} = r_k - \alpha_k c$ 
   $\tilde{r}_{k+1} = \tilde{r}_k - \alpha_k A^T \tilde{u}_k$ 
end

```

ALGORITHM 4.1. Bi-CG

```

Choose an initial guess  $x_0$  and
some  $\tilde{r}_0$ 
 $\mathbf{r}_0 = b - A\mathbf{x}_0$ 
 $\mathbf{u}_{-1} = \mathbf{w}_{-1} = 0, \alpha_{-1} = \sigma_{-1} = 1$ 
for  $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$  do
   $\rho_k = (\mathbf{r}_k, \tilde{r}_k)$ 
   $\beta_k = (-1/\alpha_{k-1})(\rho_k/\sigma_{k-1})$ 
   $\mathbf{v}_k = \mathbf{r}_k - \beta_k \mathbf{u}_{k-1}$ 
   $\mathbf{w}_k = \mathbf{v}_k - \beta_k(\mathbf{u}_{k-1} - \beta_k \mathbf{w}_{k-1})$ 
   $\mathbf{c} = A\mathbf{w}_k$ 
   $\sigma_k = (\mathbf{c}, \tilde{r}_k)$ 
   $\alpha_k = \rho_k/\sigma_k$ 
   $\mathbf{u}_k = \mathbf{v}_k - \alpha_k \mathbf{c}$ 
   $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{x}_k + \alpha_k(\mathbf{v}_k + \mathbf{u}_k)$ 
  if  $x_{k+1}$  is accurate enough,
    then quit
   $\mathbf{r}_{k+1} = \mathbf{r}_k - \alpha_k A(\mathbf{v}_k + \mathbf{u}_k)$ 
end

```

ALGORITHM 4.2. CGS

constructed. In this approach the Bi-CG residuals r_k and search directions u_k themselves are not computed explicitly, nor are they needed in the process. See ALG. 4.2 for CGS.

As is explained in [102], $\phi_k(A)$ may not be a particularly well suited reduction operator for $\phi_k(A)r_0$. But, as we will see in Section 4.3, there are more arguments for not selecting $\tilde{\phi}_k = \phi_k$. For instance, we wish to avoid irregular convergence and large intermediate residuals. In [102] it was suggested to choose $\tilde{\phi}_k$ as a product of linear factors, which were constructed to minimize residuals in only one direction at a time. This led to the Bi-CGSTAB algorithm. This was further generalized to a composite of higher degree factors which minimize residuals over ℓ -dimensional subspaces: BiCGStab2, for $\ell = 2$, in [49], and BiCGstab(ℓ), the more efficient and more stable variant also for general ℓ , in [85, 92] (see also [88]).

Obviously, there is a variety of possibilities for the polynomials $\tilde{\phi}_k$. In the

next sections we investigate polynomials that are similar to the Bi-CG polynomial, i.e., polynomials that are defined by a coupled two-term recurrence. This leads to a generalized CGS (GCGS) algorithm, of which CGS and Bi-CGSTAB are just particular instances.

4.3. Disadvantages of squaring the iteration polynomial. For an eigenvalue λ of A , the component of the CGS residual, in the direction of the eigenvector associated with λ , is equal to $\nu_\lambda \phi_k(\lambda)^2$, where ν_λ is the component of r_0 in the direction of the same eigenvector (assuming λ is a semi-simple eigenvalue). The corresponding component of the Bi-CG residual is precisely $\nu_\lambda \phi_k(\lambda)$ and the tendency of $|\phi_k(\lambda)|$ to be small for non-large k and for exterior λ explains the good reduction abilities of CGS with respect to the exterior components.

Unfortunately, squaring has disadvantages: $|\phi_k(\lambda)|^2$ may be large even if $|\nu_\lambda \phi_k(\lambda)|$ is moderate. This may happen especially during the initial stage of the process (when k is small) and the CGS component will be extremely large. In such a case, the CGS residual \mathbf{r}_k is extremely large. Although the next residual \mathbf{r}_{k+1} may be moderate, a single large residual is enough to prevent the process of finding an accurate final approximate solution in finite precision arithmetic: in [92], Section 2.2 (see also [88]), it was shown that

$$(4.4) \quad \begin{aligned} \left| \|\mathbf{r}_m\|_2 - \|b - A\mathbf{x}_m\|_2 \right| &\leq \bar{\xi} \Gamma \max_{k \leq m} \|\mathbf{r}_k\|_2, \\ \text{with } \Gamma &:= m n_A \|A^{-1}\|_2 \|A\|_2, \end{aligned}$$

where $\bar{\xi}$ is the relative machine precision and n_A is the maximum number of nonzero entries per row of A . Except for the constant Γ this estimate seems to be sharp in practice: in actual computations we do not see the factor Γ (see [88]). Moreover the local bi-orthogonality, essential for Bi-CG and (implicitly) for CGS, will seriously be disturbed². This will slow down the speed of convergence. CGS is notorious for large intermediate residuals and irregular convergence behavior. The fact that $|\phi_k(\lambda)|^2$ can be large was precisely the reason in [102] to reject the choice $\tilde{\phi}_k = \phi_k$ and to consider a product of degree 1 factors that locally minimize the residual with respect to the norm $\|\cdot\|_2$. As anticipated, this approach usually improves the attainable *accuracy*, (i.e., the distance between $\|\mathbf{r}_m\|_2$ and $\|b - A\mathbf{x}_m\|_2$; cf. (4.4)) as well as the rate of convergence. However, the degree 1 factors do not tend to favor the reduction of the exterior components as we wish here.

²The Neumaier trick (cf. the “additional note” in Section 4.7) cures the loss of accuracy, but it does not improve the speed of convergence [91].

In summary, we wish to avoid “quadratically large” residual components, while retaining “quadratically small” components.

Of course the selected polynomials $\tilde{\phi}_k$ should also lead to an efficient algorithm. Before specifying polynomials $\tilde{\phi}_k$ in the Sections 4.5 and 4.6, we address this efficiency subject in Section 4.4.

4.4. Generalized CGS: methods of CGS type. In this section we derive an algorithm that delivers $\mathbf{r}_k = \tilde{\phi}_k(A)\phi_k(A)r_0$, where $\tilde{\phi}_k$ is a polynomial defined by a coupled two-term recurrence and where ϕ_k is the Bi-CG polynomial.

Consider the Bi-CG recurrence for the search directions u_k and the residuals

r_{k+1}

$$(4.5) \quad u_{-1} \equiv 0, \quad r_0 \equiv b - Ax_0,$$

$$(4.6) \quad u_k = r_k - \beta_k u_{k-1},$$

$$(4.7) \quad r_{k+1} = r_k - \alpha_k A u_k,$$

and the polynomial recurrence for the polynomials $\tilde{\phi}_{k+1}$ and $\tilde{\psi}_k$ evaluated in A

$$(4.8) \quad \tilde{\psi}_{-1}(A) \equiv 0, \quad \tilde{\phi}_0(A) \equiv I,$$

$$(4.9) \quad \tilde{\psi}_k(A) = \tilde{\phi}_k(A) - \tilde{\beta}_k \tilde{\psi}_{k-1}(A),$$

$$(4.10) \quad \tilde{\phi}_{k+1}(A) = \tilde{\phi}_k(A) - \tilde{\alpha}_k A \tilde{\psi}_k(A),$$

for scalar sequences $(\tilde{\alpha}_k)$ and $(\tilde{\beta}_k)$. For ease of notation we will write Φ_k for $\tilde{\phi}_k(A)$ and Ψ_k for $\tilde{\psi}_k(A)$ from now on. Our goal is to compute $\mathbf{r}_{k+1} = \Phi_{k+1} r_{k+1}$. We will concentrate on the vector updates first, i.e., for the moment we will assume that the iteration coefficients $\tilde{\alpha}_k$ and $\tilde{\beta}_k$ are explicitly given.

Suppose we have the following vectors at step k :

$$(4.11) \quad \Psi_{k-1} u_{k-1}, \quad \Psi_{k-1} r_k, \quad \Phi_k u_{k-1} \quad \text{and} \quad \Phi_k r_k.$$

Note that for $k = 0$ these vectors are well defined. We proceed by showing how the index of vectors in (4.11) can be increased.

We use the Bi-CG recurrence (4.6) to update $\Phi_k u_k$:

$$\Phi_k u_k = \Phi_k r_k - \beta_k \Phi_k u_{k-1}.$$

Before we can update $\Psi_k u_k$ a similar way, i.e.,

$$(4.12) \quad \Psi_k u_k = \Psi_k r_k - \beta_k \Psi_k u_{k-1},$$

we need the vectors $\Psi_k r_k$ and $\Psi_k u_{k-1}$. These vectors follow from (4.9):

$$(4.13) \quad \Psi_k r_k = \Phi_k r_k - \tilde{\beta}_k \Psi_{k-1} r_k,$$

$$(4.14) \quad \Psi_k u_{k-1} = \Phi_k u_{k-1} - \tilde{\beta}_k \Psi_{k-1} u_{k-1}.$$

This in combination with (4.12) gives us $\Psi_k u_k$. The vectors $\Psi_k r_{k+1}$ and $\Phi_{k+1} u_k$ follow from (4.7) and (4.10):

$$\Psi_k r_{k+1} = \Psi_k r_k - \alpha_k A \Psi_k u_k,$$

$$\Phi_{k+1} u_k = \Phi_k u_k - \tilde{\alpha}_k A \Psi_k u_k.$$

Finally, to obtain $\Phi_{k+1} r_{k+1}$ we apply the recurrences (4.7) and (4.10):

$$(4.15) \quad \Phi_k r_{k+1} = \Phi_k r_k - \alpha_k A \Phi_k u_k,$$

$$(4.16) \quad \Phi_{k+1} r_{k+1} = \Phi_k r_{k+1} - \tilde{\alpha}_k A \Psi_k r_{k+1}.$$

When α_k and $\tilde{\alpha}_k$ are known before updating (4.15) and (4.16), we can avoid one of the matrix-vector products by combining these equations. This leads to

$$\Phi_{k+1} r_{k+1} = \Phi_k r_k - A(\alpha_k \Phi_k u_k - \tilde{\alpha}_k \Psi_k r_{k+1}),$$

and, hence, we only need $A \Psi_k u_k$ and $A(\alpha_k \Phi_k u_k - \tilde{\alpha}_k \Psi_k r_{k+1})$ in order to complete one iteration step, and the corresponding computational scheme needs two matrix-vector multiplications per iteration step, just as CGS.

The iteration coefficients α_k and β_k have to be computed such that r_k and Au_k are orthogonal to the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_k(A^T; \tilde{r}_0)$. According to (4.1) and (4.2), these coefficients are determined by θ_{k-1}/θ_k , ρ_k and σ_k . From (4.10) it follows that the leading coefficient of $\tilde{\phi}_k$ is given by $(-\tilde{\alpha}_{k-1})(-\tilde{\alpha}_{k-2}) \cdots (-\tilde{\alpha}_0)$ and hence

$$\frac{\theta_{k-1}}{\theta_k} = \frac{-1}{\tilde{\alpha}_{k-1}}.$$

For the scalar ρ_k we can rewrite the inner product (cf. (4.3)):

$$\rho_k = (\Phi_k r_k, \tilde{r}_0).$$

Note that the vector $\Phi_k r_k$ is available. However, for the scalar σ_k rewriting the inner product does not help because $A \Phi_k u_k$ is no longer available, since we have combined (4.15) and (4.16). Fortunately, we can replace $A \Phi_k u_k$ by the vector $A \Psi_k u_k$, which is available. It follows from (4.9) that the degree of $\tilde{\psi}_k - \tilde{\phi}_k$ is smaller than k and thus that

$$(A(\Phi_k - \Psi_k)u_k, \tilde{r}_0) = (Au_k, (\tilde{\phi}_k(A^T) - \tilde{\psi}_k(A^T))\tilde{r}_0) = 0.$$

Therefore, we have that

$$\sigma_k = (A\Psi_k u_k, \tilde{r}_0).$$

The algorithm for this *generalized CGS* (GCGS) method is given ALG. 4.3. In this algorithm, the following substitutions have been made:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_{k-1} &= \Phi_k u_{k-1}, & \mathbf{v}_k &= \Phi_k u_k, & \mathbf{w}_k &= \Psi_k u_k, \\ \mathbf{r}_k &= \Phi_k r_k, & \mathbf{s}_k &= \Psi_k r_{k+1}, & \mathbf{t}_k &= \Psi_k r_k, \end{aligned}$$

and the equations (4.12) and (4.14) are combined to one single equation.

The algorithm is very similar to ALG. 4.2. In terms of computational work per iteration step (per 2 matrix-vector multiplications) GCGS needs only two more vector updates than CGS; moreover, GCGS needs only storage for two more vectors.

In Sections 4.5 and 4.6 we will discuss some possible choices for the recurrence coefficients of the polynomials $\tilde{\phi}_k$. Section 4.5 contains the well known CGS and Bi-CGSTAB method. The new methods can be found in Section 4.6.

4.5. Well known methods of CGS type. We present here the CGS and the Bi-CGSTAB method to show that they fit in the frame of generalized CGS methods and to facilitate comparison of efficiencies.

4.5.1. CGS: using the Bi-CG polynomials. The choice $\tilde{\alpha}_k = \alpha_k$, $\tilde{\beta}_k = \beta_k$ leads to CGS. In ALG. 4.3 the vectors \mathbf{v}_k and \mathbf{t}_k as well as the vectors \mathbf{u}_k and \mathbf{s}_k are identical in this situation and some computational steps are now redundant.

4.5.2. Bi-CGSTAB: using products of optimal first degree factors. As explained in Section 4.3, to avoid irregular convergence and large intermediate residuals, a product of degree 1 factors that locally minimize the residual is suggested in [102].

In our formulation Bi-CGSTAB can be obtained as follows. Take $\tilde{\beta}_k = 0$, so that the recurrences (4.12)-(4.16) reduce to

$$(4.17) \quad \Phi_k u_k = \Phi_k r_k - \beta_k \Phi_k u_{k-1},$$

$$(4.18) \quad \Phi_k r_{k+1} = \Phi_k r_k - \alpha_k A\Phi_k u_k,$$

$$(4.19) \quad \Phi_{k+1} u_k = \Phi_k u_k - \tilde{\alpha}_k A\Phi_k u_k,$$

$$(4.20) \quad \Phi_{k+1} r_{k+1} = \Phi_k r_{k+1} - \tilde{\alpha}_k A\Phi_k r_{k+1},$$

and take $\tilde{\alpha}_k$ such that $\|\Phi_k r_{k+1} - \tilde{\alpha}_k A\Phi_k r_{k+1}\|_2$ is minimal. Hence,

$$\tilde{\alpha}_k = \frac{(\Phi_k r_{k+1}, A\Phi_k r_{k+1})}{(A\Phi_k r_{k+1}, A\Phi_k r_{k+1})}.$$

```

Choose an initial guess  $\mathbf{x}_0$  and some  $\tilde{r}_0$ 
 $\mathbf{r}_0 = b - A\mathbf{x}_0$ 
 $\mathbf{u}_{-1} = \mathbf{w}_{-1} = \mathbf{s}_{-1} = \mathbf{0}$ ,
 $\alpha_{-1} = \sigma_{-1} = \tilde{\alpha}_{-1} = \tilde{\sigma}_{-1} = 1$ 
for  $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$  do
   $\rho_k = (\mathbf{r}_k, \tilde{r}_0)$ 
   $\beta_k = (-1/\tilde{\alpha}_{k-1})(\rho_k/\sigma_{k-1})$ 
   $\mathbf{v}_k = \mathbf{r}_k - \beta_k \mathbf{u}_{k-1}$ 
  choose  $\tilde{\beta}_k$ 
   $\mathbf{t}_k = \mathbf{r}_k - \tilde{\beta}_k \mathbf{s}_{k-1}$ 
   $\mathbf{w}_k = \mathbf{t}_k - \beta_k(\mathbf{u}_{k-1} - \tilde{\beta}_k \mathbf{w}_{k-1})$ 
   $\mathbf{c} = A\mathbf{w}_k$ 
   $\sigma_k = (\mathbf{c}, \tilde{r}_0)$ 
   $\alpha_k = \rho_k/\sigma_k$ 
   $\mathbf{s}_k = \mathbf{t}_k - \alpha_k \mathbf{c}$ 
   $\tilde{\alpha}_k = (\mathbf{s}_k, \mathbf{t}_k)/(\mathbf{t}_k, \mathbf{t}_k)$ 
   $\mathbf{u}_k = \mathbf{v}_k - \tilde{\alpha}_k \mathbf{c}$ 
   $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{x}_k + \alpha_k \mathbf{v}_k + \tilde{\alpha}_k \mathbf{s}_k$ 
  if  $\mathbf{x}_{k+1}$  is accurate enough, then quit
   $\mathbf{r}_{k+1} = \mathbf{r}_k - A(\alpha_k \mathbf{v}_k + \tilde{\alpha}_k \mathbf{s}_k)$ 
end

```

ALGORITHM 4.3. GCGS

For efficiency reasons one usually combines (4.17) and (4.19). Notice that $\tilde{\phi}_k$ is now a product of the linear factors $(1 - \tilde{\alpha}_k t)$.

A pseudo-code for Bi-CGSTAB is given in ALG. 4.4.

4.6. New methods of CGS type. The BiCGstab methods generally converge more smoothly than CGS, but they do not approximate the exterior components of the solution as well as CGS. We wish to preserve this approximation property, while smoothing the convergence at the same time³.

³As explained in Section 4.3, we want smooth convergence by avoiding a priori extremely large components. The smoothing techniques in, e.g., [111], work a posteriori and do *not*

```

Choose an initial guess  $\mathbf{x}_0$  and some  $\tilde{r}_0$ 
 $\mathbf{r}_0 = b - A\mathbf{x}_0$ 
 $\mathbf{u}_{-1} = \mathbf{w}_{-1} = \mathbf{s}_{-1} = 0,$ 
 $\alpha_{-1} = \sigma_{-1} = \tilde{\alpha}_{-1} = \tilde{\sigma}_{-1} = 1$ 
for  $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$  do
     $\rho_k = (\mathbf{r}_k, \tilde{r}_0)$ 
     $\beta_k = (-1/\tilde{\alpha}_{k-1})(\rho_k/\sigma_{k-1})$ 
     $\mathbf{w}_k = \mathbf{r}_k - \beta_k(\mathbf{w}_{k-1} - \tilde{\alpha}_k\mathbf{c}_{k-1})$ 
     $\mathbf{c}_k = A\mathbf{w}_k$ 
     $\sigma_k = (\mathbf{c}_k, \tilde{r}_0)$ 
     $\alpha_k = \rho_k/\sigma_k$ 
     $\mathbf{s}_k = \mathbf{r}_k - \alpha_k\mathbf{c}_k$ 
     $\mathbf{t}_k = A\mathbf{s}_k$ 
     $\tilde{\alpha}_k = (\mathbf{s}_k, \mathbf{t}_k)/(\mathbf{t}_k, \mathbf{t}_k)$ 
     $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{x}_k + \alpha_k\mathbf{w}_k + \tilde{\alpha}_k\mathbf{s}_k$ 
    if  $\mathbf{x}_{k+1}$  is accurate enough, then quit
     $\mathbf{r}_{k+1} = \mathbf{s}_k - \tilde{\alpha}_k\mathbf{t}_k$ 
end

```

ALGORITHM 4.4. Bi-CGSTAB

4.6.1. CGS2: using related Bi-CG polynomials. We will argue that a related Bi-CG polynomial will meet our conditions to a certain extent: in this subsection, $\tilde{\phi}_k$ is the Bi-CG polynomial generated by r_0 and \tilde{s}_0 , some vector different from \tilde{r}_0 . For \tilde{s}_0 one may take, for instance, a random, but fixed vector. The roots of the Bi-CG polynomial ϕ_k converge (for increasing k) towards eigenvalues corresponding to eigenvectors with nonzero weights ν_λ . The roots of this $\tilde{\phi}_k$ will converge to the same eigenvalues, but, and this is important, in a *different* manner. If both ϕ_k and $\tilde{\phi}_k$ reduce a component of r_0 poorly, as may be the case initially, then both corresponding roots have not yet converged to the corresponding eigenvalue. In other words, both $\phi_k(\lambda)$ and $\tilde{\phi}_k(\lambda)$ are significantly different from zero. But, since both polynomials are distinct, the product $|\tilde{\phi}_k(\lambda)\phi_k(\lambda)|$ is smaller than $\max(|\phi_k(\lambda)|^2, |\tilde{\phi}_k(\lambda)|^2)$ and one may hope

affect the rate of convergence nor the attainable accuracy.

that applying $\tilde{\phi}_k(A)\phi_k(A)$ as a reduction operator to r_0 will not lead to as bad an amplification of this component as $\phi_k(A)^2$ (CGS). If both ϕ_k and $\tilde{\phi}_k$ reduce a component of r_0 well, as may be the case later in the iteration process, then both corresponding roots have converged to the same corresponding eigenvalue. In this case we have a quadratic reduction of that component.

We give more details for the resulting scheme. The scheme is very efficient: although we work (implicitly) with two different Bi-CG processes the iteration steps do not require matrix-vector multiplications in addition to the ones in the GCGS scheme (ALG. 4.3). As before, we write $\tilde{\phi}_k(A)$ as Φ_k (and $\tilde{\psi}_k(A)$ as Ψ_k).

As with the Bi-CG polynomial ϕ_k (see Section 4.2), we seek coefficients $\tilde{\alpha}_k$ and $\tilde{\beta}_k$ such that $\Phi_k r_0$ and $A\Psi_k r_0$ are orthogonal to the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_k(A^T; \tilde{s}_0)$. According to (4.1) and (4.2) we may write

$$\tilde{\beta}_k = \frac{\tilde{\theta}_{k-1}}{\tilde{\theta}_k} \frac{\tilde{\rho}_k}{\tilde{\sigma}_{k-1}} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\alpha}_k = \frac{\tilde{\rho}_k}{\tilde{\sigma}_k},$$

where

$$(4.21) \quad \tilde{\rho}_k = (\Phi_k r_0, \chi_k(A^T) \tilde{s}_0) \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\sigma}_k = (A\Psi_k r_0, \chi_k(A^T) \tilde{s}_0)$$

and $\tilde{\theta}_k$ is the leading coefficient of some polynomial χ_k of degree k and $\chi_k(0) = 1$. Normally, like in Bi-CG, practically any choice for χ_k would lead to another two-term recurrence in order to construct a basis for $\mathcal{K}_k(A^T; \tilde{s}_0)$. That would make the algorithm expensive, especially since matrix multiplications are involved. Surprisingly, we can avoid this construction, and thus the computational work, because we can use the Bi-CG polynomial ϕ_k , which is already (implicitly) available. Replacing χ_k by ϕ_k in (4.21) gives us for the iteration coefficients that

$$\tilde{\beta}_k = \frac{-1}{\alpha_{k-1}} \frac{\tilde{\rho}_k}{\tilde{\sigma}_{k-1}} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\alpha}_k = \frac{\tilde{\rho}_k}{\tilde{\sigma}_k},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\rho}_k &= (\Phi_k r_0, \phi_k(A^T) \tilde{s}_0) = (\Phi_k \phi_k(A) r_0, \tilde{s}_0) = (\mathbf{r}_k, \tilde{s}_0), \quad \text{and} \\ \tilde{\sigma}_k &= (A\Psi_k r_0, \phi_k(A^T) \tilde{s}_0) = (A\Psi_k \phi_k(A) r_0, \tilde{s}_0) = (A\mathbf{v}_k, \tilde{s}_0). \end{aligned}$$

Here we used the fact that multiplication with polynomials in A is commutative:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_k(A) \tilde{\phi}_k(A) r_0 &= \tilde{\phi}_k(A) \phi_k(A) r_0 = \Phi_k r_k, \quad \text{and} \\ \phi_k(A) \tilde{\psi}_k(A) r_0 &= \tilde{\psi}_k(A) \phi_k(A) r_0 = \Psi_k r_k. \end{aligned}$$

```

Choose an initial guess  $\mathbf{x}_0$ , some  $\tilde{r}_0$  and some  $\tilde{s}_0$ 
 $\mathbf{r}_0 = b - A\mathbf{x}_0$ 
 $\mathbf{u}_{-1} = \mathbf{w}_{-1} = \mathbf{s}_{-1} = 0$ ,
 $\alpha_{-1} = \sigma_{-1} = \tilde{\alpha}_{-1} = \tilde{\sigma}_{-1} = 1$ 
for  $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$  do
   $\rho_k = (\mathbf{r}_k, \tilde{r}_0)$ 
   $\beta_k = (-1/\tilde{\alpha}_{k-1})(\rho_k/\sigma_{k-1})$ 
   $\mathbf{v}_k = \mathbf{r}_k - \beta_k \mathbf{u}_{k-1}$ 
   $\tilde{\rho}_k = (\mathbf{r}_k, \tilde{s}_0)$ 
   $\tilde{\beta}_k = (-1/\alpha_{k-1})(\tilde{\rho}_k/\tilde{\sigma}_{k-1})$ 
   $\mathbf{t}_k = \mathbf{r}_k - \tilde{\beta}_k \mathbf{s}_{k-1}$ 
   $\mathbf{w}_k = \mathbf{t}_k - \beta_k(\mathbf{u}_{k-1} - \tilde{\beta}_k \mathbf{w}_{k-1})$ 
   $\mathbf{c} = A\mathbf{w}_k$ 
   $\sigma_k = (\mathbf{c}, \tilde{r}_0)$ 
   $\alpha_k = \rho_k/\sigma_k$ 
   $\mathbf{s}_k = \mathbf{t}_k - \alpha_k \mathbf{c}$ 
   $\tilde{\sigma}_k = (\mathbf{c}, \tilde{s}_0)$ 
   $\tilde{\alpha}_k = \tilde{\rho}_k/\tilde{\sigma}_k$ 
   $\mathbf{u}_k = \mathbf{v}_k - \tilde{\alpha}_k \mathbf{c}$ 
   $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{x}_k + \alpha_k \mathbf{v}_k + \tilde{\alpha}_k \mathbf{s}_k$ 
  if  $x_{k+1}$  is accurate enough, then quit
   $\mathbf{r}_{k+1} = \mathbf{r}_k - A(\alpha_k \mathbf{v}_k + \tilde{\alpha}_k \mathbf{s}_k)$ 
end

```

ALGORITHM 4.5. CGS2

A pseudo-code for this computational scheme, which we will call *CGS2*, is given in ALG. 4.5. Compared with CGS, CGS2 needs two more vector updates and two more inner products per iteration and storage for three additional vectors.

4.6.2. Shifted CGS: using delayed Bi-CG polynomials. We wish to avoid extremely large factors $|\tilde{\phi}_k(\lambda)\phi_k(\lambda)|$. Such factors may occur if $\tilde{\phi}_k\phi_k$ has a (nearly) double root corresponding to an eigenvector component that has not converged (yet). The choice of $\tilde{\phi}_k$ in the preceding section does not

exclude this possibility. In our approach below, we explicitly try to avoid these unwanted double roots associated with eigenvector components that have not converged yet. As before, we still want to have near double roots corresponding to converged components.

It is well known that for $A = A^T$ the roots of the Bi-CG polynomial ϕ_{k-1} separate those of ϕ_k and a product of these two polynomials seems to be a good candidate for avoiding large residuals. This idea can be implemented as follows.

For some $\mu \in \mathbb{C}$, take

$$\tilde{\phi}_k(\lambda) = (1 - \mu\lambda) \phi_{k-1}(\lambda),$$

or equivalently, take

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\beta}_k &= 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\alpha}_k = \mu, \quad \text{for } k = 0, \\ \tilde{\beta}_k &= \beta_{k-1} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\alpha}_k = \alpha_{k-1}, \quad \text{for } k > 0. \end{aligned}$$

in the GCGS algorithm in ALG. 4.3.

A possible choice for μ is, for instance, the inverse of an approximation for the largest eigenvalue of A . This value for μ can be roughly determined with Gershgorin disks or with a few steps of Arnoldi's algorithm [2, 80]. As explained in the previous section, one may expect a smoother convergence behavior for symmetric problems. Additionally, the choice of μ may reduce the influence of the largest eigenvalue on the convergence behavior. For general nonsymmetric problems, where complex roots may appear, one may hope for a similar behavior of this scheme. We will refer to this approach as *Shifted CGS*. Note that in terms of computational work we save 2 inner products as compared with CGS2.

4.7. Numerical examples. The new GCGS methods (in Section 4.6) do not seem to be superior to BiCGstab(ℓ) as solvers of linear equations (although it seems they can compete). This should not come as a surprise, because they were not designed for this purpose. However, as we will see, they can be attractive as linear solver in a Newton scheme for nonlinear equations. The GCGS methods improve on CGS, with smoother and faster convergence, avoiding large intermediate residuals, leading to more accurate approximations (see, Section 4.7.1 for CGS2, and Section 4.7.2 for Shifted CGS). At the same time, they seem to maintain the good reduction properties of CGS with respect to the exterior components, and thus improving on BiCGstab methods as solvers in a Newton scheme (see, Section 4.7.3 and 4.7.4).

For large realistic problems, it is hard to compare explicitly the effects of the linear solvers on, say, the exterior components. Here, we support the validity

FIGURE 4.1. Convergence history for device `dr15c`, 469741 nonzeros (ILU(0) preconditioning).

of our heuristic arguments by showing that the convergence behavior in the numerical examples is in line with our predictions.

4.7.1. Characteristics of CGS2. The CGS2 algorithm (ALG. 4.5), which uses a product of two nearby Bi-CG polynomials, was tested with success at IIS in Zürich (this section) and at Philips in Eindhoven (Section 4.7.3).

At IIS the package PILS [74] written in C and FORTRAN was used for solving two linear systems extracted from the simulation of two devices called `dr15c` and `mct70c`, respectively. The computations were done on a Sun Sparc 10 in double precision ($\bar{\xi} \approx 0.5 \times 10^{-15}$) and ILU(0) [74, 62] was used as a preconditioner. The plots in FIG. 4.1 and FIG. 4.2 show the convergence behavior of CGS2, CGS, Bi-CGSTAB, and BiCGstab(2). In CGS2 we took random vectors for both \tilde{r}_0 and \tilde{s}_0 . In the other methods we took the standard choice $\tilde{r}_0 = r_0$. Along the x -axis the number of matrix-vector multiplications is given. The y -axis represents the relative residual norm $\|\mathbf{r}_k\|_2 / \|\mathbf{r}_0\|_2$ on logarithmic scale.

FIGURE 4.2. Convergence history for device `mct70c`, 1969203 nonzeros (ILU(0) preconditioning).

One observation is that CGS2 does not amplify the initial residual as much as CGS does. Its convergence behavior is much smoother. When we tried CGS with a random vector as $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0$ too, its convergence behavior improved, but still CGS2 was better. Furthermore, the plots show that CGS2 can compete with Bi-CGSTAB and BiCGstab(2). The accuracy of the approximate solution delivered by all methods was of comparable size, except for the accuracy of the approximate solution of CGS in `mct70c`, which was two orders of magnitude less than the others. Since the iterations were terminated when $\|\mathbf{r}_k\|_2/\|\mathbf{r}_0\|_2 \leq 10^{-9}$ and the relative machine precision is $\bar{\xi} \approx 0.5 \times 10^{-15}$, these results are in line with (4.4).

4.7.2. Characteristics of Shifted CGS. The Shifted CGS method (Section 4.6.2) uses a combination with a lower degree Bi-CG polynomial. In the examples to be discussed next, the parameter μ was taken as the inverse of the real part of the largest eigenvalue estimate, delivered by a few steps of Arnoldi's

FIGURE 4.3. Convergence history for example 1, 33292 nonzeros (ILU(0) preconditioning).

algorithm. Along the x -axis the number of matrix-vector multiplications is given and the y -axis represents the scaled true residual norm $\|b - A\mathbf{x}_k\|_2 / \|\mathbf{r}_0\|_2$.

4.7.2.1. Example 1. We start with a system with a symmetric positive definite matrix. For such a system the polynomial behavior of the error reduction with CGS is more easily interpreted, and because of the orthogonal eigensystem the situation is not further confused with arguments in angles between subspaces. The linear system stems from a (82×83) finite volume discretization over the unit square, with Dirichlet boundary conditions along $y = 0$ and Neumann conditions along the other parts of the boundary, of

$$-(Du_x)_x - (Du_y)_y = 1,$$

where the function D is defined as

$$D = 1000 \quad \text{for } 0.1 \leq x, y \leq 0.9, \text{ and } D = 1 \text{ elsewhere.}$$

Symmetric ILU(0) preconditioning [62] was used. FIG. 4.3 confirms our heuristic arguments that for a symmetric system a combination with a lower degree Bi-

FIGURE 4.4. Convergence history for example 2, 7840 nonzeros, (ILU(0) preconditioning).

CG polynomial can make the convergence somewhat smoother. The three peaks in the convergence history for CGS are not found in the history for our Shifted CGS variant. Notice that full accuracy of the approximate solution is attained for both methods, as may be explained by the fact that no residual norm is larger than the initial residual norm (cf. (4.4)).

4.7.2.2. Example 2. This example is taken from [19]. The linear system stems from a (42×42) finite volume discretization over the unit square with Dirichlet boundary conditions, of

$$-\Delta u + 2 \exp(2(x^2 + y^2))u_x - 100u = F,$$

where the right hand side is taken such that the vector with all ones is the solution. ILU(0) preconditioning was used.

The convergence behavior of both methods reflects the fact that the matrix is now nonsymmetric. Both methods converge less smoothly. The improvement is not impressive, but on the average it seems that all residual norms of Shifted

CGS stay well below those of CGS. As a result, the accuracy of Shifted CGS is two orders of magnitude better compared with the accuracy of CGS: the maximum intermediate residual for CGS is $\approx 3 \times 10^2$ times larger than the maximum one of Shifted CGS (cf. FIG. 4.4 and (4.4)).

4.7.3. CGS2 as linear solver in a Newton scheme. In this subsection we discuss numerical results of nonlinear device simulations in which the linear system of equations that appear in Newton's method are solved by CGS2, CGS, and Bi-CGSTAB. The numerical data for the figures was obtained from device simulations with the package CURRY [73], written in FORTRAN, developed at Philips in Eindhoven. In this package the Jacobian matrices are explicitly formed. The computations were done on an HP workstation in double precision. With this package the evolution of the solution of the device CAP01T with respect to Time (in seconds), and of the device DIODE with respect to voltage (in volt), is followed by a continuation method [43].

In each continuation step the value of the relevant parameter (volt or second) is increased by a certain step size and the next solution is computed by a Newton process in which the solution of the previous step is used as an initial guess. The irregularities in the convergence history in the figures are caused by convergence failures of the Newton process. In case Newton's method fails to converge for a particular step size, CURRY tries to solve this subproblem by using the continuation method with the step size halved. If Newton's method again fails to converge for this subproblem, this strategy is repeated up to 5 times (after which CURRY gives up).

The figures 4.5 and 4.6 show the convergence behavior of CURRY in combination with CGS2, CGS, or Bi-CGSTAB (all with ILU(0) preconditioning), as a linear solver in the consecutive Newton steps. Actually, for reasons explained in the introduction of this paper, CURRY, in the case of Bi-CGSTAB, switches to CGS in the last step of the Newton process for a particular continuation step. This improves the overall convergence of the continuation method significantly.

The figures should be understood as follows. The vertical axis shows the value of the continuation parameter, dictated by the continuation strategy in CURRY. The horizontal axis shows the cumulative number of matrix multiplications (MV's) used by the linear solver. The simulation is a success when the bottom of the plot is reached. The execution time is proportional to the number of MV's, so the fewer MV's the better the performance.

FIG. 4.5 shows the convergence behavior of a transient phase simulation (from 3 to 4 volts) in Time for the device CAP01T. With all three choices of the linear solvers CGS2, CGS, and Bi-CGSTAB+ (the "+" indicating the switch

FIGURE 4.5. CAPO1T: Convergence behavior of CURRY in combination with CGS2, CGS, and Bi-CGSTAB+.

to CGS), the package CURRY manages to compute the solution of a full simulation. Clearly, CGS2 is the method of choice in this example. Observe the long stagnation phase between 10^{-9} and 10^{-8} seconds. Typically, in other transient simulations (not shown here) with similar stagnation phases, CGS2 improved the overall performance of CURRY significantly.

FIG. 4.6 shows the convergence behavior of a simulation for the voltage (from 0 to 40 volts) of the device DIODE. The plot shows a typical convergence behavior of CURRY for simulation of “difficult” devices for which the combination of CURRY and CGS fails, e.g., in this case almost immediately (and therefore hard to see in the plot). The combination with Bi-CGSTAB+ converges initially much better than the combination with CGS2, but stalls at voltage level 23 and fails. CURRY with CGS2, on the other hand, after some difficulties in the initial phase, converges quite rapidly. In this example, and also in others, only

FIGURE 4.6. DIODE: Convergence behavior of CURRY in combination with CGS2, CGS, and Bi-CGSTAB+.

the combination of CURRY with CGS2 is able to compute the solution of a full simulation.

4.7.4. Shifted CGS as linear solver in a Newton scheme. Here we present a comparison of Shifted CGS and other linear solvers in a Newton scheme for solving the classical *driven cavity* problem from incompressible fluid flow. We compare Shifted CGS, CGS2, CGS, Bi-CGSTAB, and BiCGstab(2). In step k of the Newton process, the linear system (involving the exact Jacobian), is solved to a relative residual norm reduction of 2^{-k} (see [30]), subject to a maximum of 100 matrix vector multiplications. The correction vector obtained in this way was then used in a linesearch procedure [31] to get the new approximation. If the relative change of the (Newton) residual was less than 10^{-6} the iterations were stopped.

Following closely the presentations in [43, 17] the driven cavity problem in

stream function-vorticity formulation is described by these equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \nu \Delta \omega + (\psi_{x_2} \omega_{x_1} - \psi_{x_1} \omega_{x_2}) &= 0 \text{ in } \Omega, \\ -\Delta \psi &= \omega \text{ in } \Omega, \\ \psi &= 0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega, \\ \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial n}(x_1, x_2)|_{\partial\Omega} &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x_2 = 1, \\ 0 & \text{if } 0 \leq x_2 < 1, \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

where Ω is the unit square and the viscosity ν is the reciprocal of the Reynolds number Re . In terms of ψ alone this can be written as

$$\nu \Delta^2 \psi + (\psi_{x_2} (\Delta \psi)_{x_1} - \psi_{x_1} (\Delta \psi)_{x_2}) = 0 \text{ in } \Omega,$$

subject to the same boundary conditions. This equation was discretized with central differences on a 41×41 regular grid. As preconditioner we used the Modified ILU(2) decomposition [46] of the biharmonic operator Δ^2 . As initial guess we took $\psi = 0$.

In FIG. 4.7 we show a plot of the convergence of Newton for $Re=1000$. The marks indicate a Newton step. Also in this example, the parameter μ in Shifted CGS was taken as the inverse of the real part of the largest eigenvalue estimate, delivered by a few steps of Arnoldi's algorithm.

As can be seen clearly, only the combination of Newton with Shifted CGS and CGS2 is successful in this example. The combination with CGS can keep up in the beginning but then CGS has trouble solving the linear system, which causes the stagnation. The combination with Bi-CGSTAB stagnates all together. This could be attributed to the fact that Bi-CGSTAB is not able to solve the linear systems, because they are very nonsymmetric [85]. BiCGstab(2) on the other hand is able to solve the linear systems (in the beginning) but apparently delivers a correction that is not of much use to Newton.

Note that in this case the combination of Newton with Shifted CGS is preferable, because it is more efficient: Shifted CGS uses two inner products less than CGS2.

Additional note. In [102] it was observed that replacing the residual \mathbf{r}_k in CGS by the true residual $b - A\mathbf{x}_k$ has a negative effect on the iteration process. Separately, Neumaier [68] reports good results with a different strategy that does include the use of the true residual. His strategy can be summarized as follows:

Add the line “ $\mathbf{x}_{\text{best}} = 0$ ” after the first line in CGS and replace the last line with

FIGURE 4.7. Driven Cavity: Convergence behavior of Newton in combination with different linear solvers.

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$$\mathbf{r}_{k+1} = b - A\mathbf{x}_{k+1}$$

if  $\|\mathbf{r}_{k+1}\|_2 \leq \|\mathbf{r}_{\text{best}}\|_2$  then
   $b = \mathbf{r}_{\text{best}} = \mathbf{r}_{k+1}$ 
   $\mathbf{x}_{\text{best}} = \mathbf{x}_{\text{best}} + \mathbf{x}_{k+1}$ 
   $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = 0$ 
endif

```

We have tested this approach on several problems and for those problems we confirm the observation that indeed this modification to CGS has no adverse influence on the convergence behavior and that accuracy is reached within machine precision (i.e., $\|\mathbf{r}_m\|_2 - \|b - A\mathbf{x}_m\|_2 \lesssim \bar{\xi} \Gamma \|\mathbf{r}_0\|_2$ with Γ as in (4.4)). For an explanation and other related strategies, see [91].

4.8. Conclusions. We have shown how the CGS algorithm can be generalized to a method that uses the product of two nearby Bi-CG polynomials as a reduction operator on the initial residual. Two methods are suggested to improve the accuracy and the speed of convergence, without losing the quadratic

reduction of errors in converged eigenvector directions. This is important, since the Newton process seems to benefit from this property. Several numerical examples are given that confirm our heuristic arguments.

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CHAPTER 5

ACCELERATED INEXACT NEWTON SCHEMES FOR LARGE SYSTEMS OF NONLINEAR EQUATIONS

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Abstract. Classical iteration methods for linear systems, such as Jacobi Iteration, can be accelerated considerably by Krylov subspace methods like GMRES. In this paper, we describe how Inexact Newton methods for nonlinear problems can be accelerated in a similar way and how this leads to a general framework that includes many well-known techniques for solving linear and nonlinear systems, as well as new ones. Inexact Newton methods are frequently used in practice to avoid the expensive exact solution of the large linear system arising in the (possibly also inexact) linearization step of Newton's process. Our framework includes acceleration techniques for the "linear steps" as well as for the "nonlinear steps" in Newton's process. The described class of methods, the **AIN** (Accelerated Inexact Newton) methods, contains methods like GMRES and GMRESR for linear systems, Arnoldi and Jacobi-Davidson for linear eigenproblems, and many variants of Newton's method, like Damped Newton, for general nonlinear problems. As numerical experiments suggest, the **AIN** approach may be useful for the construction of efficient schemes for solving nonlinear problems.

Key words. Nonlinear problems, Newton's method, Inexact Newton, Iterative methods

AMS subject classification. 65H10

5.1. Introduction. Our goal in this paper is twofold. A number of iterative solvers for linear systems of equations, such as FOM [79], GMRES [82],

GCR [110], Flexible GMRES [81], GMRESR [105] and GCRO [29], are in structure very similar to iterative methods for linear eigenproblems, like shift and invert Arnoldi [2, 80], Davidson [26, 80], and Jacobi-Davidson [90]. We will show that all these algorithms can be viewed as instances of an Accelerated Inexact Newton (**AIN**) scheme (cf. ALG. 5.3), when applied to either linear equations or to linear eigenproblems. This observation may help us in the design and analysis of algorithms by “transporting” algorithmic approaches from one application area to another. Moreover, our aim is to identify efficient **AIN** schemes for nonlinear problems as well, and we will show how we can learn from the algorithms for linear problems.

To be more specific, we will be interested in the numerical approximation of the solution u of the nonlinear equation

$$(5.1) \quad F(u) = 0,$$

where F is some smooth (nonlinear) map from a domain in \mathbb{R}^n (or \mathbb{C}^n) that contains the solution u , into \mathbb{R}^n (or \mathbb{C}^n), where n is typically large.

Some special types of systems of equations will play an important motivating role in this paper.

The first type is the linear system of equations

$$(5.2) \quad Ax = b,$$

where A is a nonsingular matrix and b , x are vectors of appropriate size; A and b are given, x is unknown. The dimension n of the problem is typically large and A is often sparse. With $u = x$ and $F(u) := b - Au$, (5.2) is equivalent to (5.1). This type will serve as the main source of inspiration for our ideas.

The second type concerns the generalized linear eigenproblem

$$(5.3) \quad Av = \lambda Bv.$$

With $u = (v, \lambda)$ we have that, for normalized v , with $F(u) := Av - \lambda Bv$, equation (5.3) is equivalent to (5.1). This type is an example of a mildly nonlinear system and will serve as an illustration for the similarity between various algorithms, seen as instances of **AIN** (see Section 5.6).

However, the **AIN** schemes that we will discuss will be applicable to more general nonlinear problems, like, for instance, equations that arise from discretizing nonlinear partial differential equations of the form

$$(5.4) \quad -\nabla(a\nabla u) + bg(u)\nabla u + ch(u) = f \text{ on } \Omega,$$

where Ω is a domain in \mathbb{R}^2 or \mathbb{R}^3 , $a, b \in C^1(\bar{\Omega})$, $c \in C(\bar{\Omega})$, $h, g \in C^1(\mathbb{R})$, and $f \in L^2(\Omega)$, and u satisfies suitable boundary conditions. An example of (5.4) is, for instance

$$(5.5) \quad -\Delta u - \lambda e^u = 0 \text{ on } \Omega,$$

where Ω is some domain in \mathbb{R}^2 and $u = 0$ on $\partial\Omega$ (see also Section 5.8).

Guided by the known approaches for the linear system (cf. [81, 105, 29]) and the eigenproblem (cf. [90, 84]) we will define accelerated Inexact Newton schemes for more general nonlinear systems. This leads to a combination of Krylov subspace methods for Inexact Newton (cf. [55, 17] and also [30]) with acceleration techniques (as in [4]) and offers us an overwhelming choice of techniques for further improving the efficiency of Newton type methods. As a side-effect this leads to a surprisingly simple framework for the identification of many well-known methods for linear, eigen, and nonlinear problems.

Our numerical experiments for nonlinear problems, like problem (5.5), serve as an illustration for the usefulness of our approach.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 5.2 we briefly review the ideas behind the Inexact Newton method. In Section 5.3 we introduce the Accelerated Inexact Newton methods (**AIN**). We will examine how iterative methods for linear problems are accelerated and we will distinguish between a Galerkin approach and a Minimal Residual approach. These concepts are then extended to the nonlinear case. In Section 5.4 we make some comments on the implementation of **AIN** schemes. In Section 5.5 we show how many well-known iterative methods for linear problems fit in the **AIN** framework. In Section 5.6 and Section 5.7 we consider instances of **AIN** for the mildly nonlinear generalized eigenproblem and for more general nonlinear problems. In Section 5.8 we present our numerical results and some concluding remarks are in Section 5.9.

5.2. Inexact Newton methods. Newton type methods are very popular for solving systems of nonlinear equations as, for instance, represented by (5.4). If u_k is the approximate solution at iteration number k , Newton's method requires for the next approximate solution of (5.1), the evaluation of the Jacobian $J_k := F'(u_k)$ and the solution of the *correction equation*

$$(5.6) \quad J_k p = -r_k, \text{ where } r_k := F(u_k).$$

Unfortunately, it may be very expensive, or even practically impossible to determine the Jacobian and/or to solve the correction equation exactly, especially for larger systems.

1. Set $k = -1$ and choose an initial approximation u_0 .
2. Repeat until u_k is accurate enough:
 - (a) $k = k + 1$
 - (b) Compute the residual $r_k = F(u_k)$.
 - (c) Compute an approximation J_k for the Jacobian $F'(u_k)$.
 - (d) *Solve the correction equation (approximately).* Compute an (approximate) solution p_k of the correction equation

$$J_k p = -r_k.$$

- (e) *Update.* Compute the new approximation:
 $u_{k+1} = u_k + p_k.$

ALGORITHM 5.1. Inexact Newton

In such situations one aims for an approximate solution of the correction equation, possibly with an approximation for the Jacobian (see, e.g., [30]). ALG. 5.1 is an algorithmical representation of the resulting Inexact Newton scheme.

For an initial guess u_0 sufficiently close to a solution, Newton's method has asymptotically at least quadratic convergence behavior. However, this quadratic convergence is usually lost if one uses inexact variants and often the convergence is not much faster than linear. In the next section we make suggestions how this (linear) speed of convergence may be improved.

NOTE: It is our aim to restore, as much as possible, the asymptotic convergence behavior of exact Newton and we do not address the question of global convergence.

5.3. Accelerating Inexact Newton methods. Newton's method is a one step method, that is, in each step, Newton's method updates the approximate solution with information from the previous step only. However, in the computational process, subspaces have been built gradually, that contain useful information concerning the problem. This information may be exploited to improve the current approximate solution, and this is what we propose to do. More precisely, we will consider alternative update strategies for step (e) of the

1. Set $k = -1$ and choose an initial approximation x_0 .
2. Repeat until x_k is accurate enough:
 - (a) $k = k + 1$
 - (b) $r_k = b - Ax_k$
 - (c) $p_k = \text{diag}(A)^{-1}r_k$
 - (d) $x_{k+1} = x_k + p_k$

ALGORITHM 5.2. Jacobi Iteration

Inexact Newton algorithm ALG. 5.1.

5.3.1. Acceleration in the linear case. The linear system $Ax = b$ can be written as $F(x) := b - Ax = 0$, and $-A$ is the Jacobian of F . When the approximate solution p_k is computed as $p_k = M^{-1}r_k$, where M is some preconditioning matrix (approximating A), then the Inexact Newton algorithm, ALG. 5.1, reduces to a standard Richardson-type iteration process for the splitting $A = M - R$. For instance, the choice $M = D$, where $D = \text{diag}(A)$ leads to Jacobi iteration (see ALG. 5.2).

One may improve the convergence behavior of standard iterations schemes by

- using more sophisticated preconditioners M , and/or
- applying acceleration techniques in the update step.

Different preconditioners and different acceleration techniques lead to different algorithms, some of which are well-known.

Examples of iterations schemes that use more sophisticated preconditioners are, for instance, Gauss-Seidel iteration, where $M = L + D$, with L is the strict lower triangular part of A and $D = \text{diag}(A)$ and SOR where $M = \omega(L + D)$, and ω is a relaxation parameter.

Examples of iterations schemes that use acceleration techniques are algorithms that take their updates to the approximate solution as a linear combination of previous directions p_j . Preferable updates $\tilde{p}_k := \sum_{j \leq k} \gamma_j p_j$ are those for which $b - Ax_{k+1}$, where $x_{k+1} = x_k + \tilde{p}_k$, is minimal in some sense: e.g., $\|b - Ax_{k+1}\|_2$ is minimal, as in GMRES [82] and GCR [110], or $b - Ax_{k+1}$ is orthogonal to the p_j for $j \leq k$, as in FOM or GENCG [79], or $b - Ax_{k+1}$ is “quasi-minimal”, as in Bi-CG [57], and QMR [41].

Of course the distinction between preconditioning and acceleration is not a clear one. Acceleration techniques with a limited number of steps can be seen as a kind of dynamic preconditioning as opposed to the static preconditioning with fixed M . In this view one is again free to choose an acceleration technique. Examples of such iteration schemes are Flexible GMRES [81], GMRESR [105] and GCRO [29].

All these accelerated iteration schemes for linear problems construct approximations $x_{k+1} = x_0 + V_k y_k$, $V_k := [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k]$, with y_k the solution of a *smaller* or an *easier* projected problem. For example, GMRES computes y_k such that $\|b - A(x_k + V_k y_k)\|_2$ is minimal, or equivalently $(AV_k)^*(b - A(x_k + V_k y_k)) = 0$; FOM computes y_k such that $V_k^*(b - A(x_k + V_k y_k)) = 0$, whereas Bi-CG and QMR compute y_k as the solution of a larger tri-diagonal problem obtained with oblique projections.

For stability (and efficiency) reasons one usually constructs another basis for the span of V_k with certain orthogonality properties, depending on the selected approach.

5.3.2. Acceleration in the nonlinear case. We are interested in iteration schemes for finding a zero of a general nonlinear mapping F . For the linear case, the methods mentioned above are, apart from the computation of the residual, essentially a mix of two components: (1) the computation of a new search direction (which involves the residual), and (2) the update of the approximation (which involves the current search direction and possibly previous search directions, and the solution y_k of a projected problem). The first component may be interpreted as preconditioning, while the second component is the acceleration.

Looking more carefully on how y_k in the linear case is computed, we can distinguish between two approaches based on two different conditions. With $G_k(y) := F(x_k + V_k y)$, the FOM and the other “oblique” approaches lead to methods that compute y such that (for appropriate W_k) $W_k^* G_k(y) = 0$ (a *Galerkin* condition), whereas the GMRES approach leads to methods that compute y such that $\|G_k(y)\|_2$ is minimal (a *Minimal Residual* condition).

From these observations for the linear case we now can formulate iteration schemes for the nonlinear case.

The Inexact Newton iteration can be accelerated in a similar way as the standard linear iteration. This acceleration can be accomplished by updating the solution by a correction \tilde{p}_k in the subspace spanned by all correction directions p_j ($j \leq k$).

To be more precise, the update \tilde{p}_k for the approximate solution is given by

$\tilde{p}_k = V_k y$, where $V_k = [v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k]$ for some basis (v_j) of the *search space* \mathcal{V}_k spanned by p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k . Furthermore, with $G_k(y) = F(u_k + V_k y)$, we propose to determine y by

- a *Galerkin* condition on $G_k(y)$: y is a solution of

$$(5.7) \quad W_k^* G_k(y) = 0,$$

where W_k is some matrix of the same dimensions as V_k ,

- or a *Minimal Residual* (MR) condition on $G_k(y)$: y is a solution of

$$(5.8) \quad \min_y \|G_k(y)\|_2,$$

- or a mix of both, a *Restricted Minimal Residual* (RMR) condition on $G_k(y)$: y is a solution of

$$(5.9) \quad \min_y \|W_k^* G_k(y)\|_2.$$

Equation (5.7) generalizes the FOM approach, while equation (5.8) generalizes the GMRES approach.

Solving (5.7) means that the component of the residual r_{k+1} in the subspace \mathcal{W}_k (spanned by W_k) vanishes. For W_k one may choose, for instance, $W_k = V_k$ (as in FOM), or $W_k = [W_{k-1}, w_k]$ where w_k is the component of $J_k p_k$ orthogonal to W_{k-1} , (as in GMRES: $w_k = (I - W_{k-1} W_{k-1}^*) J_k p_k$). For linear equations the Minimal Residual and the Galerkin approach coincide for the last choice.

As is known from the linear case, a complication of the Galerkin approach is that equation (5.7) may have no solution, which means that this approach may lead to breakdown of the method. In order to circumvent this shortcoming to some extent we have formulated the Restricted Minimal Residual approach (5.9). Compared to (5.7) this formulation is also attractive for another reason: one can apply standard Gauss-Newton [31] schemes for solving general nonlinear least squares problems to it. One might argue that a drawback of a Gauss-Newton scheme is that it may converge slowly (or not at all). However, for least squares problems with zero residual solutions, the asymptotic speed of convergence of a Gauss-Newton method is that of Newton's method. This means, that if the Galerkin problem (5.7) has a solution, a Gauss-Newton scheme applied to (5.9) will find it fast and efficient (see also Section 5.8).

Note that equations (5.7)–(5.9) represent nonlinear problems in only k variables, which may be much easier to solve than the original problem. If these smaller nonlinear problems can be formulated cheaply, then the costs for an update step may be considered as being relatively small.

Note also that since equations (5.7)–(5.9) are nonlinear, they may have more than one solution. This fact may be exploited to steer the computational process to a specific preferable solution of the original problem.

Accelerated Inexact Newton. For the Galerkin approach, step (e) in the Inexact Newton’s algorithm, ALG. 5.1, is replaced by four steps in which

- the search subspace \mathcal{V}_{k-1} is expanded by an approximate “Newton correction” and a suitable basis is constructed for this subspace,
- a shadow space \mathcal{W}_k is selected on which we project the original problem,
- the projected problem (5.7) is solved,
- and the solution is updated.

This is represented, by the steps (e)–(h) in ALG. 5.3. The Minimal Residual approach and the Restricted Minimal Residual approach can be represented in a similar way.

5.4. Computational considerations. In this section we make some comments on implementation details that mainly focus on limiting computational work and memory space.

5.4.1. Restart. For small k , problems (5.7)–(5.9) are of small dimension and may often be solved at relatively low computational costs (e.g., by some variant of Newton’s method).

For larger k they may become a serious problem in itself. In such a situation, one may wish to restrict the subspaces \mathcal{V} and \mathcal{W} to subspaces of smaller dimension (see ALG. 5.3, step (i)). Such an approach limits the computational costs per iteration, but it may also have a negative effect on the speed of convergence.

For example, the simplest choice, restricting the search subspace to a 1-dimensional subspace leads to Damped Inexact Newton methods, where, for instance, the damping parameter α is the solution of $\min_{\alpha} \|G_k(\alpha)\|_2$, where $G_k(\alpha) = F(u_k + p_k\alpha)$.

Of course, a complete restart is also feasible, say after each m th step (cf. step (i) of ALG. 5.3):

1. Set $k = -1$ and choose an initial approximation u_0 .
 $V = []$, $W = []$.
2. Repeat until u_k is accurate enough:
 - (a) $k = k + 1$
 - (b) Compute the residual $r_k = F(u_k)$.
 - (c) Compute an approximation J_k for the Jacobian $F'(u_k)$.
 - (d) *Solve the correction equation (approximately).*
Compute an (approximate) solution p_k for the correction equation

$$J_k p = -r_k.$$

- (e) *Expand the search space.* Select a v_k in the $\text{span}(V_{k-1}, p_k)$ that is linearly independent of V_{k-1} and update $V_k = [V_{k-1}, v_k]$.
- (f) *Expand the shadow space.* Select a w_k that is linearly independent of W_{k-1} and update $W_k = [W_{k-1}, w_k]$.
- (g) *Solve the projected problem.* Compute nontrivial solutions y of the projected system

$$W_k^* G_k(y) = 0.$$

- (h) *Update.* Select a y_k (from the set of solutions y) and update the approximation: $u_{k+1} = u_k + V_k y_k$.
- (i) *Restart.* $\ell = \dim(\text{span}(V_k))$. If ℓ is too large, select an $\ell' < \ell$, select $\ell \times \ell'$ matrices R_V and R_W and compute $V_k = V_k R_V$, $W_k = W_k R_W$ (i.e., take suitable combinations of the columns of V_k and W_k).

ALGORITHM 5.3. Accelerated Inexact Newton

- (i) If $\dim(\text{span}(V_k)) > m$ then $V_k = []$ and $W_k = []$.

The disadvantage of a complete restart is that we have to rebuild subspace information again. Usually it leads to a slower speed of convergence.

It seems like an open door to suggest that parts of subspaces better be retained at restart, but in practical situations it is very difficult to predict what those parts should be. A meaningful choice would depend on spectral properties of the Jacobian as well as on the current approximation. When solving linear equations with GMRESR [105], good results have been reported in [108] when selecting a number of the first and the last columns (cf. step (i) of ALG. 5.3); e.g.,

- (i) If $\dim(\text{span}(V_k)) > 10$ then $V_k = V_k R_V$ and $W_k = W_k R_W$, with $R_V = R_W = [e_1, \dots, e_5, e_7, \dots, e_{11}]$.

In [29], a variant of GMRESR, called GCRO, is proposed, which implements another choice. For subspaces of dimension $l+m$, the first l columns are retained, together with a combination of the last m columns. This combination is taken such that the approximate solution, induced by a minimal residual condition, is the same for both the subspaces of dimension $l+m$ and $l+1$. To be more specific, if $u_{k+1} = u_k + V_k y_k$, where y_k solves $\min_y \|F(u_k + V_k y)\|_2$, then V_k is replaced by $[V_{k_l}, V_{k_m} y_{k_m}]$ (denoting $V_k = [V_{k_l}, V_{k_m}]$ and $y_k = [y_{k_l}, y_{k_m}]$).

5.4.2. Update. In the update step (step (h) of ALG. 5.3), a solution y_k of the projected problem has to be selected from the set of solutions y . Selection may be necessary since many nonlinear problems have more than one solution. Sometimes, this may be the reason for poor convergence of (Inexact) Newton: the sequence of approximate solutions “wavers” between different exact solutions. For larger search subspaces, the search subspace may contain good approximations for more than one solution. This may be exploited to steer the sequence of approximate solution to the wanted solution u_{k+1} and it may help to avoid wavering convergence behavior.

The selection of y_k should be based on additional properties of the solution u_{k+1} . For instance, we may look for the solution largest in norm, or as in the case of eigenvalue problems, for a solution of which one component is close to some specific value (for instance, if one is interested in eigenvalues close to, say, 0, the Ritz vector with Ritz value closest to 0 will be chosen).

5.4.3. The projected problem. Even though problems of small dimension can be solved with relatively low computational costs, step (g) in ALG. 5.3 is not necessarily inexpensive. The projected problem is embedded in the large subspace and it may require quite some computational effort to represent the problem in a small subspace (to which y belongs) of dimension $\ell := \dim(\text{span}(V_k))$ ($y \in \mathbb{C}^\ell$). In the case of linear equations (or linear eigenvalue problems) the computation of an $\ell \times \ell$ -matrix as $W_k^* A V_k$ requires ℓ^2 inner products. For this type of problems, and for many others as well, one may save on the computational costs by re-using information from previous iterations.

5.4.4. Expanding the search subspace. The AIN algorithm breaks down if the search subspace is not expanded. This happens when p_k belongs to the span of V_{k-1} (or, in finite precision arithmetic, if the angle between p_k and this subspace is very small). Similar as for GMRES, one may then replace p_k by $J_k v_\ell$, where v_ℓ is the last column vector of the matrix V_{k-1} .

With approximate solution of the correction equation, a breakdown will also occur if the new residual r_k is equal to the previous residual r_{k-1} . We will have such a situation if $y_{k-1} = 0$. Then, instead of modifying the expansion process in iteration number k , one may also take measures in iteration number $k - 1$ in order to avoid $y_{k-1} = 0$. In [105] a few steps by LSQR are suggested when the linear solver is a Krylov subspace method: $p_k = J_{k-1}^T r_{k-1}$ may already cure the stagnation.

5.5. How linear solvers fit in the AIN framework. In this section we will show how some well-known iterative methods for the solution of linear systems fit in the AIN framework. The methods that follow from specific choices in AIN are equivalent to well-known methods only in the sense that, at least in exact arithmetic, they produce the same basis vectors for the search spaces, the same approximate solutions, and the same Newton corrections (in the same sense as in which GMRES and ORTHODIR are equivalent).

With $u = x$, $F(u) := b - Au$, the linear equation (5.2) is equivalent to the one in (5.1) and $J_k = -A$. In this section, M denotes a preconditioning matrix for A (i.e., for a vector v , $M^{-1}v$ is easy to compute and approximates $A^{-1}v$).

5.5.1. GCR. With the choice, $p_k = M^{-1}r_k$, $w_k = Av_k$, and v_k such that $w_k \perp \text{span}(W_{k-1})$, the AIN algorithm ALG. 5.3 (without restart) is equivalent to preconditioned GCR [110].

5.5.2. FOM and GMRES. The choice $p_k = M^{-1}r_k$ and v_k such that $v_k \perp \text{span}(V_{k-1})$, gives algorithms that are related to FOM and GMRES [82].

With the additional choice $w_k = v_k$, **AIN** algorithm ALG. 5.3 is just FOM, while the choice $w_k = Av_k$ gives an algorithm that is equivalent to GMRES.

5.5.3. GMRESR. Taking $w_k = Av_k$, and v_k such that w_k is perpendicular to $\text{span}(W_{k-1})$ as in GCR and taking p_k as an approximate solution of the equation $Ap = r_k$, **AIN** algorithm ALG. 5.3 is equivalent to the GMRESR algorithms [105]. One might compute p_k by a few steps of GMRES, for instance.

5.6. AIN schemes for mildly nonlinear problems. In this section we will discuss numerical methods for the iterative solution of the generalized eigenproblem (5.3). We will show that they also fit in the general framework of the **AIN** ALG. 5.3 methods.

As already mentioned these **AIN** methods consist of two parts. In one part an approximate solution of the correction equation (cf. step (d) of Alg 5.3) is used to extend the search space. In the other part a solution of the projected problem (cf. step (g) in ALG. 5.3) is used to construct an update for the approximate solution.

We will start with the derivation of a more suitable form for the (Newton) correction equation for the generalized eigenproblem. After that, we will make some comments on how to solve the projected problem.

The correction equation. In order to avoid some of the complications that go with complex differentiation, we will mainly focus on the numerical computation of eigenvectors with a fixed component in some given direction (rather than on the computation of eigenvectors with a fixed norm).

First, let \tilde{u} be a fixed vector with a nontrivial component in the direction of the desired eigenvector x . We want to compute approximations u_k for x with a normalized component in the \tilde{u} -direction: $(u, \tilde{u}) = (x, \tilde{u}) = 1$. We will select ϑ_k such that the residual $r_k := (A - \vartheta_k B)u_k$ is orthogonal to w , where w is another fixed nontrivial vector, i.e., the approximate eigenvalue ϑ_k is given by $\vartheta_k := w^* Au_k / w^* Bu_k$.

Consider the map F given by

$$F(u) := (A - \vartheta B)u, \text{ where } \vartheta := \frac{w^* Au}{w^* Bu},$$

and u belongs to the hyper-plane $\{y \in \mathbb{C}^n \mid (y, \tilde{u}) = 1\}$. The Jacobian $J_k = F'(u_k)$ is then given by

$$J_k = \left(I - \frac{Bu_k w^*}{w^* Bu_k} \right) (A - \vartheta_k B)|_{\tilde{u}^\perp},$$

and the correction equation reads as

$$(5.10) \quad p \perp \tilde{u}, \text{ such that } \left(I - \frac{Bu_k w^*}{w^* Bu_k} \right) (A - \vartheta_k B)p = -r_k.$$

Since $r_k \perp w$, this equation is equivalent to

$$(5.11) \quad \begin{bmatrix} A - \vartheta_k B & Bu_k \\ \tilde{u}^* & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} p \\ \varepsilon \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -r_k \\ 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

that is, p is the solution of (5.10) if and only if p is the solution of (5.11).

The projected problem. For the Generalized eigenvalue problem we are in the fortunate position that all the solutions of problems of moderate size can be computed by standard methods such as for instance the QZ [63] method. However, before we can apply these methods we have to reformulate the projected problem because of the exceptional position of u_k in $W^*F(u_k + V_k y)$.

The key to this reformulation is the observation that in the methods we consider the affine subspace $u_k + \text{span}(V_k)$ is equal to V_k because V_k contains u_k by itself. Now, as an alternative to step (g) in ALG. 5.3, we may also compute all the solutions y of

$$W_k^* F(V_k y) = 0.$$

This problem can now be solved by for instance the QZ method, and after selecting y_k a new approximation u_{k+1} is given by $u_{k+1} := V_k y_k$.

5.6.1. Arnoldi's method. We consider the simplified case where $B = I$, i.e., the standard eigenproblem. If we do only one step of a Krylov subspace method (Krylov dimension 1) for the solution of the correction equation (5.10), then we obtain for the correction p_k :

$$p_k = -\alpha r_k.$$

Hence, $p_k = -\alpha(A - \vartheta_k I)u_k$. Note that this may be a poor (very) approximation, because, in general, $r_k \not\perp \tilde{u}$. The approximate eigenvector u_k belongs to the search subspace $\text{span}(V_{k-1})$ and expanding the search subspace by the component of p_k orthogonal to $\text{span}(V_{k-1})$ is equivalent to expanding this space with the orthogonal component of Au_k , which would be the “expansion” vector in Arnoldi's method. Hence, the search subspace is precisely the Krylov subspace generated by A and u_0 . Apparently, Arnoldi's method is an AIN method (with a “very inexact Newton step”) without restart.

The choice $W_k = V_k$ corresponds to the standard one in Arnoldi and produces ϑ 's that are called Ritz values, while the choice $W_k = AV_k$ leads to Harmonic Ritz values [70].

5.6.2. Davidson's method. As is the case in Arnoldi's method, Davidson's method [26] also carries out only one step of a Krylov subspace method for the solution of the correction equation. However, in contrast to Arnoldi's method, Davidson also incorporates a preconditioner.

He suggests to solve (5.10) approximately by p_k with

$$p_k = -M^{-1}r_k,$$

where M is the inverse of the diagonal of $A - \vartheta_k B$. Other choices have been suggested as well (cf. e.g., [22, 66]). Because of the preconditioner, even if $B = I$, the search space is not simply the Krylov subspace generated by A and u_0 . This may lead to an advantage of Davidson's method over Arnoldi's method.

For none of the choices of the preconditioner, proper care has been taken of the projections (see (5.10)): the preconditioner should approximate the inverse of the projected matrix (see (5.10)) as a map from \tilde{u}^\perp onto w^\perp rather than of $A - \vartheta_k B$.

However, if M is the diagonal of $A - \vartheta B$, and we choose \tilde{u} and w equal to the same, arbitrary standard basis vector (as Davidson does [26]) then

$$\left(I - \frac{Bu_k w^*}{w^* Bu_k}\right) M \left(I - \frac{u_k w^*}{w^* u_k}\right) p = -r_k,$$

whenever $w \perp r_k$ and p solves $Mp = -r_k$. Note that $p \perp w$, because M is diagonal and $r_k \perp w$. Therefore, for this particular choice of w (and \tilde{u}), the diagonal M may be expected to be a good preconditioner for the correction equation (including the projections) in the cases where M is a good preconditioner for $A - \vartheta_k B$. Observe that this argument does not hold for non-diagonal preconditioners M .

5.6.3. Jacobi-Davidson. Davidson methods with a non-diagonal preconditioner do not take care properly of the projections in the correction equation (5.10). This observation was made in [90], and a new algorithm was proposed for eigenproblems by including the projections in the Davidson scheme. In addition, these modified schemes allow for more general approximate solutions p_k than $p_k = -M^{-1}r_k$. For instance, the use of ℓ steps of a preconditioned Krylov subspace method for the correction equation is suggested, leading to Arnoldi type of methods in which the variable polynomial preconditioning is determined efficiently and the projections have been included correctly. The new methods have been called *Jacobi-Davidson* methods (Jacobi took proper care of the projections, but did not build a search subspace as Davidson did (see [90] for details and further references)).

The analysis and results in [13, 84] show that these Jacobi-Davidson methods can also be effective for solving generalized eigenproblems, even without any matrix inversion.

The Jacobi-Davidson methods allow for a variety of choices that may improve efficiency of the steps and speed of convergence and are good examples of **AIN** methods in which the projected problem (5.7) is used to steer the computation.

For an extensive discussion, we refer to [84].

5.7. AIN schemes for general nonlinear problems. In this section we summarize some iterative methods for the solution of nonlinear problems that have been proposed by different authors, and we show how these methods fit in the **AIN** framework.

Brown and Saad [17] describe a family of methods for solving nonlinear problems. They refer to these methods as *nonlinear Krylov subspace projection methods*. Their modifications to Newton's method are intended to enhance robustness and are heavily influenced by ideas presented in [31]. One of their methods is a variant of Damped Inexact Newton, in which they approximate the solution of the correction equation by a few steps of Arnoldi or GMRES and determine the damping parameter α by a "linesearch backtracking technique". So this is just another **AIN** scheme, with a special 1-dimensional subspace acceleration. They also propose a model trust region approach, where they take their update to the approximation from the Krylov subspace \tilde{V}_m generated by m steps of (preconditioned) Arnoldi or GMRES as $p_k = \tilde{V}_m \tilde{y}_k$, where \tilde{y}_k is the point on the dogleg curve for which $\|\tilde{y}_k\|_2 = \tau$, the trust region size: \tilde{y}_k is an approximation for $\min_y \|F(u_k + \tilde{V}_m \tilde{y})\|_2$. This could be considered as a block version of the previous method.

In [4] Axelsson and Chronopoulos propose two nonlinear versions of a (truncated) Generalized Conjugate Gradient type of method. Both methods fit in the **AIN** framework. The first method, NGCG, is a Minimal Residual **AIN** method with $p_k = -r_k$ and V_k orthonormal; in other words the correction equation is not solved. The second method, NNGCG, differs from NGCG in that p_k is now computed as an approximate solution (by some method) of the correction equation (5.6), where the accuracy is such that $\|F(u_k) - F'(u_k)p_k\| \leq \rho_k \|F(u_k)\|$, for some non-increasing sequence (ρ_j) , $0 \leq \rho_j < 1$ (see, e.g., [30]). So the method NNGCG is a Minimal Residual **AIN** method. It can be viewed as generalization of GMRESR [105]. Under certain conditions on the map F they prove global convergence.

In [54], Kaporin and Axelsson propose a class of nonlinear equation solvers

(GNKS) in which the ideas presented in [17] and [4] are combined. There, the direction vectors p_k are obtained as linear combinations of the columns of \tilde{V}_m and V_k . To be more precise, $p_k = [\tilde{V}_m, V_k]y_k$, where y_k solves $\min_y \|F(u_k + [\tilde{V}_m, V_k]y)\|_2$. This problem is then solved by a special Gauss-Newton iteration scheme, which avoids excessive computational work, by taking into account the acute angle between r_k and $J_k p_k$, and the rate of convergence. The method generalizes GCRO [29].

5.8. Numerical experiments. In this section we test several **AIN** schemes and present results of numerical experiments on three different nonlinear problems. For tests and test results with methods for linear and eigen problems we refer to their references. The purpose of this presentation is to show that acceleration may be useful also in the nonlinear case. By useful, we mean that additional computational cost is compensated for by faster convergence.

Different **AIN** schemes distinguish themselves by the way they (approximately) solve the correction equation and the projected problem (cf. Section 5.3.2 and 5.7). Out of the overwhelming variety of choices we have selected a few possible combinations, some of which lead to **AIN** schemes that are equivalent to already proposed methods and some of which lead to new methods. We compare the following (existing) *Minimal Residual AIN* schemes:

- LINESEARCH, the backtracking linesearch technique [17, pp. 458];
- DOGLEG, the model trust region approach as proposed in [17, pp. 462];
- NNGCG, a variant of the method proposed in [4], solving (5.8) by the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm [64];
- GNKS, the method proposed in [54];

and the (new) *Restricted Minimal Residual AIN* schemes:

- RMR A, choosing $W_k = V_k$; and
- RMR B, choosing $W_k = [W_{k-1}, w_k]$, where w_k is the component of $J_k p_k$ orthogonal to W_{k-1} .

For these last two schemes, the minimization problem (5.9) was solved by the Gauss-Newton variant described in [54]. The necessary subspaces for the direction p_k or the projected problem were obtained by 10 steps of GMRES, or (in the third example) also by at most 50 iterations of the generalized CGS variant CGS2 [37].

In all cases the exact Jacobian was used. Furthermore, we used orthonormal matrices V_k and W_k , obtained from a modified Gram-Schmidt process and restricted to the last 10 columns in an attempt to save computational work. The computations were done on a Sun Sparc 20 in double precision and the iterations were stopped when $\|r_k\|_2 \leq 10^{-6}$. A method *failed*, either when the convergence was too slow, i.e., when $|\|r_{k+1}\|_2 - \|r_k\|_2| < 10^{-6}\|r_{k+1}\|_2$, or when to number of nonlinear iterations (per step) exceeded 200.

Since the computational cost of the methods is approximately proportional to the costs of the number of function evaluations and matrix multiplications, the following counters are given in the tables:

- NI, the number of nonlinear iterations;
- FE, the number of function evaluations;
- MV, the number of multiplications by the Jacobian;
- PRE, the number of applications of the preconditioner;
- TOTAL, the sum of FE, MV and PRE.

5.8.1. A 1D Burgers' equation. As a first test problem we consider the following 1D Burgers' Equation [52]

$$(5.12) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \sin(2u) \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} &= \mu \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}, \\ u(x, 0) &= g(x), \quad x \in \Omega, \\ u(x, t) &= \psi(x, t), \quad x \in \partial\Omega, \end{aligned}$$

where $\Omega = [0, 1]$.

We discretized the spatial variable x with finite differences with 64 grid points and for the time derivative we used

$$\theta \dot{u}_{n+1} + (1 - \theta) \dot{u}_n = \frac{u_{n+1} - u_n}{\Delta t},$$

with $\theta = \frac{2}{3}$ and $\Delta t = 10^{-2}$. u_n denotes the solution at time $t_n = t_0 + n\Delta t$. For this test the solution u_n was computed for $n = 1, 2, \dots, 30$ and as an initial guess to u_{n+1} we took u_n . No preconditioning was used.

In table TAB. 5.1 we show the results for problem (5.12) with

$$g(x) = \pi - 2\pi x, \quad \psi(x, t) = g(x), \quad \text{and } \mu = 10^{-2}.$$

Method	NI	FE	MV	TOTAL
LINESEARCH	594	1818	4853	6671
DOGLEG	644	3559	6140	9699
NNGCG	229	4426	11769	16195
GNKS	187	852	7067	7919
RMR A	230	926	4471	5397
RMR B	236	856	4606	5462

TABLE 5.1. Results for Burgers' Equation.

A plot of the solutions u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{30} is given in FIG. 5.1. The table shows the cumulative value of the counters for each method after completing the computation of u_{30} .

If we look at the number of nonlinear iterations (NI), we see that acceleration indeed reduces this number. However, in the case of GNKS this does not result in less work, because the number of matrix multiplications (MV) increases too much. Here both the Galerkin approaches RMR A and RMR B are less expensive than all the other methods. RMR A being the winner.

FIGURE 5.1. Solution of Burgers' Equation.

5.8.2. The Bratu problem. As a second test problem we consider the Bratu problem [43, 17]. We seek a solution (u, λ) of the nonlinear boundary value problem:

$$(5.13) \quad -\Delta u - \lambda e^u = 0 \text{ in } \Omega, \quad u = 0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega.$$

For Ω we took the unit square and we discretized with finite differences on a 31×31 regular grid. It is known, cf. [43], that there exist a critical value λ^* such that for $0 < \lambda < \lambda^*$, problem (5.13) has two solutions and for $\lambda > \lambda^*$ problem (5.13) has no solutions. In order to locate this critical value we use the arc length continuation method as described in [43, section 2.3 and 2.4]. Problem (5.13) is replaced by a problem of the form

$$\begin{cases} F(u_s, \lambda(s)) = 0, \\ \ell(u_s, \lambda(s), s) = 0, \end{cases}$$

where ℓ , a scalar valued function, is chosen such that s is some arc length on the solution branch and u_s is the solution of (5.13) for $\lambda = \lambda(s)$. We preconditioned GMRES by ILU(0) [62] of the discretized Laplace operator Δ .

The first table TAB. 5.2 shows the results after a full continuation run: starting from the smallest solution (u, λ) with $\lambda = 1$ the solution branch is followed along the (discretized) arc with $s_n = s_0 + n\Delta s$ for step-size $\Delta s = 1$ and $n = 1, 2, \dots, 80$. Again we see that acceleration may be useful, in spite of the fact that there is little room for it, because on the average approximately only 4.5 Newton iterations were necessary to compute the solution per continuation step. In this example RMR B performs better than RMR A.

Table TAB. 5.3 shows the results for the case where we solve (5.13) for fixed $\lambda = 6.8$ (near the critical value). In this case Galerkin acceleration is even more useful and the differences are more pronounced.

The sup norm of the solution for the different values of λ are plotted in FIG. 5.2. The two solutions at $\lambda \approx 4$ along the diagonal of the unit square are shown in FIG. 5.3.

5.8.3. The driven cavity problem. In this Section we present test results for the classical *driven cavity* problem from incompressible fluid flow. We follow closely the presentations in [43, 17]. In stream function-vorticity formulation

Method	NI	FE	MV	PRE	TOTAL
LINESEARCH	391	1013	3732	3421	8166
DOGLEG	381	2664	3010	3010	8684
NNGCG	361	1297	4243	3091	8631
GNKS	358	1056	6896	2780	10732
RMR A	389	539	4005	3399	7943
RMR B	361	414	3806	3091	7311

TABLE 5.2. Results for the Bratu Problem, solved by the arc length continuation method.

Method	NI	FE	MV	PRE	TOTAL
LINESEARCH	29	85	336	308	729
DOGLEG	27	151	494	260	905
NNGCG	9	49	196	88	333
GNKS	38	119	1806	370	2295
RMR A	6	13	77	55	145
RMR B	6	12	79	55	146

TABLE 5.3. Single solve of the Bratu Problem, $u_0 = 0$, $\lambda = 6.8$.

FIGURE 5.2. Sup norms of the solution u along the arc.

FIGURE 5.3. Solutions u at $\lambda \approx 4$ along the diagonal of the domain.

the equations are

$$\begin{aligned} \nu \Delta \omega + (\psi_{x_2} \omega_{x_1} - \psi_{x_1} \omega_{x_2}) &= 0 \text{ in } \Omega, \\ -\Delta \psi &= \omega \text{ in } \Omega, \\ \psi &= 0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega, \\ \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial n}(x_1, x_2)|_{\partial\Omega} &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x_2 = 1, \\ 0 & \text{if } 0 \leq x_2 < 1, \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

where Ω is the unit square and the viscosity ν is the reciprocal of the Reynolds number Re . In terms of ψ alone this can be written as

$$\nu \Delta^2 \psi + (\psi_{x_2} (\Delta \psi)_{x_1} - \psi_{x_1} (\Delta \psi)_{x_2}) = 0 \text{ in } \Omega,$$

subject to the same boundary conditions. This equation was discretized with finite differences on a 25×25 grid, see FIG. 5.4. The grid lines are distributed as the roots of the Chebychev polynomial of degree 25. As preconditioner we used the Modified ILU(2) [46] decomposition of the biharmonic operator Δ^2 . Starting from the solution for $Re = 0$, we computed several solutions, using the the arc length continuation method (cf. the previous example, and [43]) with step sizes $\Delta s = 100$ for $0 \leq Re \leq 1400$, $\Delta s = 200$ for $1400 < Re \leq 2600$, and $\Delta s = 400$ for $Re = 3000$.

TAB. 5.4 shows the results of this test when using 10 steps of GMRES and CGS2 [37] for the correction equation. In the case of CGS2 we approximately solved the correction equation to a relative residual norm precision of 2^{-k} , where k is the current Newton step [30], with a maximum of 50 steps. Clearly, the methods using (the basis produced by) 10 steps of GMRES perform very poorly for this example. Only GNKS is able to complete the full continuation run, but requires a large number of Newton steps. If we look at the results for the AIN schemes for which CGS2 is used, we see that, except for the LINESEARCH method, these methods perform much better. The Restricted Minimal Residual methods are again the most efficient ones.

This test also reveals a possible practical drawback of methods like DOGLEG and GNKS. These methods exploit an affine subspace to find a suitable update for the approximation. This may fail, when the problem is hard or when the preconditioner is not good enough. In that case the dimension of the affine subspace must be large, which may be, because of storage requirements and computational overhead, not feasible. For the schemes that use approximate solutions of the correction equation, delivered by some arbitrary, iterative method, e.g., CGS2, one can easily adapt the precision, which leaves more freedom.

GMRES					
Method	NI	FE	MV	PRE	TOTAL
LINESEARCH	fails at $Re = 400$ after a TOTAL of 545.				
DOGLEG	fails at $Re = 100$ after a TOTAL of 113.				
NNGCG	fails at $Re = 2200$ after a TOTAL of 19875				
GNKS	641	2315	30206	6210	38731
RMR A	fails at $Re = 2000$ after a TOTAL of 13078				
RMR B	fails at $Re = 800$ after a TOTAL of 7728				
CGS2					
Method	NI	FE	MV	PRE	TOTAL
LINESEARCH	fails at $Re = 1300$ after a TOTAL of 4342.				
NNGCG	141	555	7003	6119	13677
RMR A	137	297	6266	5969	12532
RMR B	137	167	6277	5937	12381

TABLE 5.4. Results for the Driven Cavity problem, solved by the arc length continuation method for $Re = 100, \dots, 3000$.

Plots of the stream lines for the values

$$\psi = -0.12, -0.1, -0.08, -0.06, -0.04, -0.02, \\ 0.0, 0.0025, 0.001, 0.0005, 0.0001, 0.00005$$

(cf. [43]) are given in FIG. 5.5–5.9. The plots show virtually the same solutions as in [43].

5.9. Conclusions. We have shown how the classical Newton iteration scheme for nonlinear problems can be accelerated in a similar way as standard Richardson-type iteration schemes for linear equations. This leads to the **AIN** framework in which many well-known iterative methods for linear, eigen, and general nonlinear problems fit. From this framework an overwhelming number of possible iterations schemes can be formulated. We have selected a few and shown by numerical experiments that especially the Restricted Minimal Residual methods can be very useful for further reducing computational costs.

FIGURE 5.4. Grid for the Driven Cavity problem, (25×25) .

FIGURE 5.5. Stream lines of the Driven Cavity problem, $Re = 100$.

FIGURE 5.6. Stream lines of the Driven Cavity problem, $Re = 400$.

FIGURE 5.7. Stream lines of the Driven Cavity problem, $Re = 1600$.

FIGURE 5.8. Stream lines of the Driven Cavity problem, $Re = 2000$.

FIGURE 5.9. Stream lines of the Driven Cavity problem, $Re = 3000$.

CHAPTER 6

JACOBI-DAVIDSON STYLE QR AND QZ ALGORITHMS FOR THE PARTIAL REDUCTION OF MATRIX PENCILS

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Abstract. The Jacobi-Davidson subspace iteration method offers possibilities for solving a variety of eigenproblems. In practice one has to apply restarts because of memory limitations, in order to restrict computational overhead, and also if one wants to compute several eigenvalues. In general, restarting has negative effects on the convergence of subspace methods. We will show how effective restarts can be incorporated in the Jacobi-Davidson methods, very similar to the implicit restart procedure for the Arnoldi process. We will present two algorithms, JDQR for the standard eigenproblem, and JDQZ for the generalized eigenproblem, that are based on the iterative construction of the (generalized) partial Schur form with the Jacobi-Davidson approach. The algorithms are suitable for the efficient computation of several (even multiple) eigenvalues, and the corresponding eigenvectors, near a user-specified target value in the complex plane.

Key words. Linear eigenproblems; Generalized eigenproblems; Schur form; Generalized Schur form; QR-algorithm; QZ-algorithm; Jacobi-Davidson; Iterative methods

AMS subject classification. 65F15, 65N25

6.1. Introduction. In this paper we propose two iterative methods, one for computing solutions of the standard eigenproblem

$$(6.1) \quad (\mathbf{A} - \lambda \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0},$$

and the other for computing solutions for the generalized eigenproblem¹

$$(6.2) \quad (\beta \mathbf{A} - \alpha \mathbf{B}) \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0},$$

where \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are large and sparse ($n \times n$)-matrices, which may be complex and/or non-normal. Of course, with $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{I}$ the generalized eigenproblem reduces to a standard eigenproblem, and we could have restricted ourselves to the generalized eigenproblem case. However, simplifications are possible when $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{I}$, which help reduce the memory requirements and the computational complexity. For this reason, and also since the standard problem allows for a less complicated description, we have chosen to consider both situations in detail.

Our algorithms are based on the Jacobi-Davidson method described in [90], and adapted for generalized eigenproblems (and other polynomial eigenproblems) in [84]. We have chosen the Jacobi-Davidson approach for the computation of a partial Schur form for the standard eigenproblem, and for a partial generalized Schur form for the generalized eigenproblem. The partial Schur forms have been chosen mainly for numerical stability, since they involve orthogonal bases. These bases are also useful for deflation, another ingredient of our algorithms.

In the Jacobi-Davidson approach a search subspace is generated onto which the given eigenproblem is projected. The much smaller projected eigenproblem is solved and this leads to approximations for the wanted eigenvectors and eigenvalues of the given larger problem. This is the ‘Davidson’ part of the method. Then, a correction equation for a selected eigenpair is considered. The solution of the correction equation defines an orthogonal correction for the current eigenvector approximation (in fact if the exact value for the eigenvalue would have been known, then the correction equation defines the exact eigenvector); this is the ‘Jacobi’ part of the algorithm. The correction is then used for the expansion of the search subspace and the process is repeated.

The correction equation may be solved by any method of choice, and for large problems it is often more efficient to solve this equation only approximately by some iterative method. The speed of convergence of this iterative method may be improved by preconditioning, and this is where in the Jacobi-Davidson method preconditioning takes place. It should be noted that the preconditioning does not affect the given eigenproblem. By including shifts in the Jacobi-Davidson method, and by a proper selection of the approximate eigenpair for the correction equation, the process can be guided to find eigenpairs close to a given

¹The family $\mathbf{A} - \lambda \mathbf{B}$ is called a *matrix pencil* and the generalized eigenvalues $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle$, solutions of (6.2), are also called eigenvalues of the matrix pencil (cf. e.g., [96]).

target value. More details will be given in Section 6.2.1 and Section 6.3.1, and for a complete description of the Jacobi-Davidson method we refer to [90, 84].

A problem in the Jacobi-Davidson method is that convergence towards a specific eigenvalue is favored, and for efficient computation of several eigenvalues, one has to apply the usual restart with a different target. Because of memory limitations one may also be forced to restart, even before an eigenpair is found. Restarts have the disadvantage that a subspace which may contain very useful information, is replaced by one single vector, so that much valuable information is lost. This problem has been solved elegantly for the Arnoldi method [94], and our approach (cf. Section 6.2.2 and Section 6.3.2) is related to this (see also [90, Section 5.3]). For the Jacobi-Davidson method this problem is solved by our new algorithms. In these algorithms the given large system is projected on a suitably filtered subspace, and this leads to a similar, but much smaller, problem. The projected problem is reduced to Schur form by either the QR [38] or the QZ [63] method. Also the construction of the subspace and the projected system may be viewed as iterative inexact forms of QR and QZ. For this reason we have named our new methods JDQR and JDQZ, respectively. JDQR generates a partial Schur form for the standard eigenproblem, a partial “QR-decomposition”; JDQZ produces a partial generalized Schur form for the generalized eigenproblem, a partial “QZ-decomposition”.

Our Section 6.2 focuses on the standard eigenproblem and is organized as follows. The Jacobi-Davidson method is briefly discussed in Section 6.2.1. In Section 6.2.2, the original algorithm of [90] is slightly adapted, by incorporating an ordered Schur decomposition of the projected eigenproblem. An ordered Schur form can be used to select the approximate eigenpair and to select a properly limited sized subspace for continuing the process. This culminates in the construction of the JDQR method, in Section 6.2.3: by combining the Schur decomposition of the projected problem with the iteratively obtained partial Schur decomposition of the given large problem, a simple and efficient algorithm is obtained. The rate of convergence of Jacobi-Davidson depends on the accuracy by which the correction equation is solved. If it is solved iteratively, then it may be attractive to include preconditioning. This requires extra care because of the projection operations included in the correction equation; attention to this will be paid in Section 6.2.4. In our approach, a preconditioner constructed for one Ritz pair appears to be effective also for nearby Ritz pairs (see Section 6.2.7). Some observations on the selection of approximate eigenpairs are made in Section 6.2.5. In Section 6.2.6, it is explained that the search subspace for the obtained partial Schur decomposition provides a suitable limited subspace for continuing the iterative process.

The generalized eigenproblem is central in Section 6.3, where JDQR is generalized to JDQZ. The JDQZ approach basically allows for two different choices for constructing the projected problem (cf. Sections 6.3.1 and 6.3.5), one of which is very useful for computing interior eigenvalues. For such eigenvalues, it appears to be more effective to select more carefully the approximate eigenpairs than to strive for optimal expansion of the search subspace (cf. Section 6.3.5). The derivation of JDQZ is given in Section 6.3.3, while in Section 6.3.4 it is explained how preconditioning for the correction equation can be incorporated.

In Section 6.4, we illustrate the convergence behavior of JDQR and JDQZ with numerical experiments for a number of eigenproblems. Aspects that are investigated concern, amongst others, the accuracy of the solution of the correction equation (Section 6.4.1), the effect of preconditioning (Section 6.4.2), multiple eigenvalues (Section 6.4.3 and Section 6.4.7), interior eigenvalues (Section 6.4.4 and Section 6.4.8), and different approaches for the construction of the projected problem (Section 6.4.4 and Section 6.4.8), and implicit versus explicit deflation (Section 6.4.6).

Section 6.5 contains our conclusions.

REMARK 6.1. All computations can be done in complex arithmetic if necessary. An alternative for real matrices would be to use quasi Schur forms with 2×2 blocks on the diagonal, which can be done in real arithmetic. It is possible to derive a variant of Jacobi-Davidson based on this blocked form. However, this variant will necessarily also involve a blocked version of the correction equation, which will double the computational work per iteration step. The construction of a suitable block-preconditioner may be a problem as well. Hence, it is not clear whether implementations with quasi Schur forms may be competitive, and we will not discuss this possibility further in this paper.

REMARK 6.2. With bold face letters we indicate that variables are associated with the large n -dimensional space, and for low dimensional spaces we use italic letters.

We use a tilde to indicate that a quantity approximates the corresponding quantity without tilde: $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ approximates \mathbf{q} , etc.. The algorithms are given in MATLAB-style. We use the MATLAB conventions when we refer to entries in matrices and vectors. In particular, where in the algorithms new values overwrite old ones, the tildes are deleted.

6.2. The standard eigenproblem. We will focus on the standard eigenproblem (6.1) in this section.

6.2.1. Jacobi-Davidson. For the standard eigenproblem, Jacobi-Davidson selects the approximate eigenvector from a *search subspace* $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$ that is expanded in each step. Each iteration consists of two parts: the ‘Davidson’ part, where the *projected eigenproblem*

$$(6.3) \quad (\mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V} - \tilde{\lambda} \mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{V}) u = 0,$$

is solved and a solution $(u, \tilde{\lambda})$ is selected. The *Ritz value* $\tilde{\lambda}$ and the *Ritz vector* $\tilde{\mathbf{q}} \equiv \mathbf{V}u$ form an approximate eigenvalue and eigenvector, respectively, with *residual* $\mathbf{r} \equiv (\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda} \mathbf{I}) \tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ (we will assume that $\|\tilde{\mathbf{q}}\|_2 = 1$). Observe that $\mathbf{r} \perp \tilde{\mathbf{q}}$. In the second part, the ‘Jacobi’ part, the search subspace is expanded by a vector $\mathbf{v} \perp \tilde{\mathbf{q}}$, that solves (approximately) the *correction equation*

$$(6.4) \quad \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^* \mathbf{v} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^*)(\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda} \mathbf{I})(\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^*) \mathbf{v} = -\mathbf{r}.$$

The expanded search subspace is $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{v}\}$. In exact arithmetic, \mathbf{V} is an orthogonal matrix, $\mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{I}$. We have used modified Gram-Schmidt in our computations for the construction of an orthogonal basis of the search subspace.

As observed in the introduction, if $\tilde{\lambda}$ is replaced in the correction equation (6.4) by an eigenvalue λ , then the associated eigenvector is contained in the space spanned by \mathbf{V} and the exact solution of the correction equation. Usually we have no better estimate for λ than the Ritz value $\tilde{\lambda}$ and then the solution of the correction equation is the best we can do for expansion. If this correction equation (6.4) is solved exactly, then the speed of convergence for the selected Ritz values is asymptotically quadratical (cf. [90, 84]).

In our applications, the projected problem (6.3) will be of relatively small dimension, i.e., $\dim(\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}) \ll n$, and can be solved efficiently by standard algorithms for dense problems.

6.2.2. Practical selection and implicit restart. If we reduce the projected eigenproblem (6.3) to Schur form by the QR algorithm [38], then we can exploit the Schur form for the selection of a Ritz pair $(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \tilde{\lambda})$, and for restriction of the dimension of the subspace $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$, in the following way.

Suppose we are interested in the eigenpair(s) with eigenvalue close to some specified *target* value τ , and suppose that the Schur form of the *interaction matrix* $M \equiv \mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V}$, given by

$$M U = U S, \quad U^* U = I, \quad \text{and} \quad S \text{ upper triangular,}$$

is ordered such that

$$(6.5) \quad |S(1, 1) - \tau| \leq |S(2, 2) - \tau| \leq \cdots \leq |S(j, j) - \tau|,$$

where j is the dimension of $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$. Then

$$(6.6) \quad (\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \tilde{\lambda}) \equiv (\mathbf{V}U(:, 1), S(1, 1))$$

is the Ritz approximation corresponding to the projected system (6.3) with Ritz value closest to the target τ . Furthermore, $\mathbf{V}U(:, 1:i)$, with $i < j$, spans the subspace that has the best information for the i eigenvalues closest to τ . Therefore, if we want to reduce the dimension of the search subspace from j to j_{\min} , $j_{\min} < j$, then we discard the columns $\mathbf{v}_{j_{\min}+1}$ through \mathbf{v}_j , and continue the JD algorithm with

$$(6.7) \quad \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V}U(:, 1:j_{\min}).$$

It is convenient that $\mathbf{V}U(:, 1:j_{\min})$ is already orthogonal.

We refer to this reduction strategy as *implicit restart*.

REMARK 6.3. Our restart strategy follows similar ideas as in the Implicitly Restarted Arnoldi (IRA) [94]. However, in [94] implicit shifts are used to delete the *unwanted* part, instead of explicitly selecting the *wanted* portion of the Krylov subspace as we do. The situation for IRA is more complicated because the reduced search subspace has to be a Krylov subspace. For further details, see [94, 58].

A reordering algorithm for the Schur form can be found in, for instance, [95, 44, 76]; a Fortran implementation is available from LAPACK [1]. A simple MATLAB implementation for reordering with respect to a target value τ , is given in Appendix .2. For completeness, a theoretical justification is given there as well.

In ALG. 6.1, an implementation of the JD algorithm for the standard eigenproblem is given in MATLAB-style. This implementation includes the implicit restart option based on ordered Schur forms. It also includes reordering, and is adjusted for one eigenvalue closest to a target τ . This “basic” algorithm will be extended for the computation of a number of eigenvalues in the neighborhood of τ (in Section 6.2.3), and preconditioning will be included (Section 6.2.4).

REMARK 6.4. In the implementations of our algorithms, we consider an approximate eigenpair $(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \tilde{\lambda})$ converged if the residual \mathbf{r} is sufficiently small ($\|\mathbf{r}\| \leq \epsilon$); then $(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \tilde{\lambda})$ is a “detected” eigenpair. Weighted residuals (e.g., $\|\mathbf{r}\| \leq \epsilon\|\mathbf{A}\|$) or more sophisticated stopping criteria can be employed as well (cf. [21]).

In TAB. 6.1 we have listed the main computation-intensive ingredients per iteration of JD.

```

function [q, λ] = JD (A, τ, v0, ε, jmax, jmin)
V = []; VA = []; M = [];
j = 0; found = 0;
while ~ found,
    if j == 0,
        v = v0;
    else
        — the correction equation —
        Solve v (approximately) from:
            q*v = 0 and
            (I - q*q*)(A - λI)(I - q*q*) v = -r.
    end
    — the projected problem —
    v = mgs (V, v); v = v/||v||2; vA = Av;
    M = [M, V*vA; v*VA, v*vA];
    V = [V, v]; VA = [VA, vA];
    [U, S] = schur (M); [U, S] = qrsort (τ, U, S);
    j = j + 1;
    — Ritz approximation —
    λ = S(1,1); q = VU(:,1);
    r = (A - λI) q;
    found = (||r||2 < ε),
    — “found and implicit restart” —
    if found,
        break;
    elseif j == jmax,
        — implicit restart —
        j = jmin; J = [1:j];
        V = VU(:,J); VA = VA U(:,J);
        S = S(J,J); M = S; U = I;
    end
end

```

JD returns an eigenpair (\mathbf{q}, λ) of the matrix \mathbf{A} with λ near the target τ . \mathbf{v}_0 is an initial guess, and ϵ is the stopping tolerance. j_{\max} and j_{\min} specify the dimension of the subspace \mathbf{V} before and after implicit restart, respectively. `schur` is a MATLAB function that computes a Schur decomposition $MU = US$. The functions `mgs` (modified Gram-Schmidt) and `qrsort` (Sort Schur form) are given in Appendix .2.

ALGORITHM 6.1. JD with implicit restart.

Part	DOTS	AXPYS	MVS
The correction equation	variable		
The projected problem	$3j$	$j - 1$	1^a
Ritz approximation	1	j	1^b
Restart	0	$2j_{\min}$	0

^aIf Krylov subspace methods are used to solve the correction equation, then the product $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{v}$ is often already available, as a side-product. No MV is needed in this part then.

^bInstead of computing the residual \mathbf{r} as $(\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda}\mathbf{I})\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$, \mathbf{r} may also be computed as $\mathbf{V}_A U(:, 1) - \tilde{\lambda}\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$, where $\mathbf{V}_A \equiv \mathbf{A}\mathbf{V}$ (cf. ALG. 6.1); depending on the number of nonzeros in \mathbf{A} and the value of j , this may be more efficient.

TABLE 6.1. The computational costs of implicitly restarted JD per iteration. j is the dimension of $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$.

6.2.3. JDQR. Now we focus on the efficient computation of several eigenpairs. The idea is to use the JD algorithm for the computation of a *partial Schur form*, which is defined as follows (cf. [80]).

DEFINITION 6.1. A *partial Schur form* of dimension k for a matrix \mathbf{A} is the following decomposition:

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{Q}_k = \mathbf{Q}_k R_k$$

where \mathbf{Q}_k is an orthogonal $(n \times k)$ -matrix, and R_k is an upper triangular $(k \times k)$ -matrix. A column \mathbf{q}_i of the matrix \mathbf{Q}_k is a *Schur vector*, and the pair $(\mathbf{q}_i, \lambda_i)$, with $\lambda_i = R_k(i, i)$, is a *Schur pair*.

The diagonal entries of the matrix R_k represent eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} , and if (x, λ) is an eigenpair of R_k then $(\mathbf{Q}_k x, \lambda)$ is an eigenpair of \mathbf{A} .

Steps I, II, and III below represent the JDQR algorithm for computing a partial Schur form. A MATLAB implementation of JDQR is not given until Section 6.2.4, where preconditioning for the correction equations is discussed.

I. For the first Schur pair, we apply the JD algorithm. This leads to a search subspace \mathbf{V} . For the interaction matrix $M \equiv \mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V}$ we compute an ordered Schur form $MU = US$. The first Schur pair of the projected problem is taken as the approximation to a Schur pair of the original large eigenproblem. This is used for the correction equation (6.4), of which the (approximate) solution \mathbf{v}

gives the expansion of the subspace (\mathbf{V} is expanded with the orthogonal complement \mathbf{v}' of \mathbf{v} to \mathbf{V}). With the expanded subspace $\mathbf{V} = [\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{v}']$ we construct again the Schur form for the corresponding interaction matrix, and this process is repeated until a Schur pair has been detected. Upon convergence, when $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$ is of dimension j , say, the subspace reduced by the detected Schur vector, $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V}U(:, 2:j)$, can be used as the starting subspace for a new Schur pair.

II. Now suppose that $k-1$ Schur pairs have been detected, i.e., we already have the partial Schur form $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{Q}_{k-1} = \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}R_{k-1}$. We want to expand \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} , with a suitable \mathbf{q} , so that

$$(6.8) \quad \mathbf{A} [\mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \quad \mathbf{q}] = [\mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \quad \mathbf{q}] \begin{bmatrix} R_{k-1} & s \\ 0 & \lambda \end{bmatrix}.$$

The new Schur pair (\mathbf{q}, λ) should satisfy

$$\mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^* \mathbf{q} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (\mathbf{A} - \lambda \mathbf{I})\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} s = \mathbf{0},$$

or, since $s = \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^* (\mathbf{A} - \lambda \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{q}$,

$$\mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^* \mathbf{q} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*) (\mathbf{A} - \lambda \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0}.$$

Hence, (\mathbf{q}, λ) satisfies

$$(6.9) \quad \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^* \mathbf{q} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*) (\mathbf{A} - \lambda \mathbf{I}) (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*) \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0},$$

and the Schur pair (\mathbf{q}, λ) is therefore also an eigenpair of the *deflated matrix*

$$(6.10) \quad (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*) \mathbf{A} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*).$$

We solve this eigenproblem, by the procedure sketched in I., for the deflated matrix (6.10). More precisely, the JD algorithm for the deflated matrix (6.10) constructs a subspace $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$ for finding approximate eigenpairs, and \mathbf{V} is an orthogonal matrix such that $\mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} = \mathbf{0}$. For the *deflated interaction matrix* M we have

$$(6.11) \quad M \equiv \mathbf{V}^* (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*) \mathbf{A} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*) \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V}.$$

The ordered Schur form $MU = US$ (see (6.5)) gives an approximation $(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \tilde{\lambda}) \equiv (\mathbf{V}U(:, 1), S(1, 1))$ for a wanted eigenpair of the deflated matrix (6.10). Then, according to the Jacobi-Davidson approach, the search subspace $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$ is

expanded by the orthogonal complement of \mathbf{v} to \mathbf{V} , where \mathbf{v} is the (approximate) solution of the *deflated correction equation*

$$(6.12) \quad \begin{cases} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^* \mathbf{v} = 0, & \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^* \mathbf{v} = 0 \quad \text{and} \\ (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^*)(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*)(\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda} \mathbf{I})(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*)(\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^*) \mathbf{v} = -\mathbf{r}, \end{cases}$$

where $\mathbf{r} \equiv (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*)(\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda} \mathbf{I})(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*) \tilde{\mathbf{q}}$.

Note that the projections in (6.12) can be subdivided into two parts; the part $(\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^*)$ associated with Jacobi-Davidson, and the deflation part $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*)$. Observe also that $\mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^* \mathbf{r} = 0$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}^* \mathbf{r} = 0$.

III. When the Schur pair $(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \tilde{\lambda})$ is sufficiently close to (\mathbf{q}, λ) , then we may continue for still another Schur pair. In that case, the matrix \mathbf{V} of dimension $n \times j$, say, is reduced to $\mathbf{V}U(:, 2:j)$, in order to obtain a subspace orthogonal to $\text{span}\{\mathbf{Q}_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{q}}\}$, and we continue the process.

REMARK 6.5. Two deflation techniques can be found in literature for methods like Arnoldi. They are referred to as explicit and implicit deflation (cf., e.g., [80, Ch. VI, Section 2.3]). In explicit deflation, the computation is continued with a deflated matrix after detection of Schur vectors. For efficiency reasons, $\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{Q} \Lambda \mathbf{Q}^*$ is used (Schur-Wielandt deflation), rather than the more stable representation $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{Q}^*) \mathbf{A} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{Q}^*)$. In implicit deflation, each new vector for the search subspace is generated with \mathbf{A} itself and is then made orthogonal to the detected Schur vectors, before adding it to the search subspace. Our approach, is a mixture of both techniques. In the correction equation we use the deflated matrix. Since the solutions of the deflated correction equations are orthogonal to the detected Schur vectors, there is no need to use the deflated matrix for obtaining the deflated interaction matrix M ; we compute M as $M = \mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V}$.

When we use Krylov subspace methods for the solution of the correction equation, then the work with either of the two representations of the deflated matrix is the same (cf. REMARK 6.9).

Exclusively implicit deflation is possible as well: solve the correction equation approximately with the non-deflated \mathbf{A} and put the resulting solution orthogonal to the detected Schur vectors. In this approach we avoid expensive matrix vector multiplications, but explicit deflation appears to improve the condition number of the linear system, and this leads to a faster converging process for the correction equation (6.4). The decrease of the number of iteration steps, for the correction equation, appears often to compensate for the more expensive multiplications (for a numerical illustration of this, see Section 6.4.6).

Moreover, the deflated correction equations (6.12) appear to lead to more stable results. This can be understood as follows. Without deflation the resulting solution of the correction equation may have a significant component in the space spanned by the detected Schur vectors. By subtracting this component (as in implicit deflation) cancellation may occur. If we work with an explicitly deflated matrix, such cancellation is avoided.

REMARK 6.6. As in implicitly deflated Arnoldi methods, the accuracy of an approximate Schur pair in our method does not only depend on the norm of the residual and the condition number of the pair, but also on the approximation errors in the previously detected Schur pairs (cf. e.g., [80, Ch. IV, Section 2.5] and [58, Section 6.4.1]): in the derivation of the algorithms it is assumed that $\mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{Q} = 0$ implies $\mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{Q} = 0$, which is true for exact Schur vectors. In practice, $\text{span}\{\mathbf{A} \mathbf{Q}\}$ will not be contained in $\text{span}\{\mathbf{Q}\}$.

6.2.4. Preconditioning. In this section we will discuss preconditioning for the correction equation. Preconditioning is not straight forward, because of the projections involved. We will derive explicit expressions for left and right preconditioned correction equations.

In each iteration step we need to solve a deflated correction equation (6.12), for a given $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ and $\tilde{\lambda}$. For the approximate solution of this equation we may use a Krylov subspace method, e.g., GMRES [82], or BiCGstab(ℓ) [85]. The rate of convergence and the efficiency of Krylov subspace methods is often improved by preconditioning. The identification of an effective preconditioner may be a problem. For instance, for interior eigenvalues the construction of an effective incomplete LU-factorization [62, 46] for $\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda} \mathbf{I}$ may require much fill-in², which makes the construction expensive. As we will argue in Section 6.2.7, it may be a good strategy to compute a preconditioner \mathbf{K} for $\mathbf{A} - \tau \mathbf{I}$ for a fixed value of τ only, and to use

$$(6.13) \quad \tilde{\mathbf{K}} \equiv (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^*) (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*) \mathbf{K} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*) (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^*)$$

as the preconditioner for various $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ and $\tilde{\lambda}$. Note that the projections on \mathbf{K} are necessary to let $\tilde{\mathbf{K}}$ operate on the proper subspace (cf. [84]).

We will now derive the expressions for the preconditioned correction equation. For convenience, we introduce the following notations:

²These incomplete factorizations have not been designed for linear systems related to eigenproblems. The solutions for which these factorizations are most effective are usually rather smooth, which means that components of slowly varying eigenvectors are favored by the preconditioning.

NOTATION 6.1.

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k &\equiv [\mathbf{Q}_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{q}}], && \text{the matrix } \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \text{ expanded by the approximate} \\
&&& \text{Schur vector } \tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \\
\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k &\equiv \mathbf{K}^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k, && \text{the matrix of the preconditioned "Schur" vec-} \\
&&& \text{tors,} \\
\tilde{H}_k &\equiv \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^* \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k, && \text{the projected preconditioner } \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^* \mathbf{K}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k.
\end{aligned}$$

A typical use of the preconditioner in a Krylov subspace method, for our purposes looks like:

$$\begin{aligned}
(6.14) \quad & \text{solve } \mathbf{t}, \text{ with } \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^* \mathbf{t} = 0, \text{ from} \\
& (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{K} (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{t} = \mathbf{s} \\
& \text{for } \mathbf{s}, \text{ with } \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^* \mathbf{s} = 0,
\end{aligned}$$

where \mathbf{K} is a preconditioner for $\mathbf{A} - \tau \mathbf{I}$.

The following identities, formulated in a lemma, are useful for obtaining an explicit expression for the solution of (6.14).

LEMMA 6.1. *If \tilde{H}_k is nonsingular, then*

$$(6.15) \quad (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) = (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*),$$

$$(6.16) \quad (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) = (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*),$$

$$(6.17) \quad (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{K}^{-1} (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) = (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{K}^{-1}.$$

Proof. These identities follow straight forward from expanding the products. For example:

$$\begin{aligned}
(\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) &= (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) - (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^* \\
&= (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) - (\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^* - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \\
&= (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*).
\end{aligned}$$

□

The following lemma gives us an explicit expression for the solution \mathbf{t} of (6.14), in terms of easily computable matrix vector products with \tilde{H}_k^{-1} and \mathbf{K}^{-1} . The lemma generalizes PROP. 7.5 in [84]. Note that \tilde{H}_k is of small dimension, so it is easily inverted. \mathbf{K} has never to be explicitly inverted, instead $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{K}^{-1} \mathbf{s}$ can be computed by solving \mathbf{v} from $\mathbf{K} \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{s}$.

LEMMA 6.2. If \tilde{H}_k is nonsingular, then the solution \mathbf{t} of equation (6.14) is given by

$$(6.18) \quad \mathbf{t} = (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{K}^{-1} \mathbf{s},$$

Proof. The expression (6.18) follows from multiplying (6.14) by $(\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{K}^{-1}$, and using identities of LEMMA 6.1. \square

REMARK 6.7. If one stores the matrix $\mathbf{Y}_{k-1} \equiv \mathbf{K}^{-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}$ of preconditioned Schur vectors, one only has to compute the last column $\mathbf{K}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ of the matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k = [\mathbf{Y}_{k-1}, \mathbf{K}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}]$, at each iteration step. Furthermore, when storing the projected preconditioner $H_{k-1} \equiv \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^* \mathbf{K}^{-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}$, only the last column and last row of

$$\tilde{H}_k = \begin{bmatrix} H_{k-1} & \mathbf{Q}_k^* \mathbf{K}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^* \mathbf{Y}_k & \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^* \mathbf{K}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \end{bmatrix}$$

have to be computed in an iteration step.

REMARK 6.8. If the preconditioner \mathbf{K} is indefinite, then the matrix \tilde{H}_k may become singular, for an “unlucky” choice of approximate Ritz pair $(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \tilde{\lambda})$. This causes a breakdown, but it never happened in our experiments. The breakdown may be cured by selecting a different nearby approximating Ritz pair $(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}', \tilde{\lambda}')$ temporarily, for the current Jacobi-Davidson iteration.

Left preconditioning. From LEMMA 6.2, it follows that the left preconditioned correction equation is equivalent with

$$(6.19) \quad \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^* \mathbf{v} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{K}^{-1} (\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda} \mathbf{I}) (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{v} = -\hat{\mathbf{r}},$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{r}} \equiv (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{K}^{-1} \mathbf{r}$ (cf. [84, Th. 7.4]).

Note that the projection has to be applied explicitly to the residual. For the unpreconditioned case there was no need for explicit projection, since there, the fact that the residual is associated with a deflated matrix and with a Ritz pair, implied orthogonality to $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k$.

Observe that, for $\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{I}$, this equation (6.19) is equivalent to the one in (6.12).

Right preconditioning. Also right preconditioning for the correction equation may be used.

With $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}_k \equiv (\mathbf{K}^*)^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k$, this leads to

$$(6.20) \quad \hat{\mathbf{Y}}_k^* \hat{\mathbf{v}} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{Y}}_k^*) (\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda} \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{K}^{-1} (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{Y}}_k^*) \hat{\mathbf{v}} = -\hat{\mathbf{r}},$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{r}} \equiv (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{Y}}_k^*) \mathbf{r}$. The vector \mathbf{v} can be obtained from $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$ by $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{K}^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{v}}$.

REMARK 6.9. If one uses Krylov subspace methods for solving the second equation in (6.19), then one encounters matrix vectors products of the form

$$(6.21) \quad (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{K}^{-1} (\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda} \mathbf{I}) (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{t},$$

with \mathbf{t} of the form $\mathbf{t} = (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{s}$. Then, obviously, $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^* \mathbf{t} = 0$, and for the approximate solution \mathbf{v} it holds that $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^* \mathbf{v} = 0$, if that is the case for the initial guess. Moreover, the projection $(\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*)$ in front of \mathbf{t} in (6.21) is redundant then, and (6.21) reduces to

$$(6.22) \quad (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{K}^{-1} (\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda} \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{t},$$

A similar remark applies for (6.20).

A pseudo-code for the preconditioned Jacobi-Davidson QR algorithm is given in ALG. 6.2.

In TAB. 6.2 we have listed the main computational ingredients per iteration of JDQR.

Part	DOTS	AXPYS	MVS	K
The correction equation	variable			
The projected problem	$3j$	$j - 1$	1^a	0
Ritz approximation	$k + 1$	$j + k$	1^b	1
Found	0	$2j - 2$	0	0
Restart	0	$2j_{\min}$	0	0

^aIf Krylov subspace methods are used to solve the correction equation, then the product $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{v}$ is often already available as a side-product. No MV is needed in this part then.

^bInstead of computing the residual \mathbf{r} as $(\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda} \mathbf{I}) \tilde{\mathbf{q}}$, \mathbf{r} may also be computed as $\mathbf{V}_A U(:, 1) - \tilde{\lambda} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}$, where $\mathbf{V}_A \equiv \mathbf{A}\mathbf{V}$ (cf. ALG. 6.2); depending on the number of nonzeros in \mathbf{A} and the value j , this may be more efficient.

TABLE 6.2. The computational costs of JDQR per iteration. The integers j and k are the dimensions of $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$ and $\text{span}\{\mathbf{Q}\}$, respectively.

6.2.5. The selection of Ritz pairs. At each iteration step of the Jacobi-Davidson method, an approximate eigenpair $(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \tilde{\lambda})$ has to be selected from the Ritz pairs $(\mathbf{V}u_i, \theta_i)$, that are solutions of the projected eigenproblem $(\mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V} -$

```

function [Q, R] = JDQR (A, K, tau, v0, epsilon, kmax, jmax, jmin)
Q = []; R = []; Y = []; H = [];
V = []; VA = []; M = [];
k = 0; j = 0;
while k < kmax,
    if j == 0,
        v = v0;
    else
        — the correction equation —
        r = (I - Ytilde Htilde^-1 Qtilde*) K^-1 r;
        Solve v (approximately) from:
            Qtilde* v = 0    and
            (I - Ytilde Htilde^-1 Qtilde*) K^-1 (A - lambda I) (I - Ytilde Htilde^-1 Qtilde*) v = -r.
    end
    — the projected problem —
    v = mgs (V, v); v = v / ||v||_2; vA = Av;
    M = [M, V*vA; v*VA, v*vA];
    V = [V, v]; VA = [VA, vA];
    [U, S] = schur (M); [U, S] = qrsort (tau, U, S);
    j = j + 1; found = 1;
    while found,
        — Ritz approximation —
        lambda = S(1, 1); q = VU(:, 1); y = K^-1 q;
        r = (A - lambda I) q; [r, s] = mgs (Q, r);
        Qtilde = [Q, q]; Ytilde = [Y, y]; Htilde = [H, Q*y; q*Y, q*y];
        :
        “found and implicit restart part”, see ALG. 6.3
        :
    end
end
end

```

JDQR returns a partial Schur form (\mathbf{Q}, R) of the matrix \mathbf{A} of dimension k_{\max} with eigenvalues near the target τ . \mathbf{K} is a preconditioner for $\mathbf{A} - \tau \mathbf{I}$, \mathbf{v}_0 is an initial guess, and ϵ is the stopping tolerance. j_{\max} and j_{\min} specify the dimension of the subspaces \mathbf{V} before and after implicit restart, respectively. `schur` is a MATLAB function that computes a Schur decomposition. The functions `mgs` (modified Gram-Schmidt) and `qrsort` (Sort Schur form) are given in Appendix .2.

```

found = ( $\|\mathbf{r}\|_2 < \epsilon$ ) & ( $j > 1 \mid k = k_{\max} - 1$ );
if found,
  — found —
   $\mathbf{Q} = \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}$ ;  $R = [R, s; \text{zeros}(1, k), \lambda]$ ;
   $k = k + 1$ ; if  $k == k_{\max}$ , break; end
   $\mathbf{Y} = \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}$ ;  $H = \tilde{H}$ ;
   $J = [2:j]$ ;  $j = j - 1$ ;
   $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V}U(:, J)$ ;  $\mathbf{V}_A = \mathbf{V}_A U(:, J)$ ;
   $S = S(J, J)$ ;  $M = S$ ;  $U = I$ ;
elseif  $j == j_{\max}$ ,
  — implicit restart —
   $j = j_{\min}$ ;  $J = [1:j]$ ;
   $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V}U(:, J)$ ;  $\mathbf{V}_A = \mathbf{V}_A U(:, J)$ ;
   $S = S(J, J)$ ;  $M = S$ ;  $U = I$ ;
end

```

ALGORITHM 6.3. “Found and implicit restart part” of JDQR.

$\theta I)u = 0$. For the selected Ritz pair, the correction equation provides the optimal expansion of the search subspace. However, the speed of convergence also depends on the ability to identify the most suitable Ritz pair (see also [90, Section 5]).

A poor choice of the Ritz pair will lead to an expansion of the search subspace in a poor direction. This affects the convergence to the wanted eigenvector, and this is a situation that we want to avoid. For limiting the dimension of the search subspace (cf. Section 6.2.2), it is even more important to avoid poor selections, because by discarding correct information, convergence can be hampered, and even completely destroyed.

Suppose we are interested in the eigenpair(s) with eigenvalue close to some specified *target* value τ . By selecting the pair with Ritz value closest to the target value, we hope to have the best approximation that is available in the search subspace. With respect to extremal eigenvalues, at least for standard normal eigenproblems, this approach can be justified theoretically as follows.

Recall that, for normal matrices, Ritz values are convex combinations of

eigenvalues, and consider the Ritz value $\tilde{\lambda}$ that is close to an extremal eigenvalue λ (an extreme point of the field of values). Then the λ -component in the convex combination for $\tilde{\lambda}$ will be the largest with a size depending on the separation of λ and the distance of λ to $\tilde{\lambda}$. Correspondingly, among all eigenvector components of the Ritz vector associated with $\tilde{\lambda}$, the component of the Ritz vector, in the eigenvector direction associated with λ , will be the largest in modulus (the components for eigenvectors are square roots of the corresponding components of eigenvalues). If $\tilde{\lambda}$ is still not close to λ , as in the initial stage of the process, the fact that (for symmetric problems) extremal eigenvalues optimize the Rayleigh quotient on the whole space, while extremal Ritz values optimize this quotient on the search subspace, may provide some confidence that the extremal Ritz values are the most appropriate approximations for the extremal eigenvalues. For interior eigenvalues λ , convex combinations of eigenvalues, in which the λ -component is small or even zero, can be close (or even equal) to λ : the Ritz value closest to the target value may be associated with a Ritz vector of which the angle with the target eigenvector is much larger than for other Ritz vectors. In [65, 70, 90] it is suggested to use *harmonic Ritz* pairs for these eigenvalues. As we will see in Section 6.3.5.1, the harmonic Ritz value closest to the target value can be viewed as an extremal Ritz values for a related problem. Therefore, we also adopt this approach. However, since the definition of harmonic Ritz values fits better in the context of generalized eigenproblems, we postpone our discussion on this subject to our treatment of generalized eigenproblems in Section 6.3.1. For the standard problem, we consider also a strategy for selecting standard Ritz values closest to the target value, also if the target is in the interior of the spectrum.

6.2.5.1. Identification of suitable Ritz values (tracking). If the Ritz vector in the previous iteration is already a fair approximation, then the norm of the residual gives information on the selected Ritz vector in the current step: in case of a poor selection, the new residual can be much larger than the previous one. It would then require additional computational work to find a Ritz pair with small residual norm (and still close enough to the target τ). A cheap alternative in this case is to select a Ritz value that is close to a previously accepted one (and forget about τ). In our experiments we have replaced in such cases the target by the Ritz value that is selected and accepted in the previous step, where we consider a Ritz value *acceptable* if the associated residual is smaller than some specified threshold ϵ_{tr} . After convergence of the Ritz pair, the original target value is restored at the start of the computation for the next eigenpair.

This *tracking strategy* does not require any additional computational costs per step, while it appears to reduce the number of steps significantly.

In view of the discussion in Section 6.2.5 for extremal eigenvalues, improvement for these eigenvalues may not be expected with the tracking strategy for normal problems.

6.2.6. Notes on the speed of convergence. The JDQR algorithm has nice properties with respect to the overall performance. While adjusting for one Schur pair, the subspace $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$ also accumulates components for other Schur pairs. As a result, after one Schur pair has been detected, other Schur pairs may follow more quickly than after a complete restart. These components will appear in a similar way as for the Shift-and-Invert Arnoldi [80] process, with a shift $\tilde{\lambda}$ for a (deflated) eigenproblem, as can be understood as follows.

For simplicity, suppose that \mathbf{A} has a complete set of eigenpairs $(\mathbf{x}_i, \lambda_i)$ with $\lambda_1 < \lambda_2 < \dots < \lambda_n$ and that we are trying to find an approximation $(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \tilde{\lambda})$ for $(\mathbf{x}_1, \lambda_1)$. The exact solution of (6.4) is given by

$$(6.23) \quad \mathbf{v} = -\tilde{\mathbf{q}} + (\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda}\mathbf{I})^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{q}}\epsilon,$$

with $\epsilon = 1/(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}^*(\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda}\mathbf{I})^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{q}})$ (cf. [90, Section 4.1]). Writing $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ as $\sum \gamma_i \mathbf{x}_i$, it follows that

$$(6.24) \quad (\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda}\mathbf{I})^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{q}} = \sum_i \frac{\gamma_i}{\lambda_i - \tilde{\lambda}} \mathbf{x}_i.$$

We may assume, without loss of generality, that $\gamma_i \neq 0$, because $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ is a Ritz vector which means that $\gamma_i = 0$ either if $\angle(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{V}) = 0$ or $\pi/2$. The latter case is unlikely to happen, due to rounding errors, and the first case indicates full convergence.

Hence, eigenvector components corresponding to eigenvalues closer to $\tilde{\lambda}$ will be amplified more in $(\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda}\mathbf{I})^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$. The component orthogonal to $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ is used as an expansion for \mathbf{V} and thus, as soon as $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ has a large component in the direction of \mathbf{x}_1 , say that the angle is less than $\pi/4$, then necessarily components other than \mathbf{x}_1 become dominant. That is

$$(6.25) \quad \mathbf{v} \sim \sum_{i \neq 1} \frac{\gamma_i}{\lambda_i - \tilde{\lambda}} \mathbf{x}_i.$$

In FIG. 6.1 we have illustrated this phenomenon. The bullets represent the amplification factors $1/|\lambda_i - \tilde{\lambda}|$ for components in the direction of \mathbf{x}_i ($i = 2, 3, 4$); THETA represents $\tilde{\lambda}$.

FIGURE 6.1. Amplification factors of eigenvectors

In the subsequent iterations similar amplifications will occur and the closer λ_i is to $\tilde{\lambda}$, the more rapid the angle $\angle(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{V})$ will decrease.

This argument is repetitive: if the angle $\angle(\mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{V})$ becomes very small, then the corresponding γ_2 will be very small and other components, due to orthogonalization, will become more dominant.

Consequently, while the process converges to a Schur pair, the search subspace \mathbf{V} will provide good initial approximations for the nearby Schur pairs. Moreover, slow convergence during one stage may be compensated for by faster convergence in the next stage, because the subspace $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$ will be enriched with more components of other Schur pairs, due to repeated amplifications. This is observed in our numerical experiments, see Section 6.4.

6.2.7. The quality of the deflated preconditioner. Even when the preconditioner \mathbf{K} is constructed for a fixed τ , then the correction equation still involves projections that become more expensive after each Schur pair that has been detected, but this does not necessarily lead to a more expensive computational process (compared with explicit restart). When iterative solvers are used, they may converge faster because the field of values of the projected operator $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_k \mathbf{Q}_k^*)(\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda} \mathbf{I})(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_k \mathbf{Q}_k^*)$ is contained in the field of values of $\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda} \mathbf{I}$, and that may be smaller, specially after exterior eigenvalues have been detected.

The projections may also have a positive effect on the preconditioner.

With $(\mathbf{A} - \tau \mathbf{I}) = \mathbf{K} - \mathbf{R}$ it follows that

$$(6.26) \quad (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_k \mathbf{Q}_k^*)(\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\lambda} \mathbf{I})(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_k \mathbf{Q}_k^*) = \\ (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_k \mathbf{Q}_k^*) \mathbf{K} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_k \mathbf{Q}_k^*) - (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_k \mathbf{Q}_k^*) \mathbf{R} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_k \mathbf{Q}_k^*) - (\tau - \tilde{\lambda})(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_k \mathbf{Q}_k^*),$$

We see that, on the one hand, the preconditioning error is enlarged by a small shift $(\tau - \tilde{\lambda})\mathbf{I}$, but on the other hand, the projections diminish the error by filtering out the detected Schur vectors. If the error \mathbf{R} is large with respect to eigenvectors corresponding to eigenvalues near τ , then the projected error $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_k \mathbf{Q}_k^*) \mathbf{R} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_k \mathbf{Q}_k^*)$ will be significantly smaller, and the only penalty is a (small) shift due to $\tau - \tilde{\lambda}$. It seems plausible (cf. [100, Ch. IV]) that this will not lead to a significantly less effective preconditioner, and it may help to explain the effectiveness of a fixed preconditioner running with JDQR in our experiments.

6.3. The generalized eigenproblem. We now consider the generalized eigenproblem (6.2) and derive the JDQZ algorithm following the approach for JDQR.

CONVENTION 6.1. We denote a generalized eigenvalue of the matrix pair (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) as a pair $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle$. This approach is preferred because underflow or overflow for $\lambda = \alpha/\beta$ in finite precision arithmetic may occur when α and/or β are zero or close to zero, in which case the pair is still meaningful and useful [63, 77], [96, Ch. VI].

REMARK 6.10. Observe that, for each $\gamma \neq 0$, the pairs $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle$ and $\langle \gamma\alpha, \gamma\beta \rangle$ correspond to the same generalized eigenvalue. Rather than scaling the coefficients of $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle$ in our algorithms (for instance, such that $\beta \in [0, 1]$ and $\beta^2 + |\alpha|^2 = 1$), we follow the advise in [63], and we show the results as produced by the QZ-algorithm: the size of α and β may give valuable information on the conditioning of the computed eigenpair. However, in the construction of our algorithm, scaling does play a role.

6.3.1. Jacobi-Davidson. For standard eigenproblems, the search subspace and the test subspace in Jacobi-Davidson are identical, but for generalized problems, other choices appear to be more natural (cf. [84]). A similar observation applies to the projectors in the correction equation.

As appears from the analysis in [84], for asymptotic quadratic speed of convergence we are restricted in our choices, although there are still a number of possibilities. As we will see, the computation of a *partial generalized Schur form*,

will lead naturally to basically two specific choices for the test subspace, and to two related choices for the projectors in the correction equation.

For generalized eigenproblems, a partial generalized Schur form is defined as follows.

DEFINITION 6.2. A *partial generalized Schur form* of dimension k for a matrix pair (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) is the decomposition

$$(6.27) \quad \mathbf{A}\mathbf{Q}_k = \mathbf{Z}_k S_k, \quad \mathbf{B}\mathbf{Q}_k = \mathbf{Z}_k T_k,$$

where \mathbf{Q}_k and \mathbf{Z}_k are orthogonal $(n \times k)$ -matrices, and S_k and T_k are upper triangular $(k \times k)$ -matrices. A column \mathbf{q}_i of \mathbf{Q}_k is referred to as a *generalized Schur vector*, and we refer to a pair $(\mathbf{q}_i, \langle \alpha_i, \beta_i \rangle)$, with $\langle \alpha_i, \beta_i \rangle = \langle S_k(i, i), T_k(i, i) \rangle$ as a *generalized Schur pair*.

The formulation in (6.27) is equivalent with

$$(6.28) \quad \mathbf{Z}_k^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{Q}_k = S_k \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{Z}_k^* \mathbf{B} \mathbf{Q}_k = T_k.$$

Further, if $(x, \langle \alpha, \beta \rangle)$ is a generalized eigenpair of (S_k, T_k) then $(\mathbf{Q}_k x, \langle \alpha, \beta \rangle)$ is a generalized eigenpair of (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) .

For presentation purposes, we will briefly describe Jacobi-Davidson for the generalized eigenproblem (6.2); for details we refer to [84].

As for standard eigenproblems, in each step the approximate eigenvector $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ is selected from a *search subspace* $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$. This approximation with associated approximate generalized eigenvalue $\langle \tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta} \rangle$ is “tested” with respect to some subspace $\text{span}\{W\}$:

$$(6.29) \quad \tilde{\beta} \mathbf{A} \tilde{\mathbf{q}} - \tilde{\alpha} \mathbf{B} \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \perp \text{span}\{\mathbf{W}\}.$$

For the generalized case, it is, in view of (6.27) and (6.28), natural to take the *test subspace* $\text{span}\{\mathbf{W}\}$ different from the search subspace: the Petrov-Galerkin approach. Search subspace and test subspace are of the same dimension, say j . Equation (6.29) leads to the *projected eigenproblem*

$$(6.30) \quad (\tilde{\beta} \mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V} - \tilde{\alpha} \mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{B} \mathbf{V}) u = 0,$$

that can be solved by conventional techniques, and a solution $(u, \langle \tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta} \rangle)$ is selected. Observe that (6.30) is a j -dimensional problem, and u is a j -vector. The *Petrov vector* $\tilde{\mathbf{q}} \equiv \mathbf{V}u$ and the residual $\mathbf{r} \equiv \tilde{\beta} \mathbf{A} \tilde{\mathbf{q}} - \tilde{\alpha} \mathbf{B} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}$, associated with the

Petrov value $\langle \tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta} \rangle$, are computed. The subspaces $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$ and $\text{span}\{\mathbf{W}\}$ are expanded in each step of the iterative process. For certain vectors \mathbf{p} , $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}$, and \mathbf{y} , the search subspace is expanded by a vector \mathbf{v} that is orthogonal to \mathbf{p} and that solves approximately the *correction equation*

$$(6.31) \quad \left(\mathbf{I} - \frac{\tilde{\mathbf{z}}\mathbf{y}^*}{\mathbf{y}^*\tilde{\mathbf{z}}} \right) (\tilde{\beta}\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\alpha}\mathbf{B}) \left(\mathbf{I} - \frac{\tilde{\mathbf{q}}\mathbf{p}^*}{\mathbf{p}^*\tilde{\mathbf{q}}} \right) \mathbf{v} = -\mathbf{r}.$$

In the next step, $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{v}\}$ is the new search subspace. Under special but obvious conditions that prevent $\mathbf{y}^*\tilde{\mathbf{z}}$, and similar other expressions, from converging towards 0, the choice \mathbf{y} in $\text{span}\{W\}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}$ in $\text{span}\{\mathbf{A}\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \mathbf{B}\tilde{\mathbf{q}}\}$ leads to quadratic convergence, see [84, Th. 3.2]. In the general context in [84], there are no other restrictions on \mathbf{p} , $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}$, and \mathbf{y} .

In our present approach we want orthogonal matrices \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{W} , similar to \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Q} in (6.27), and we favor orthogonal projections. Therefore, we construct \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{W} to be orthogonal: new columns of \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{W} are orthogonalized by modified Gram-Schmidt. With $\mathbf{p} = \tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ the right projection in (6.31) is orthogonal. With $\mathbf{y} = \tilde{\mathbf{z}}$ the left projection is orthogonal also, and, as we will see, this choice is in line with the natural choice for the test subspace, without violating the restrictions for quadratic convergence.

We use the QZ algorithm [63] to reduce (6.30) to a generalized Schur form. With j the dimension of $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$, this algorithm yields orthogonal $(j \times j)$ -matrices U_R and U_L , and upper triangular $(j \times j)$ -matrices S_A and S_B , such that

$$(6.32) \quad U_L^*(\mathbf{W}^*\mathbf{A}\mathbf{V})U_R = S_A \quad \text{and} \quad U_L^*(\mathbf{W}^*\mathbf{B}\mathbf{V})U_R = S_B.$$

As for the standard case, for this generalized situation, there is also an algorithm that reorders this decomposition such that the first column of U_R and the $(1,1)$ -entries of S_A and S_B represent the wanted Petrov solution of (6.30). We will discuss this algorithm in Section 6.3.2 and Appendix 3.

With the decomposition in (6.32), we construct an approximate partial generalized Schur form (cf. (6.27)): $\mathbf{V}U_R$ approximates a \mathbf{Q}_k , and $\mathbf{W}U_L$ approximates the associated \mathbf{Z}_k . The Jacobi-Davidson method generates a \mathbf{V} for which $\mathbf{V}U_R$ approximates a \mathbf{Q}_k (in general the first column will be in leading position). Since $\text{span}\{\mathbf{Z}_k\} = \text{span}\{\mathbf{A}\mathbf{Q}_k\} = \text{span}\{\mathbf{B}\mathbf{Q}_k\}$ (cf. (6.27)), it makes sense to choose \mathbf{W} such that, for some scalars ν_0, μ_0 with, say, $|\nu_0|^2 + |\mu_0|^2 = 1$, the space $\text{span}\{\mathbf{W}\}$ coincides with $\text{span}\{\nu_0\mathbf{A}\mathbf{V} + \mu_0\mathbf{B}\mathbf{V}\}$. This choice is also in line with the restriction $\mathbf{w} = \tilde{\mathbf{z}}$ and the other restrictions on \mathbf{w} and $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}$, mentioned above.

In summary, for suitable fixed scalars ν_0, μ_0 , we propose the following Jacobi-Davidson method:

- reduce the projected problem (6.30) to an ordered generalized Schur decomposition (6.32) and select as approximate generalized eigenpair:

$$(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \langle \tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta} \rangle) \equiv (\mathbf{V}U_R(:, 1), \langle S_A(1, 1), S_B(1, 1) \rangle);$$

- for

$$(6.33) \quad \gamma \tilde{\mathbf{z}} \equiv \nu_0 \mathbf{A} \tilde{\mathbf{q}} + \mu_0 \mathbf{B} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{r} \equiv \tilde{\beta} \mathbf{A} \tilde{\mathbf{q}} - \tilde{\alpha} \mathbf{B} \tilde{\mathbf{q}},$$

where γ is a normalization constant, compute an approximate solution $\mathbf{v} \perp \tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ of the resulting correction equation

$$(6.34) \quad \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^* \mathbf{v} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{z}} \tilde{\mathbf{z}}^*)(\tilde{\beta} \mathbf{A} - \tilde{\alpha} \mathbf{B})(\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^*) \mathbf{v} = -\mathbf{r};$$

- expand \mathbf{V} with \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{W} with \mathbf{w} , where

$$(6.35) \quad \mathbf{w} \equiv \nu_0 \mathbf{A} \mathbf{v} + \mu_0 \mathbf{B} \mathbf{v}.$$

It can be shown that, with the above choices for $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}$ and \mathbf{W} ,

$$(6.36) \quad \tilde{\mathbf{z}} = \mathbf{W}U_L(:, 1).$$

In this approach, the relation between the partial generalized Schur form for the large problem and the complete generalized Schur form for the small problem (6.30) via right vectors ($\tilde{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{V}U_R(:, 1)$) is similar to the relation via left vectors ($\tilde{\mathbf{z}} = \mathbf{W}U_L(:, 1)$). The fact that $\tilde{\mathbf{z}} = \mathbf{W}U_L(:, 1)$, is also convenient for restart purposes, as we will see in Section 6.3.2.

Finally, we will explain how to select the scalars ν_0 and μ_0 . The restriction $|\nu_0|^2 + |\mu_0|^2 = 1$ is for scaling and avoids trivial expansions. We pursue three approaches. The first two, in Sections 6.3.1.1–6.3.1.2, are closely related, and can be viewed as a generalizations of the approach by Ritz values for standard eigenproblems, for optimal expansion of the test subspace. The third one, in Section 6.3.5.1, is more closely related to the approach by harmonic Ritz values, and aims for optimal selection of Petrov pairs.

6.3.1.1. Fixed values for ν_0 and μ_0 . If \mathbf{v} is the expansion vector for the search subspace then, in the general setting, we have to expand the test subspace by $\nu_0\mathbf{A}\mathbf{v} + \mu_0\mathbf{B}\mathbf{v}$. Note that, if $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ is the new approximate eigenvector then expanding the old search subspace by \mathbf{v} is equivalent to expanding it by $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$, so that the new test subspace can also be obtained by expanding with $\nu_0\mathbf{A}\tilde{\mathbf{q}} + \mu_0\mathbf{B}\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$. For $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{I}$, the obvious choice would be, $\nu_0 = 0$ and $\mu_0 = 1$. However, if $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{I}$, the obvious choice would be $\nu_0 = 1$ and $\mu_0 = 0$. In this case, although $\mathbf{B}\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ is in the direction of $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$, if $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ is close to some eigenvector \mathbf{q} , multiplication by \mathbf{B} may diminish the most important eigenvector components of $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$, if the eigenvalue of \mathbf{B} associated to \mathbf{q} is (very) small. Therefore, expanding the test space by $\mathbf{B}\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ may be (much) less optimal than expanding by $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$. In the presence of rounding errors, this effect may be even more prominent.

For the standard case, where either $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{I}$ or $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{I}$, $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{q} = \alpha\mathbf{q}$ and $\mathbf{B}\mathbf{q} = \beta\mathbf{q}$, for $\langle\alpha, \beta\rangle$ with either $\alpha = 1$ or $\beta = 1$, the optimal choice with respect to the \mathbf{q} -components seems to be

$$(6.37) \quad \nu_0 = \frac{\bar{\alpha}}{\sqrt{|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2}} \quad \text{and} \quad \mu_0 = \frac{\bar{\beta}}{\sqrt{|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2}},$$

since this choice maximizes

$$\|\nu_0\mathbf{A}\mathbf{q} + \mu_0\mathbf{B}\mathbf{q}\|_2 \quad (= |\nu_0\alpha + \mu_0\beta| \|\mathbf{q}\|_2).$$

Also, for the generalized problem, where $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{q} = \alpha\mathbf{z}$ and $\mathbf{B}\mathbf{q} = \beta\mathbf{z}$, if $(\mathbf{q}, \langle\alpha, \beta\rangle)$ is the desired eigenpair, we can select ν_0 and μ_0 as in (6.37). With respect to \mathbf{q} , this choice maximizes

$$\|\nu_0\mathbf{A}\mathbf{q} + \mu_0\mathbf{B}\mathbf{q}\|_2 \quad (= |\nu_0\alpha + \mu_0\beta| \|\mathbf{z}\|_2).$$

This approach can be viewed as an attempt to expand the test subspace $\text{span}\{\mathbf{W}\}$ optimally in the direction of \mathbf{z} , where \mathbf{z} is the normalized vector $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{q}$ (or $\mathbf{B}\mathbf{q}$).

Since we have to choose ν_0 and μ_0 before we even know the generalized eigenvalue $\langle\alpha, \beta\rangle$, the best we can do, certainly in the initial phase of the process, is to select

$$(6.38) \quad \nu_0 \equiv \frac{\bar{\tau}}{\sqrt{1 + |\tau|^2}} \quad \text{and} \quad \mu_0 \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + |\tau|^2}},$$

where τ is the target value.

6.3.1.2. Adaptive values for ν_0 and μ_0 . needed

For a well-balanced expansion of the test subspace, the expressions in (6.37) suggest that we take advantage of the current approximations $\langle \tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta} \rangle$ for the generalized eigenpair. Intuitively

$$(6.39) \quad \nu_0 \equiv \frac{\tilde{\alpha}}{\sqrt{|\tilde{\alpha}|^2 + |\tilde{\beta}|^2}} \quad \text{and} \quad \mu_0 \equiv \frac{\tilde{\beta}}{\sqrt{|\tilde{\alpha}|^2 + |\tilde{\beta}|^2}}$$

might be a good choice. Ideally, at convergence, the space $\text{span}\{\mathbf{W}\}$ should coincide with $\text{span}\{\bar{\alpha}\mathbf{AV} + \bar{\beta}\mathbf{AV}\}$. Since \mathbf{V} is expanded by \mathbf{v} , this suggests to expand \mathbf{W} by

$$(6.40) \quad \mathbf{w} \equiv \nu_0 \mathbf{Av} + \mu_0 \mathbf{Bv}.$$

Unfortunately, since all intermediate ν_0 and μ_0 are different, this does not guarantee that at convergence $\bar{\alpha}\mathbf{Aq} + \bar{\beta}\mathbf{Bq} \in \text{span}\{\mathbf{W}\}$. Nevertheless this *adaptive* variant (6.39)-(6.40) turns out to work better in practice than the fixed variant in Section 6.3.1.1. For the $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}$ in the correction equation (6.34) we took $\mathbf{WU}_L(:, 1)$ (see (6.36)). This vector is in the direction of the orthogonal projection of $\nu_0 \mathbf{Aq} + \mu_0 \mathbf{Bq}$ onto $\text{span}\{\mathbf{W}\}$ and, in practice, the angle between the vectors $\mathbf{WU}_L(:, 1)$ and $\nu_0 \mathbf{Aq} + \mu_0 \mathbf{Bq}$ appears to converge rapidly towards zero.

REMARK 6.11. If, for standard eigenproblems, test subspaces coincide with the corresponding search subspaces, then we refer to the approximate eigenpairs as Ritz pairs: the approximate eigenpairs are associated with the Ritz-Galerkin approximation. If the subspaces do not coincide, we prefer the name Petrov pairs, because of its relation with Petrov-Galerkin approximation. Petrov values associated with the standard eigenproblem for \mathbf{A} and the choice $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{AV}$ are called harmonic Ritz values. The reference to ‘‘Ritz’’ in their name expresses the fact that these Petrov values are the reciprocals of the Ritz values associated with the standard eigenproblem for \mathbf{A}^{-1} with test and search subspace both equal to \mathbf{AV} .

For generalized eigenproblems, there is no canonical relation between search and test subspace (except for unitary \mathbf{B}) and we believe that the name Petrov pairs is appropriate here. However, in our approach, orthogonality and the QZ-algorithm are central. As we have explained above, this leads quite naturally to some specific choice of the test subspaces. Therefore, we call the Petrov pairs associated with the choice made in Section 6.3.1.1 the *standard Petrov* pairs.

6.3.2. Practical selection and implicit restart. When we reduce the projected eigenproblem (6.30) to a generalized Schur form by the QZ algorithm [63], then we can exploit the generalized Schur form for various purposes: — selection of a Petrov pair $(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \langle \tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta} \rangle)$, — selection of the corresponding left vector $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}$, — restriction of the dimension of the subspaces $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$ and $\text{span}\{\mathbf{W}\}$, if necessary. We will explain the first and last point in more detail.

Suppose that the generalized Schur form of the interaction pair

$$(M_A, M_B) \equiv (\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V}, \mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{B} \mathbf{V}),$$

given by

$$U_L^* M_A U_R = S_A \quad \text{and} \quad U_L^* M_B U_R = S_B,$$

is ordered with respect to τ such that

$$(6.41) \quad |S_A(1,1)/S_B(1,1) - \tau| \leq |S_A(2,2)/S_B(2,2) - \tau| \leq \cdots \leq |S_A(j,j)/S_B(j,j) - \tau|,$$

where j is the dimension of $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$. Then

$$(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \langle \tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta} \rangle) \equiv (\mathbf{V} U_R(:, 1), \langle S_A(1,1), S_B(1,1) \rangle)$$

is the Petrov approximation corresponding to the projected system (6.30) with Petrov value closest to the target τ . The corresponding left vector is given by $\tilde{\mathbf{z}} \equiv \mathbf{W} U_L(:, 1)$. Furthermore, $\mathbf{V} U_R(:, 1:i)$, with $i < j$, spans the subspace that contains the i most promising Petrov vectors. The corresponding test subspace is given by $\mathbf{W} U_L(:, 1:i)$. Therefore, similar to the approach in Section 6.2.2 (cf. [90, Section 5.3]), when we want to reduce the dimension of the subspace (“implicit restart”) to j_{\min} , $j_{\min} < j$, then we simply discard the columns $\mathbf{v}_{j_{\min}+1}$ through \mathbf{v}_j , and $\mathbf{w}_{j_{\min}+1}$ through \mathbf{w}_j , and continue the Jacobi-Davidson algorithm with

$$\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V} U_R(:, 1:j_{\min}) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W} U_L(:, 1:j_{\min}).$$

For a reordering algorithm for the generalized Schur form, see, for instance, [106, 107]. A simple MATLAB implementation for reordering with respect to a target value τ is given in Appendix 3. A theoretical explanation is given there as well.

6.3.3. JDQZ. In this section we focus on the efficient computation of a set of generalized eigenpairs. The idea is to use the Jacobi-Davidson method for generalized eigenproblems (Section 6.3.1) for the computation of a partial generalized Schur form.

Suppose that we have the partial generalized Schur form

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{Q}_{k-1} = \mathbf{Z}_{k-1}S_{k-1} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{B}\mathbf{Q}_{k-1} = \mathbf{Z}_{k-1}T_k.$$

Analogously to (6.8), we want to expand this partial generalized Schur form with a suitable \mathbf{q} and \mathbf{z} , to

$$(6.42) \quad \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} & \mathbf{q} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z}_{k-1} & \mathbf{z} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} S_{k-1} & s \\ 0 & \alpha \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$$\mathbf{B} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} & \mathbf{q} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z}_{k-1} & \mathbf{z} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} T_k & t \\ 0 & \beta \end{bmatrix}.$$

From this we deduce that the generalized Schur pair $(\mathbf{q}, \langle \alpha, \beta \rangle)$ satisfies

$$(6.43) \quad \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^* \mathbf{q} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (\beta \mathbf{A} - \alpha \mathbf{B}) \mathbf{q} - \mathbf{Z}_{k-1} u = \mathbf{0},$$

for $u \equiv \mathbf{Z}_{k-1}^* (\beta \mathbf{A} - \alpha \mathbf{B}) \mathbf{q}$. This leads to

$$\mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^* \mathbf{q} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Z}_{k-1} \mathbf{Z}_{k-1}^*) (\beta \mathbf{A} - \alpha \mathbf{B}) \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0}.$$

Hence, $(\mathbf{q}, \langle \alpha, \beta \rangle)$ satisfies

$$(6.44) \quad \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^* \mathbf{q} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Z}_{k-1} \mathbf{Z}_{k-1}^*) (\beta \mathbf{A} - \alpha \mathbf{B}) (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*) \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0}.$$

and the generalized Schur pair $(\mathbf{q}, \langle \alpha, \beta \rangle)$ is therefore also an eigenpair of the *deflated matrix pair*

$$(6.45) \quad ((\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Z}_{k-1} \mathbf{Z}_{k-1}^*) \mathbf{A} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*), (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Z}_{k-1} \mathbf{Z}_{k-1}^*) \mathbf{B} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*)).$$

In JDQZ we solve this eigenproblem with the Jacobi-Davidson method for the generalized eigenproblem.

In more detail, the procedure is as follows. Let \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{W} be orthogonal $(n \times j)$ -matrices such that $\mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} = \mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{Z}_{k-1} = \mathbf{0}$. Let

$$M_A \equiv \mathbf{W}^* (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Z}_{k-1} \mathbf{Z}_{k-1}^*) \mathbf{A} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*) \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V} \quad \text{and}$$

$$M_B \equiv \mathbf{W}^* (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Z}_{k-1} \mathbf{Z}_{k-1}^*) \mathbf{B} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*) \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{B} \mathbf{V},$$

and denote the generalized Schur form of the matrix pair (M_A, M_B) by

$$(6.46) \quad U_L^* M_A U_R = S_A \quad \text{and} \quad U_L^* M_B U_R = S_B.$$

If this generalized Schur form is ordered with respect to the target value τ , then

$$(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \langle \tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta} \rangle) \equiv (\mathbf{V}U_R(:, 1), \langle S_A(1, 1), S_B(1, 1) \rangle)$$

is a Petrov pair approximation for a solution of (6.44). The corresponding left vector is given by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{z}} \equiv \mathbf{W}U_L(:, 1).$$

The Jacobi-Davidson method expands \mathbf{V} with the orthogonal complement of \mathbf{v} that is an (approximate) solution of the *generalized deflated correction equation* (6.47)

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^* \mathbf{v} = 0, & \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^* \mathbf{v} = 0, & \text{and} \\ (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{z}} \tilde{\mathbf{z}}^*)(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Z}_{k-1} \mathbf{Z}_{k-1}^*)(\tilde{\beta} \mathbf{A} - \tilde{\alpha} \mathbf{B})(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*)(\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^*) \mathbf{v} = -\mathbf{r}, \end{cases}$$

where $\mathbf{r} \equiv (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Z}_{k-1} \mathbf{Z}_{k-1}^*)(\tilde{\beta} \mathbf{A} - \tilde{\alpha} \mathbf{A})(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*) \tilde{\mathbf{q}}$. We also have to expand \mathbf{W} ; we expand with the orthogonal complement of $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Z}_{k-1} \mathbf{Z}_{k-1}^*)(\nu_0 \mathbf{A} + \mu_0 \mathbf{B})(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*) \tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ to \mathbf{W} .

When the generalized Schur pair $(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \langle \tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta} \rangle)$ is sufficiently close to $(\mathbf{q}, \langle \alpha, \beta \rangle)$, then we may continue for still another generalized Schur pair. In that case \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{W} are replaced by $\mathbf{V}U_R(:, 2:j)$ and $\mathbf{W}U_L(:, 2:j)$, in order to obtain a new search subspace orthogonal to $\text{span}\{\mathbf{Q}_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{q}}\}$, and a new test subspace orthogonal to $\text{span}\{\mathbf{Z}_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{z}}\}$, respectively, and we continue the process.

6.3.4. Preconditioning. In this section we discuss preconditioning for the generalized deflated correction equation.

The correction equation (6.44) involves an operator for which the domain and the image space differ. This means that Krylov subspace methods cannot be applied right away. Fortunately, this can be fixed easily by incorporating preconditioning.

Similarly to Section 6.2.4, we propose to use

$$(6.48) \quad (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{z}} \tilde{\mathbf{z}}^*)(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Z}_{k-1} \mathbf{Z}_{k-1}^*) \mathbf{K} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}^*)(\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^*).$$

for some preconditioner $\mathbf{K} \approx \mathbf{A} - \tau \mathbf{B}$.

We modify our notation slightly (cf. NOTATION 6.1):

NOTATION 6.2.

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k &\equiv [\mathbf{Q}_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{q}}], & \text{the matrix } \mathbf{Q}_{k-1} \text{ expanded by } \tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \\ \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_k &\equiv [\mathbf{Z}_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{z}}], & \text{the matrix } \mathbf{Z}_{k-1} \text{ expanded by } \tilde{\mathbf{z}}, \\ \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k &\equiv \mathbf{K}^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_k, & \text{the expanded matrix of preconditioned vectors,} \\ \tilde{H}_k &\equiv \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^* \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k, & \text{the projected preconditioner } \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^* \mathbf{K}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_k.\end{aligned}$$

In this notation the left preconditioned correction equation for the generalized correction equation can be written as

(6.49)

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^* \mathbf{v} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{K}^{-1} (\tilde{\beta} \mathbf{A} - \tilde{\alpha} \mathbf{B}) (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{v} = -\hat{\mathbf{r}},$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{r}} \equiv (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k^*) \mathbf{K}^{-1} \mathbf{r}$. Observe that, for $\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{I}$, this equation is equivalent with the one in (6.47).

Of course, right preconditioned generalized correction equations can be derived in a similar manner. With $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}_k \equiv (\mathbf{K}^*)^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_k$,

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}}_k^* \hat{\mathbf{v}} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{Y}}_k^*) (\tilde{\beta} \mathbf{A} - \tilde{\alpha} \mathbf{B}) \mathbf{K}^{-1} (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{Y}}_k^*) \hat{\mathbf{v}} = -\hat{\mathbf{r}},$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{r}} \equiv (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_k \tilde{H}_k^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{Y}}_k^*) \mathbf{r}$. Then $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{K}^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{v}}$.

Note that for the operators in the preconditioned correction equation, the domain and the image space coincide, so that Krylov subspace methods can be used.

A pseudo-code for the preconditioned Jacobi-Davidson QZ-algorithm with harmonic Petrov values (to be discussed in Section 6.3.5.1) is given in ALG. 6.4.

In TAB. 6.3 we have listed the main computational ingredients per iteration of JDQZ.

6.3.5. The selection of Petrov pairs. In the approaches with fixed and adaptive parameters for the generalized case in Section 6.3.1.1 and Section 6.3.1.2, our goal is optimal expansion of the test subspace, implicitly leading to optimal expansion of the search subspace as well. But the speed of convergence of a Jacobi-Davidson algorithm also depends on the ability to select the “correct” Petrov pairs (cf. Section 6.2.5).

Of course, here the selection can be improved too by a tracking strategy, as explained in Section 6.2.5.1. We need some confidence that we are tracking the correct Petrov value. In Section 6.2.5.1, we proposed to rely on the norm of the previous residual. Unfortunately, this strategy will not be helpful in the initial stage of the process, where there are no small residuals.

```

function [Q, Z, RA, RB] = JDQZ (A, B, K, τ, v0, ε, kmax, jmin, jmax)
Q = []; Z = []; RA = []; RB = []; Y = []; H = [];
V = []; VA = []; VB = []; W = []; MA = []; MB = [];
γ = √(1 + |τ|2); α0 = τ/γ, β0 = 1/γ; k = 0; j = 0;
while k < kmax,
  if j == 0,
    v = v0;
  else
    — the correction equation —
    r = (I - ỸH̃-1Q̃*) K-1r;
    Solve v (approximately) from:
      Q̃* v = 0 and
      (I - ỸH̃-1Q̃*) K-1(β A - α B)(I - ỸH̃-1Q̃*) v = -r.
  end
  — the projected problem —
  v = mgs (V, v); v = v/||v||2; vA = Av; vB = Bv;
  w = (β0vA - α0vB); w = mgs (Z, w); w = mgs (W, w); w = w/||w||2;
  MA = [MA, W* vA; w* vA, w* vA]; MB = [MB, W* vB; w* vB, w* vB];
  V = [V, v]; VA = [VA, vA]; VB = [VB, vB]; W = [W, w];
  [UL, UR, SA, SB] = qz (MA, MB);
  [UL, UR, SA, SB] = qzsort (τ, UL, UR, SA, SB);
  j = j + 1; found = 1;
  while found,
    — harmonic Petrov approximation —
    α = SA(1, 1); β = SB(1, 1);
    q = VUR(:, 1); z = WUL(:, 1); y = K-1z;
    r = A q; [r, sA] = mgs (Z, r); rB = B q; [rB, sB] = mgs (Z, rB);
    r = β r - α rB;
    Q̃ = [Q, q]; Ỹ = [Y, y]; H̃ = [H, Q* y; q* Y, q* y];
    “found and implicit restart part”, see ALG. 6.5
  end
end
end

```

JDQZ returns a partial generalized Schur form $(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{Z}, R_A, R_B)$ of dimension k_{\max} of the matrix pair (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) with generalized eigenvalues near the target τ . \mathbf{K} is a preconditioner for $\mathbf{A} - \tau\mathbf{B}$, \mathbf{v}_0 is an initial guess, and ϵ is the stopping tolerance. j_{\max} and j_{\min} specify the dimension of the search subspace before and after implicit restart, respectively. `qz` is a MATLAB function that computes a generalized Schur decomposition. The functions `mgs` (modified Gram-Schmidt) and `qzsort` (Sort generalized Schur form) can be found in Appendix .3.

ALGORITHM 6.4. Preconditioned JDQZ, using harmonic Petrov values.

```

found = ( $\|\mathbf{r}\|_2 < \epsilon$ ) & ( $j > 1 \mid k = k_{\max} - 1$ );
if found,
  — found —
   $\mathbf{Q} = \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}; \mathbf{Z} = \tilde{\mathbf{Z}};$ 
   $R_A = [R_A, s_A; \text{zeros}(1, k), \alpha]; R_B = [R_B, s_B; \text{zeros}(1, k), \beta];$ 
   $k = k + 1;$  if  $k = k_{\max},$  break; end
   $\mathbf{Y} = \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}; H = \tilde{H};$ 
   $J = [2:j]; j = j - 1;$ 
   $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V}U_R(:, J); \mathbf{V}_A = \mathbf{V}_A U_R(:, J); \mathbf{V}_B = \mathbf{V}_B U_R(:, J);$ 
   $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}U_L(:, J); S_A = S_A(J, J); S_B = S_B(J, J);$ 
   $M_A = S_A; M_B = S_B; U_R = I; U_L = I;$ 
elseif  $j == j_{\max},$ 
  — implicit restart —
   $j = j_{\min}; J = [1:j];$ 
   $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V}U_R(:, J); \mathbf{V}_A = \mathbf{V}_A U_R(:, J); \mathbf{V}_B = \mathbf{V}_B U_R(:, J);$ 
   $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}U_L(:, J); S_A = S_A(J, J); S_B = S_B(J, J);$ 
   $M_A = S_A; M_B = S_B; U_R = I; U_L = I;$ 
end

```

ALGORITHM 6.5. “Found and implicit restart part” of preconditioned JDQZ, with harmonic Petrov values.

In Section 6.3.5.1 we will introduce harmonic Petrov values. We will see that the harmonic Petrov values, that are closest to a target, can be obtained as extremal Ritz values for a specific test subspace, also if the target is in the interior of the spectrum. Specifically for such a situation, the harmonic Petrov values appear to be attractive competitors for the standard Petrov values of the approaches in Section 6.3.1.1 and Section 6.3.1.2: for generalized eigenproblems the costs for the computation of the standard Petrov values is the same as for harmonic Petrov values, and, because of the extremality property, harmonic Petrov values closest to the target appear to be the best choices, also in early stages of the process (cf. Section 6.2.5). A tracking strategy is not required nor helpful in this case.

Part	DOTS	AXPYS	MVs	K
The correction equation	variable			
The Projected problem	$6j + k$	$2j - 1$	2^a	0
The Petrov approximation	$2k + 1$	$2j + 3k$	2^b	1
Found	0	$4j - 4$	0	0
Restart	0	$4j_{\min}$	0	0

^a If Krylov subspace methods are used to solve the correction equation, then the products $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{v}$ and $\mathbf{B}\mathbf{v}$ are often already available, as side-products. No MVs are needed in this part then.

^b Instead of computing the residual \mathbf{r} as $(\tilde{\beta}\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\alpha}\mathbf{B})\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$, \mathbf{r} may also be computed as $\tilde{\beta}\mathbf{V}_A U(:, 1) - \tilde{\alpha}\mathbf{V}_B U(:, 1)$, where $\mathbf{V}_A \equiv \mathbf{A}\mathbf{V}$ and $\mathbf{V}_B \equiv \mathbf{B}\mathbf{V}$ (cf. ALG. 6.4); depending on the number of nonzeros in \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and the value of j , this may be more efficient.

TABLE 6.3. The computational costs of JDQZ per iteration. The integers j and k are the dimensions of $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$ and $\text{span}\{\mathbf{Q}\}$, respectively.

6.3.5.1. A harmonic Petrov value approach. We first consider the computation of the eigenvalues of a standard eigenproblem ($\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{I}$), that are close to some target value τ in the interior of (the convex hull of) the spectrum. The transformation $\lambda \rightsquigarrow 1/(\lambda - \tau)$ maps these eigenvalues λ to extremal eigenvalues of $(\mathbf{A} - \tau\mathbf{I})^{-1}$ and in that case the “correct” eigenpair approximations can be obtained easily (cf. Section 6.2.5). But, we want to avoid matrix inversion. With some formula manipulation, it can be shown that this can be achieved by taking the search subspace and the test subspace both equal to $\text{span}\{(\mathbf{A} - \tau\mathbf{I})\mathbf{V}\}$ (cf. [90, Section 5.1]): the resulting eigenvalue approximations $\tilde{\lambda}$ for \mathbf{A} are then the solutions of

$$(6.50) \quad \mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V} u - \tilde{\lambda} \mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{V} u = 0, \quad \text{where } \mathbf{W} \equiv (\mathbf{A} - \tau \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{V}.$$

The solutions $\tilde{\lambda}$ are called *harmonic Ritz values* of \mathbf{A} , with respect to τ (cf. [70, 90], and also [65]); $\mathbf{V}u$ is the associated *harmonic Ritz vector*. Since \mathbf{W} and $\gamma\mathbf{W}$, with $\gamma \equiv 1/\sqrt{1 + |\tau|^2}$, span the same space, the harmonic Ritz values appear as Petrov values for the test subspace generated as in (6.35), with

$$(6.51) \quad \nu_0 \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + |\tau|^2}} \quad \text{and} \quad \mu_0 \equiv -\frac{\tau}{\sqrt{1 + |\tau|^2}}.$$

For generalized problems, with ν_0 and μ_0 as in (6.51), the Petrov values closest to the target value correspond to absolute largest Ritz values of the

standard eigenproblem, with matrix $(\mathbf{A} - \tau \mathbf{B})^{-1}(\bar{\tau} \mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B})$. Therefore, for this generalized case also a better selection of appropriate eigenpair approximations may be expected. We refer to the Petrov values associated with this choice of test subspace as *harmonic Petrov* values.

Observe that it does not make sense to try to improve the mixture \mathbf{W} of $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{V}$ and $\mathbf{B}\mathbf{V}$ by taking $\nu_0 = \tilde{\beta}$ and $\mu_0 = -\tilde{\alpha}$, if a better generalized eigenvalue approximation $\langle \tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta} \rangle$ becomes available (cf. Section 6.3.1.2). On the contrary, as is explained in Section 6.3.1.1, this would spoil precisely the interesting components in the expansion vector of \mathbf{W} . However, recall that, with the harmonic approach in (6.51), our goal is not an optimal mixture, but a less risky selection procedure.

From the above arguments, it will be clear that the harmonic approach will not be better than the adaptive approach, when we want extremal eigenvalues: no better selection may be expected, but the expansion of the test subspace will be less optimal. However, for interior eigenvalues, experiments show (cf. Section 6.4.4 and Section 6.4.8) that the harmonic approach can work much better than the adaptive approach, even if the latter one is enhanced with the tracking strategy.

6.4. Numerical experiments. In this section we present numerical results, obtained with JDQR and JDQZ, for several eigenproblems and generalized eigenproblems. The purpose of these experiments is to get a good impression of the actual behavior of these methods. We have not tried to find the most efficient parameter choices for each particular problem. We will illustrate the effect of a more accurately solving the correction equation, and the effect of including appropriate preconditioning. We will show that the harmonic Petrov value choice for the test subspace may lead to superior convergence behavior, not only for the generalized eigenproblem, but also for the standard eigenproblem. We will demonstrate that the projections in the correction equation (6.12), involving detected Schur vectors, are essential components of the algorithms. We will see that the tracking strategy (Section 6.2.5.1) can be very helpful. We will also consider eigenproblems where multiple eigenvalues are involved.

The computations were done in double complex precision (≈ 15 digits) on a Sun workstation. To facilitate comparison, we have selected for all cases $j_{\max} = 15$, $j_{\min} = 10$ (the dimension of the subspace before and after implicit restart, respectively), and a fixed random real vector \mathbf{v}_0 as an initial guess (cf. ALG. 6.2 and ALG. 6.4).

As iterative solvers for the correction equation, we have considered full GMRES [82] with a maximum of m steps, denoted by GMRES_m , and BiCGstab(2)

[85]. For BiCGstab(2) a maximum of 100 matrix multiplications was allowed. As stopping criterion for the iterative methods for the correction equation, we have used $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_i\|_2 < 2^{-j}\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0\|_2$, where $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0$ is the initial residual, $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_i$ is the residual corresponding to the approximate solution produced by the inner method, and j is the iteration number for the current eigenvalue approximation in the outer iteration. Hence, as the outer iterations proceed, the inner iterations are solved more accurately. This choice was inspired by the fact that the Jacobi-Davidson method may be viewed as a Newton process [84, 87], and for Newton processes this stopping criterion may lead to efficient algorithms [30]. As the initial guess for the inner iteration method we always took the null-vector. The tracking strategy of Section 6.2.5.1 has been used in all examples, except where stated differently.

In the figures of the convergence behavior for JDQR and JDQZ, the performance is plotted in terms of the actual amount of work, in millions of floating point operations (flops), versus \log_{10} of the residual norm. The reason for this is that the computational work in JDQR and JDQZ consists of two parts of a different nature: one part is for the *inner iteration* process, in which a correction equation is (approximately) solved; the other part is for the *outer iteration*, in which an approximation for the (generalized) Schur pair is constructed. If in the inner iteration the correction equation is solved more accurately, then the number of outer iterations may decrease. Therefore, it would be misleading to monitor the total number of matrix multiplications. It might give a bad impression of the total costs, because most of the matrices are sparse and therefore the dot products and vector updates in the outer and the inner iteration represent substantial costs in JDQR and JDQZ.

Furthermore, we have plotted the entire convergence behavior. This means that the convergence history of the residuals of all sub-sequentially selected approximate eigenpairs is plotted. Whenever the residual norm curve drops below the acceptance level, indicated by the dotted horizontal line, an eigenvalue is accepted and the search process for the next one is continued. A large residual norm in the step immediately after acceptance marks the start of a new search.

Construction of suitable initial subspaces Specifically in the first few steps of the process the Ritz or Petrov vectors are usually poor approximations of the wanted eigenvectors, and the target value τ may be relatively (much) closer to the wanted eigenvalues than any of the approximate eigenvalues. In these cases, the correction equations (6.19) and (6.49), lead to relatively poor expansions of the search subspace. To see this, recall that the wanted eigenvector

would be in the new search subspace if this space would have been expanded by the exact solution for the correction equation with the wanted eigenvalue instead of $\tilde{\lambda}$ (cf. Section 6.2.1). This observation indicates how to improve the expansion in the first few steps: take in the correction equation τ instead of $\tilde{\lambda}$. To detect whether $\tilde{\lambda}$ is close enough to replace τ , we monitor the norm of the residual: we take $\tilde{\lambda}$ ($(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})$) instead of τ ($(\tau, 1)$) in the correction equation as soon as the first residual norm drops below a threshold value ϵ_{tr} .

Moreover, in all experiments we used GMRES₁ for the first j_{min} iterations, in order to build up a search subspace $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$ in a relatively inexpensive way. Especially when a preconditioner is involved, this approach can be justified with arguments similar those in the preceding paragraph (cf. [84, Section 9.4]).

In our experiments we will vary values for some of the parameters in JDQR and JDQZ. For easy reference, we recall their meaning:

<i>parameter</i>	<i>description</i>
τ	the target value
k_{max}	the number of wanted Schur pairs
ϵ	the stopping tolerance in the outer iteration
ϵ_{tr}	the tracking threshold (cf. Section 6.2.5.1)

6.4.1. The influence of the correction equation. The purpose of this example is to show the effect of a more accurate solution of the correction equation. We consider the Square Dielectric Waveguide standard eigenproblem DW1024 of order 2048 [6]. The problem comes from an integrated circuit application. The rightmost eigenvalues and their eigenvectors are wanted.

We took $\tau = 1.0$, $k_{\text{max}} = 4$, $\epsilon = 10^{-9}$, $\epsilon_{\text{tr}} = 10^{-4}$, and we have not used preconditioning.

The computed eigenvalues are given in TAB. 6.4. The convergence history is plotted in FIG. 6.2 for JDQR, for GMRES₁ and GMRES₁₀. A summary of the number of iterations, the number of matrix multiplications (MVs), and the number of flops is given in TAB. 6.5.

When solving the correction equation more accurately, the number of MVs is increased, but the number of outer iterations is reduced significantly (see TAB. 6.5), resulting in a much better overall performance.

With GMRES₁ the search subspace is the span of the residuals, and in that case JD (with implicit restart) generates the same subspaces as Implicitly

Restarted Arnoldi [94]. The eigenvalues are not well separated in this case and therefore Arnoldi converges only slowly. This explains the poor convergence of JDQR with GMRES₁.

Note that after two iterations, JDQR converges quite fast. For the next eigenvalues there is no such initial stagnation. Apparently, in the iterations for the first eigenvalue, components for the next Schur vectors are already collected in $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$ (cf. Section 6.2.6).

9.6473e - 01
9.6551e - 01
9.7780e - 01
9.7880e - 01

TABLE 6.4. 4 eigenvalues of DW1024, computed by JDQR (cf. Section 6.4.1).

Method for the correction equation	JDQR iterations	MVs	flops $\times 10^6$
GMRES ₁	185	185	1.023e + 02
GMRES ₁₀	43	296	4.661e + 01

TABLE 6.5. Summary of results for DW1024 (cf. Section 6.4.1).

6.4.2. The effect of preconditioning. When increasing the number of steps in GMRES, the correction equation will be solved more accurately, and the number of outer iterations may decrease as we have seen. But sometimes we need too many inner iterations with GMRES for acceptable convergence of the outer iterations. However, with appropriate preconditioning, we may see a dramatic improvement.

We consider the standard eigenproblem BWM2000 of order 2000 for the Brusselator wave model [6, 80]. The problem models the concentration waves for reaction and transport interaction of chemical solutions in a tubular reactor. Our task is to determine the eigenvalues with largest real part in order to verify whether their real parts are positive or negative (corresponding to stable or unstable modes).

For this problem, we have selected: $\tau = 1.0$, $k_{\max} = 5$, $\epsilon = 10^{-9}$, and $\epsilon_{\text{tr}} = 10^{-4}$.

FIGURE 6.2. Convergence history for DW1024, showing the effect of solving the correction equations more accurately (cf. Section 6.4.1).

The computed eigenvalues are listed in TAB. 6.6. The convergence history is plotted in FIG. 6.3 for JDQR with unpreconditioned GMRES₁₀, and with GMRES₁₀ + ILU(0) preconditioning. A summary of the results is given in TAB. 6.7.

From FIG. 6.3 we see that JDQR with GMRES₁₀ does not converge (we checked even up to GMRES₅₀, with little or no improvement), but with preconditioning JDQR performs rather well. Again we see that the speed of convergence for the first eigenvalue is somewhat slower than the speed of convergence for the other eigenvalues. Note that, although the projections in the correction equation become more expensive with each detected eigenvalue, the computational work for each eigenvalue is roughly constant, except for the first eigenvalue.

6.4.3. Multiple eigenvalues. In this example multiple eigenvalues are involved: the Chuck Matrix of order 656 (CK656) [6]. The goal is to compute the eigenvalues with magnitude greater than 1.0. The eigenvalues appear in clusters: each cluster consists of two pairs of almost multiple eigenvalues.

For this problem, we have selected: $\tau = 5.0$, $k_{\max} = 10$, $\epsilon = 10^{-9}$, and $\epsilon_{\text{tr}} = 10^{-4}$.

$-1.8000e+00$	+	$3.0327e+00i$
$-6.7500e-01$	-	$2.5287e+00i$
$-6.7500e-01$	+	$2.5287e+00i$
$2.4427e-07$	-	$2.1395e+00i$
$2.4427e-07$	+	$2.1395e+00i$

TABLE 6.6. 5 eigenvalues of BWM2000, computed by JDQR (cf. Section 6.4.2).

Method for the correction equation	JDQR iterations	MVs	flops $\times 10^6$
GMRES ₁₀ (no convergence)	*	*	*
GMRES ₁₀ + ILU(0)	45	213	4.518e + 01

TABLE 6.7. Summary of results for BWM2000 (cf. Section 6.4.2).

FIGURE 6.3. Convergence history for BWM2000, illustrating the effect of including preconditioning in the solver of the correction equation (cf. Section 6.4.2).

The computed eigenvalues are listed in TAB. 6.8. The convergence history is plotted in FIG. 6.4 for JDQR with GMRES₁, GMRES₁₀, and BiCGstab(2), all with ILU(2) preconditioning, for the correction equation. A summary of the results is given in TAB. 6.9.

For all three combinations the multiple eigenvalues are easily detected. For this example, GMRES₁₀ results in a somewhat better overall performance in comparison with GMRES₁, but the combination with BiCGstab(2) is the clear winner (cf. TAB. 6.9).

The initial fast convergence may be explained by the fact the target τ is close to the rightmost double eigenvalue, which is relatively well separated from the other eigenvalues.

1.1980e + 00	1.1980e + 00
1.5940e + 00	1.5940e + 00
1.4120e + 00	1.4120e + 00
1.4190e + 00	1.4190e + 00
5.5024e + 00	5.5024e + 00

TABLE 6.8. 10 eigenvalues of CK656, computed by JDQR (cf. Section 6.4.3).

Method for the correction equation	JDQR iterations	MVs	flops $\times 10^6$
GMRES ₁	121	121	3.346e + 01
GMRES ₁₀	64	291	2.959e + 01
BiCGstab(2)	48	226	2.260e + 01

TABLE 6.9. Summary of results for CK656 (cf. Section 6.4.3).

6.4.4. Harmonic Ritz values. The JDQR algorithm computes a partial Schur form for the standard eigenproblem with Ritz pairs for the Schur pairs. However, with JDQZ for $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{I}$, we can also compute a partial Schur form for the standard eigenproblem with harmonic Petrov pairs. Here we give an example that illustrates the improved convergence behavior for harmonic Petrov values.

We consider the Quebec Hydroelectric Power System problem QH882 of order 882 [6]. This matrix represents the Hydro-Quebec power system's small-signal model. The eigenvalues λ of interest are the eigenvalues in the box $-300 < \text{Re}(\lambda) < 100$, $0 < \text{Im}(\lambda) < 120\pi$ in the complex plane.

FIGURE 6.4. Convergence history for CK656. Also multiple eigenvalues are easily detected (cf. Section 6.4.3).

For this problem, we have selected: $\tau = -150.0 + 180.0i$, $k_{\max} = 5$, $\epsilon = 10^{-6}$, and $\epsilon_{\text{tr}} = 10^{-3}$.

The computed eigenvalues are given in TAB. 6.10. The convergence history is plotted in FIG. 6.7, for JDQR, JDQZ with the adaptive choice of test subspace (cf. Section 6.3.1.2), and JDQZ with the harmonic choice (cf. Section 6.3.5.1).

This problem is rather difficult: the eigenvalues in the neighborhood of τ are in the interior of the spectrum, see FIG. 6.5 and 6.6. For all three methods, the correction equation was solved with GMRES₂₀, preconditioned with the exact inverse of $\mathbf{A} - \tau\mathbf{I}$. A summary of the results is given in TAB. 6.9.

Although the computational complexity of JDQR is less than the computational complexity of JDQZ (cf. TAB. 6.2 and 6.3), it is not the most efficient method here. From the irregular convergence behavior of JDQR in FIG. 6.7 we may conclude that JDQR has problems in selecting the “correct” Ritz pairs and as a result the convergence is delayed. As anticipated (cf. Section 6.3.1),

JDQZ with the harmonic choice of test subspace makes better selections, as is indicated by the smooth convergence, and hence, its performance is much better. The adaptive version of JDQZ converges faster than JDQR, but not faster than the harmonic version of JDQZ. Apparently, for fast convergence in this case, it is more important to have “correct” Petrov approximations, than to focus on a more optimal test subspace.

$-1.8665e + 02$	+	$1.9464e + 02 i$
$-1.6661e + 02$	+	$1.9768e + 02 i$
$-1.6349e + 02$	+	$1.9524e + 02 i$
$-1.4913e + 02$	+	$1.9729e + 02 i$
$-1.3607e + 02$	+	$2.0215e + 02 i$

TABLE 6.10. 5 eigenvalues of QH882, computed by JDQR (cf. Section 6.4.4).

Method	Iterations	MVs	flops $\times 10^6$
JDQR	99	1482	$1.221e + 02$
JDQZ Adaptive	62	802	$8.252e + 01$
JDQZ Harmonic	57	665	$7.133e + 01$

TABLE 6.11. Summary of results for QH882 (cf. Section 6.4.4).

6.4.5. Tracking. Tracking was proposed in Section 6.2.5.1, in order to avoid the performance degeneration, that is caused by irregular convergence behavior of Ritz values. Here we illustrate (in FIG. 6.8) the effects one may see without tracking for JDQR. We applied JDQR to the example of Section 6.4.4 with the same choice of parameters, except for ϵ_{tr} ($\epsilon_{\text{tr}} = 0$ here).

In the previous example we have already seen that the convergence behavior of JDQR was rather irregular. By leaving out the tracking mechanism, the irregularities are even more pronounced. Eventually JDQR loses track completely and stagnates. The peaks in the convergence behavior show that sometimes the Ritz pair, that is selected in the JDQR process, does not correspond to the close-by Schur pair. As a result the search subspace is expanded in a poor direction. Clearly, for this example, this may lead to failure of convergence.

It also appears that, as was anticipated, the convergence behavior of JDQZ with the harmonic choice of test subspace is hardly affected by leaving out the tracking mechanism. Also the adaptive choice does pretty well without, but this

FIGURE 6.5. Spectrum of QH882 (cf. Section 6.4.4).

FIGURE 6.6. Part of the spectrum of QH882.

does not mean that it always selects the “correct” Ritz pairs, as we will see in our final example in Section 6.4.8.

6.4.6. The influence of \mathbf{Q}_k and \mathbf{Z}_k in the correction equation. In this example we show that the projections with detected Schur vectors (cf. (6.47)) are very essential in the correction equation (cf. Section 6.2.6) and we show what happens when these projections are neglected. Note that we take the Jacobi projections (with $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}$) still into account.

We consider the Bounded Finline Dielectric Waveguide generalized eigenproblem BFW782 [6] of order 782. This problem stems from a finite element discretization of the Maxwell equation for propagating modes and magnetic field profiles of a rectangular waveguide filled with dielectric and PEC structures. The resulting matrix \mathbf{A} is nonsymmetric and the matrix \mathbf{B} is positive definite. Of special interest are the generalized eigenvalues $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle$ with positive real part (i.e., $\text{Re}(\alpha/\beta) \geq 0$) and their corresponding eigenvectors.

For this problem, the parameters were set to: $\tau = 2750.0$, $k_{\max} = 5$, $\epsilon = 10^{-9}$, and $\epsilon_{\text{tr}} = 10^{-6}$.

The spectrum of this matrix pair is shown in FIG. 6.9. A magnification of the region of interest is plotted in FIG. 6.10. The computed generalized eigenvalues, represented as α/β , are given in TAB. 6.12. With JDQZ we discovered all 4 positive generalized eigenvalues.

The convergence history is plotted in FIG. 6.11, for the harmonic version of JDQZ with GMRES₁₀, and for BiCGstab(2). A summary of the results is given in TAB. 6.13. We see that JDQZ converges quite nicely for GMRES₁₀ and BiCGstab(2). It should be noted that although it seems that with BiCGstab(2) only 4 generalized eigenvalue are computed, in fact 5 generalized eigenvalue are

FIGURE 6.7. Convergence history for QH882 obtained with the tracking strategy (for all variants). Although QH882 is a standard eigenproblem, for computing interior eigenvalues it is more efficient to use test subspaces that are different from the search subspaces (middle and lower figure). A better selection of the Petrov pair (lower figure) appears to compensate for a less optimum expansion of the test subspace. (cf. Section 6.4.4).

computed: the 2 rightmost generalized eigenvalue, that are relatively close, are found almost simultaneously.

In FIG. 6.12 the convergence behavior of JDQZ with GMRES₁₀, and with BiCGstab(2), is given for the case where the correction equation (6.47) is solved without taking into account the projections involving \mathbf{Q}_k and \mathbf{Z}_k . Of course, the correction equations that are used include the rank one projection involving $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}$: these projections are essential for Jacobi-Davidson. Furthermore, deflation in this case is realized by making the approximate solution of the correction equation orthogonal to the detected Schur vectors with modified Gram-Schmidt. By doing the latter *twice*, the overall performance improved significantly: in the

FIGURE 6.8. Convergence history for QH882 without tracking. For interior eigenvalues, the tracking strategy improves JDQR significantly (compare the present upper figure with the upper figure in FIG. 6.7), while there is no improvement for the two JDQZ variants (compare the two middle figures and the two lower figures of the present figure and FIG. 6.7) (cf. Section 6.4.5)

results shown here (cf. FIG. 6.12) modified Gram-Schmidt is applied twice.

However, as explained in Section 6.2.6, we do not benefit from an improved operator in the inner iteration. Although the resulting algorithm is computationally cheaper, FIG. 6.12 shows that this does not lead to an overall better performance: the speed of convergence becomes increasingly slower and even stagnates eventually.

6.4.7. More multiple eigenvalues. We consider the eigenproblem

$$\Delta u = \lambda u,$$

with Neumann boundary conditions on the cube $[0, 4]^3$. Finite element discretization of this equation on an $11 \times 11 \times 11$ regular grid, with tetrahedral

$-1.1373e + 03$
$5.6467e + 02$
$1.2634e + 03$
$2.4843e + 03$
$2.5233e + 03$

TABLE 6.12. 5 generalized eigenvalues of BFW782, computed by JDQZ (cf. Section 6.4.6).

Method for the correction equation	JDQZ iterations	MVs	flops $\times 10^6$
GMRES ₁₀	37	233	$3.17e + 01$
BiCGstab(2)	32	429	$3.88e + 01$

TABLE 6.13. Summary of results for BFW782 (cf. Section 6.4.6).

FIGURE 6.9. Spectrum of BFW782 (cf. Section 6.4.6).

FIGURE 6.10. Part of the spectrum of BFW782.

FIGURE 6.11. Convergence history for BFW782.

FIGURE 6.12. Convergence history for BFW782 without deflating the matrices in the correction equations, with respect to the detected Schur vectors. Without deflation the convergence of the linear solver for the correction is much slower (compare the above figures with those in FIG. 6.11) (cf. Section 6.4.6).

$3.8178e - 02$	$1.4503e + 05$	$2.9540e + 05$
$7.1673e + 04$	$1.4503e + 05$	$3.7044e + 05$
$7.1673e + 04$	$2.1811e + 05$	$3.7044e + 05$
$7.1673e + 04$	$2.9411e + 05$	$3.7044e + 05$
$1.4503e + 05$	$2.9411e + 05$	$3.7242e + 05$

TABLE 6.14. 15 generalized eigenvalues of AC1331, computed by JDQZ (cf. Section 6.4.7).

elements and linear interpolation functions, leads to a generalized eigenproblem of order 1331 (AC1331). It has one positive generalized eigenvalue $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle$ relatively close to zero (i.e., $\alpha/\beta \approx 0$). The other generalized eigenvalues are also positive and may be doublets or even triplets.

For this problem, the parameters were set to: $\tau = 0.0$, $k_{\max} = 15$, $\epsilon = 10^{-9}$, and $\epsilon_{\text{tr}} = 10^{-4}$.

The computed 15 leftmost generalized eigenvalues, represented as α/β are given in TAB. 6.14. The residual norm versus the number of flops is plotted in FIG. 6.13 for the harmonic version of JDQZ with GMRES₁₀ and with BiCGstab(2), respectively. A summary of the results is given in TAB. 6.15.

From the plots we see the effect that multiple generalized eigenvalues may have on the convergence behavior. JDQZ converges initially quite fast until the point that it “discovers” that the generalized eigenvalue is actually double or triple. The convergence speed stagnates for a few iterations (2 or 3 peaks in the plot with GMRES, and a plateau in the plot with BiCGstab(2)), after which they are discovered quickly one after another. This behavior is in agreement with Section 6.2.6: during the stagnation phase components of other Schur vectors are amplified in the inner iteration and collected in the search subspace, leading to faster convergence for the next Schur pairs. The stagnation can be explained by the fact, that with rank 1 Jacobi projections the correction equation may become (nearly) singular when selecting Petrov approximations for multiple generalized eigenvalues. The iterative methods used for solving the correction equation often suffer from this (see also [98]). (Variable) block versions of the correction equation that take this multiplicity into account may be preferable in such cases, but this falls outside the scope of this paper.

6.4.8. Harmonic Ritz values for generalized problems. Our last example shows again that for interior generalized eigenvalues the harmonic version JDQZ is superior to the adaptive version.

We consider the MHD416 generalized eigenproblem of order 416 [6, 84, 12].

Method for the correction equation	JDQZ iterations	MVs	flops $\times 10^6$
GMRES ₁₀	93	601	2.325e + 03
BiCGstab(2)	61	1253	3.368e + 03

TABLE 6.15. Summary of results for AC1331 (cf. Section 6.4.7).

FIGURE 6.13. Convergence history for AC1331: stagnation followed by fast detection of triple generalized eigenvalues (cf. Section 6.4.7).

FIGURE 6.14. Spectrum of MHD416 (cf. Section 6.4.8).

FIGURE 6.15. Alfvén branch of MHD416 (cf. Section 6.4.8).

This problem stems from a magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) model, where the interaction of hot plasma and a magnetic field is studied. The matrix \mathbf{A} is non-Hermitian and the matrix \mathbf{B} is Hermitian positive definite. Our goal is to compute interior generalized eigenvalues corresponding to the so called “Alfvén” branch of the spectrum, see FIG. 6.14 and 6.15.

For this problem, the parameters were set to: $\tau = -0.1 + 0.5i$, $k_{\max} = 20$, $\epsilon = 10^{-9}$, and $\epsilon_{\text{tr}} = 10^{-4}$.

The computed generalized eigenvalues are plotted in FIG. 6.16. The convergence history for the adaptive and the harmonic version of JDQZ with GMRES₁ are plotted in FIG. 6.17. The exact inverse of $\mathbf{A} - \tau \mathbf{B}$ (for τ fixed) was used as preconditioner.

Note the irregular behavior of the adaptive version of JDQZ. The tracking mechanism fails and the convergence becomes more and more problematic as the iteration count increases. It even stagnates after a while. The harmonic version of JDQZ does not encounter such problems here. For all generalized eigenvalues the rate of convergence is almost the same: in the computation for one Schur pair, the search subspace apparently accumulates components for next Schur pairs as well.

6.5. Conclusions. We have proposed two algorithms, JDQR and JDQZ, for computing several selected eigenpair approximations for standard and generalized eigenproblems, respectively. The methods are based on the Jacobi-Davidson method and compute iteratively a partial (generalized) Schur form with (generalized) eigenvalues near a user-specified target value. For both methods, no exact inversion of any matrix is strictly necessary, so that they are suitable for solving large eigenproblems.

FIGURE 6.16. 20 generalized eigenvalues computed by JDQZ for MHD416 (cf. Section 6.4.8).

Fast convergence is obtained with a projected correction equation that is solved (approximately) by iterative methods with appropriate preconditioning. The convergence of JDQR and JDQZ is asymptotically quadratical if this correction equation is solved exactly. Furthermore, while converging to a particular Schur pair, the search subspace accumulates components of other Schur pairs with (generalized) eigenvalues near the target as well. This usually leads to faster convergence for the next eigenpairs.

The dimension of the involved subspaces can be controlled by an efficient implicit restart technique in such a way that the most relevant part of the subspace is maintained at restart.

The algorithms incorporate simple mechanisms for selecting the wanted eigenpair approximations. Also multiple (generalized) eigenvalues can be detected.

Whereas in the Jacobi-Davidson method the test subspace can be chosen arbitrarily, in the JDQZ algorithm essentially two choices for the test subspace remain: the (adaptive) standard Petrov value choice, and the harmonic Petrov value choice. It is argued, and confirmed as well by our experiments, that especially for interior eigenvalues, the harmonic approach is also superior for

FIGURE 6.17. Convergence history of JDQZ for MHD416. harmonic Petrov values allow a good selection of Petrov pairs for computing interior generalized eigenvalues (upper figure), also for generalized problems (cf. Section 6.4.8).

generalized eigenproblems

Acknowledgements. We acknowledge helpful discussions with Paul Smit and with Beresford Parlett (on naming conventions). Martin van Gijzen kindly provided the matrices for example AC1331.

.1. Modified Gram-Schmidt. Here we give a MATLAB implementation of Modified Gram-Schmidt. As input it takes a $(n \times j)$ -matrix \mathbf{V} , with $\mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{I}$, and a n -vector \mathbf{v} . On return, \mathbf{v} is made orthogonal to $\text{span}\{\mathbf{V}\}$. The j -vector s holds the values of the coefficients involved.

```
function [v, s] = mgs(V, v)
j = size(V, 2);
s = [];
```

```

for  $i = 1:j$ ,
     $s = [s, \mathbf{V}(:, i)' * \mathbf{v}]$ ;
     $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}(:, i) * s(i)$ ;
end

```

.2. Sorting the Schur form. Before giving MATLAB functions for sorting a Schur form, we indicate how the diagonal entries of the upper triangular matrix S in a Schur form can be reordered in any order by unitary transformations without destroying the upper triangular form.

Clearly, it is sufficient to discuss the 2×2 case, and to show that the order of the diagonal entries can be reversed:

$$S \equiv \begin{bmatrix} \lambda & \gamma \\ 0 & \mu \end{bmatrix}.$$

With

$$T \equiv S - \mu I = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda - \mu & \gamma \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

let G be the Givens rotation such that the first column of TG is zero. Since the first column of G^*TG and the $(2, 1)$ -entry of $G^*IG = I$ are both zero, we necessarily must have that

$$G^*SGe_1 = G^*TGe_1 + \mu G^*IGe_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \mu \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Therefore, G^*SG is upper triangular and similar to S and, consequently, the order of the diagonal entries of G^*SG is reversed with respect to those of S .

The MATLAB functions below implement the sorting of a Schur decomposition $MU = US$. As input `qsort` takes the target τ , a unitary matrix U and an upper triangular matrix S . On return, the diagonal entries of S are ordered with respect to τ and the matrix U is updated correspondingly.

The function `select` detects the position in a sequence of a scalar closest to a value τ .

With plane-rotations, the function `swap` swaps the diagonal entries $S(k, k)$ and $S(k+1, k+1)$ for $k = j-1, j-2, \dots, i$, assuming that $j > i$. It updates the other entries of S and U accordingly. The resulting matrix S contains at position (i, i) the value $S(j, j)$ of the original matrix, while the values in the left $(i-1 \times i-1)$ upper block are unchanged.

```

function [U, S] = qrsort (tau, U, S)
k = size (S, 1);
for i = 1:k - 1,
    s = diag (S(i:k, i:k));
    j = select (tau, s) + i - 1;
    [U, S] = swap (U, S, j, i);
end

function j = select (tau, s)
[a, j] = min(abs (tau - s));

function [U, S] = swap (U, S, j, i)
for k = j - 1: -1:i,
    x = [S(k, k + 1), S(k, k) - S(k + 1, k + 1)];
    G([2, 1], [2, 1]) = planerot (x)*;
    S(:, [k, k + 1]) = S(:, [k, k + 1])G;
    S([k, k + 1], :) = G*S([k, k + 1], :)
    U(:, [k, k + 1]) = U(:, [k, k + 1])G;
end

```

.3. Sorting the generalized Schur form. Before giving the MATLAB functions, we explain how the generalized Schur form can be sorted.

Clearly, it is sufficient to consider the 2×2 case, and to show that the order of the eigenvalue pairs can be reversed. Thereto, consider

$$S_A \equiv \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 & \gamma_A \\ 0 & \alpha_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad S_B \equiv \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 & \gamma_B \\ 0 & \beta_2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

With

$$T \equiv \beta_2 S_A - \alpha_2 S_B = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_2 \alpha_1 - \alpha_2 \beta_1 & \beta_2 \gamma_A - \alpha_2 \gamma_B \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

let G_R be the Givens rotation such that the first column of TG_R is zero and let G_L be the Givens rotation such that, for some scalar γ ,

$$\gamma G_L^* S_B G_R e_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Since the first column of $G_L^* T G_R$ and the $(2, 1)$ -entry of $G_L^* S_B G_R$ are both zero,

we necessarily must have that

$$\gamma G_L^* S_A G_R e_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Hence, both $G_L^* S_A G_R$ and $G_L^* S_B G_R$ are upper triangular and similar to S_A and S_B and consequently the order of the eigenvalue pairs are reversed, where pairs are considered to be identical if the associated quotients are equal.

The MATLAB functions below implement the sorting of a generalized Schur decomposition $M_A U_R = U_L S_A$ and $M_B U_R = U_L S_B$. As input `qzsort` takes the target τ , the upper triangular matrices S_A and S_B , and the unitary matrices U_L and U_R . On return, the eigenvalue pairs of (S_A, S_B) are ordered with respect to τ and the matrices U_L and U_R are updated correspondingly.

The function `select` detects the position of the scalar closest τ . The function `swap` transfers the eigenvalue pairs $\langle S_A(j, j), S_B(j, j) \rangle$ to the position (i, i) by way of plane-rotations, leaving the pairs in the positions $(1, 1), \dots, (i-1, i-1)$ unchanged. The other entries of S_A, S_B, U_L and U_R are updated correspondingly.

```
function [U_L, U_R, S_A, S_B] = qzsort (tau, U_L, U_R, S_A, S_B)
k = size (S_A, 1);
for i = 1:k - 1,
    s = diag (S_A(i:k, i:k));
    t = diag (S_B(i:k, i:k));
    j = select (tau, s, t) + i - 1;
    [U_L, U_R, S_A, S_B] = swap (U_L, U_R, S_A, S_B, j, i);
end
```

```
function j = select (tau, s, t)
[a, j] = min(abs (tau - s ./ t));
```

```
function [U_L, U_R, S_A, S_B] = swap (U_L, U_R, S_A, S_B, j, i)
for k = j - 1: -1:i,
    x = S_B(k + 1, k + 1)S_A(k, k + 1) - S_A(k + 1, k + 1)S_B(k, k + 1);
    x = [x, S_B(k + 1, k + 1)S_A(k, k) - S_A(k + 1, k + 1)S_B(k, k)];
    G([2, 1], [2, 1]) = planerot (x)*;
    S_A(:, [k, k + 1]) = S_A(:, [k, k + 1])G;
    S_B(:, [k, k + 1]) = S_B(:, [k, k + 1])G;
```

```
     $U_R(:, [k, k + 1]) = U_R(:, [k, k + 1])G;$   
     $x = S_A(k, k);$   
     $x = [x; S_A(k + 1, k)];$   
     $G = \text{planerot}(x);$   
     $S_A([k, k + 1], :) = GS_A([k, k + 1], :);$   
     $S_B([k, k + 1], :) = GS_B([k, k + 1], :);$   
     $U_L([k, k + 1], :) = U_L([k, k + 1], :)G^*;$   
end
```


SUMMARY

In this thesis we describe new computational methods for the iterative solution of linear, nonlinear, and eigenproblems. The solution of this kind of problems plays an important role in scientific models for helping to answer questions regarding: weather forecasting, car safety, flying properties of an aircraft, the protection of dykes against flooding, the characteristics of a semiconductor, the load a bridge can take, the way in which chemical reactions take place, etc.

Handling this kind of problem can be done by means of partial differential equations. The size of the set equations, obtained after discretization, may challenge the possibilities of the existing direct methods. In fact, in actual computation a significant part of the computing time is required for solving these linear algebra subproblems, and this makes it paramount to consider alternatives. In particular, it may be more efficient or even necessary to use appropriate iterative methods.

Iterative methods are relevantly different from direct methods, in that they do not attempt to solve the given problem in one complete step of given computational complexity. Instead, they attempt to improve a given approximation in a number of successive steps. Each of these steps is of modest computational complexity, and the number of steps is usually not known in advance. A popular iterative approach is to construct a subspace and to transform the given large problem into a much smaller problem. The solution of this much easier to handle smaller problem then leads to a correction for the existing approximation. By selecting a suitable expansion for the subspace this process may be repeated. In real applications it is sometimes possible to select an appropriate iterative method for which only a modest number of iterations is sufficient to obtain an acceptable solution, and in such cases these iterative methods are very attractive.

In the last decades much research has been devoted to the construction of suitable iterative methods, and many algorithms have been suggested. However,

the usage of these methods does not go without problems. Sometimes too many iterations are needed to converge, and consequently too much cpu-time is needed, and sometimes they simply do not converge to the desired answer. The lack of convergence may be due to the fact that the method is not appropriate for the given problem in view of required mathematical properties, but it may also happen that rounding errors spoil a potentially converging process.

The methods proposed in this thesis have improved properties with respect to the above mentioned problems. By carefully inspecting situations where a specific method fails it may be deduced whether this is due to rounding errors, for which some of these methods can be improved, or whether this is inherent to the selection of a subspace for the method. In the latter case we can look for alternative selection strategies. By doing so, we can often obtain better approximate solutions as well as save computing resources (computer memory and cpu-time).

In Chapter 1–4 we focus on iterative methods for linear problems in particular. The existing methods GMRES, CGS, and Bi-CGSTAB are investigated and shortcomings are identified. Our investigations have led to methods with better convergence properties for relevant classes of problems. In particular we have proposed the method GCRO, as an alternative for the existing method GMRESR, the method GCGS, as an alternative for CGS in a Newton scheme, and Bi-CGSTAB(ℓ), as alternative for the popular Bi-CGSTAB method. The improved properties are illustrated by their behavior on well-chosen numerical examples.

In Chapter 5 we present a framework for the solution of general nonlinear problems. Many existing algorithms are covered by this framework. The framework is suggested, in a quite natural way, by the subspace approaches that are used in various iterative methods. It deepens our understanding of the underlying relationships and it also brings new computational approaches to the surface. Numerical experiments give evidence that this may lead to more efficient computational schemes for given problems.

In the last chapter, Chapter 6, we propose a new algorithm for the partial solution of standard eigenproblems (JDQR), and one for generalized eigenproblems (JDQZ). An important difference, with respect to the standard Lanczos and Arnoldi methods, is that our methods may be combined with preconditioning techniques. This may help to speed up the convergence and it makes the solution of very large eigenproblems feasible. Our approaches are based upon the recently published Jacobi-Davidson algorithms, and it includes strategies for keeping the required subspaces of low dimension. A number of numerical experiments illustrate the potential of this approach.

SAMENVATTING

In deze dissertatie wordt een aantal nieuwe methoden beschreven voor het iteratief oplossen van lineaire, niet-lineaire, en/of eigen problemen met behulp van de computer. De oplossing van dit soort problemen speelt een belangrijke rol in wetenschappelijke modellen die helpen bij het beantwoorden van vragen als: wat voor het weer wordt het, hoe veilig is een auto, wat is het vlieggedrag van een vliegtuig, hoe bestendig zijn dijken tegen overstromingen, hoe snel werkt een halfgeleider, hoeveel belasting kan een brug verdragen, hoe verloopt een chemische reactie, enzovoorts.

In de praktijk modeleert men dit soort vraagstukken met behulp van partiële differentiaal vergelijkingen. De grootte van de na discretisatie verkregen stelsels grenst in de regel aan de mogelijkheden van de bestaande directe oplossingsmethoden. In feite bestaat een significant percentage van de gebruikte computertijd, die gespendeerd wordt aan het oplossen van een bepaald probleem, uit het oplossen van deze deelproblemen. Dit maakt het interessant om alternatieven te overwegen. In het bijzonder kan het efficiënter of zelfs noodzakelijk zijn een geschikte iteratieve methode te gebruiken.

Een belangrijk verschil tussen directe en iteratieve methoden is dat iteratieve methoden het probleem niet in één enkele stap van gegeven rekenkundige complexiteit oplossen. Een iteratieve methode probeert daarentegen een bestaande benadering te verbeteren in snel opeenvolgende, kleinere stappen. Elk van deze stappen is van geringe rekenkundige complexiteit en het aantal stappen ligt normaal gesproken niet van te voren vast. Een populaire iteratieve aanpak is om een deelruimte te construeren en daarmee het grote probleem te reduceren tot een veel kleiner, gelijksoortig probleem. De gemakkelijk te verkrijgen oplossing daarvan leidt dan tot een correctie van de meest recente benadering. Door de deelruimte adequaat uit te breiden kan dit proces herhaald worden. In veel toepassingen is het mogelijk een iteratieve methode te kiezen die maar een bescheiden aantal van zulke stappen nodig heeft om tot een acceptabele

oplossing te komen. In die gevallen is zo'n iteratieve methode natuurlijk zeer aantrekkelijk.

In de laatste decennia is heel wat onderzoek gewijd geweest aan de ontwikkeling van geschikte iteratieve methoden en al heel wat verschillende methoden zijn voorgesteld. Echter, een probleem blijft dat ze lang niet altijd naar tevredenheid werken. Soms vergen ze te veel iteraties en dus te veel computertijd, en soms convergeren ze niet naar de gewenste oplossing. Het gebrek aan convergentie kan te wijten zijn aan de ongeschiktheid van de iteratieve methoden voor een gegeven probleem, gelet op vereiste wiskundige aspecten, maar het kan ook gebeuren dat door afrondingsfouten de benaderde oplossing onacceptabele afwijkingen gaat vertonen.

De in dit proefschrift voorgestelde nieuwe methoden brengen nu hierin verbetering. Door zorgvuldig na te gaan waar het fout kan gaan, kan men afleiden of het aan afrondfouten ligt of dat het inherent is aan de keuze van de deelruimten. Men kan dan maatregelen inbouwen om afrondfouten te voorkomen of men kan geschiktere deelruimten kiezen. Zo kan in veel gevallen een betere approximatie gevonden worden en bovendien de rekentijd aanzienlijk verkort worden.

In hoofdstuk 1 tot en met 4 staan iteratieve methoden voor lineaire problemen centraal. De bestaande methoden GMRES, CGS, en Bi-CGSTAB worden onder de loep genomen en een aantal tekortkomingen wordt blootgelegd. Dit leidt dan tot methoden met verbeterde convergentie-eigenschappen voor relevante klassen van problemen. In het bijzonder wordt de methode GCRO voorgesteld, als een alternatief voor GMRESR, de methode qCGS, als een alternatief voor CGS in een Newton schema, en BiCGstab(ℓ), als een alternatief voor de populaire Bi-CGSTAB methode. De verbeterde eigenschappen worden geïllustreerd met toepasselijke numerieke experimenten.

In hoofdstuk 5 wordt een raamwerk geïntroduceerd voor het oplossen van algemene niet-lineaire problemen. Het raamwerk is geïnspireerd op de overeenkomsten van al bestaande deelruimte methoden en er vloeien vele bekende methoden uit voort. Het vergroot het inzicht in de onderlinge relaties en het brengt ook nieuwe mogelijkheden aan het licht. Numeriek experimenten laten zien dat deze aanpak kan leiden tot efficiëntere algoritmen voor een gegeven probleem.

In het laatste hoofdstuk, hoofdstuk 6, worden twee algoritmen beschreven, die geschikt zijn voor het berekenen van enkele eigenwaarden en eigenvectoren van standaard en gegeneraliseerde eigenproblemen. Een zeer belangrijk verschil, in vergelijking met bestaande methoden zoals Lanczos en Arnoldi, is dat deze methoden, JDQR en JDQZ geheten, het mogelijk maken de convergentiesnelheid te verhogen door middel van preconditionering. Dit laatste brengt het oplossen van zeer grote eigenproblemen onder handbereik. De methoden zijn

gebaseerd op de recent gepubliceerde Jacobi-Davidson algorithmen, en bevatten ondermeer strategieën om de dimensie van de deelruimten onder de duim te houden. Een aantal numerieke experimenten illustreren het potentieel van deze aanpak.

APPENDIX A

PYTHON IMPLEMENTATION OF BISTBL

The following is a Python 3 translation of the BISTBL FORTRAN subroutine presented in Section 3.4 of Chapter 3. The three phases of the algorithm—BiCG, convex polynomial stabilisation, and reliable update—are factored into separate functions.

NUMPY replaces the BLAS/LAPACK calls throughout. The interface uses two callables: `mv(v)` returns Av , and `solve_precond(v)` returns $K^{-1}v$ (pass `lambda v: v.copy()` for no preconditioning). The BiCG inner loops are vectorised over the j index, and the polynomial coefficient vectors are built by the helper `_make_poly`. The function returns the approximate solution together with a convergence flag, the achieved relative residual norm, and the number of matrix–vector products used.

```
1  """
2  bistbl.py -- Enhanced BiCGstab(1) solver with reliable
      update.
3
4  Python 3 translation of bistbl.f (D.R. Fokkema, 1995).
5  Copyright (c) 1995 D.R. Fokkema. Permission to copy all
      or part of
6  this work is granted, provided that the copies are not
      made or
7  distributed for resale, and that the copyright notice
      and this notice
8  are retained.
9  """
10
11 from __future__ import annotations
12 import numpy as np
```

```

13 from numpy.typing import NDArray
14
15 # Reliable-update threshold (delta in the paper)
16 _DELTA: float = 1e-2
17 # Minimum |varrho| used in convex combination safeguard
18 _SAFEGUARD: float = 0.7
19
20
21 def bistbl(
22     l: int,
23     b: NDArray,
24     mv,
25     solve_precond,
26     x0: NDArray | None = None,
27     tol: float = 1e-8,
28     max_mv: int = 1000,
29 ) -> tuple[NDArray, int, float, int]:
30     """
31     Solve  $Ax = b$  using enhanced BiCGstab(l).
32
33     Implements the three-part iteration described in
34     Fokkema, Sleijpen &
35     Van der Vorst (1996): l steps of BiCG, a convex
36     polynomial
37     stabilisation phase, and a reliable-update mechanism
38     that corrects
39     residual drift caused by floating-point cancellation
40     .
41
42     Parameters
43     -----
44     l : int
45         Polynomial degree ( $l \geq 1$ ).  $l = 1$  gives
46         standard BiCGstab.
47     b : ndarray, shape (n,)
48         Right-hand side.
49     mv : callable
50          $mv(v) \rightarrow$  ndarray -- returns  $A @ v$ .
51     solve_precond : callable
52          $solve\_precond(v) \rightarrow$  ndarray -- returns  $K^{-1}$ 
53         v.
54     Pass ‘‘lambda v: v.copy()‘‘ for no

```

```

        preconditioning.
49  x0 : ndarray, shape (n,), optional
50      Initial guess. Defaults to zero.
51  tol : float
52      Convergence tolerance: stop when  $\|r\| \leq \text{tol} * \|r_0\|$ .
53  max_mv : int
54      Maximum number of matrix-vector products.
55
56  Returns
57  -----
58  x : ndarray, shape (n,)
59      Approximate solution.
60  info : int
61      0 converged, 1 max_mv reached, 2 breakdown.
62  rel_res : float
63      Final relative residual norm  $\|r\| / \|r_0\|$ .
64  nmv : int
65      Matrix-vector products used.
66  """
67  n = len(b)
68  x = np.zeros(n) if x0 is None else np.array(x0,
        dtype=float)
69
70  r = np.zeros((l + 1, n)) # r[0..l]: residual
        Krylov vectors
71  u = np.zeros((l + 1, n)) # u[0..l]: search
        direction vectors
72
73  # --- Initialise ---
74  r[0] = solve_precond(b - mv(x))
75  r_shadow = r[0].copy() # fixed shadow residual
76  b_ref = r[0].copy() # stored rhs for reliable
        update
77  x_ref = x.copy() # stored x for reliable
        update
78  x[:] = 0.0
79
80  rnorm0 = np.linalg.norm(r[0])
81  rnorm = rnorm0
82  mxnrms = mxnrms = rnorm0
83

```

```

84     alpha = 0.0;  omega = 1.0;  rho0 = 1.0
85     nmv = 0
86
87     # =====
88     # Main iteration loop
89     # =====
90     while rnrn > tol * rnrn0 and nmv < max_mv:
91
92         # -----
93         # BiCG phase
94         # -----
95         rho0 = -omega * rho0
96
97         for k in range(1, l + 1):
98             rho1 = r_shadow @ r[k - 1]
99             if rho0 == 0.0:
100                 return x_ref + x, 2, rnrn / rnrn0, nmv
101             beta = alpha * rho1 / rho0
102             rho0 = rho1
103
104             u[:k] = r[:k] - beta * u[:k]
105             u[k] = solve_precond(mv(u[k - 1])); nmv
106                 += 1
107
108             sigma = r_shadow @ u[k]
109             if sigma == 0.0:
110                 return x_ref + x, 2, rnrn / rnrn0, nmv
111             alpha = rho1 / sigma
112
113             x += alpha * u[0]
114             r[:k] -= alpha * u[1:k + 1]
115             r[k] = solve_precond(mv(r[k - 1])); nmv
116                 += 1
117
118             rnrn = np.linalg.norm(r[0])
119             mxnrnx = max(mxnrnx, rnrn)
120             mxnrmr = max(mxnrmr, rnrn)
121
122         # -----
123         # Convex polynomial phase
124         # -----
125         rnrn, omega = _poly_step(l, r, u, x)

```

```

124
125     # -----
126     # Reliable update phase
127     # -----
128     mxnrmx = max(mxnrmx, rnrnm)
129     mxnrnr = max(mxnrmr, rnrnr)
130
131     xpdt = (rnrnm < _DELTA * rnrnr0) and (rnrnr0 <
132           mxnrmx)
133     rcmp = ((rnrnm < _DELTA * mxnrnr) and (rnrnr0 <
134           mxnrnr)) or xpdt
135
136     if rcmp:
137         r[0] = solve_precond(b_ref - mv(x))
138         mxnrnr = rnrnr
139         if xpdt:
140             x_ref += x; x[:] = 0.0
141             b_ref = r[0].copy()
142             mxnrmx = rnrnr
143
144     # =====
145     # End of iterations
146     # =====
147     x += x_ref
148
149     r0 = solve_precond(b - mv(x))
150     rnrnr = np.linalg.norm(r0)
151     info = 0 if rnrnr <= tol * rnrnr0 else 1
152     return x, info, rnrnr / rnrnr0, nmv
153
154 def _poly_step(
155     l: int,
156     r: NDArray,
157     u: NDArray,
158     x: NDArray,
159 ) -> tuple[float, float]:
160     """
161     Convex polynomial stabilisation step.
162
163     Computes the (l+1)-coefficient vectors y0 and y1
164     that minimise the

```

```

163     norms of the candidate updated residuals, forms
        their safeguarded
164     convex combination, and applies the resulting update
        to r[0], u[0],
165     and x in-place.
166
167     Returns (rnorm, omega) where rnorm is the updated
        residual norm and
168     omega is the trailing coefficient y0[1] used in the
        next BiCG step.
169     """
170     Z      = r @ r.T                # Gram matrix,
        Z[i, j] = r[i].r[j]
171     Z_int = Z[1:1, 1:1] if l > 1 else None
172
173     y0 = _make_poly(1, Z, Z_int, rhs_col=0, first=-1.0,
        last=0.0)
174     y1 = _make_poly(1, Z, Z_int, rhs_col=1, first= 0.0,
        last=-1.0)
175
176     kappa0 = np.sqrt(y0 @ Z @ y0)
177     kappal = np.sqrt(y1 @ Z @ y1)
178     varrho = (y1 @ Z @ y0) / (kappa0 * kappal)
179
180     y0 -= np.sign(varrho) * max(abs(varrho), _SAFEGUARD)
        * (kappa0 / kappal) * y1
181
182     u[0] -= y0[1:] @ u[1:]          # u0 -= sum_{j>=1} y0[j]
        u[j]
183     x    += y0[1:] @ r[1:]          # x  += sum_{j>=1} y0[j]
        r[j-1]
184     r[0] -= y0[1:] @ r[1:]          # r0 -= sum_{j>=1} y0[j]
        r[j]
185
186     return float(np.sqrt(y0 @ Z @ y0)), float(y0[1])
187
188
189 def _make_poly(
190     l: int,
191     Z: NDArray,
192     Z_int: NDArray | None,
193     rhs_col: int,

```

```
194     first: float,
195     last: float,
196 ) -> NDArray:
197     """
198     Build a polynomial coefficient vector y of length l
199         +1.
200
201     Sets y[0] = first and y[l] = last. The interior
202     entries y[1:l] are
203     determined by the normal equations Z[1:l, 1:l] y[1:l]
204     ] = Z[1:l, rhs_col],
205     which arise from minimising the norm of the
206     candidate residual under
207     the given endpoint constraints.
208     """
209     y = np.zeros(l + 1)
210     y[0] = first
211     y[l] = last
212     if l > 1:
213         y[1:l] = np.linalg.solve(Z_int, Z[1:l, rhs_col])
214     return y
```


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